

**ASPECTS OF TURBULENT CONVECTION:
IMPLICATIONS FOR SOLAR DIFFERENTIAL ROTATION
AND SMALL-SCALE DYNAMOS**

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BY

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Certificate

This is to certify that the thesis entitled '**Aspects of Turbulent Convection: Implications for Solar Differential Rotation and Small-Scale Dynamos**', submitted to Jawaharlal Nehru University by **Mr Kishore Gopalakrishnan** for the award of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy is his original work. This has not been submitted to any other university for any degree or diploma.

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Declaration

I hereby declare that the work reported in this thesis is entirely original. This thesis has been composed independently by me at the Inter-University Centre for Astronomy and Astrophysics, Pune, under the supervision of Prof. Nishant Kumar Singh. I further declare that the subject matter presented in the thesis has not previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, associateship, fellowship, or any other similar title of any university or institution.

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Synopsis

The outer 30% of the Sun’s radial extent is unstably stratified; in this layer, heat is predominantly carried by convection. In stars much lighter than the Sun, convection occurs throughout the star, while heavier stars than the Sun have convective cores (Kippenhahn, Weigert, and Weiss 2012, section 22.3). Convection affects processes such as elemental mixing, angular momentum transport, and magnetic field generation.

Numerical simulations (e.g Miesch et al. 2008) of the Sun’s convection zone (CZ) predict that the velocity spectrum peaks at a wavenumber corresponding to the scale height at the bottom of the CZ. A similar phenomenon occurs in a simpler setup, convection between two plates maintained at fixed temperatures, where the most unstable mode has a wavenumber of the order of the depth of the domain (Chandrasekhar 1961, section 15). The most widely used theory of stellar convection, mixing length theory (MLT) (Kippenhahn, Weigert, and Weiss 2012, chap. 7), assumes that convection is dominated by eddies whose size is of the order of the local scale height.

On the other hand, recent observations (Hanasoge, Duvall, and Sreenivasan 2012; Hanasoge, Hotta, and Sreenivasan 2020) suggest that the velocity power spectrum peaks at much larger wavenumbers. The disagreement between simulations and theory on the one hand, and observations on the other, is referred to as the *convective conundrum*. One aspect of this thesis involves the construction of simplified models (shell models) to understand this disagreement.

A problem intimately related to convection is the question of how far convective flows from the CZ can *overshoot* into the RZ (radiative zone). Overshoot is important in stellar evolution modelling, as it means that convection can mix elements even in regions which are stably stratified. We have studied the dynamics of a cool blob of fluid descending in a stably stratified background.

The Sun’s rotational rate is a function of both radius and latitude: the Sun’s equator rotates faster than the poles, while there are shear layers at the base of the CZ (the tachocline) and near the surface. Various studies (Guerrero et al. 2013; Gastine et al. 2013; Käpylä, Käpylä, and Brandenburg 2014) have suggested that reproducing this differential rotation profile may require suppression of the convective velocities relative to the standard estimates. The problem of differential rotation is thus tied to the convective conundrum.

The Sun exhibits a sunspot cycle of 11 years, with an associated magnetic cycle

of 22 years. Further, sunspots preferentially form at different latitudes during different phases of the solar cycle. The canonical model of sunspot formation relies on the Sun's differential rotation profile to form flux tubes at the base of the CZ, which then rise to the surface and form sunspots (Babcock 1961; Leighton 1969; for a recent review of this picture, see Fan 2021). Recent helioseismic studies of active regions (patches of enhanced magnetic field on the Sun's surface, each of which often contains multiple sunspots) have cast doubt on this picture. In particular, Singh, Raichur, and Brandenburg (2016) and Waidele et al. (2023) report local strengthening of the f mode (a specific helioseismic mode) up to 48 hours before the emergence of an active region. This is much longer than the time rising flux tubes are expected to spend near the surface (Cheung et al. 2010), where the eigenfunction of the f mode peaks. Analytical studies of magnetic effects on helioseismic modes are limited to predictions of frequency shifts. While simulations have been performed in the past to study such effects (Singh, Brandenburg, and Rheinhardt 2014; Singh et al. 2015, 2020), they use extremely simple two-dimensional forced-turbulence setups in stepped-isothermal backgrounds. The amplitude of a particular mode is sensitive to the forcing function employed, and hence one needs to perform three-dimensional simulations of convection to understand the relevant effects. Part of the thesis describes such simulations that we have performed.¹

Once one doubts the canonical model of sunspot formation (and thus, by extension, the mechanism responsible for the solar cycle), it is natural to ask how far other mechanisms can reproduce the observational behaviour of sunspots. Some of our work has demonstrated nonlinear cycles in simulations, driven by interplay between rotation and the small-scale dynamo (SSD). Helical large-scale dynamo mechanisms generate magnetic fields such that the helicity spectrum has different signs at high and low wavenumbers (usually referred to as a *bihelical* spectrum). Motivated by this, we have also performed observational studies. However, we find that with the current state of observations, conclusions must be drawn with extreme caution.

Convective flows are anisotropic and have a nonzero correlation time. On the other hand, most theoretical studies of the SSD assume the correlation time of the velocity field is zero, and that it is isotropic. Even numerical studies typically focus on the isotropic case. Since the SSD is expected to be excited on the Sun, it is natural to study the effects on it of more realistic velocity fields that have properties similar to convective flows. We have thus analytically studied the effect of a nonzero correlation time on the kinematic stage of the SSD. In parallel, we have used anisotropically forced simulations of rotating turbulence to study whether there are latitudinal effects on the growth rate and the saturation level of the SSD.

Chapter 1 is introductory, while **chapter 13** states the main results of this thesis. The rest of the chapters are grouped into 6 parts, which we now describe.

¹Most of the simulations described in the thesis were performed using the Pencil code (Pencil Code Collaboration et al. 2021); see <http://pencil-code.org>.

Part I: Turbulence

Chapter 2 deals with the generation of anisotropy in rotating forced turbulence. While this chapter is not directly related to convection, it will be useful in interpreting the more complicated simulations discussed in a later chapter (chapter 6). The main result of this chapter is that in solenoidally forced rotating turbulence, rotational destabilization of vortices can lead to one-dimensionalization of the flow below the forcing scale, with the velocity component along the rotational axis being larger than the other two components.

Part II: Kinematic dynamo

In general, the Lorentz force turns the evolution of the magnetic field into a nonlinear problem, which is difficult to study analytically. As a first step, one can study the *kinematic limit*, where the magnetic field is assumed to be so weak that the effect of the Lorentz force on the velocity field can be neglected. The statistical properties of the velocity field can then be treated as given quantities, and one is interested in the statistical properties of the magnetic field. This part of the thesis is devoted to the study of the kinematic dynamo.

Magnetic fields are often correlated at length scales much larger than that of the turbulent velocity field. Mean-field magnetohydrodynamics takes advantage of this scale-separation to make the problem analytically tractable (Moffatt 1978; Krause and Rädler 1980). ‘Large-scale dynamo’, or LSD, refers to the generation of magnetic fields ordered on the system scale by fluid motions correlated at much smaller scales.

The statistical properties of the velocity field are often treated as deterministic quantities in kinematic studies. **Chapter 3** presents a simple calculation which shows that fluctuations of the turbulent kinetic energy at a particular spatial scale can induce the growth of a magnetic field at much larger scales.

The simplest treatments of the LSD are valid when the correlation time of the velocity field is zero. **Chapter 4** relaxes this assumption. As a toy problem, we first examine the diffusion of a passive scalar. We then apply the same technique to the evolution equation for the averaged magnetic field. A previous attempt to solve this problem (Nicklaus and Stix 1988) turns out to have predicted a turbulent diffusivity for the magnetic field that is the same as that for a passive scalar. We find additional contributions to the turbulent diffusion of the magnetic field.

It is well known that in a turbulent fluid, intermittent magnetic fields can be generated which are typically ordered on scales comparable to or smaller than that of the velocity field (the ‘small-scale dynamo’ or SSD) (Kazantsev 1968; Molchanov, Ruzmaïkin, and Sokolov 1985). The SSD grows on a timescale comparable to the eddy turnover time; this is much smaller than the timescale for growth of the LSD and the typical ages of astrophysical objects. Kulsrud and Anderson (1992) argue that the presence of SSD-generated magnetic fields invalidates the usual treatment of the LSD. While their conclusion has since been challenged (e.g. Subramanian

1998), magnetic fields generated by the SSD are still expected to affect the evolution of any object that contains a sufficiently turbulent plasma (i.e. where the magnetic Reynolds number, R_m , is above some critical value).

Intermittency leads to the higher moments of the magnetic field growing faster than would be expected from the growth rates of the lower moments (i.e. $\langle B^n \rangle$ growing faster than does $\langle B \rangle^n$). To study the SSD, one thus needs to consider second- or higher-order moments. In **chapter 5**, we use the technique described in chapter 4 to find out how the correlation time of the velocity field affects the evolution of the two-point correlation of the magnetic field.

Part III: Nonlinear dynamo

We earlier mentioned that the magnetic activity of the Sun depends on the latitude. In the CZ, the flows themselves are anisotropic, with the vertical component being larger than the horizontal components. The rotation of the Sun is another source of anisotropy for the flows. The angle between the direction of gravity and the rotational axis is dependent on the latitude. In **chapter 6**, we use simulations of anisotropically forced turbulence in rotating domains (with the direction of anisotropy allowed to be different from the rotational axis) to find out how the growth rate and the saturation level of the SSD are affected. The main result of this chapter is that at high Re , the saturation level of the SSD is suppressed much more strongly by rotation than the growth rate.

Part IV: Solar magnetic fields

The preceding two parts dealt with dynamos. It is now natural to ask whether one can, using solar observations, distinguish between different dynamo mechanisms. In this context, the spatial and spectral distribution of the magnetic helicity is of interest. In **chapter 7**, we describe major discrepancies between results from different telescopes, suggesting that one needs to be extremely careful while interpreting current observations of photospheric magnetic fields.

Part V: Convection and plumes

Chapter 8 studies the evolution of a cool blob of fluid (a *thermal*) descending in a stably stratified background. The motivation here is to understand overshoot by using semi-analytic models for the evolution of a thermal. We find a scaling relation between the initial size of the thermal and the depth of its penetration. We also show that assumptions about the internal structure of the thermal have a much stronger effect on its dynamics than expected.

Supposing one understands the dynamics of isolated blobs of fluid, one then has to construct additional models for (i) how multiple blobs interact; and (ii) how such flows affect the background state. Given the vast differences between experimentally accessible regimes and stellar regimes, three-dimensional numerical simulations are

indispensable to motivate such models (or, for that matter, to guide the construction of any theory of stellar convection). One of the challenges in solving the convective conundrum is the limited parameter regime that is computationally accessible. **Chapter 9** constructs a shell model for stratified convection to qualitatively study the effects of this restriction. We find indications that the convective conundrum may be explainable without appealing to rotation or magnetic fields, and that the nature of convection is sensitive to the thermal Prandtl number.

We earlier mentioned that the conventional picture of sunspot formation is starting to be questioned. One factor in favour of the conventional picture is that it readily explains why sunspots preferentially form in a certain range of *active latitudes*. **Chapter 10** uses simulations of rotating convection to examine latitudinal effects on magnetic cycles. The goal of such a study is to understand if alternative mechanisms also allow the existence of active latitudes on the Sun. We indeed find that at certain latitudes of our setup, magnetic cycles are excited which seem to depend on the existence of an SSD.

Part VI: Helioseismology

The Sun supports a wide variety of waves. Depending on the nature of the restoring force, the corresponding modes (Leibacher and Stein 1981) are classified into various branches. The eigenfunctions of each type of mode have characteristic dependences on depth, and are thus sensitive to different layers of the Sun. Helioseismology uses observations of the amplitudes and frequencies of these modes at the solar surface to infer the properties of deeper layers (Christensen-Dalsgaard 2002).

One expects a particular mode to not be strongly dependent on the solar structure in regions where its eigenfunction is small. This is motivated by the fact that if a perturbation is added to a wave evolution equation, time-independent perturbation theory tells us that to the lowest order in the perturbation, the frequency shift of a particular mode is given by the trace of the projection of the perturbation onto the corresponding eigenmode (Sakurai 2006, p. 304). Thus, it is important to understand how the eigenfunctions of various modes depend on the radius. **Chapter 11** examines a long-standing debate about the number of radial nodes of the lowest p mode. We find that the number of radial nodes of a particular p mode depends on the wavenumber. In a plane-parallel domain, the difference is due to the fact that waves of high-enough horizontal wavenumber are internally reflected before reaching the bottom of the domain, with modes which are reflected from the bottom of the domain having one node less than those which are internally reflected. However, this explanation does not work in a spherical domain, where, in the Cowling approximation, one simply finds that a p mode of a particular order has one node more when $l \neq 0$ than when $l = 0$.

It is difficult to confirm or rule out specific dynamo mechanisms using currently available magnetograms (chapter 7). Moreover, even when taken at face value, magnetograms only tell us about the magnetic field configuration at the surface of the Sun. Does helioseismology allow us to say anything about subsurface magnetic

fields? The immediate motivation for this question is that such information could help us understand the mechanism of sunspot formation. More generally, since magnetic fields are sometimes invoked to explain the convective conundrum or the formation of the tachocline, constraining them might help confirm or rule out these explanations. In **chapter 12**, we examine magnetic effects on helioseismic modes. We do this by imposing prescribed magnetic fields in three-dimensional simulations of convection and measuring the responses of various modes. While we confirm the qualitative findings of previous two-dimensional forced-turbulence simulations, further work is required to make a connection with observations.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

We first describe the problems that motivated the work in this thesis. We will then mention how its chapters fit into the big picture.

1.1 The convective conundrum

In a fluid, heat can be transported in three ways: (i) emission and absorption of photons (radiation); (ii) molecular collisions (conduction); and (iii) bulk motion of the fluid (convection).

The heat flux due to conduction is described by Fourier's law:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{cond}} = -k\nabla T \tag{1.1}$$

where k is the thermal conductivity, and T is the temperature. In the solar context, the mean free path of photons is very small compared to the length scales of interest, except in the very tenuous outer layers. While the outer layers of the Sun are not unworthy of study, they are not the focus of this thesis. When the mean free path of photons is small, radiation can be treated similar to conduction, by defining a temperature-dependent radiative conductivity (Kippenhahn, Weigert, and Weiss 2012, chapter 5). Hereafter, when we refer to conductivity or conduction, it should be understood as including the radiative contribution.

The densities and temperatures at the center of the Sun are enormous. In such conditions, heat can be generated by nuclear fusion (Krane 1987, section 14.3). Further from the center, the densities and temperatures decrease, so that nuclear fusion does not occur. Nevertheless, the heat generated at the center has to be carried to the surface, whence it can escape as radiation.

The temperature gradient between the center of the Sun and its surface can cause the transport of heat by conduction. However, it turns out that a system where hotter fluid underlies cooler fluid is stable only when the entropy of the fluid increases with height. When the fluid is unstably stratified, fluid motions grow, thereby allowing some of the heat to be transported by convection.

The outer 30% of the Sun’s radial extent is unstably stratified. In stars much lighter than the Sun, convection occurs throughout the star, while heavier stars than the Sun have convective cores (Kippenhahn, Weigert, and Weiss 2012, section 22.3). Convection affects processes such as elemental mixing, angular momentum transport, and magnetic field generation.

From an engineer’s point of view, convection is important for industrial applications such as heat exchangers. Various models and scaling relations are thus available for such convective flows (e.g. Bergman et al. 2011, section 8.5). However, convection in stars occurs in a parameter regime very different from those encountered in everyday life, and so the aforementioned models and scaling relations are not expected to be valid.

In a weakly stratified fluid in which the top boundary is maintained at a lower temperature than the bottom boundary (the simplest possible convecting system, Rayleigh-Bénard convection), the *Rayleigh number* (Ra) quantifies how unstable the stratification is, and may be interpreted as a measure of how strongly convection is driven. The convective instability sets in when Ra is above some critical value. Just above this critical value, the fastest growing unstable mode has a wavenumber of the order of the height of the system (Chandrasekhar 1961, section 15).

The standard theory of astrophysical convection is mixing length theory (MLT), where the eddies responsible for convection are assumed to be of a single scale (a fixed fraction of the scale height; this fraction is a free parameter) (Böhm-Vitense 1992, chap. 6; Kippenhahn, Weigert, and Weiss 2012, chap. 7). This results in the convective flux being determined by the solution of a cubic equation at each radius. The predictions of MLT are very sensitive to the mixing length parameter, and hence MLT has been criticised as an unfalsifiable theory (Canuto 1996). Further, Abbett et al. (1997) have found that even when the mixing length parameter is adjusted to match the value of the total flux in a simulation of convection, it is unable to reproduce the depth-dependence of quantities such as the temperature and the entropy gradient.

Various authors have proposed models of convection that assume more realistic or physically motivated flow structures or spectra (e.g. Canuto 1996; Canuto and Dubovikov 1998; Rempel 2004). Nevertheless, such models have not caught on because of the apparent versatility of MLT. It is worth noting that while MESA, a popular stellar evolution code, has recently moved beyond astrophysical MLT (which we described above) by solving a differential equation for the specific kinetic energy (see Jermyn et al. 2023, section 3), it still uses a mixing length assumption to model the dissipation of kinetic energy.

Simulations of the entirety of the Sun’s convection zone (CZ) typically predict that the velocity spectrum peaks at low wavenumbers, corresponding to the scale height at the bottom of the CZ. Figure 1.1 shows various inferences for the power spectrum of the azimuthal component of the velocity field in the CZ. The line marked ‘ASH’ comes from a simulation covering $0.71R_{\odot} < r < 0.98R_{\odot}$ (where R_{\odot} denotes the radius of the Sun), using the Anelastic Spherical Harmonic code (Miesch et al. 2008). The simulation using the Stagger code (Stein and Nordlund

Figure 1.1: Estimates (from both observations and simulations) of the power spectrum of the azimuthal component of the velocity in the Sun’s CZ. This figure is from Proxauf (2021, figure 3.3).

2006; Stein and Nordlund 2007) only includes the top 20 Mm of the CZ (Gizon and Birch 2012, caption of fig. 1), and thus gives a spectrum peaking at large wavenumbers ¹

On the other hand, based on time-distance helioseismology, Hanasoge, Duvall, and Sreenivasan (2012)² have predicted an upper limit (marked as ‘HDS2012’ in figure 1.1) that is much lower at the low-wavelength end. Roudier et al. (2012) and Proxauf (2021) have obtained similar results based on tracking the velocities of granules in solar images. The line marked ‘ring pipeline’ has been obtained by Proxauf (2021) by applying ring-diagram helioseismology to SDO/HMI images. Hanasoge, Hotta, and Sreenivasan (2020), by measuring the coupling between normal modes,

¹Gizon and Birch (2012, fig. 1), who seem to be the source of the spectrum marked as ‘stagger’ in figure 1.1, show the spectrum computed from the 96 Mm × 96 Mm × 20 Mm simulations run by Stein and Nordlund (2007). Note that Gizon and Birch (2012) have erroneously cited an earlier work describing an even smaller simulation, only 2.5 Mm deep (Stein and Nordlund 2006).

²Hanasoge, Duvall, and Sreenivasan (2012) predicted an even lower upper limit than that shown in figure 1.1; the latter is the result of correcting some mistakes pointed out by Proxauf (2021).

have obtained results (not shown) consistent with the above observations. On the other hand, Greer et al. (2015) have used an unconventional implementation of ring-diagram helioseismology to obtain results (marked ‘GHFT2015’) inconsistent with the above observations.

The mismatch between observations on the one hand, and theory and simulations on the other hand, is dubbed the *convective conundrum*. A variety of explanations have been proposed.

According to one proposal, the deep convection zone is dominated by cool downflowing plumes (‘entropy rain’) from a highly unstable layer near the surface (Spruit 1997; Brandenburg 2016; Cossette and Rast 2016). In this picture, the length scale of convection is set by the scale height at the surface or by the depth of the top unstable layer, and so convective flows need not be excited at large scales deep in the convection zone. Possible reasons for not observing such downflows in simulations of deep convection are that (i) enhanced diffusivities suppress these small-scale flows; and (ii) near-surface layers are typically not included in such simulations. However, Hotta, Iijima, and Kusano (2019) claim that the mere inclusion of near-surface layers in simulations is not sufficient to explain the convective conundrum.

Another proposed solution to the convective conundrum is that the flows are suppressed by small-scale magnetic fields (Fan and Fang 2014; Hotta, Rempel, and Yokoyama 2015; Hotta and Kusano 2021). The small-scale magnetic fields supposedly result in an enhanced turbulent Prandtl number (the ratio of the turbulent kinematic viscosity to the turbulent thermal diffusivity), which may then suppress the large-scale velocities (O’Mara et al. 2016; Karak, Miesch, and Bekki 2018). However, it is still unclear (Karak, Miesch, and Bekki 2018) if an enhanced turbulent Prandtl number can reproduce the differential rotation profile observed in the Sun.

A third proposal is that rotation suppresses convective flows at the largest scales (Featherstone and Hindman 2016a; Vasil, Julien, and Featherstone 2021). However, arguments about the influence of rotation typically make assumptions about the convective amplitudes, and thus it is not clear if rotation alone is enough to suppress the convective velocities, or if the velocities get suppressed by some other effect, allowing rotation to become important.

More promisingly, based on 3D numerical simulations of non-rotating, non-magnetic, and anelastic convection in spherical domains at $Pr = 1$ (the Prandtl number, Pr , is the ratio of the kinematic viscosity to the thermal diffusivity; the latter may include both conduction and radiation), Featherstone and Hindman (2016b) report that the kinetic energy at large scales decreases as Ra increases. Since $Ra \sim 10^{20}$ in the Sun (Schumacher and Sreenivasan 2020), this may explain, to some extent, the convective conundrum. However, Käpylä (2021) finds that the spectral distribution of velocity is insensitive to Ra . This discrepancy might be due to the different sub-grid-scale (SGS) models they use. The SGS diffusion in Featherstone and Hindman (2016b) is applied to the total entropy, whereas Käpylä (2021) applies it only to the entropy fluctuations such that it does not contribute to the mean energy flux.

1.2 Differential rotation

The rotational rate of the Sun varies with latitude, such that the equator rotates faster than the poles. Further, it also varies radially, such that there are two localized layers of strong shear: one, called the tachocline, is located at the bottom of the CZ (Goode et al. 1991; Spiegel and Zahn 1992; Thompson et al. 1996), while the other is located near the surface (Thompson et al. 1996; Barekat, Schou, and Gizon 2014).

Simulations where the Coriolis number (which measures the dynamical importance of the Coriolis force) is comparable to that estimated for the Sun show ‘antisolar’ differential rotation (where the equator rotates slower than the poles). One needs to have higher Coriolis numbers to obtain solar differential rotation (Guerrero et al. 2013; Gastine et al. 2013; Käpylä, Käpylä, and Brandenburg 2014). Moreover, Gastine et al. (2013) and Käpylä, Käpylä, and Brandenburg (2014) report that the differential rotation profile is bistable, i.e. for intermediate values of the Coriolis number, both solar and antisolar differential rotation profiles are possible, with the actual profile depending on the initial conditions.

As mentioned earlier, the Coriolis number estimated for the Sun depends on the value of the turbulent velocity and its correlation length. Resolution of the convective conundrum would thus help us understand the Sun’s differential rotation profile.

1.3 Magnetic fields, sunspots and the solar cycle

Occasionally, dark regions (called sunspots) form on the surface of the Sun. These regions can last for weeks, and their diameters can reach 60 Mm (Solanki 2003, sections 2.3–2.4).

We now summarize some observational properties of sunspots (for a review, see Hathaway 2015, sections 3.3, 3.6) that are used to constrain their formation mechanisms. The number of sunspots varies cyclically, with a period of roughly 11 years. Further, sunspots preferentially form in a band of latitudes, the active latitudes. At the beginning of the cycle (just after the maximum), sunspots tend to form close to a latitude of 30° ; as the cycle progresses, they tend to form closer and closer to the equator (this is referred to as Spörer’s law). In groups of sunspots, the leading sunspot (in the sense of the Sun’s rotation) is, on average, closer to the equator than the trailing one. Hale’s polarity rules describe the fact that the sign of the magnetic field in the leading sunspot tends to be the opposite for groups on opposite sides of the equator, or for groups in the same hemisphere but in consecutive sunspot cycles. Joy’s law states that the angle between the equator and the the line joining these spots increases with latitude.

We now know that the 11-year sunspot cycle is accompanied by a magnetic cycle, 22 years long. The most popular model of sunspot formation, the Babcock-Leighton model (Babcock 1961; Leighton 1969; for a recent review of this picture, see Fan

2021), suggests that sunspots are formed by flux tubes rising from the bottom of the Sun’s convection zone. A major argument in favour of these models is that they predict Spörer’s law, Joy’s law, and Hale’s polarity rules (Babcock 1961; Leighton 1969; Charbonneau 2020, section 5). However, recent observations cast doubt on this picture.

Kosovichev and Stenflo (2008) and Schunker et al. (2020) have shown that Joy’s law is not obeyed in newborn active regions (patches of enhanced magnetic field on the Sun’s surface, each of which often contains multiple sunspots); rather, it only becomes evident two days later. This disagrees with what is expected from models of rising flux tubes.

An independent point of disagreement with the rising flux tube model comes from recent helioseismic studies of active regions. Singh, Raichur, and Brandenburg (2016) and Waidele et al. (2023) report local strengthening of the f mode (a specific helioseismic mode) up to 48 hours before the emergence of an active region. This is much longer than the time rising flux tubes are expected to spend near the surface (Cheung et al. 2010), where the eigenfunction of the f mode peaks. Analytical studies of magnetic effects on helioseismic modes are limited to predictions of frequency shifts. While simulations have been performed in the past to study such effects (Singh, Brandenburg, and Rheinhardt 2014; Singh et al. 2015, 2020), they use extremely simple two-dimensional forced-turbulence setups in stepped-isothermal backgrounds.

Magnetic fields themselves may affect the Sun’s differential rotation. For example, Matilsky et al. (2022) have found that a magnetic field in the Sun’s radiative zone can explain the sharpness of its tachocline.

1.4 Structure of the thesis

The rest of this thesis is grouped into 6 parts, excluding **chapter 13** which summarizes the results of the thesis. Let us see how these parts fit into the context laid out above.

Part I: Turbulence

Chapter 2 deals with the generation of anisotropy in rotating forced turbulence. While this chapter is not directly related to convection, it will be used to interpret simulations performed in a later chapter (chapter 6).

Part II: Kinematic dynamo

Astrophysical magnetic fields are observed on galactic, stellar, and planetary scales (Brandenburg and Subramanian 2005b, section 2; Jones 2011). As mentioned earlier, stars such as the Sun exhibit periodic magnetic cycles. The Earth itself has a dipolar magnetic field that shields it from the solar wind. Dynamo theory

attempts to explain the generation and sustenance of such magnetic fields (Moffatt 1978; Krause and Rädler 1980; Brandenburg and Subramanian 2005b; Shukurov and Subramanian 2022).

In general, the Lorentz force turns the evolution of the magnetic field into a nonlinear problem, which is difficult to study analytically. As a first step, one can study the *kinematic limit*, where the magnetic field is assumed to be so weak that the effect of the Lorentz force on the velocity field can be neglected. The statistical properties of the velocity field can then be treated as given quantities, and one is interested in the statistical properties of the magnetic field. This part of the thesis is devoted to the study of the kinematic dynamo.

Magnetic fields are often correlated at length scales much larger than that of the turbulent velocity field. Mean-field magnetohydrodynamics takes advantage of this scale-separation to make the problem analytically tractable (Moffatt 1978; Krause and Rädler 1980). ‘Large-scale dynamo’, or LSD, refers to the generation of magnetic fields ordered on the system scale by fluid motions correlated at much smaller scales.

The statistical properties of the velocity field are often treated as deterministic quantities in kinematic studies. **Chapter 3** presents a simple calculation which shows that fluctuations of the turbulent kinetic energy at a particular spatial scale can induce the growth of a magnetic field at much larger scales.

The simplest treatments of the LSD are valid when the correlation time of the velocity field is zero. **Chapter 4** relaxes this assumption. As a toy problem, we first examine the diffusion of a passive scalar. We then apply the same technique to the evolution equation for the averaged magnetic field.

It is well known that in a turbulent fluid, intermittent magnetic fields can be generated which are typically ordered on scales comparable to or smaller than that of the velocity field (the ‘small-scale dynamo’ or SSD) (Kazantsev 1968; Molchanov, Ruzmaïkin, and Sokolov 1985). The SSD grows on a timescale comparable to the eddy turnover time; this is much smaller than the timescale for growth of the LSD and the typical ages of astrophysical objects. Kulsrud and Anderson (1992) argue that the presence of SSD-generated magnetic fields invalidates the usual treatment of the LSD. While their conclusion has since been challenged (e.g. Subramanian 1998), magnetic fields generated by the SSD are still expected to affect the evolution of any object that contains a sufficiently turbulent plasma (i.e. where the magnetic Reynolds number, R_m , is above some critical value).

Intermittency leads to the higher moments of the magnetic field growing faster than would be expected from the growth rates of the lower moments (i.e. $\langle B^n \rangle$ growing faster than does $\langle B \rangle^n$). To study the SSD, one thus needs to consider second- or higher-order moments. In **chapter 5**, we use the technique described in **chapter 4** to find out how the correlation time of the velocity field affects the evolution of the two-point correlation of the magnetic field.

Part III: Nonlinear dynamo

We earlier mentioned that the magnetic activity of the Sun shows strong latitudinal dependence. In the CZ, the flows themselves are anisotropic, with the vertical component being larger than the horizontal components. The rotation of the Sun is another source of anisotropy for the flows. The angle between the direction of gravity and the rotational axis is dependent on the latitude. In **chapter 6**, we perform simulations of anisotropically forced turbulence in rotating domains (with the direction of anisotropy allowed to be different from the rotational axis) to find out how the growth rate and the saturation level of the SSD are affected.

Part IV: Solar magnetic fields

The preceding two parts dealt with dynamos. It is now natural to ask whether it is observationally possible to distinguish between different dynamo mechanisms. The study described in **chapter 7** began as an attempt to reproduce some earlier work. However, we found major discrepancies between results from different telescopes, suggesting that one needs to be extremely careful while interpreting current observations of photospheric magnetic fields.

Part V: Convection and plumes

Chapter 8 studies the evolution of a cool blob of fluid descending in a stably stratified background. The motivation here is to understand how far flows from the CZ can penetrate into the stably stratified layer beneath.

Supposing one understands the dynamics of isolated blobs of fluid, one then has to construct additional models for (i) how multiple blobs interact; and (ii) how such flows affect the background state. Given the vast differences between experimentally accessible regimes and stellar regimes, three-dimensional numerical simulations are indispensable to motivate such models (or, for that matter, to guide the construction of any theory of stellar convection). One of the challenges in solving the convective conundrum is the limited parameter regime that is computationally accessible. **Chapter 9** constructs a simplified model of stratified convection to qualitatively study the effects of this restriction.

We earlier mentioned some problems with the conventional picture of sunspot formation. One factor in favour of the conventional picture is that it readily explains why sunspots preferentially form in a certain range of *active latitudes*. **Chapter 10** uses simulations of rotating convection to examine latitudinal effects on magnetic cycles. The long-term goal of such a study would be to check if alternative mechanisms also allow the existence of active latitudes.

Part VI: Helioseismology

The Sun supports a wide variety of waves. Depending on the nature of the restoring force, the corresponding modes (Leibacher and Stein 1981) are classified into various branches. The eigenfunctions of each type of mode have characteristic dependences on depth, and are thus sensitive to different layers of the Sun. Helioseismology uses observations of the amplitudes and frequencies of these modes at the solar surface to infer the properties of deeper layers (Christensen-Dalsgaard 2002).

One expects a particular mode to not be strongly dependent on the solar structure in regions where its eigenfunction is small. This is motivated by the fact that if a perturbation is added to a wave evolution equation, time-independent perturbation theory tells us that to the lowest order in the perturbation, the frequency shift of a particular mode is given by the trace of the projection of the perturbation onto the corresponding eigenmode (Sakurai 2006, p. 304). Thus, it is important to understand how the eigenfunctions of various modes depend on the radius. **Chapter 11** examines a long-standing debate about the number of radial nodes of the lowest p mode.

It is difficult to confirm or rule out specific dynamo mechanisms using currently available magnetograms (chapter 7). Moreover, even when taken at face value, magnetograms only tell us about the magnetic field configuration at the surface of the Sun. Does helioseismology allow us to say anything about subsurface magnetic fields? The immediate motivation for this question is that such information could help us understand the mechanism of sunspot formation. More generally, since magnetic fields are sometimes invoked to explain the convective conundrum or the formation of the tachocline, constraining them might help confirm or rule out these explanations. In **chapter 12**, we examine magnetic effects on helioseismic modes. We do this by imposing prescribed magnetic fields in simulations of convection and measuring the responses of various modes.

Part I
Turbulence

Chapter 2

Vortices and anisotropy in rotating turbulence

2.1 Introduction

In simulations of rapidly rotating convection, various authors have reported the formation of large-scale vortices whose size is apparently only limited by the size of the simulation box (Chan 2003, 2007; Käpylä, Mantere, and Hackman 2011; Guervilly, Hughes, and Jones 2014, 2017; Bushby et al. 2018). In particular, Bushby et al. (2018) report that such large-scale vortices are reproduced by three independently written codes, suggesting that they are not a numerical artefact. Käpylä (2019b, fig. 3) has also observed such vortices in simpler simulations of rotating anisotropically forced turbulence. In chapter 6, we will see that such vortices can excite a dynamo. While this was our initial motivation for the study described in this chapter, we will soon see that the purely hydrodynamic case holds some surprises.

Most theoretical treatments of rotating turbulence (e.g. Baqui and Davidson 2015; Nazarenko and Schekochihin 2011, section 4.1) postulate or predict that rotational effects are negligible at wavenumbers larger than the Zeman wavenumber, which is defined on dimensional grounds based on the rotation and dissipation rates (Zeman 1994, eq. 6). One thus expects that even when rotation causes the turbulence to be anisotropic, such anisotropy is restricted to wavenumbers smaller than the Zeman wavenumber, with the anisotropic cascade giving way to an isotropic one at wavenumbers much larger than the Zeman scale. The idea of turbulence returning to isotropy at large wavenumbers is not unique to rotating turbulence; a similar idea is prevalent in treatments of stratified turbulence (Dougherty 1961; Bolgiano 1959).

In this chapter, we study the generation of anisotropy in simulations of isothermal forced rotating turbulence. Section 2.2 discusses how the anisotropy of turbulence at different scales can be quantified. Section 2.3 describes our simulation setup. Section 2.4 examines the onset of the large-scale vortex instability. Here, we

find interesting behaviour even in the absence of the large-scale vortex. In section 2.5, we examine the scale-wise anisotropy of rotating turbulence to understand this behaviour. Section 2.6 demonstrates that at high-enough Re , the small scales return to isotropy as one would naively expect. Section 2.7 explores how our results are affected by our choice of forcing function. Finally, we summarize our findings in section 2.8.

2.2 Quantifying the anisotropy of turbulence

There are two ways of thinking of anisotropy. One, preferred in theoretical studies, is that the turbulent eddies have different length scales in different directions. Another is that the individual velocity components have different RMS (root mean square) amplitudes. At least for incompressible turbulence, the condition $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0$ leads us to expect both these notions to be closely linked.

Since both the turnover time and the power spectrum in turbulence are scale-dependent, different scales are expected to be affected differently by an imposed external source of anisotropy (be it rotation, a magnetic field, or stratification). It is thus useful to quantify the anisotropy of turbulence at different scales.

2.2.1 Anisotropy of length scales

The conventional method is to compute the velocity power spectrum by restricting the wavevectors which are summed over. One then characterizes the anisotropy by computing two different velocity power spectra: $E_{\perp}(k)$ and $E_{\parallel}(k)$,¹ which correspond to binning the Fourier-space double correlation of the velocity field according to the components of the wavevector perpendicular and parallel to the direction of anisotropy respectively. This seems to be preferred in theoretical studies (e.g. Goldreich and Sridhar 1995; Nazarenko and Schekochihin 2011).

2.2.1.1 Definitions

Let the direction of anisotropy be $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$. Denoting

$$\Phi_{ii}(\mathbf{k}) \equiv \langle u_i(\mathbf{k}) u_i^*(\mathbf{k}) \rangle \quad (2.1)$$

we define (see Baqui and Davidson 2015, eqs. 1, 2)

$$E(k) \equiv \frac{1}{2} \int d\mathbf{k} \delta(|\mathbf{k}| - k) \Phi_{ii}(\mathbf{k}) \quad (2.2)$$

$$E_{\parallel}(k) \equiv \frac{1}{2} \int d\mathbf{k} \delta(|\mathbf{k} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{z}}| - k) \Phi_{ii}(\mathbf{k}) \quad (2.3)$$

$$E_{\perp}(k) \equiv \frac{1}{2} \int d\mathbf{k} \delta(|\mathbf{k} \times \hat{\mathbf{z}}| - k) \Phi_{ii}(\mathbf{k}) \quad (2.4)$$

¹These are conventionally denoted as $E(k_{\perp})$ and $E(k_{\parallel})$ respectively.

These are normalized such that (Baqui and Davidson 2015, eq. 3)

$$\int_0^\infty dk E(k) = \int_0^\infty dk E_{\parallel}(k) = \int_0^\infty dk E_{\perp}(k) = \frac{1}{2} \langle u^2 \rangle \quad (2.5)$$

2.2.1.2 What if the turbulence is isotropic?

If the turbulence is homogeneous, isotropic, and nonhelical, we can write (see Batchelor 1953, eq. 3.4.12; Moffatt 1978, eq. 7.56; Lesieur 2008, eq. 5.84)

$$\Phi_{ii}(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{E(|\mathbf{k}|)}{2\pi |\mathbf{k}|^2} \quad (2.6)$$

Plugging this into equation 2.3, we find

$$E_{\parallel}(a) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int d\mathbf{k} \delta(|\mathbf{k} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{z}}| - a) \frac{E(|\mathbf{k}|)}{|\mathbf{k}|^2} \quad (2.7)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int d\mathbf{k}_{\perp} \frac{E\left(\sqrt{a^2 + |\mathbf{k}_{\perp}|^2}\right)}{a^2 + |\mathbf{k}_{\perp}|^2} \quad (2.8)$$

$$= \int_0^\infty k_{\perp} dk_{\perp} \frac{E\left(\sqrt{a^2 + k_{\perp}^2}\right)}{a^2 + k_{\perp}^2} \quad (2.9)$$

$$= \int_0^\infty dk_{\perp} \frac{k_{\perp}}{a^2 + k_{\perp}^2} E\left(\sqrt{a^2 + k_{\perp}^2}\right) \quad (2.10)$$

$$= \int_a^\infty dk \frac{E(k)}{k} \quad (2.11)$$

which agrees with the relation derived by Davidson (2004, eq. 8.37c). Similarly, from equation 2.4, we find

$$E_{\perp}(a) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int d\mathbf{k} \delta(|\mathbf{k} \times \hat{\mathbf{z}}| - a) \frac{E(|\mathbf{k}|)}{|\mathbf{k}|^2} \quad (2.12)$$

$$= \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk_{\parallel} \int d\mathbf{k}_{\perp} \delta(|\mathbf{k}_{\perp}| - a) \frac{E\left(\sqrt{k_{\parallel}^2 + |\mathbf{k}_{\perp}|^2}\right)}{k_{\parallel}^2 + |\mathbf{k}_{\perp}|^2} \quad (2.13)$$

$$= \int_0^\infty dk_{\parallel} \int_0^\infty dk_{\perp} k_{\perp} \delta(k_{\perp} - a) \frac{E\left(\sqrt{k_{\parallel}^2 + k_{\perp}^2}\right)}{k_{\parallel}^2 + k_{\perp}^2} \quad (2.14)$$

$$= \int_0^\infty dk_{\parallel} \frac{a}{k_{\parallel}^2 + a^2} E\left(\sqrt{k_{\parallel}^2 + a^2}\right) \quad (2.15)$$

$$= \int_a^\infty dk \frac{a E(k)}{k\sqrt{k^2 - a^2}} \quad (2.16)$$

We thus see that even when the turbulence is homogeneous, isotropic, and nonhelical, one cannot expect $E_{\parallel}(k) = E_{\perp}(k)$.

2.2.1.3 Aliasing

Consistent with what we saw above, Davidson (2004, sections 8.1.5, 8.1.9) notes that in general, 1D (e.g. $E_{\parallel}(k)$) or 2D (e.g. $E_{\perp}(k)$) spectra cannot be interpreted in the same way as 3D spectra (e.g. $E(k)$). The point is that, for example, fixing the value of k_{\parallel} (which is just the projection of \mathbf{k} onto $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$) does not fix the value of $|\mathbf{k}|$, and thus $E_{\parallel}(k_{\parallel})$ depends on all modes for which $|\mathbf{k}| \geq k_{\parallel}$. Davidson refers to this as ‘aliasing’.

2.2.2 Anisotropy of velocity components

In this chapter, following Käpylä (2019b, eq. 30, 2019a, eq. 17), we quantify the vertical anisotropy of the flow by

$$A_V \equiv \frac{\langle u_x^2 \rangle + \langle u_y^2 \rangle - 2 \langle u_z^2 \rangle}{\langle u^2 \rangle} \quad (2.17)$$

where $\langle \square \rangle$ denotes the volume average of \square . Note that $-2 \leq A_V \leq 1$, and $A_V = 0$ if the turbulence is isotropic. The spectral analogue of this quantity is (e.g. Käpylä 2019a, eq. 27):

$$A_V(k) \equiv \frac{E_x(k) + E_y(k) - 2E_z(k)}{E(k)} \quad (2.18)$$

where, for example, $E_x(k)$ is the scalar 3D power spectrum of u_x .

2.3 Simulation setup

We consider isothermal forced turbulence in a cubical periodic box of side L . Rotation is added in the f -plane approximation, i.e. spatial variation of the Coriolis force is ignored, and there is no centrifugal force. We choose units in which the sound speed c , and the initial (uniform) density ρ_0 are 1; and $L = 2\pi$. These choices mean that if we define $k_0 \equiv 2\pi/L$, the unit for time is $(ck_0)^{-1}$; length is k_0^{-1} ; and mass is $\rho_0 k_0^{-3}$. We solve the continuity and momentum equations:

$$\frac{D \ln \rho}{dt} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \quad (2.19)$$

$$\rho \frac{D \mathbf{u}}{dt} = -c^2 \nabla \rho - 2\rho \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{u} + \nabla \cdot (2\rho \nu \overleftrightarrow{S}) + \rho \mathbf{F} \quad (2.20)$$

where

$$S_{ij} \equiv \frac{1}{2} \left(\partial_i u_j + \partial_j u_i - \frac{2}{3} \delta_{ij} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \right) \quad (2.21)$$

with ρ being the density; \mathbf{u} the velocity; $D/dt \equiv \partial/\partial t + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla$ the convective derivative; c the speed of sound; $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ the rotational rate; ν the kinematic viscosity;

and \mathbf{F} a forcing function. The forcing function is given by (Haugen, Brandenburg, and Mee 2004)

$$\mathbf{F} = f_0 c \sqrt{\frac{kc}{\delta t}} \frac{\mathbf{k} \times \hat{\mathbf{e}}}{\sqrt{k^2 - (\mathbf{k} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{e}})^2}} \cos(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x} + \phi) \quad (2.22)$$

where δt is the length of the timestep, and f_0 is a dimensionless factor that controls the amplitude of the forcing. The quantities \mathbf{k} , $\hat{\mathbf{e}}$, and ϕ are randomly chosen at each timestep, subject to the following constraints: \mathbf{k} is chosen such that $2.5 < k < 3.5$ (resulting in a mean wavenumber $k_f \approx 3.13$); $\hat{\mathbf{e}}$ is a unit vector randomly chosen in the plane normal to \mathbf{k} ; and $-\pi \leq \phi < \pi$. Further, we choose $f_0 = 3 \times 10^{-2}$. Since this forcing function is divergence-free, we refer to it as ‘solenoidal’ forcing.

The equations described above are solved using the PENCIL code (Pencil Code Collaboration et al. 2021).² Spatial derivatives are discretized using a sixth-order finite difference scheme, while the equations are evolved in time using a third-order Runge-Kutta method. Upwinding is used for advection of the density and the velocity.

The initial velocity is set to zero, while the initial density is set to ρ_0 . The timestep is chosen to keep the Courant numbers based on the advective and diffusive terms less than 0.6 and 0.25 respectively.

In addition to the parameters whose values are mentioned above, the setup is completely specified by Ω , ν , and the grid size.

We now define certain diagnostics which are useful to characterize the simulation. The Reynolds number, $\text{Re} \equiv 2\pi u_{\text{rms}} / (\nu k_f)$, quantifies how turbulent the flow is. The Coriolis number, $\text{Co} \equiv 2\pi\Omega / (u_{\text{rms}} k_f)$, quantifies the dynamical importance of the Coriolis force. The Mach number, $\text{Ma} \equiv u_{\text{rms}} / c$, can be used to judge the degree of compressibility of the flow.

2.4 Onset of the large-scale vortex instability

We first consider the set of simulations whose parameters are given in table 2.1 (along with some diagnostic values). Appendix 2.A describes a resolution-independence study. Each simulation is run for $500/(ck_0)$ time units, out of which averaged quantities are measured over the last $300/(ck_0)$ time units (if the turnover time is estimated as $2\pi/(u_{\text{rms}} k_f)$, this corresponds to 10–30 turnover times).

Figure 2.1 shows how A_V (equation 2.17) varies as a function of the rotation rate for different values of the viscosity. Unexpectedly, we find that the value of A_V decreases with increasing rotation for small rotation rates. This corresponds to the vertical velocity component (for the sake of brevity, we shall use ‘vertical’ to mean ‘along the rotation axis’ here) being larger than those in the other two directions.

For $\Omega \gtrsim 0.2 ck_0$, we find that at least when ν is small enough, A_V quickly becomes large and positive. Figure 2.2 shows that in these cases, most of the

²<http://pencil-code.org>

$\frac{\Omega}{ck_0}$	$\frac{\nu}{ck_0^{-1}}$	N_x	Re	Co	Ma
0.05	10^{-2}	32	17	1.2	0.08
0.15	10^{-2}	32	17	3.6	0.08
0.25	10^{-2}	32	17	5.9	0.08
0.5	10^{-2}	32	17	11.8	0.08
1	10^{-2}	32	17	24.0	0.08
0	5×10^{-3}	32	44	0.0	0.11
0.005	5×10^{-3}	32	44	0.1	0.11
0.05	5×10^{-3}	32	45	0.9	0.11
0.15	5×10^{-3}	32	45	2.7	0.11
0.25	5×10^{-3}	32	45	4.4	0.11
0.5	5×10^{-3}	32	46	8.7	0.12
1	5×10^{-3}	32	46	17.5	0.11
0	3×10^{-3}	64	86	0.0	0.13
0.2	3×10^{-3}	64	90	3.0	0.13
0.5	3×10^{-3}	64	96	6.9	0.14
0	2×10^{-3}	64	141	0.0	0.14
0.15	2×10^{-3}	64	146	2.1	0.15
0.2	2×10^{-3}	64	150	2.7	0.15
0.25	2×10^{-3}	64	153	3.3	0.15
0.5	2×10^{-3}	64	173	5.8	0.17
0.15	10^{-3}	128	318	1.9	0.16
0.25	10^{-3}	128	353	2.8	0.18
0.05	5×10^{-4}	128	647	0.6	0.16
0.15	5×10^{-4}	128	672	1.8	0.17
0.2	5×10^{-4}	128	702	2.3	0.18
0.25	5×10^{-4}	128	714	2.8	0.18
0.05	2×10^{-4}	256	1653	0.6	0.16
0.1	2×10^{-4}	256	1669	1.2	0.17
0.15	2×10^{-4}	256	1702	1.8	0.17
0.2	2×10^{-4}	256	1758	2.3	0.18
0.25	2×10^{-4}	256	1862	2.7	0.19

Table 2.1: Parameter values for the solenoidally forced simulations. All the simulations were run in cubical domains with $N_x = N_y = N_z$.

Figure 2.2: The fraction of kinetic energy at $k < k_f$ as a function of Ω for different values of ν .

Figure 2.3: The vertically averaged vertical vorticity (filtered before averaging to discard modes with $k \geq 3k_0$) for $\nu = 2 \times 10^{-3} c/k_0$ and two different rotation rates. In both cases, the velocity field is that at $t = 400 (ck_0)^{-1}$.

kinetic energy³ is concentrated at length scales larger than the forcing scale. Figure 2.3 shows the vertically averaged vertical vorticity, computed after applying a low-pass filter ($k < 3$) to the Fourier transform of the velocity field.

In our simulations, the onset of the instability appears to occur in the range $2 \lesssim \text{Co} \lesssim 4$ (as long as Re is high enough). On the other hand, in simulations of rotating convection, Käpylä, Mantere, and Hackman (2011, p. 5) find that the threshold is in the interval $2.1 < \text{Co}_{\text{KMH11}} < 3.4$ (where Co_{KMH11} is the Coriolis number defined in their equation 10). If the same numerical values are used for u_{rms} in the definitions of Co and Co_{KMH11} , and we account for the fact that the velocity spectrum in their simulations peaks at a wavenumber roughly 7/4 times their reference wavenumber, we find $\text{Co}_{\text{KMH11}} \approx \text{Co}/2$. The threshold they find thus seems quite a bit higher than ours. However, comparison is complicated by the fact that while they define u_{rms} as a volume average, only about half of the depth of their box has significant convective flows (see their figure 3). The value of u_{rms} they use thus likely underestimates the RMS velocity field in the convecting region, meaning they overestimate the Coriolis number. Similar comments apply to the threshold $\text{Co}_{\text{CCC12}} \approx 9$, found by Cai, Chan, and Chow (2022, p. 3).

Aside, one may be worried about the formation of such vortices whose scale is apparently only constrained by the size of the box. However, recall that our simulations use the f -plane approximation, where the spatial variation of the Coriolis force is ignored. Rhines (1975) has shown that at least for 2D turbulence, using the β -plane approximation (in which linear contributions to the spatial variation of the Coriolis force are retained) causes the inverse cascade of vorticity to terminate at a nonzero wavenumber.

³This was actually calculated from the velocity power spectrum. Since these simulations are at low Mach number, we do not expect our results to be affected by neglecting density fluctuations.

2.5 Anisotropy at small scales

We earlier saw that for low-enough values of the viscosity, the anisotropy of the volume- and time-averaged RMS velocity components shows a non-monotonic trend with the rotation rate. To understand what is going on, we now check how the anisotropy depends on the spatial scale considered.

Figure 2.4a shows $A_V(k)$ (equation 2.18) for different values of Ω in simulations with the same value of ν . Consistent with what we saw earlier, we find that at wavenumbers smaller than the forcing wavenumber, $A_V(k)$ attains large, positive values as Ω increases. However, we also find that at wavenumbers larger than the forcing wavenumber, $A_V(k)$ attains *negative* values, with the absolute value of $A_V(k)$ at these scales increasing with Ω . Figure 2.4b shows a series of simulations with a larger value of ν , where no large-scale vortex is formed. We still find that A_V is negative at wavenumbers larger than the forcing wavenumber, suggesting that the effect at play is independent of the large-scale vortex instability.

In simulations of the decay of initially isotropic, rotating, incompressible turbulence, Bartello, Métais, and Lesieur (1994, fig. 8b) observed a similar strengthening of the axial component of the velocity field at small scales. They explained this by the fact that vortices with vorticities (in a rotating frame) antiparallel to the rotational axis become unstable, according to the Rayleigh criterion (Chandrasekhar 1961, section 66), when the rotational rate is of the same order as their vorticity. The resulting instability leads to three-dimensionalization of such flow structures. Since this mechanism tends to drain energy from flows perpendicular to the rotation axis, the net result is that the axial component of the velocity field becomes larger than the other two components. Relative strengthening of the axial component of the velocity field is also predicted by the EDQNM calculations of Cambon and Jacquin (1989, fig. 7).⁴

In rotating turbulence, the Zeman wavenumber (Zeman 1994, eq. 6),

$$k_{ZE} \equiv \frac{\Omega^{3/2}}{\epsilon^{1/2}} \quad (2.23)$$

is usually thought to separate rotationally influenced small wavenumbers from isotropic large wavenumbers (e.g. Baqui and Davidson 2015, pp. 2, 14); the idea is that when $k > k_{ZE}$, the turnover time of the velocity field is smaller than the rotational period, leading to rotational effects being unimportant. In figures 2.4a and 2.4b, for each value of Ω , the Zeman wavenumber has been indicated by using a dashed line for $k < k_{ZE}$, and a solid line for $k > k_{ZE}$. Especially in figure 2.4b, we see that the position of the Zeman wavenumber does not affect the formation of the negative- A_V subrange at $k > k_f$.

⁴Bartello, Métais, and Lesieur (1994, p. 14) mention that Teissedre and Dang (1987) observed this effect in direct numerical simulations; lacking access to the study by Teissedre and Dang, we have not been able to verify this.

Figure 2.4: Variation of $A_V(k)$ and the kinetic energy spectrum with the rotation rate for two different values of ν . The black vertical dotted line marks the forcing wavenumber, which the grey vertical dotted line marks the wavenumber corresponding to the Taylor scale in the simulation with the slowest rotational rate. In each case, the portion of the spectrum at wavenumbers smaller than the Zeman wavenumber (defined in equation 2.23) is marked by a dashed line, while a solid line is used for larger wavenumbers.

Figure 2.5: Effect of the position of the dissipative scale on the spectral anisotropy in a set of simulations with $\Omega = 0.25 ck_0$. Solid lines denote simulations with normal viscosity (constant ν , listed in table 2.1), while dashed lines denote simulations with Smagorinsky viscosity. The black vertical dotted line marks the forcing wavenumber.

2.6 Return to isotropy at large Reynolds numbers

As long as Re is large enough, one expects turbulence to become isotropic at wavenumbers much larger than the Zeman and integral wavenumbers. However, simulations that resolve the large range of wavenumbers required to see such an effect are computationally expensive. To get a hint of what happens at higher Re than those discussed above, we additionally consider large-eddy simulations in which the viscous force is still as described in section 2.3, but the kinematic viscosity, ν , is replaced by the Smagorinsky viscosity (Lesieur 2008, section 12.2.8):

$$\nu_{\text{Smag}} \equiv (C_{\text{Smag}}\Delta)^2 \sqrt{2S_{ij}S_{ij}} \quad (2.24)$$

where Δ is the grid spacing, and $C_{\text{Smag}} = 0.2$ (the recommended value of C_{Smag} is between 0.1 and 0.2). In what follows, we have used two such simulations, with 256^3 and 512^3 grid points respectively (and all other parameters kept identical).

We define the Taylor microscale, which describes the typical length scale associated with velocity gradients in the flow (Lesieur 2008, eq. 6.65), as

$$L_{\text{Tay}} \equiv \sqrt{15 \frac{\langle u^2 \rangle}{\langle \omega^2 \rangle}} \quad (2.25)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\omega} \equiv \nabla \times \mathbf{v}$. In homogeneous and isotropic turbulence, it is thought of as the length scale below which viscous effects start becoming important. Figure 2.5

Figure 2.6: The effect of the forcing function on the spectral anisotropy for $\nu = 5 \times 10^{-4} c/k_0$ and $\Omega = 0.25 ck_0$. The forcing function marked ‘solenoidal’ is given by equation 2.22, while that marked ‘irrotational’ is given by equation 2.26. The amplitudes of the forcing functions have been chosen to keep the Mach numbers comparable, and all other parameters are kept identical.

shows that as the Taylor microscale gets further and further from the integral scale, the flow indeed becomes more isotropic at large wavenumbers. The subrange of constant $A_V(k)$ in figure 2.4 is then explained by the inertial range being too small to allow a complete return to isotropy.

2.7 The effect of the forcing function

Baqui and Davidson (2015, pp. 1–2) point out that rotating forced turbulence can be sensitive to the nature of the forcing function. To check this, instead of the forcing function given by equation 2.22, let us consider

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{irr}} = \nabla \phi, \quad \phi \equiv \phi_0 \sqrt{\frac{cR}{\delta t}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{a})^2}{R^2}\right) \quad (2.26)$$

where \mathbf{a} is a randomly chosen position at each timestep, and we set $R = 0.5/k_0$ and $\phi_0 = 0.85c$. This forcing function is irrotational, i.e. it injects no vorticity. Figure 2.6 shows that with such a forcing function, the velocity components remain isotropic at small scales. Recalling our discussion of the work by Bartello, Métais, and Lesieur (1994), it seems plausible that the anisotropy we see at small scales is related to the destabilization of vortices which are injected by the forcing function. This accounts for the absence of the effect when the forcing function is irrotational.

2.8 Conclusions

We have found that if the forcing function is not irrotational, rotating isotropically forced turbulence develops anisotropy at scales below the forcing scale, such that the velocity component along the rotation axis is larger than the other components. While at high-enough Re , the turbulence becomes isotropic at wavenumbers much larger than the forcing scale, wavenumbers close to the forcing scale remain anisotropic. This effect is due to rotational destabilization of vortices, and is not sensitive to the value of the Zeman wavenumber. We have also shown that this effect is distinct from the well-known large-scale-vortex instability.

Interestingly, the effect we have found does not seem to be predicted by quasi-linear calculations of the kind used to explain the Lambda effect. For example, contrary to the results in figure 2.1, Käpylä and Brandenburg (2008, eqs. A.1–6) predict that if the rotation is along the z axis, neither $\langle v_x^2 + v_y^2 \rangle$ nor $\langle v_z^2 \rangle$ are affected by rotation.

Anisotropy of turbulence is expected to suppress the growth rate of the small-scale dynamo; we will later show (chapter 6) that both the growth rate and the saturation level are indeed suppressed due to rotation in regimes where a large-scale vortex is not formed.

In the astrophysically relevant case of irrotational forcing (by supernovae), we have found no generation of anisotropy at small scales due to rotation. However, we note that our choice of an isothermal equation of state ensures that vorticity cannot be produced by baroclinic torques. We speculate that for an ideal-gas equation of state, such torques would lead to the generation of vorticity at intermediate scales even when the forcing function is irrotational, still leading to anisotropy at small scales. We intend to test this in the future.

Appendices to chapter 2

2.A Grid-independence study

Figures 2.7 and 2.8 show how A_V and the fraction of the large-scale kinetic energy depend on the number of grid points for some of the solenoidally forced simulations. We see that in the regime where no large-scale vortex is formed, these quantities are not strongly dependent on the grid size. Further, figure 2.9 shows that the grid resolution does not affect our conclusions on the generation of spectral anisotropy (section 2.5).

Figure 2.7: A_V as a function of the grid size for some combinations of ν and Ω . The total number of grid points is N_x^3 (excluding the ghost points). The inscribed white dots denote the grid sizes used for the presented results.

Figure 2.8: Grid-dependence of the fraction of the kinetic energy at $k < k_f$ (similar notation to figure 2.7).

Figure 2.9: Grid-dependence of $A_V(k)$ and the kinetic energy spectrum. The grid sizes used for figure 2.4 are marked with stars. The black vertical dotted line marks the forcing wavenumber.

Part II
Kinematic dynamo

Chapter 3

Fluctuating turbulent diffusivity

3.1 Introduction

The turbulent electromotive force, which is determined by correlations between the fluctuating velocity and magnetic fields, plays a crucial role in mean-field dynamo theory. For homogeneous and isotropic turbulence, using the quasilinear approximation, one can express the turbulent electromotive force in terms of the turbulent transport coefficients α (which is proportional to the mean kinetic helicity) and η (the turbulent diffusivity, which is proportional to the mean kinetic energy) when the magnetic field is weak (Moffatt 1978, chapter 7). The contribution of α , if nonzero, may cause growth of the mean magnetic field, while η always dissipates it when the turbulence is homogeneous.

Even when the mean kinetic helicity is zero, Kraichnan (1976) found that fluctuations of the kinetic helicity can suppress the turbulent diffusivity. If the fluctuations are strong or long-lived enough, the effective diffusivity may become negative, leading to growth of the large-scale magnetic field (Kraichnan 1976; Moffatt 1978, sec. 7.11; Singh 2016). This effect, usually referred to as the ‘incoherent α effect’, has also been studied in combination with shear (Sokolov 1997; Vishniac and Brandenburg 1997; Silant’ev 2000; Sridhar and Singh 2014). The ‘incoherent α -shear dynamo’ has been invoked (Brandenburg et al. 2008) to explain the generation of a large-scale magnetic field in simulations of nonhelical turbulence with background shear (Yousef et al. 2008; Singh and Jingade 2015).

To derive his result, Kraichnan (1976) used a process of double-averaging, where one first obtains the mean-field equations at some mesoscale, and then fluctuations of the mesoscale transport coefficients may lead to effects at some larger scale upon subsequent averaging. There are two viewpoints (not mutually exclusive) on the applicability of this method. One is that we require the system to have scale separation, such that the turbulent spectra peak at some small scale, while averaged quantities themselves fluctuate at some mesoscale, and then there exists an even larger scale where a magnetic field can grow (e.g. Moffatt 1978, p. 178). As an example of a physical system where such a picture may be relevant, we

note that in the solar photosphere, mesoscales can be identified with granulation or supergranulation (for a review on supergranulation, see Rincon and Rieutord 2018). Another viewpoint is to think of multiscale averaging as a renormalization procedure which tells us something about the contributions of higher moments of the velocity field to the turbulent transport coefficients (e.g. Moffatt 1983, sec. 11; Silant'ev 2000, p. 341). In this light, it is interesting that more rigorous methods also predict that the turbulent diffusivity is suppressed (see chapter 4).

Regardless of one's viewpoint, it seems natural to wonder why fluctuations of the helicity should have a more privileged position than fluctuations of the kinetic energy (i.e. the turbulent magnetic diffusivity). Dynamos can be driven or boosted by spatial variations of the *microscopic* magnetic diffusivity or the magnetic permeability (Busse and Wicht 1992; Rogers and McElwaine 2017; Giesecke et al. 2010; Pétrélis, Alexakis, and Gissinger 2016; Gressel, Rüdiger, and Elstner 2023). Further, in simulations, it is found that fluctuations of α coexist with fluctuations of η (e.g. Brandenburg et al. 2008, fig. 10). While Silant'ev (1999, 2000) has considered fluctuations of the turbulent diffusivity (and found that the effective turbulent diffusivity is suppressed), he has not included the effect of turbulent diamagnetism (expulsion of the magnetic field from turbulent regions); the latter is a natural consequence of spatial variations of the turbulent kinetic energy, and thus cannot be ignored.

Here, we explore the effects of mesoscale fluctuations of the turbulent magnetic diffusivity, with nonzero correlation time, on the evolution of the large-scale magnetic field. The procedure we follow is the same as that of Singh (2016).

In section 3.2, we derive the evolution equation for the large-scale magnetic field, along with an expression for its growth rate, by using the quasilinear approximation. In section 3.3, we simplify the expression for the growth rate, assuming the fluctuations of η are isotropic. In section 3.4, we explain how the growth rate is modified by anisotropy. In section 3.5, we relate the growth in some regimes to a negative effective turbulent diffusivity. In section 3.6, we show how to estimate the dynamo numbers in astrophysical systems, taking the solar photosphere as an example. Finally, we discuss the implications of our results and possible future directions in section 3.7.

3.2 Derivation of the evolution equation and the growth rate

3.2.1 Setup and assumptions

The mean magnetic field, \mathbf{B} , evolves according to (e.g. Moffatt 1978, eq. 7.7)

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times (\mathbf{V} \times \mathbf{B} + \boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}}) + \eta_m \nabla^2 \mathbf{B} \quad (3.1)$$

where \mathbf{V} is the mean velocity; η_m is the microscopic magnetic diffusivity; and \mathcal{E} , the turbulent electromotive force (EMF), is related to the correlation between the fluctuating velocity and magnetic fields.

Since the MHD equations are nonlinear, the evolution equations for moments of a particular order depend on moments of higher orders. For example, the EMF in equation 3.1 is a double-correlation of the fluctuating fields. To keep the system of equations manageable, one has to truncate this hierarchy by applying a *closure*. To avoid solving for the fluctuating magnetic field, one requires an expression for the EMF in terms of the mean magnetic field itself. If the mean magnetic field is weak and varies slowly, one typically assumes that the EMF depends only on the mean magnetic field and its first derivatives, obtaining a general expression of the form $\mathcal{E}_i = \alpha_{ij}B_j + \eta_{ijk}\partial_j B_k$. Here, and in what follows, repeated indices are summed over. The tensors α_{ij} and η_{ijk} may depend on the statistical properties of the velocity field. The expressions for these tensors depend on the closure used.

One of the most widely used closures in dynamo theory is the quasilinear approximation (also called the first-order smoothing approximation, FOSA; or the second-order correlation approximation, SOCA) (e.g. Moffatt 1978, sec. 7.5; Krause and Rädler 1980, sec. 4.3). The quasilinear approximation is rigorously valid only when either the magnetic Reynolds number (the ratio of the diffusive to the advective timescale) or the Strouhal number (the ratio of the velocity correlation time to its turnover time) is small (Krause and Rädler 1980, p. 49). The former is never small in the astrophysical systems of interest, while it is unclear if the latter is small. Nevertheless, in the context of mean-field dynamo theory, the quasilinear approximation often remains qualitatively correct well outside its domain of formal validity.¹ More complicated closures such as the EDQNM closure (e.g. Pouquet, Frisch, and Léorat 1976) and the DIA (Kraichnan 1977) are extremely difficult to work with.

For weakly inhomogeneous nonhelical turbulence, the EMF is given in the quasilinear approximation by (Roberts and Soward 1975, eq. 3.11)

$$\mathcal{E} = -\frac{1}{2}\nabla\eta \times \mathbf{B} - \eta\nabla \times \mathbf{B} \quad (3.2)$$

where η is the turbulent diffusivity (proportional to the turbulent kinetic energy). We note that Silant'ev (1999, 2000) did not consider the first term above.² Comparing this term with the $\mathbf{V} \times \mathbf{B}$ term in equation 3.1, we see that the former can be thought of as describing an effective velocity $-\nabla\eta/2$ that acts on the mean magnetic field. This transports the magnetic field in the direction in which the turbulent

¹We will later see in chapter 4 that the quasilinear approximation is correct for a random field (here, η) with zero correlation time. Applying it to a field whose correlation time is nonzero leads to missing terms at all orders (in the correlation time) except the lowest order. Nevertheless, since the goal of this chapter is to demonstrate a new effect, we use the quasilinear approximation for the sake of simplicity.

²Appendix 3.B describes how the absence of this term qualitatively changes the behaviour of the system.

kinetic energy decreases. By analogy with the reduction of the magnetic field in diamagnetic materials, this is usually referred to as ‘turbulent diamagnetism’ or ‘diamagnetic pumping’. For stratified turbulence, or in the presence of small-scale magnetic fields, additional terms arise (Vainshtein and Kichatinov 1983), but we ignore those effects in this work. As mentioned in the introduction, the effect of helical turbulence (α) has been extensively studied, so we restrict ourselves to turbulence that is nonhelical pointwise. The first term of equation 3.2 may be considered one of many contributions to the off-diagonal components of α_{ij} . In the literature, such contributions are sometimes described in terms of a vector $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$; see Rädler, Kleeorin, and Rogachevskii (2003, eq. 42). While the calculations we present can be carried out using the α_{ij} and η_{ijk} tensors in their full glory, we use a simpler expression in order to keep the results interpretable.

Although the mean-field approach does not formally require scale-separation, we associate averages with length/time scales for clarity of exposition. Let us assume that η fluctuates at length/time scales (henceforth referred to as the mesoscales) much larger than the scales at which the turbulent velocity fluctuates. We employ a double-averaging approach (Kraichnan 1976; Singh 2016), in which we treat η (at the mesoscale) as a stochastic scalar field which is a function of both position and time (i.e. $\eta = \eta(\mathbf{x}, t)$). For any mesoscale quantity \square , we use $\langle \square \rangle$ and $\bar{\square}$ to denote its averages at the larger scale. We assume this average satisfies Reynolds’ rules (e.g. Monin and Yaglom 1971, sec. 3.1).

If we set the mean velocity to zero, ignore the microscopic diffusivity (which is usually much smaller than the turbulent diffusivity in the systems of interest), and use equation 3.2, we can write equation 3.1, the evolution equation for the mesoscale magnetic field, as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times \left(-\frac{1}{2} \nabla \eta \times \mathbf{B} - \eta \nabla \times \mathbf{B} \right) \quad (3.3)$$

In section 3.2.3, we assume the fluctuations of η are statistically homogeneous, stationary, and separable in order to obtain an integro-differential equation for the large-scale magnetic field. In section 3.2.4, we simplify this equation by assuming the fluctuations of η are white noise, while in section 3.2.5, we also keep terms linear in the correlation time of η .

3.2.2 Evolution equation in Fourier space

We now move to Fourier space with

$$\tilde{f}(\mathbf{k}, t) \equiv \int \frac{d\mathbf{x}}{(2\pi)^3} e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}} f(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (3.4)$$

where we have used a tilde to denote the spatial Fourier transform of a quantity. The convolution theorem takes the form

$$\int \frac{d\mathbf{x}}{(2\pi)^3} e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}} f(\mathbf{x})g(\mathbf{x}) = \int d\mathbf{p} \tilde{f}(\mathbf{p})\tilde{g}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}) \quad (3.5)$$

Equation 3.3 then becomes (omitting the temporal arguments whenever there is no ambiguity)

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k})}{\partial t} = \mathbf{k} \times \int d\mathbf{p} \left(\frac{\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p}}{2} \right) \times \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{p}) \tilde{\eta}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}) \quad (3.6)$$

Taking the average of the above, we obtain

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \rangle = \mathbf{k} \times \int d\mathbf{p} \left(\frac{\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p}}{2} \right) \times \left(\langle \tilde{\eta}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}) \rangle \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{p}) \rangle + \langle \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}) \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{p}) \rangle \right) \quad (3.7)$$

where we have split the mesoscale fields into their mean and fluctuating parts, i.e. $\tilde{\mathbf{B}} = \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}} \rangle + \tilde{\mathbf{b}}$ and $\tilde{\eta} = \langle \tilde{\eta} \rangle + \tilde{\mu}$. We write the equation for $\tilde{\mathbf{b}}$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{k})}{\partial t} = \mathbf{k} \times \int d\mathbf{p} \left(\frac{\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p}}{2} \right) \times & \left(\langle \tilde{\eta}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}) \rangle \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{p}) + \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}) \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{p}) \rangle \right. \\ & \left. + \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}) \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{p}) - \langle \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}) \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{p}) \rangle \right) \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

We now apply the quasilinear approximation, where the equations for the fluctuating fields are truncated by keeping only terms which are at most linear in the fluctuating fields. We then obtain

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{k})}{\partial t} = \mathbf{k} \times \int d\mathbf{p} \left(\frac{\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p}}{2} \right) \times \left(\langle \tilde{\eta}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}) \rangle \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{p}) + \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}) \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{p}) \rangle \right) \quad (3.9)$$

3.2.3 Homogeneity and separability

To simplify the preceding expression, we assume that the moments of $\eta(\mathbf{x}, t)$ are statistically homogeneous and stationary. We can then write, say, $\langle \mu(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1) \mu(\mathbf{y}, \tau_2) \rangle = C(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}, \tau_1 - \tau_2)$. Further, we assume that $\langle \mu(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1) \mu(\mathbf{y}, \tau_2) \rangle$ can be written as the product of a temporal correlation function and a spatial correlation function, i.e. $C(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}, \tau_1 - \tau_2) = Q(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) S(\tau_1 - \tau_2)$. In Fourier space, these assumptions can be expressed as

$$\langle \tilde{\eta}(\mathbf{k}, t) \rangle = \bar{\eta} \delta(\mathbf{k}) \quad (3.10a)$$

$$\langle \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{p}, \tau_1) \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{q}, \tau_2) \rangle = \tilde{Q}(\mathbf{p}) S(\tau_1 - \tau_2) \delta(\mathbf{p} + \mathbf{q}) \quad (3.10b)$$

For S , we require

$$2 \int_0^\infty S(t) dt = 1 \quad (3.11)$$

and define the correlation time of η as

$$\tau_\eta \equiv 2 \int_0^\infty t S(t) dt \quad (3.12)$$

We can then write

$$\mathbf{k} \times \int d\mathbf{p} \left(\frac{\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p}}{2} \right) \times \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{p}) \langle \tilde{\eta}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}) \rangle = -\bar{\eta} k^2 \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{k}) \quad (3.13)$$

and

$$\mathbf{k} \times \int d\mathbf{p} \left(\frac{\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p}}{2} \right) \times \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{p}) \rangle \langle \tilde{\eta}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}) \rangle = -\bar{\eta} k^2 \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \rangle \quad (3.14)$$

Using equation 3.13, equation 3.9 can be written as

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{k})}{\partial t} = -\bar{\eta} k^2 \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{k}) + \mathbf{k} \times \int d\mathbf{p} \left(\frac{\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p}}{2} \right) \times \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{p}) \rangle \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}) \quad (3.15)$$

which gives us

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{k}, t) &= \mathbf{k} \times \int_0^t d\tau \int d\mathbf{p} e^{-\bar{\eta} k^2 (t-\tau)} \left(\frac{\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p}}{2} \right) \times \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{p}, \tau) \rangle \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}, \tau) \\ &\quad + \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{k}, 0) \end{aligned} \quad (3.16)$$

We assume that the initial fluctuations of the mesoscale magnetic field are uncorrelated with μ . Using the above along with equation 3.10b, we can write

$$\langle \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{q}, t) \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{k}, t) \rangle = \mathbf{k} \times \int_0^t d\tau e^{-\bar{\eta} k^2 (t-\tau)} \left(\mathbf{k} + \frac{\mathbf{q}}{2} \right) \times \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{q}, \tau) \rangle \tilde{Q}(\mathbf{q}) S(t - \tau) \quad (3.17)$$

Putting the above in equation 3.7 gives us an equation for $\langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{q}, \tau) \rangle$. However, this is an integro-differential equation which is difficult to solve in general. The resulting equation can be simplified by assuming τ_η is small. In section 3.2.4, we assume $\tau_\eta = 0$ and simplify the evolution equation for the large-scale magnetic field. In section 3.2.5, we simplify the evolution equation neglecting $\mathcal{O}(\tau_\eta^2)$ terms.

3.2.4 Evolution equation with white-noise fluctuations

Assuming $S(t) = \delta(t)$, we write equation 3.17 as

$$\langle \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{q}, t) \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{k}, t) \rangle = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{k} \times \left[\left(\mathbf{k} + \frac{\mathbf{q}}{2} \right) \times \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{q}, t) \rangle \right] \tilde{Q}(\mathbf{q}) \quad (3.18)$$

Recalling that $\mathbf{k} \cdot \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}, t) \rangle = 0$, we can use the above to write

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathbf{k} \times \int d\mathbf{p} \left(\frac{\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p}}{2} \right) \times \langle \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}, t) \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{p}, t) \rangle \\ &= \int d\mathbf{s} \frac{1}{8} \tilde{Q}(\mathbf{s}) (4k^4 - 8k^2 \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{s} + 3(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{s})^2 + 2k^2 s^2 - s^2 \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{s}) \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}, t) \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (3.19)$$

where $\mathbf{s} \equiv \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}$. Defining

$$A^{(0)} \equiv Q(\mathbf{0}), \quad A_i^{(1)} \equiv \left. \frac{\partial Q(\boldsymbol{\xi})}{\partial \xi_i} \right|_{\boldsymbol{\xi}=\mathbf{0}}, \quad A_{ij}^{(2)} \equiv \left. \frac{\partial^2 Q(\boldsymbol{\xi})}{\partial \xi_i \partial \xi_j} \right|_{\boldsymbol{\xi}=\mathbf{0}}, \quad A_i^{(3)} \equiv \left. \frac{\partial^3 Q(\boldsymbol{\xi})}{\partial \xi_i \partial \xi_j \partial \xi_j} \right|_{\boldsymbol{\xi}=\mathbf{0}} \quad (3.20)$$

we write

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{k} \times \int d\mathbf{p} \left(\frac{\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p}}{2} \right) \times \left\langle \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}, t) \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{p}, t) \right\rangle \\ = \frac{1}{8} \left(4A^{(0)}k^4 - 8iA_i^{(1)}k^2k_i - 3A_{ij}^{(2)}k_ik_j - 2A_{ii}^{(2)}k^2 + iA_i^{(3)}k_i \right) \left\langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}, t) \right\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (3.21)$$

Note that the functions defined in equation 3.20 depend only on the value of $Q(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ and its spatial derivatives at the origin. Putting this in equation 3.7 and using equation 3.14, we obtain

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left\langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \right\rangle = (-\bar{\eta}k^2 + g(\mathbf{k})) \left\langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \right\rangle + ih(\mathbf{k}) \left\langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \right\rangle \quad (3.22)$$

where

$$g(\mathbf{k}) \equiv -\frac{3}{8}A_{ij}^{(2)}k_ik_j - \frac{1}{4}A_{ii}^{(2)}k^2 + \frac{1}{2}A^{(0)}k^4 \quad (3.23a)$$

$$h(\mathbf{k}) \equiv \frac{1}{8}A_i^{(3)}k_i - A_i^{(1)}k^2k_i \quad (3.23b)$$

We see that $g(\mathbf{k})$ describes corrections to the turbulent diffusivity (along with a k^4 hyperdiffusive term), while the term involving $h(\mathbf{k})$ describes advection of the large-scale magnetic field with an effective velocity $A_i^{(3)}/8 - A_i^{(1)}k^2$.

To aid the interpretation of equation 3.22, we note that if the spatial correlation function of the fluctuations of η is an isotropic Gaussian (see appendix 3.A), we can write

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left\langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \right\rangle = -\left(\bar{\eta} - \frac{9}{8}\beta \right) k^2 \left\langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \right\rangle + \mathcal{O}(k^4), \quad (3.24)$$

where $\beta \equiv A^{(0)}/l_c^2 > 0$ represents the diffusivity arising from fluctuations of η with a correlation length l_c . Thus, we find that fluctuations of η reduce the turbulent diffusion of the large-scale magnetic field.

3.2.5 Evolution equation with nonzero correlation time

We expand

$$\left\langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{p}, \tau) \right\rangle = \left\langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{p}, t) \right\rangle - (t - \tau) \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left\langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{p}, t) \right\rangle + \mathcal{O}((t - \tau)^2) \quad (3.25)$$

The idea is that when we substitute this into equation 3.17, assume $t \gg \tau_\eta$, and perform the time integral, the powers of $(t - \tau)$ become powers of τ_η . The

convergence of this series requires that the large-scale magnetic field vary on a timescale much larger than τ_η . Note that on the RHS of the above, we can neglect $\mathcal{O}(t - \tau)$ contributions to $\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{p}, t) \rangle$ and use equation 3.22. Similarly, we can expand

$$\exp(-\bar{\eta}k^2(t - \tau)) = 1 - (t - \tau)\bar{\eta}k^2 + \mathcal{O}((t - \tau)^2) \quad (3.26)$$

We then write equation 3.17 as

$$\langle \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}, t) \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{p}, t) \rangle = \tilde{Q}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}) \mathbf{p} \times \left[\left(\frac{\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p}}{2} \right) \times \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{k}, t) \right] \quad (3.27)$$

where

$$\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{k}, t) \equiv \frac{1}{2} \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}, t) \rangle - \frac{\tau_\eta}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}, t) \rangle - \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}, t) \rangle \frac{\tau_\eta}{2} \bar{\eta}k^2 \quad (3.28)$$

Using equation 3.22, we write

$$\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{k}, t) = \frac{1}{2} \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}, t) \rangle - \frac{\tau_\eta}{2} g(\mathbf{k}) \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}, t) \rangle - \frac{i\tau_\eta}{2} h(\mathbf{k}) \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}, t) \rangle \quad (3.29)$$

We note that $\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{k}, t) = 0$ (since $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0$) and use equations 3.27 and 3.29 to write

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{k} \times \int d\mathbf{p} \left(\frac{\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p}}{2} \right) \times \langle \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}, t) \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{p}, t) \rangle \\ = [g(\mathbf{k}) + ih(\mathbf{k})] [1 - \tau_\eta g(\mathbf{k}) - i\tau_\eta h(\mathbf{k})] \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}, t) \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (3.30)$$

where h and g are defined in equations 3.23. Putting this in equation 3.7 and using equation 3.14, we write

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \rangle = [g(\mathbf{k}) + ih(\mathbf{k})] [1 - \tau_\eta g(\mathbf{k}) - i\tau_\eta h(\mathbf{k})] \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \rangle - \bar{\eta}k^2 \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \rangle + \mathcal{O}(\tau_\eta^2) \quad (3.31)$$

3.2.6 Growth rate of the large-scale magnetic field

Let us now focus on the problem of whether a particular Fourier mode of the large-scale magnetic field grows or decays. We assume $\langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}, t) \rangle \propto \exp(\lambda t)$. Plugging this into equation 3.31 and taking its real part, we find

$$\text{Re}(\lambda) = -\bar{\eta}k^2 + g(\mathbf{k}) - \tau_\eta [g(\mathbf{k})]^2 + \tau_\eta [h(\mathbf{k})]^2 + \mathcal{O}(\tau_\eta^2) \quad (3.32)$$

where h and g are defined in equations 3.23. From the fact that above, only $[g(\mathbf{k})]^2$ contains a k^8 term, we can see that the growth rate always becomes negative for large-enough k (small-enough scales) as long as $\tau_\eta \neq 0$. Note that while in the white-noise case, $h(\mathbf{k})$ only contributed a drift term, it now affects the growth rate as well.

Since we assumed the large-scale magnetic field varies on timescales much larger than τ_η , our derivation is self-consistent only when $|\tau_\eta \lambda| \ll 1$.

3.3 Dynamo numbers when the fluctuations are isotropic

If $Q(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ is isotropic, i.e. $Q(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = Q(|\boldsymbol{\xi}|)$ (see Monin and Yaglom 1975, sec. 12.1), we can write the quantities defined in equation 3.20 as

$$A_i^{(1)} = 0, \quad A_{ij}^{(2)} = \delta_{ij} \frac{A_{mm}^{(2)}}{3}, \quad A_i^{(3)} = 0 \quad (3.33)$$

so that

$$h(\mathbf{k}) = 0, \quad g(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{4A^{(0)}k^4 - 3k^2A_{mm}^{(2)}}{8} \quad (3.34)$$

Equation 3.32 can then be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Re}(\lambda) = & -k^2 \left(\bar{\eta} + \frac{3A_{mm}^{(2)}}{8} \right) + k^4 \left(\frac{A^{(0)}}{2} - \frac{9\tau_\eta}{64} [A_{mm}^{(2)}]^2 \right) \\ & + \frac{3\tau_\eta A^{(0)} A_{mm}^{(2)} k^6}{8} - \frac{\tau_\eta [A^{(0)}]^2 k^8}{4} \end{aligned} \quad (3.35)$$

If we further define³

$$\mathcal{D}_1 \equiv -\frac{3A_{mm}^{(2)}}{8\bar{\eta}}, \quad \mathcal{D}_2 \equiv \frac{9\tau_\eta}{32} \frac{[A_{mm}^{(2)}]^2}{A^{(0)}}, \quad l_c \equiv \sqrt{-\frac{3A^{(0)}}{A_{ii}^{(2)}}}, \quad K \equiv kl_c, \quad T \equiv \frac{l_c^2}{\bar{\eta}} \quad (3.36)$$

we can write equation 3.35 as

$$T \text{Re}(\lambda) = -K^2 (1 - \mathcal{D}_1) + \frac{4\mathcal{D}_1 K^4}{9} (1 - \mathcal{D}_2) - \frac{32\mathcal{D}_1 \mathcal{D}_2 K^6}{81} - \frac{64\mathcal{D}_1 \mathcal{D}_2 K^8}{729} \quad (3.37)$$

The growth rate at a particular wavenumber is thus determined by two dynamo numbers, \mathcal{D}_1 and \mathcal{D}_2 . In appendix 3.A, we express the dynamo numbers in terms of more observationally relevant quantities by assuming a particular form for the correlation function Q . We see that \mathcal{D}_1 describes how strong the fluctuations of η are as compared to its mean value, while $\mathcal{D}_2/\mathcal{D}_1$ is proportional to the ratio of the correlation time of the fluctuations to the diffusion timescale determined from the mean of η and the correlation length of its fluctuations.

Figure 3.1 shows the growth rate (equation 3.37) for two sets of dynamo numbers. We see that depending on the parameters, the growth rate may peak at large scales or at small scales.

To understand the qualitative behaviour of equation 3.37, we can schematically write it as

$$\text{Re}(\lambda) = \begin{cases} -k^2 - k^4 - k^6 - k^8 & ; \mathcal{D}_2 > 1, \mathcal{D}_1 < 1 \\ -k^2 + k^4 - k^6 - k^8 & ; \mathcal{D}_2 < 1, \mathcal{D}_1 < 1 \\ k^2 + k^4 - k^6 - k^8 & ; \mathcal{D}_2 < 1, \mathcal{D}_1 > 1 \\ k^2 - k^4 - k^6 - k^8 & ; \mathcal{D}_2 > 1, \mathcal{D}_1 > 1 \end{cases} \quad (3.38)$$

³If the correlation function attains a maximum at zero separation, $A_{mm}^{(2)} < 0$. This implies $\mathcal{D}_1 > 0$.

Figure 3.1: The mode growth rate ($T \operatorname{Re}(\lambda)$, equation 3.37) as a function of the wavenumber for two combinations of \mathcal{D}_1 and \mathcal{D}_2 .

In the first case, $\operatorname{Re}(\lambda)$ is always negative, and so there is no dynamo. In the last two cases, $\operatorname{Re}(\lambda)$ is positive for small k and becomes negative for large wavenumbers. In the second regime, it seems to be difficult to say anything concrete (depending on the values of the coefficients, one can either have growth in a range of wavenumbers or growth nowhere).

Since 3.37 is a polynomial in K , one can easily solve for its extrema. In figure 3.2, we show the dynamo growth rate (where positive) and the wavenumber of the resulting large-scale field, as a function of \mathcal{D}_1 and \mathcal{D}_2 .

If we drop the terms of order K^6 and K^8 in equation 3.37 (this does not change the qualitative behaviour when $\mathcal{D}_2 > 1$), we can estimate that if $\mathcal{D}_1 > 1$, the growth rate attains a maximum value at K_{peak} , where

$$K_{\text{peak}} \approx \sqrt{\frac{9(\mathcal{D}_1 - 1)}{8\mathcal{D}_1(\mathcal{D}_2 - 1)}}, \quad [T \operatorname{Re}(\lambda)]_{\text{max}} \approx \frac{9(\mathcal{D}_1 - 1)^2}{16\mathcal{D}_1(\mathcal{D}_2 - 1)} \quad (3.39)$$

Broadly speaking, there are two kinds of regimes in which the dynamo is excited. One, $\mathcal{D}_1 > 1$, corresponds to the fluctuations being strong enough that the effective diffusivity itself becomes negative (but the growth itself is still cut off at small scales due to higher-order terms). The other, $\mathcal{D}_2 < 1$ (with \mathcal{D}_1 also < 1), corresponds to growth with the effective diffusion remaining positive; one can see, however, from figure 3.2 that this growth happens at smaller scales than in the other regime (but may still be at scales larger than l_c). While $\mathcal{D}_2 \ll 1$ can formally lead to growing solutions regardless of the value of \mathcal{D}_1 , the growth then occurs at scales $\lesssim l_c$.

Figure 3.2: Left: The peak growth rate ($T \text{Re}(\lambda)$, equation 3.37). In the white regions, the growth rate is negative for all K . Right: The wavenumber (K) at which the growth rate peaks. Recall that for a mode with wavelength l_c , the wavenumber would be $K = 2\pi \approx 10^{0.8}$.

3.4 The effect of anisotropy

Although we have not done so in the above, it seems natural to assume that the temporal correlation function S , that appears in equation 3.10b, is even. This would allow one to take $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} S(t) dt = 1$ and define the correlation time of η as $\tau_\eta \equiv \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |t| S(t) dt$.

Because μ is a scalar, assuming its double correlation is invariant under time-reversal immediately implies $\tilde{Q}(\mathbf{k}) = \tilde{Q}(-\mathbf{k})$. We then conclude that

$$A_i^{(1)} = A_i^{(3)} = h(\mathbf{k}) = 0 \quad (3.40)$$

when the fluctuations of η are separable, homogeneous, stationary, and time-reversal-invariant; this holds even without assuming that the fluctuations of η are isotropic! We now study the dynamo assuming the double correlation of μ is time-reversal invariant and anisotropic.

Let us choose the coordinate axes 1, 2, 3 to be along the principal axes of the matrix $A^{(2)}$ (defined in equation 3.20), with the corresponding eigenvalues being $-a_1$, $-a_2$, and $-a_3$ (such that $a_1 \geq a_3 \geq a_2$). By analogy with equation 3.36, one can define the correlation length along each axis as $l_c^{(i)} \equiv \sqrt{A^{(0)}/a_i}$. It is physically reasonable to assume $Q(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ attains a local maximum at the origin, and that its correlation length is finite. This means $a_1, a_2, a_3 > 0$.

Analogous to equation 3.36, we define

$$\mathcal{D}_1 \equiv \frac{9a_3}{8\bar{\eta}}, \quad \mathcal{D}_2 \equiv \frac{81\tau_\eta a_3^2}{32A^{(0)}}, \quad l_c \equiv \sqrt{\frac{A^{(0)}}{a_3}}, \quad \mathbf{K} \equiv \mathbf{k}l_c, \quad T \equiv \frac{l_c^2}{\bar{\eta}} \quad (3.41)$$

Figure 3.3: The mode growth rate ($T \operatorname{Re}(\lambda)$, equation 3.45) as a function of the wavenumber. In all the cases, we have taken $\mathcal{D}_1 = 2$ and $\mathcal{D}_2 = 5$. Other parameters not mentioned in the legend have been set to zero.

We also define the new quantities

$$\chi_1 \equiv \frac{a_1}{a_3} - 1, \quad \chi_2 \equiv 1 - \frac{a_2}{a_3}, \quad n_1 \equiv \frac{|K_1|}{K}, \quad n_2 \equiv \frac{|K_2|}{K} \quad (3.42)$$

and a modified dynamo number

$$\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_1 \equiv \mathcal{D}_1 \left[1 + \frac{\chi_1}{9} (2 + 3n_1^2) - \frac{\chi_2}{9} (2 + 3n_2^2) \right] \quad (3.43)$$

Since $0 \leq \chi_2 < 1$, $0 \leq \chi_1 < \infty$, and $0 \leq n_1, n_2 \leq 1$, we find that $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_1 > 0$. We write $g(\mathbf{k})$ (equation 3.23) as

$$Tg(\mathbf{k}) = \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_1 K^2 + \frac{4\mathcal{D}_1}{9} K^4 \quad (3.44)$$

Noting that $\tau_\eta/T = 4\mathcal{D}_2/(9\mathcal{D}_1)$, one can substitute equation 3.44 in equation 3.32 to obtain the following expression for the growth rate:

$$T \operatorname{Re}(\lambda) = K^2 \left(\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_1 - 1 \right) + \frac{4\mathcal{D}_1 K^4}{9} \left(1 - \frac{\mathcal{D}_2 \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_1^2}{\mathcal{D}_1^2} \right) - \frac{32\mathcal{D}_2 \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_1 K^6}{81} - \frac{64\mathcal{D}_1 \mathcal{D}_2 K^8}{729} \quad (3.45)$$

As expected, this reduces to equation 3.37 on setting $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_1 = \mathcal{D}_1$. Replacing $\mathcal{D}_1 \rightarrow \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_1$ and $\mathcal{D}_2 \rightarrow \mathcal{D}_2 \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_1^2 / \mathcal{D}_1^2$, our comments in section 3.3 on the qualitative behaviour of equation 3.37 also apply to this equation. Unlike in the isotropic case, the growth rate now depends on the direction of \mathbf{K} through the direction cosines n_1 and n_2 . Figure 3.3 shows the growth rate as a function of the wavenumber for various parameter values.

3.5 Suppression of turbulent diffusion

Neglecting terms with more than two spatial derivatives of $\langle \mathbf{B} \rangle$, equation 3.31 can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \rangle = & -\bar{\eta}k^2 \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \rangle - \frac{1}{8} (3k_m k_n A_{mn}^{(2)} + 2k^2 A_{mm}^{(2)}) \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \rangle \\ & + \frac{i}{8} k_m A_m^{(3)} \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \rangle + \frac{\tau_\eta}{64} k_m k_i A_m^{(3)} A_i^{(3)} \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \rangle + \mathcal{O}(k^3) \end{aligned} \quad (3.46)$$

Following the reasoning used in section 3.4 for $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_1$, one can see that the coefficient of $\langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \rangle$ in the second term above is always positive as long as the spatial correlation function of the η -fluctuations attains a maximum at zero separation; the turbulent diffusion is suppressed. This can be seen more clearly in equation 3.24, which assumes a particular form for the spatial correlation function. The third term just describes advection with an effective velocity $\mathbf{A}^{(3)}/8$, analogous to ‘Moffatt drift’ (Moffatt 1978, sec. 7.11). The fourth term can never be negative, and is nonzero only when the fluctuations of η are anisotropic and not invariant under time-reversal. As noted in section 3.3, the higher powers of k neglected in equation 3.46 can cause growth of the large-scale magnetic field even when the effective diffusivity is positive. They also ensure that the growth rate becomes negative at small scales.

It may seem counter-intuitive that a dissipative term (η) at the mesoscale leads to a dynamo at larger scales, but it must be noted that in addition to dissipation, η also contributes an effective advection term (usually referred to as ‘turbulent diamagnetism’; see equation 3.2) when spatial variations at the mesoscale are properly accounted for. Heuristically, it seems possible to explain the suppression of turbulent diffusion by turbulent diamagnetism as follows: turbulent diamagnetism causes the magnetic field to be preferentially concentrated in regions where the turbulent diffusivity is minimal. The effective turbulent diffusivity acting on the magnetic field is then less than what would be inferred by taking an average over the entire system. See Silant’ev (1999, p. 49) for a more general explanation of reduced turbulent diffusion when two scattering mechanisms contribute to the diffusion process.

3.6 Estimates of the dynamo numbers

Unfortunately, fluctuations of the turbulent diffusivity in astrophysical systems are not sufficiently constrained by observations. The situation in the solar photosphere is comparatively better, as observations of granulation give us an idea of the order of magnitude of various quantities. To make crude estimates, we use equation 3.50 which assumes a specific form for the correlation function of η .

On the surface of the Sun, one may associate the integral scale of turbulence with granulation, which has a length scale of about 2 Mm (Rieutord et al. 2010, fig. 6)

and a timescale of about 400 s (Bahng and Schwarzschild 1961). The granulation pattern itself is correlated over the supergranulation scale, associated with a length scale of about 30 Mm and a timescale of the order of a day (Rincon and Rieutord 2018, sections 3.2.1–3.2.2). The turbulent diffusivity in the photosphere is a scale-dependent quantity, which is moreover not very well constrained (Abramenko et al. 2011, fig. 10). At the supergranulation scale, it is not unreasonable to take $\bar{\eta} = 600 \text{ km}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Taking $l_c = 30 \text{ Mm}$ and $\tau_\eta = 10^5 \text{ s}$ and assuming $f = 0.1$ ($f \equiv \langle \mu^2 \rangle / \bar{\eta}^2$), we find $\mathcal{D}_1 \approx 2 \times 10^{-2}$ and $\mathcal{D}_2 \approx 2 \times 10^{-3}$. While these estimates appear to rule out the operation of such a dynamo in the solar photosphere, one must keep in mind that the quantities involved (including f) are quite uncertain. Further, anisotropy can have a significant effect on the growth rates. Better estimates of the dynamo numbers would require measurements of the spatiotemporal correlation and strength of fluctuations of the turbulent diffusivity (or the kinetic energy) in the solar photosphere.

3.7 Conclusions

We have used a double-averaging procedure and found that just like helicity fluctuations, fluctuations of the turbulent kinetic energy can drive the growth of a large-scale magnetic field. While Silant'ev (1999, p. 49) has also reported that spatiotemporal fluctuations of the turbulent kinetic energy reduce the effective turbulent diffusion, we are not aware of any detailed studies of this effect that consistently account for the concomitant spatial gradients.

In the white-noise limit, we have found that η -fluctuations cause a reduction in the overall turbulent diffusion (in agreement with previous work), while also contributing a drift term which does not affect the growth of the field. We have then explored effects of nonzero correlation times and found the possibility of growing mean field solutions despite the overall turbulent diffusion remaining positive. When the fluctuations are isotropic, the growth rate of a particular Fourier mode of the large-scale magnetic field depends on the magnitude of its wavevector and on two dynamo numbers. Anisotropy leads to a dependence on, among other things, the direction of the wavevector.

We have studied the conditions under which this new dynamo can operate. While the conditions in the solar photosphere do not appear to favour the operation of this mechanism, the lack of precise estimates of the quantities involved makes it hard to conclusively rule out or support the resulting dynamo in this and other astrophysical scenarios. Further, we expect quantitative application to be handicapped by the inability of the quasilinear approximation to fully capture the effects of nonzero correlation time (this limitation of the quasilinear approximation will be discussed in chapter 4); a possible remedy is the use of more involved closures, such as those based on the Furutsu-Novikov theorem (appendix 4.B describes this theorem, which we apply to different problems in chapters 4 and 5).

Given the prevalence of shear in astrophysical systems, an obvious extension of

the current work would be to study the implications, for a large-scale magnetic field, of fluctuations of the turbulent kinetic energy in a shearing background. Since inhomogeneities in the density and in the small-scale magnetic energy also give rise to pumping (Vainshtein and Kichatinov 1983), we expect them to have effects similar to those described here.

Appendices to chapter 3

3.A Dynamo numbers for a simple correlation function

To physically interpret \mathcal{D}_1 and \mathcal{D}_2 (defined in equation 3.36), it is helpful to explicitly write them out for a specific functional form of Q (see equation 3.10b). We take

$$Q(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = C \exp\left(-\frac{|\boldsymbol{\xi}|^2}{2l_c^2}\right), \quad S(t) = \frac{1}{2\tau_\eta} \exp\left(-\frac{|t|}{\tau_\eta}\right) \quad (3.47)$$

which gives us

$$A^{(0)} = C > 0, \quad A_i^{(1)} = 0, \quad A_{ij}^{(2)} = -\frac{C}{l_c^2} \delta_{ij}, \quad A_i^{(3)} = 0 \quad (3.48)$$

If we define

$$\tilde{\tau} \equiv \frac{\tau_\eta}{T} = \frac{\tau_\eta \bar{\eta}}{l_c^2}, \quad f \equiv \frac{\langle \mu^2 \rangle}{\bar{\eta}^2} \quad (3.49)$$

and use the fact that $\langle \mu^2 \rangle = C/(2\tau_\eta)$ (recall that $\mu \equiv \eta - \bar{\eta}$), the dynamo numbers (equation 3.36) become

$$\mathcal{D}_1 \equiv \frac{9f\tilde{\tau}}{4}, \quad \mathcal{D}_2 \equiv \frac{81f\tilde{\tau}^2}{16} \quad (3.50)$$

Note that when $\tilde{\tau} \rightarrow 0$, \mathcal{D}_1 remains constant, while $\mathcal{D}_2 \rightarrow 0$. Here, f represents the strength of the fluctuations of η , while $\tilde{\tau}$ is a scaled measure of their correlation time.

3.B What if we did not have turbulent diamagnetism?

Instead of equation 3.2, let us consider the following expression for the EMF:

$$\boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}} = -\eta \nabla \times \boldsymbol{B} \quad (3.51)$$

Equation 3.7 is then replaced by

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle \tilde{\boldsymbol{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \rangle = \int d\mathbf{p} \mathbf{k} \times \left[\mathbf{p} \times \left\{ \langle \tilde{\eta}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}) \rangle \langle \tilde{\boldsymbol{B}}(\mathbf{p}) \rangle + \langle \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}) \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{p}) \rangle \right\} \right] \quad (3.52)$$

Equation 3.9 is replaced by

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{k})}{\partial t} = \int d\mathbf{p} \mathbf{k} \times \left[\mathbf{p} \times \left(\langle \tilde{\eta}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}) \rangle \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{p}) + \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}) \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{p}) \rangle \right) \right] \quad (3.53)$$

Equations 3.13 and 3.14 remain unchanged. Equation 3.17 becomes

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{q}, t) \tilde{\mathbf{b}}(\mathbf{k}, t) \rangle \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau e^{-\langle \eta \rangle k^2 (t-\tau)} \mathbf{k} \times \left[(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{q}) \times \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{q}, \tau) \rangle \right] \tilde{Q}(\mathbf{q}) S(t - \tau) \end{aligned} \quad (3.54)$$

Assuming $S(t) = \delta(t)$ and plugging equation 3.54 into equation 3.52, we obtain the following evolution equation for the large-scale magnetic field:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \rangle &= -\bar{\eta} k^2 \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \rangle + \frac{1}{2} \int d\mathbf{s} \tilde{Q}(\mathbf{s}) (k^2 \delta_{ij} - k_i k_j) s_j \mathbf{s} \cdot \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \rangle \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \int d\mathbf{s} \tilde{Q}(\mathbf{s}) (k^2 - \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{s})^2 \langle \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{k}) \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (3.55)$$

The second term on the RHS above is qualitatively different from any term present in equation 3.22; due to this term, the various components of the large-scale magnetic field may become coupled when the fluctuations of η are anisotropic. This equation (or its extension to the case of nonzero correlation time) may also be used to describe scenarios where the microscopic conductivity itself exhibits stochastic fluctuations. Pétrélis, Alexakis, and Gissinger (2016) and Gressel, Rüdiger, and Elstner (2023) have studied such systems.

Chapter 4

Passive tensor transport with nonzero correlation time

4.1 Introduction

The most common closure in mean-field dynamo theory is the quasilinear approximation (we even used this closure in chapter 3), in which the equations for the fluctuating variables are linearized. Strictly, this closure is valid at either low Reynolds number or low Strouhal number (St , the ratio of the correlation time of the velocity field to its turnover time¹). The former is not of astrophysical relevance. In simulations (Brandenburg and Subramanian 2005a; Käpylä et al. 2006), the Strouhal number is typically found to be in the range $0.1 \leq St \leq 1$. While this suggests that the effects of a nonzero correlation time are not negligible, it leaves room for hope that perturbative approaches can at least capture the qualitative effects of having a nonzero correlation time.

As noted in chapter 3, many authors have suggested that multiscale averaging procedures can be used to understand the corrections to the quasilinear approximation. In particular, Kraichnan (1976) has found that while the turbulent diffusion of the mean of a passive scalar is not affected by the correlation time being nonzero, that of the mean magnetic field is suppressed. However, in the absence of scale separation, the interpretation of such multiscale averaging procedures is unclear (see Hoyng 1988, p. 858); this complicates their direct application to many systems of interest.

More rigorous perturbative calculations have been performed by Knobloch (1977), Drummond (1982), and Nicklaus and Stix (1988). Using independent approaches, Knobloch (1977, using the cumulant expansion) and Drummond (1982, using a path integral formalism) have found that to the lowest order, the turbulent diffusion of the mean passive scalar is suppressed when the correlation time is

¹Note that this definition, which seems to be prevalent in the dynamo community (going back to Krause and Rädler 1980, eq. 3.14), is different from the more common definition which is used for oscillatory flows (e.g. White 1999, p. 295).

nonzero. Applying the cumulant expansion, Nicklaus and Stix (1988) have found that the turbulent diffusion of the magnetic field is also suppressed when the correlation time is nonzero.² As we will later see, comparison of the results obtained by Knobloch (1977) and Drummond (1982) for the passive scalar with that reported by Nicklaus and Stix (1988) for the magnetic field suggests that the turbulent diffusivity for the mean magnetic field is *identical* to that for the mean passive scalar even when the correlation time of the velocity field is nonzero. This disagrees qualitatively with the findings of Kraichnan (1976).

Mizerski (2023), using a renormalization group analysis, has calculated the effect of the kinetic helicity on the diffusion of the mean magnetic field in the limit of low fractional helicity. In their method, the correlation time of the velocity field is nonzero, and is implicitly determined by the equations of motion. In qualitative agreement with the other studies mentioned above, they report that turbulent diffusion of the magnetic field is suppressed in a helical velocity field. However, they have not considered the case of a passive scalar, and so it is still unclear if turbulent diffusion affects the mean passive scalar and the mean magnetic field in the same way.

For a Gaussian random velocity field, one can use the Furutsu-Novikov theorem (Furutsu 1963; Novikov 1965) to write turbulent transport coefficients as series in the correlation time of the velocity field.³ While this approach has been used to study the small-scale dynamo (Schekochihin and Kulsrud 2001; Gopalakrishnan and Singh 2024), passive scalar transport (Gleeson 2000), and the effects of shear on plasma turbulence (Zhang and Mahajan 2017), we are not aware of it being used to study the transport of the mean magnetic field.

In this chapter, our goal is to use the Furutsu-Novikov theorem to find out how a nonzero correlation time affects the mean transport of a passive scalar and a passive pseudotensor (the magnetic field). In section 4.2, we use the quasilinear approximation to study the diffusion of the mean of a passive scalar. In section 4.3, we apply the Furutsu-Novikov theorem to the same problem, highlighting the differences as compared to the quasilinear approximation. In section 4.4, we apply the same technique to the diffusion of the mean of a magnetic field. Finally, we summarize our conclusions in section 4.5.

²While Knobloch (1977) also treated the case of the mean magnetic field, that particular result has a problem which we point out in section 4.4.3.2.

³Schekochihin and Kulsrud (2001) discuss how this method is related to other methods such as the cumulant expansion.

4.2 Scalar transport in the quasilinear approximation

4.2.1 Mean and fluctuating fields

We consider a passive scalar, evolving according to

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} = \kappa \nabla^2 \theta - \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \theta \quad (4.1)$$

We split the scalar into mean and fluctuating components, $\theta = \Phi + \phi$, choosing an averaging procedure, $\langle \square \rangle$, that obeys Reynolds' rules (e.g. Monin and Yaglom 1971, sec. 3.1). For simplicity, we assume $\langle \mathbf{u} \rangle = \mathbf{0}$. The evolution equations for Φ and ϕ are

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} = \kappa \nabla^2 \Phi - \langle \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \phi \rangle \quad (4.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} = \kappa \nabla^2 \phi - \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \phi + \langle \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \phi \rangle - \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \Phi \quad (4.3)$$

4.2.2 The quasilinear approximation

In the quasilinear approximation (which we described in some detail in chapter 3), we discard second-order correlations of the fluctuating quantities in equation 4.3, and write

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} = \kappa \nabla^2 \phi - \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \Phi \quad (4.4)$$

The above is an advection-diffusion equation with a source term $-\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \Phi$. Assuming the perturbations ϕ were zero at $t \rightarrow -\infty$,⁴ we can write

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = - \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau \int d\mathbf{q} G(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{q}, \tau) \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{q}} \Phi(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \quad (4.5)$$

where the diffusive Green function is

$$G(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{x}', t') \equiv [4\pi\kappa(t-t')]^{-3/2} \exp\left(-\frac{(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}')^2}{4\kappa(t-t')}\right) \quad (4.6)$$

We now consider the term $\langle \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \phi \rangle$ in equation 4.2. Using equation 4.5, we write this term as

$$\langle \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \phi \rangle = - \left\langle \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau \int d\mathbf{q} G(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{q}, \tau) \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{q}} \Phi(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \right\rangle \quad (4.7)$$

Assuming $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0$, we write the above as

$$\langle \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \phi \rangle = - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau \int d\mathbf{q} G(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{q}, \tau) \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_j(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \rangle \frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{\partial q_j} \quad (4.8)$$

⁴Note that under the quasilinear approximation, the initial condition does not contribute to $\langle \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \phi \rangle$ at later times if it is uncorrelated with the fluctuating velocity field.

4.2.3 White-noise velocity field

Let us assume a homogeneous, isotropic, delta-correlated velocity field, i.e.

$$\langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_j(\mathbf{x}, \tau) \rangle = \frac{2}{3} E \delta_{ij} \delta(t - \tau) \quad (4.9)$$

where E is defined in equation 4.137a (appendix 4.H.3). Setting $\kappa = 0$ (so that we have $G(\mathbf{x}, t|\mathbf{q}, \tau) = \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{q}) \Theta(t - \tau)$), equation 4.8 becomes

$$\langle \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \phi \rangle = - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_j(\mathbf{x}, \tau) \rangle \frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{\partial x_j} \quad (4.10)$$

$$= - \frac{E}{3} \nabla^2 \Phi \quad (4.11)$$

where we have used $\int_0^\infty \delta(t) dt = 1/2$. Plugging the above into equation 4.2, we obtain

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} = \left(\kappa + \frac{E}{3} \right) \nabla^2 \Phi \quad (4.12)$$

where $E/3$ is referred to as the turbulent diffusivity. In this approximation, the only effect of the fluctuating velocity field (\mathbf{u}) is to enhance the diffusivity of the mean scalar field ($\Phi \equiv \langle \theta \rangle$). Note that the mean velocity field, \mathbf{U} , does not enter into the expression for the turbulent diffusivity.

4.2.4 Nonzero correlation time

Recall that equation 4.8 contains an integral over past values of Φ . If the correlation time of the velocity field (say τ_c) is small, this integral can be converted to a series in τ_c by Taylor-expanding $\Phi(\mathbf{q}, \tau)$ about the time t . Explicitly, expanding

$$\Phi(\mathbf{q}, \tau) = \Phi(\mathbf{q}, t) + (\tau - t) \frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{q}, t)}{\partial t} + \mathcal{O}((\tau - t)^2) \quad (4.13)$$

one writes⁵

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \phi \rangle = & - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau \int d\mathbf{q} G(\mathbf{x}, t|\mathbf{q}, \tau) \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_j(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \rangle \frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{q}, t)}{\partial q_j} \\ & - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau \int d\mathbf{q} G(\mathbf{x}, t|\mathbf{q}, \tau) \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_j(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \rangle (\tau - t) \frac{\partial^2 \Phi(\mathbf{q}, t)}{\partial q_j \partial t} \\ & + \mathcal{O}\left(\int_{-\infty}^t d\tau (\tau - t)^2 \langle u(\cdot, t) u(\cdot, \tau) \rangle \right) \end{aligned} \quad (4.14)$$

⁵In principle, one should also Taylor-expand the diffusive Green function which appears inside the integral, but for now, we are only interested in the contributions that are independent of κ .

The three lines on the RHS are $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c^0)$, $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c^1)$, and $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c^2)$ respectively. If one wishes to discard $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c^2)$ terms above, one can use equation 4.12 to substitute for $\partial\Phi/\partial t$ appearing on the second line.

However, we shall soon see that the higher-order velocity correlations neglected in the quasilinear approximation also have $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ contributions to the equation for $\langle \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \phi \rangle$; one thus has to go beyond the quasilinear approximation to study the effects of having a nonzero correlation time.

4.3 Scalar transport with nonzero correlation time

4.3.1 Application of the Furutsu-Novikov theorem

We use the Furutsu-Novikov theorem (appendix 4.B)

$$\langle u_i(x, t) \lambda_i(x, t) \rangle = \int \langle u_i(x, t) u_j(x', t') \rangle \left\langle \frac{\delta \lambda_i(x, t)}{\delta u_j(x', t')} \right\rangle d^3 x' dt' \quad (4.15)$$

where λ_i is some functional of u_i , and u_i is a Gaussian random field with zero mean.

We treat the evolution equation for the total passive scalar (equation 4.1) as diffusion with a source term $-\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \theta$ and write⁶

$$\theta(\mathbf{x}, t) = - \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau \int d\mathbf{q} G(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{q}, \tau) u_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \frac{\partial \theta(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{\partial q_m} \quad (4.16)$$

$$\implies \frac{\partial \theta(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial x_i} = - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau \int d\mathbf{q} G(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{q}, \tau) u_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \frac{\partial \theta(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{\partial q_m} \quad (4.17)$$

Note that G does not depend on \mathbf{u} . Defining $\lambda_i \equiv \partial_i \theta$ and taking the functional variation on both sides, we write

$$\delta \lambda_i(\mathbf{x}, t) = - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau \int d\mathbf{q} G(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{q}, \tau) [\lambda_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \delta u_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) + u_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \delta \lambda_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau)] \quad (4.18)$$

$$= - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau \int d\mathbf{q} G(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{q}, \tau) \left[\lambda_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \delta u_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) + u_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \int d\mathbf{x}'' dt'' \frac{\delta \lambda_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{\delta u_k(\mathbf{x}'', t'')} \Theta(\tau - t'') \delta u_k(\mathbf{x}'', t'') \right] \quad (4.19)$$

Using the above, we write

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\delta \lambda_i(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\delta u_j(\mathbf{x}', t')} &= - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} G(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{x}', t') \Theta(t - t') \lambda_j(\mathbf{x}', t') \\ &\quad - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \int_{t'}^t d\tau \int d\mathbf{q} G(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{q}, \tau) u_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \frac{\delta \lambda_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{\delta u_j(\mathbf{x}', t')} \Theta(t - \tau) \end{aligned} \quad (4.20)$$

⁶We have ignored a term containing the convolution of the Green function with the initial condition, since we expect its functional derivative wrt. \mathbf{u} at later times to be zero.

Averaging both sides, we write

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle \frac{\delta \lambda_i(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\delta u_j(\mathbf{x}', t')} \right\rangle &= -\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} G(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{x}', t') \Theta(t - t') \langle \lambda_j(\mathbf{x}', t') \rangle \\ &\quad - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \int_{t'}^t d\tau \int d\mathbf{q} G(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{q}, \tau) \Theta(t - t') \left\langle u_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \frac{\delta \lambda_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{\delta u_j(\mathbf{x}', t')} \right\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (4.21)$$

Now, we plug the above into equation 4.15 and write

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \theta \rangle &= \int \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_j(\mathbf{x}', t') \rangle \left\langle \frac{\delta \lambda_i(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\delta u_j(\mathbf{x}', t')} \right\rangle d\mathbf{x}' dt' \quad (4.22) \\ &= - \int d\mathbf{x}' dt' \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_j(\mathbf{x}', t') \rangle \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} G(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{x}', t') \Theta(t - t') \langle \lambda_j(\mathbf{x}', t') \rangle \\ &\quad - \int d\mathbf{q} d\mathbf{x}' dt' \int_{t'}^t d\tau \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_j(\mathbf{x}', t') \rangle \Theta(t - t') \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} G(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{q}, \tau) \left\langle u_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \frac{\delta \lambda_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{\delta u_j(\mathbf{x}', t')} \right\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (4.23)$$

The first term in the above is exactly the expression obtained using the quasilinear approximation (equation 4.7). The second term becomes zero if the correlation time of the velocity field is zero, and can be thought of as a correction to the quasilinear approximation. We note that Lipscombe, Frenkel, and Ter Haar (1991), who used the Furutsu-Novikov theorem to study the transport of a passive scalar, only retained the first term on the RHS, making their result identical to that obtained using the quasilinear approximation.

In fact, by repeated application of the Furutsu-Novikov theorem, the second term can be expanded as a series.⁷ To easily represent the terms of this series, we now define some new symbols. We will use \textcircled{a} , where $a = 1, 2, \dots$, to denote a combination of position and time variables which are integrated over. A derivative wrt. the aforementioned position variable will be denoted as $\partial^{(a)}$. \boxtimes will denote the combination (\mathbf{x}, t) . $\mathbf{u}(\textcircled{1})$ will be denoted as $\mathbf{u}\textcircled{1}$. Similarly, we will use $\boxed{1_i 2_j}$ to denote $\langle u_i \textcircled{1} u_j \textcircled{2} \rangle$. We will denote

$$\boxed{\frac{\beta_m}{1_{j_1} \dots n_{j_n}}} \equiv \left\langle \frac{\delta^n \lambda_m \textcircled{\beta}}{\delta u_{j_1} \textcircled{1} \dots u_{j_n} \textcircled{n}} \right\rangle \quad (4.24)$$

$$\partial_m(1|2) \equiv \partial_m^{(1)} G^c(\textcircled{1}|\textcircled{2}) \quad (4.25)$$

⁷After performing these calculations, we came to know that Gleeson (2000) has also used a very similar approach, but in Fourier space for non-helical turbulence. They were able to write a very elegant diagrammatic expansion of the terms in this series; they then applied Padé resummation (Bender and Orszag 1978, sec. 8.3) to obtain expressions for the turbulent diffusivity with much better convergence properties.

where G^c is the causal Green's function (see appendix 4.C). In this notation, equation 4.89 can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \boxed{\frac{\boxtimes_i}{1_{j_1} \dots n_{j_n}}} &= - S_{1,2,\dots,n} \partial_i(\boxtimes|1) \boxed{\frac{1_{j_1}}{2_{j_2} \dots n_{j_n}}} \\ &\quad - \int d\text{Ad}B \partial_i(\boxtimes|A) \boxed{A_m B_a} \boxed{\frac{A_m}{B_a 1_{j_1} \dots n_{j_n}}} \end{aligned} \quad (4.26)$$

where $S_{abc\dots}$ is an operator that symmetrizes over all the arguments indicated in the subscript.⁸ Hereafter, we will dispense with integral symbols, proceeding with the understanding that \boxtimes is the only variable that is not integrated over. Applying this relation thrice to

$$\langle \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \theta \rangle = \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \boxed{\frac{\boxtimes_i}{1_{i_1}}} \quad (4.27)$$

(equation 4.15), we obtain the expression given in appendix 4.D. Throwing away terms with more than two velocity correlations, we are left with

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \theta \rangle &= - \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_i(\boxtimes|1) \langle \lambda_{i_1} \textcircled{1} \rangle \\ &\quad - \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_i(\boxtimes|2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_2}(2|1) \partial_{i_1}(1|3) \langle \lambda_{i_3} \textcircled{3} \rangle \\ &\quad - \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_i(\boxtimes|2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_2}(2|3) \partial_{i_3}(3|1) \langle \lambda_{i_1} \textcircled{1} \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (4.28)$$

As pointed out earlier, the first term above is just the quasilinear term (see equation 4.7). To consistently obtain the $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ contributions to the above equation, one should also expand the quasilinear term as a series in the correlation time, as described in section 4.2.4.

4.3.2 The order of the neglected terms

The leading-order (in τ_c) contribution of a particular term can be deduced as follows.⁹ Each velocity correlation introduces a factor of \mathfrak{D} (see equation 4.32), for which $\int \mathfrak{D}(\tau) d\tau = \mathcal{O}(1)$. Each of the remaining time integrals contributes a factor of τ_c . The order of a particular term in τ_c is then simply the number of time integrals minus the number of velocity correlations. The object on the RHS of equation 4.27 contains one time integral with one velocity correlation, so it has no 'explicit' factors of τ_c (everything is hidden inside the functional derivative).

In figure 4.1, the vertical lines denote functional derivatives of various orders. Starting from the RHS of equation 4.27 (black circle), one obtains various terms

⁸E.g., $S_{12}A_{12} = A_{12} + A_{21}$.

⁹A term whose leading-order contribution is at a particular order in τ_c may contain higher-order contributions as well, as discussed in section 4.2.4.

Figure 4.1: Figure used to find the order in τ_c of the neglected terms; explanation in main text.

after repeated application of the recursion relation (equation 4.89 or 4.26; in the figure, each blue circle with arrows leading out corresponds to one application of the relation). A rightward step adds two time integrals and a velocity correlation, while a leftward step introduces neither velocity correlations nor time integrals. The order of a particular term in τ_c is thus simply the number of rightward steps taken to reach it, starting from the black circle. The terms we have neglected are $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c^2)$.

4.3.3 Aside: validity of the quasilinear approximation

From the discussion above, it is clear that the quasilinear approximation is valid when the correlation time of the velocity field is zero.

Even when the correlation time is nonzero, one may expect the quasilinear approximation to remain valid if the $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ correction from the quasilinear approximation (the second term of equation 4.14) is much larger than the $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ contributions from the second and third terms on the RHS of equation 4.28. We may estimate the ratios of these contributions as

$$\frac{\text{post-quasilinear}}{\text{quasilinear}} \sim \left(\frac{\tau^3 u^4}{l^4} \Phi \right) / \left(\frac{\tau^2 u^2}{l^2} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} \right) \quad (4.29)$$

where l denotes a length scale typical of the spatial derivative of an averaged quantity, τ denotes the correlation time of the fluctuating velocity field, and u is the RMS value of the fluctuating velocity field. If we further use equation 4.12 for $\partial \Phi / \partial t$, we can write

$$\frac{\text{post-quasilinear}}{\text{quasilinear}} \sim \frac{\tau u^2}{\kappa + \tau u^2 / 3}. \quad (4.30)$$

Defining $St \equiv \tau u/l$ and $Pe \equiv ul/\kappa$ (Pe , the *Peclet number*, is the ratio of the diffusive timescale to the advective timescale for the total passive scalar), we can write the above as

$$\frac{\text{post-quasilinear}}{\text{quasilinear}} \sim \frac{St Pe}{1 + St Pe/3}. \quad (4.31)$$

This shows that even when the correlation time of the velocity field is nonzero, a small-enough Pe ensures the validity of quasilinear approximation. On the other hand, when $Pe \gg 1/St$, the quasilinear approximation becomes invalid regardless of whether $St \ll 1$.

4.3.4 Simplification assuming separable, weakly inhomogeneous turbulence

4.3.4.1 Assumptions

Assuming $\kappa = 0$ (which corresponds to $Pe \gg 1$), we simplify the terms on the RHS of equation 4.28 in appendix 4.F. The expressions obtained are somewhat long. We proceed by assuming the velocity correlations are separable, i.e.

$$\langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t + \tau) \partial_{i_1 \dots i_n}^n u_j(\mathbf{x}, t) \rangle = C_{ij i_1 \dots i_n}(\mathbf{x}, t) \mathfrak{D}(\tau) \quad (4.32)$$

The temporal correlation function, \mathfrak{D} , has the properties

$$2 \int_0^\infty \mathfrak{D}(t) dt = 1 \quad (4.33a)$$

$$2 \int_0^\infty t \mathfrak{D}(t) dt = \tau_c \quad (4.33b)$$

where τ_c is the correlation time. We further assume that $C(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $\langle \lambda_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \rangle$ vary on a timescale much larger than the timescale of $\mathfrak{D}(\tau)$. Discarding terms with more than two derivatives of the mean scalar field (Φ) and taking the ‘weakly inhomogeneous’ case (where we keep only one large-scale derivative of the turbulent spectra; see appendix 4.H), we obtain simple expressions, which we describe below.

4.3.4.2 The diffusion equation for the mean scalar

Setting $\kappa = 0$, the average of the evolution equation for the total passive scalar (equation 4.1) is

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} = - \langle \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \theta \rangle \quad (4.34)$$

Using equations 4.108, 4.109, and 4.110 (appendix 4.F.4), we write the above as

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[\left(\frac{E}{3} + \frac{\tau_c g_1 H^2}{18} - \frac{\tau_c 2g_2 EN}{9} \right) \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x_i} \right] \quad (4.35)$$

where g_1 and g_2 depend on the temporal correlation function $\mathfrak{D}(\tau)$ (table 4.1); τ_c is the correlation time of the velocity field; and E , H , and N (defined in equations 4.137) are related to the energy, helicity, and enstrophy respectively.

Interestingly, for a maximally helical velocity field with a top-hat temporal correlation function ($g_2 = 1/12$ and $H^2 = 2EN$), the $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ correction to the turbulent diffusivity becomes zero. On the other hand, if the temporal correlation function is exponential, we obtain

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[\left(\frac{E}{3} - \frac{\tau_c}{144} (4EN - H^2) \right) \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x_i} \right] + \mathcal{O}(\tau_c^2) \quad (4.36)$$

Note that the $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ terms in this case cannot be zero, since the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality guarantees that $H^2 \leq 2EN$. The corrections obtained by us match those obtained by Drummond (1982, eq. 5.1) and Knobloch (1977, eq. 38).¹⁰

Examination of equation 4.35 shows that for weakly inhomogeneous turbulence, the effective diffusivity becomes negative when $\tau_c N (2g_2 - g_1 f^2) > 3$ (where we have defined $f^2 \equiv H^2/2EN \in [0, 1]$) and is positive otherwise. However, when the $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ corrections are so strong, one would expect the neglected $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c^2)$ terms to also become non-negligible, making equation 4.35 invalid.

4.3.4.3 Validity of the expansion

We now make a crude estimate of how $\tau_c N$, which controls the validity of equation 4.36, depends on Re . Assuming the velocity field is homogeneous and isotropic, we estimate (recall that N was defined in equation 4.137)

$$N \propto \int k^2 \tilde{C}_{ii}(k) d\mathbf{k} \quad (4.37)$$

where \tilde{C}_{ii} is the Fourier transform of C_{ii} (equation 4.32). Let us assume $\tilde{C}_{ii}(k)$ is a power law in $k_0 < k < k_\nu$ (which we refer to as the inertial range) and zero elsewhere. If we assume the velocity field obeys the Kolmogorov scaling relations (e.g. Davidson 2004, section 1.6) in the inertial range, the fact that $C_{ii}(\mathbf{x})$ is dimensionally a diffusivity implies $\tilde{C}_{ii}(k) \sim k^{-13/3}$. We then estimate

$$N \propto \int_{k_0}^{k_\nu} k^{-1/3} dk \propto k_\nu^{2/3} - k_0^{2/3} \approx k_\nu^{2/3} \quad (4.38)$$

where the last step assumes $k_\nu \gg k_0$. Similarly, we can also estimate $E \sim k_0^{-4/3}$, which gives us $N/(Ek_0^2) \propto \text{Re}^{1/2}$. Defining $\text{St} \equiv \tau_c u_{\text{rms}} k_0$ and noting that $E \propto \tau_c u_{\text{rms}}^2$, we find

$$\tau_c N \propto \text{St}^2 \text{Re}^{1/2} . \quad (4.39)$$

¹⁰In both cases, we compared results after assuming an exponential temporal correlation function. Knobloch's (1977) expressions need to be further simplified assuming a statistically homogeneous and isotropic Gaussian velocity field.

This means that for equation 4.36 to be valid, we require both the Strouhal number and the Reynolds number to not be large. We believe the latter limitation is due to our assumption that the velocity field at all scales can be characterized by a single scale-independent correlation time (τ_c).

4.4 Magnetic field transport with nonzero correlation time

4.4.1 Application of the Furutsu-Novikov theorem

Let us consider the induction equation with constant η :

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times (\mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{B}) + \eta \nabla^2 \mathbf{B} \quad (4.40)$$

Averaging both sides, we find that the equation for the mean magnetic field is

$$\frac{\partial \overline{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times \mathcal{E} + \eta \nabla^2 \overline{\mathbf{B}} \quad (4.41)$$

where

$$\mathcal{E} \equiv \langle \mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{b} \rangle, \quad \mathbf{b} \equiv \mathbf{B} - \overline{\mathbf{B}} \quad (4.42)$$

To solve for the evolution of the mean magnetic field without solving for the fluctuating fields, we require an expression for \mathcal{E} that depends only on known statistical properties of the velocity field and on $\overline{\mathbf{B}}$.

Treating the first term on the RHS of equation 4.40 as a source, we can write the magnetic field at some arbitrary time as (analogous to equation 4.16 for the passive scalar)

$$B_i(\mathbf{x}, t) = \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau \int d\mathbf{q} G(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{q}, \tau) \epsilon_{ijk} \epsilon_{klm} \frac{\partial}{\partial q_j} (u_l(\mathbf{q}, \tau) B_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau)) \quad (4.43)$$

We assume \mathbf{u} is a Gaussian random field. For simplicity, we also assume $\langle \mathbf{u} \rangle = \mathbf{0}$, so that the EMF can be written as $\mathcal{E} = \langle \mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{B} \rangle$. The Furutsu-Novikov theorem (appendix 4.B) takes the form

$$\langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) B_j(\mathbf{x}, t) \rangle = \int d\mathbf{x}' dt' \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_k(\mathbf{x}', t') \rangle \left\langle \frac{\delta B_j(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\delta u_k(\mathbf{x}', t')} \right\rangle \quad (4.44)$$

For the sake of brevity, we will use notation similar to that described on page 56. Explicitly,

$$\boxed{\frac{\beta_m}{1_{j_1} \dots n_{j_n}}} \equiv \left\langle \frac{\delta^n \lambda_m(\beta)}{\delta u_{j_1}(\mathbb{1}) \dots u_{j_n}(\mathbb{n})} \right\rangle \quad (4.45)$$

$$\partial_m(1|2) \equiv \delta_m^{(2)} G^c(\textcircled{1}|\textcircled{2}) \quad (4.46)$$

$$\Upsilon_{ijlm} \equiv \epsilon_{ijk} \epsilon_{klm} \quad (4.47)$$

The average of the n -th functional derivative of B (equation 4.144, appendix 4.I) can then be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \boxed{\frac{\boxtimes_i}{1_{i_1} \dots n_{i_n}}} &= - \int dA dB \partial_j(\boxtimes|\textcircled{A}) \Upsilon_{ijlm} \boxed{A_l B_a} \boxed{\frac{A_m}{1_{i_1} \dots n_{i_n} B_a}} \\ &\quad - \sum_{\alpha=1}^n \partial_j(\boxtimes|\textcircled{\alpha}) \Upsilon_{iji\alpha m} \boxed{\frac{\alpha_m}{1_{i_1} \dots (\alpha-1)_{i_{\alpha-1}} (\alpha+1)_{i_{\alpha+1}} \dots n_{i_n}}} \end{aligned} \quad (4.48)$$

Henceforth, we will adopt the convention that \boxtimes is the only variable that is not integrated over. Equation 4.44 can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) B_j(\mathbf{x}, t) \rangle &= \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_k} \boxed{\frac{\boxtimes_j}{1_k}} \quad (4.49) \\ &= - \Upsilon_{ji_2 i_1 i_3} \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_{i_2}(\boxtimes|1) \bar{B}_{i_3} \textcircled{1} \\ &\quad - \Upsilon_{i_5 i_6 i_1 i_7} \Upsilon_{jj_3 i_2 j_2} \Upsilon_{j_2 i_4 i_3 i_5} \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_{j_3}(\boxtimes|2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_4}(2|3) \partial_{i_6}(3|1) \bar{B}_{i_7} \textcircled{1} \\ &\quad - \Upsilon_{i_5 i_6 i_3 i_7} \Upsilon_{jj_3 i_2 j_2} \Upsilon_{j_2 i_4 i_1 i_5} \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_{j_3}(\boxtimes|2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_4}(2|1) \partial_{i_6}(1|3) \bar{B}_{i_7} \textcircled{3} \end{aligned} \quad (4.50)$$

where we have applied the relation 4.48 thrice and discarded any remaining terms with functional derivatives. As argued in the case of the passive scalar (section 4.3), the first term is $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c^0)$ (but also contains $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ contributions), while the next two terms are $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$, where τ_c is the correlation time of the velocity field.

4.4.2 The white-noise limit

The $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c^0)$ term of equation 4.50 is

$$\langle u_i B_j \rangle = - \Upsilon_{ji_2 i_1 i_3} \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_{i_2}(\boxtimes|1) \bar{B}_{i_3} \textcircled{1} \quad (4.51)$$

$$= - \Upsilon_{ji_2 i_1 i_3} \int d\mathbf{x}' dt' \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}', t') \rangle \frac{\partial G^c(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{x}', t')}{\partial x'_{i_2}} \bar{B}_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}', t') \quad (4.52)$$

Assuming $\eta = 0$ and discarding the $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ parts of this term, we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \langle u_i B_j \rangle &= \Upsilon_{ji_2 i_1 i_3} \int_{-\infty}^t dt' \left\langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \frac{\partial}{\partial x_{i_2}} u_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, t') \right\rangle \bar{B}_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, t) \\ &\quad + \Upsilon_{ji_2 i_1 i_3} \int_{-\infty}^t dt' \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, t') \rangle \frac{\partial \bar{B}_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial x_{i_2}} \end{aligned} \quad (4.53)$$

Assuming the velocity correlations are separable (equation 4.32) and the turbulence is homogeneous, we can use the expressions from appendix 4.H.3 and write

$$\langle V_i B_j \rangle = \frac{1}{12} \epsilon_{ii_2 j} H \bar{B}_{i_2} - \frac{E}{3} \frac{\partial \bar{B}_j}{\partial x_i} \quad (4.54)$$

where we have used the fact that the divergence of the magnetic field is zero. The EMF can then be written as

$$\mathcal{E}_k = \epsilon_{kij} \langle V_i B_j \rangle = -\frac{H}{6} \bar{B}_k - \frac{E}{3} \epsilon_{kij} \partial_i \bar{B}_j \quad (4.55)$$

which is exactly the same as the usual quasilinear expression (e.g. Moffatt 1978, chapter 7). This is usually written in the form

$$\mathcal{E}_k = \alpha \bar{B}_k - \eta \epsilon_{kij} \partial_i \bar{B}_j \quad (4.56)$$

The coefficient α describes how a helical velocity field can drive the growth of a mean magnetic field, while the coefficient η (called the turbulent diffusivity) describes dissipation of a mean magnetic field through the action of turbulence.

4.4.3 Corrections due to nonzero correlation time

4.4.3.1 Expression for the EMF

In appendix 4.J, we simplify all the three terms on the RHS of equation 4.50, keeping $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ contributions, assuming the turbulence is homogeneous and isotropic, and setting $\eta = 0$. Setting $\eta = 0$ in these terms corresponds to assuming $\text{Rm} \gg 1$ (Rm , the *magnetic Reynolds number*, is the ratio of the diffusive timescale to the advective timescale for the total magnetic field). The overall contribution to the EMF ($\mathcal{E}_k = \epsilon_{kij} \langle V_i B_j \rangle$), the contributions to which are given by equations 4.150, 4.153 and 4.156) is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}_k = & \left(-\frac{H}{6} + \frac{\tau_c g_2}{9} (2EL + HN) \right) \bar{B}_k \\ & - \left(\frac{E}{3} - \tau_c \left[\frac{2ENg_2}{9} + \frac{H^2 g_2}{18} + \frac{H^2}{24} \right] \right) \epsilon_{kr_0 r_1} \partial_{r_0} \bar{B}_{r_1} \end{aligned} \quad (4.57)$$

where we have eliminated g_1 by using the fact that $g_1 + g_2 = 1/4$ (equation 4.98); and E , H , N , and L are defined in equations 4.137. Note that the turbulent diffusion is always suppressed by the $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ terms.

Denoting the turbulent diffusivity for the mean magnetic field as η_B , and that for the mean passive scalar (equation 4.35) as η_θ , we find that

$$\eta_B - \eta_\theta = -\tau_c H^2 \left(\frac{g_1 + g_2}{18} + \frac{1}{24} \right) = -\frac{\tau_c H^2}{18} \quad (4.58)$$

where we have used $g_1 + g_2 = 1/4$ (equation 4.98). Note that this is independent of the form of the temporal correlation function of the velocity field.

4.4.3.2 Comparison with the cumulant expansion

Knobloch (1977) and Nicklaus and Stix (1988) have also studied such corrections using the cumulant expansion.^{11,12} In particular, Nicklaus and Stix (1988, eqs. 24, 26) have further simplified their results by treating the velocity field as a Gaussian random field. Our results are expected to agree with theirs for $t \gg \tau_c$. Our corrections to the α effect indeed match theirs. However, their stated correction to the turbulent diffusivity of the magnetic field differs from our result above, and is instead identical to what we had obtained for passive scalar diffusion (equation 4.35).

Knobloch's (1977, eq. 42) expression for the difference between the magnetic and scalar diffusivities can be simplified by assuming the velocity correlation is separable (equation 4.32). However, the resulting expression contains an integral of the form $\int_0^t dt_1 \int_0^{t_1} dt_2 \int_0^{t_2} dt_3 \mathfrak{D}(t - t_1) \mathfrak{D}(t_2 - t_3)$. This integral diverges as $\mathcal{O}(t; t \rightarrow \infty)$. It is unclear if this is due to missed terms in their calculations, or a limitation of the cumulant expansion. We note that Nicklaus and Stix's (1988, eqs. 24, 26) results do not exhibit this problem as the coefficient of this integral in their expressions turns out to be zero if the velocity field is Gaussian.

4.4.3.3 Relation to the α^2 effect

The negative contribution to the turbulent diffusivity in equation 4.57 is reminiscent of that obtained by Kraichnan (1976, eq. 4.8) using a multi-scale averaging procedure (also Singh 2016; for a more general discussion of such procedures, see Moffatt 1983, sec. 11). However, in Kraichnan's (1976) calculations, the helicity of the velocity field does not have any effect on the mean passive scalar. This is contrary to our finding that helicity can even suppress the diffusion of the mean passive scalar (equation 4.35). The fact that our $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ correction to the diffusion of the mean passive scalar becomes zero when the temporal correlation function is given by a top hat suggests that Kraichnan's (1976) findings may be attributable to his use of a 'renovating flow' model (which corresponds to such a temporal correlation function).

4.4.3.4 Comparison with renormalization group theory

In simulations of forced turbulence, Brandenburg, Schober, and Rogachevskii (2017, fig. 4) found that the turbulent diffusivity is smaller when the turbulence is helically forced than when it is nonhelically forced. Further, they found that for small Rm, the helicity-dependent correction to the turbulent diffusivity of the magnetic field

¹¹Nicklaus and Stix (1988, p. 155) point out some issues with the calculation reported by Knobloch (1977). We agree with the misprint they have pointed out in Knobloch's equation A.13. However, we agree with Knobloch's equation A.8. We have not attempted to verify Knobloch's equation 42.

¹²Schekochihin and Kulsrud (2001, sec. II D) have shown that at least for a simple model problem, the cumulant expansion is consistent with the method we have used.

scales as Rm^2 . This was later confirmed by Mizerski (2023) using renormalization group theory. Since we have focused on the limit of high Rm , we do not recover this scaling.

Mizerski (2023, eq. 18) also derived a correction to the turbulent diffusivity in the limit of small fractional helicity and large Rm . This correction seems consistent with our result (in the sense that the difference between the diffusivity in a helical velocity field and that in a nonhelical velocity field depends on the square of the helicity). While we assume a single scale-independent correlation time, the method used by Mizerski (2023) allows the scale-dependent correlation time to be determined by the equations of motion (and thus it does not appear as a free parameter). Note that Mizerski (2023) do not seem to have calculated the corrections to the α effect (see our equation 4.57); nevertheless, we expect such corrections to be obtainable using their method.

4.5 Conclusions

Conventional treatments of mean-field theory use the quasilinear approximation to derive expressions for transport coefficients which are exact when the correlation time of the velocity field is zero. Assuming the velocity field is a Gaussian random field with a nonzero correlation time, we have applied the Furutsu-Novikov theorem to find the lowest-order corrections to the transport coefficients for two kinds of passive tensors. In the process, we have shown that if the transport coefficients are expanded as series in the correlation time of the velocity field, the quasilinear approximation misses contributions at all orders except the lowest one (which is the term that survives in the limit where the correlation time is zero).

For the diffusion of the mean passive scalar in the limit of high Peclet number, we have verified that our result matches earlier results obtained through different methods (Drummond 1982; Knobloch 1977). Using the multi-scale averaging approach, Kraichnan (1976) has reported that the helicity of the velocity field does not affect the turbulent diffusion of the passive scalar. We have found that this is only the case for a specific form of the temporal correlation function of the velocity field, corresponding to the renovating flow model used in that work.

We have also considered the mean magnetic field (treated, in the kinematic limit, as a passive pseudovector) at high magnetic Reynolds number, and found that both the α effect and magnetic diffusion are affected by the correlation time of the velocity field. An earlier result for the diffusivity of the mean magnetic field (Nicklaus and Stix 1988, eqs. 24, 26) turns out to be identical to that for the mean passive scalar; we obtain extra (negative) contributions to the diffusivity of the mean magnetic field.

The validity of the expressions we have derived is limited by our assumption that the correlation time of the velocity field is scale-independent. While the general formalism we have used can be adapted to account for a scale-dependent correlation time, this is left to future work.

Appendices to chapter 4

4.A Moments-Cumulants formula for functions

4.A.1 Background

For any random variable (which can have nonzero mean), the following expression relates the moments of a particular order to the cumulants and moments of lower order (Smith 1995, eq. 5).

$$M_n = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{i} K_{n-i} M_i \quad (4.59)$$

In the above, M_r is the r -th moment,¹³ and K_r is the r -th cumulant. For a Gaussian with nonzero mean, this reduces to

$$M_n = K_1 M_{n-1} + (n-1) K_2 M_{n-2} \quad (4.60)$$

We would like to derive an analogous expression in the case of random functions.

4.A.2 Derivation

Given a stochastic function $f(t)$, we denote the moment generating functional by $Q[y(t)]$ and the cumulant generating functional by $C[y(t)]$. We denote the n -th (non-central) moment by M_n , and the n -th cumulant by K_n . We first note that

$$Q[y(t)] = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \int \frac{1}{r!} M_r(s_1 \dots s_r) y(s_1) \dots y(s_r) ds_1 \dots ds_r \quad (4.61)$$

$$C[y(t)] = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \int \frac{1}{r!} K_r(s_1 \dots s_r) y(s_1) \dots y(s_r) ds_1 \dots ds_r \quad (4.62)$$

$$Q[y(t)] = e^{C[y(t)]} \quad (4.63)$$

We use D_i to denote $\delta/\delta y(t_i)$, and $\mathcal{S}_{a\dots z}$ to denote symmetrization over $a\dots z$.¹⁴ We then write (omitting the arguments of $D[y(t)]$ and $C[y(t)]$)

$$D_1 Q = e^C D_1 C \quad (4.64)$$

¹³Need not be the central moment.

¹⁴For example, $\mathcal{S}_{1,2} f(1,2) = (f(1,2) + f(2,1))/2$.

$$D_n \dots D_1 Q = D_n \dots D_2 (e^C D_1 C) \quad (4.65)$$

$$= \mathcal{S}_{2\dots n} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{i} (D_n \dots D_{n-i+1} e^C) (D_{n-i} \dots D_1 C) \quad (4.66)$$

Setting $y(t) = 0$ on both sides of the above, we obtain

$$M_n(s_1 \dots s_n) = \mathcal{S}_{2\dots n} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{i} M_i(s_{n-i+1} \dots s_n) K_{n-i}(s_1 \dots s_{n-i}) \quad (4.67)$$

An equivalent way of writing the above is

$$M_n(s_1 \dots s_n) = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \sum_{\mathcal{P}_{n-1,i}} M_i(s_{\alpha_1} \dots s_{\alpha_i}) K_{n-i}(s_1, s_{\alpha_{i+1}}, \dots, s_{\alpha_{n-1}}) \quad (4.68)$$

where $\mathcal{P}_{n-1,i}$ is the family of partitions of $\{2, 3, \dots, n\}$ into the ordered sets $\{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_i\} + \{\alpha_{i+1}, \dots, \alpha_{n-1}\}$.¹⁵

4.A.3 Simplification for a Gaussian functional

For a Gaussian function, only the first two cumulants are nonzero. We thus write equation 4.67 as

$$M_n(s_1 \dots s_n) = \mathcal{S}_{2\dots n} M_{n-1}(s_2 \dots s_n) K_1(s_1) + (n-1) \mathcal{S}_{2\dots n} M_{n-2}(s_3 \dots s_n) K_2(s_1, s_2) \quad (4.69)$$

$$= \mathcal{S}_{2\dots n} M_{n-1}(s_2 \dots s_n) M_1(s_1) + (n-1) \mathcal{S}_{2\dots n} M_{n-2}(s_3 \dots s_n) M_2(s_1, s_2) - (n-1) \mathcal{S}_{2\dots n} M_{n-2}(s_3 \dots s_n) M_1(s_1) M_1(s_2) \quad (4.70)$$

4.B The Furutsu-Novikov theorem

4.B.1 Derivation

In what follows, we define

$$\tilde{f} \equiv f - \mu \quad (4.71)$$

$$\mu \equiv \langle f \rangle \quad (4.72)$$

$$R^{(n)}(s_1 \dots s_n) \equiv \frac{\delta^n R[f]}{\delta f(s_1) \dots \delta f(s_n)} \Big|_{f=\mu} \quad (4.73)$$

¹⁵For example, $\mathcal{P}_{2,1} = \{\{2\} + \{3\}; \{3\} + \{2\}\}$ and

$$\mathcal{P}_{3,1} = \{\{1\} + \{2, 3\}; \{1\} + \{3, 2\}; \{2\} + \{1, 3\}; \{2\} + \{3, 1\}; \{3\} + \{1, 2\}; \{3\} + \{2, 1\}\}$$

We first note that an arbitrary functional $R[f]$ can be expanded in a Taylor series as

$$R[f] = R[\mu] + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \int \cdots \int R^{(n)}(s_1 \dots s_n) \tilde{f}(s_1) \dots \tilde{f}(s_n) ds_1 \dots ds_n \quad (4.74)$$

Now, we differentiate the above and write

$$\frac{\delta R[f]}{\delta f(s')} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \int \cdots \int R^{(n)}(s', s_2 \dots s_n) \tilde{f}(s_2) \dots \tilde{f}(s_n) ds_2 \dots ds_n \quad (4.75)$$

where we have used the fact that $R^{(n)}$ is symmetric in all its arguments.¹⁶

On the other hand, we can use equation 4.74 to write

$$\langle \tilde{f}(s) R[f] \rangle = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \int \cdots \int R^{(n)}(s_1 \dots s_n) \langle \tilde{f}(s) \tilde{f}(s_1) \dots \tilde{f}(s_n) \rangle ds_1 \dots ds_n \quad (4.76)$$

We now use equation 4.70 from appendix 4.A (recalling that $R^{(n)}$ is symmetric in all its arguments) to perform the replacement

$$\langle \tilde{f}(s) \tilde{f}(s_1) \dots \tilde{f}(s_n) \rangle \rightarrow n \langle \tilde{f}(s) \tilde{f}(s_1) \rangle \langle \tilde{f}(s_2) \dots \tilde{f}(s_n) \rangle \quad (4.77)$$

where we have used the fact that $\langle \tilde{f} \rangle = 0$. Equation 4.76 then becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \tilde{f}(s) R[f] \rangle &= \\ & \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \int R^{(n)}(s_1 \dots s_n) \langle \tilde{f}(s) \tilde{f}(s_1) \rangle \langle \tilde{f}(s_2) \dots \tilde{f}(s_n) \rangle ds_1 \dots ds_n \end{aligned} \quad (4.78)$$

Using equation 4.75, we write the above as

$$\begin{aligned} \langle f(s) R[f] \rangle &= \langle f(s) \rangle \langle R[f] \rangle + \int \langle \tilde{f}(s) \tilde{f}(s_1) \rangle \left\langle \frac{\delta R[f]}{\delta f(s_1)} \right\rangle ds_1 \\ &= \langle f(s) \rangle \langle R[f] \rangle + \int \left[\langle f(s) f(s_1) \rangle - \langle f(s) \rangle \langle f(s_1) \rangle \right] \left\langle \frac{\delta R[f]}{\delta f(s_1)} \right\rangle ds_1 \end{aligned} \quad (4.79)$$

$$(4.80)$$

which is consistent with the expression given by Furutsu (1963, eq. 5.18) and Novikov (1965, eq. 2.3) for the zero-mean case.

Till now, we have not specified the nature of the variables s_1, s_2, \dots used above. We may think of each s_r as representing a collection $\{\mathbf{x}_r, t_r, i_r\}$, with \mathbf{x} and t representing position and time respectively. Explicitly, we have

$$f(s_r) \rightarrow f_i(\mathbf{x}_r, t_r) \quad (4.81)$$

$$\int ds_1 \rightarrow \sum_{i_1} \int d\mathbf{x}_1 dt_1 \quad (4.82)$$

¹⁶Note that the functional derivative of $R^{(n)}$ is zero, since $R^{(n)}$ is (by definition) evaluated for a particular value of f .

4.C n -th functional derivative of $\nabla\theta$

We first recall the definition of the n -th functional derivative of a functional $F[f]$ wrt. a function $f(t)$:¹⁷

$$\left. \frac{d^n F[f + \epsilon\chi]}{d\epsilon^n} \right|_{\epsilon=0} = \int \frac{\delta^n F}{\delta f(t_1) \dots \delta f(t_n)} \chi(t_1) \dots \chi(t_n) dt_1 \dots dt_n \quad (4.83)$$

where ϵ is a real number, and $\chi(t)$ is an arbitrary test function.¹⁸

Using the same notation as in section 4.3, we write (similar to equation 4.17)

$$\lambda_i(\mathbf{x}, t) = -\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau \int d\mathbf{q} G(\mathbf{x}, t|\mathbf{q}, \tau) u_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \lambda_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \quad (4.84)$$

Denoting $\bar{\lambda} \equiv \lambda[u_m + \epsilon\chi_m]$, we write

$$\bar{\lambda}_i(\mathbf{x}, t) = -\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau \int d\mathbf{q} G(\mathbf{x}, t|\mathbf{q}, \tau) (u_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) + \epsilon\chi_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau)) \bar{\lambda}_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \quad (4.85)$$

Taking n derivatives on both sides and setting $\epsilon = 0$, we write

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \frac{d^n \bar{\lambda}_i(\mathbf{x}, t)}{d\epsilon^n} \right|_{\epsilon=0} &= -\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau \int d\mathbf{q} G(\mathbf{x}, t|\mathbf{q}, \tau) u_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \left. \frac{d^n \bar{\lambda}_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{d\epsilon^n} \right|_{\epsilon=0} \\ &\quad - n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau \int d\mathbf{q} G(\mathbf{x}, t|\mathbf{q}, \tau) \chi_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \left. \frac{d^{n-1} \bar{\lambda}_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{d\epsilon^{n-1}} \right|_{\epsilon=0} \end{aligned} \quad (4.86)$$

which gives us the following relation between the functional derivatives (we use the notation $u_{j_i} \equiv u_{j_i}(\mathbf{x}^{(i)}, t^{(i)})$):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\delta^n \lambda_i(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\delta u_{j_1} \dots \delta u_{j_n}} &= -\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \int d\mathbf{q} \int_{\max(t^{(1)}, \dots, t^{(n)})}^t d\tau G(\mathbf{x}, t|\mathbf{q}, \tau) u_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \frac{\delta^n \lambda_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{\delta u_{j_1} \dots \delta u_{j_n}} \\ &\quad - \sum_{\alpha=1}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} G(\mathbf{x}, t|\mathbf{x}^{(\alpha)}, t^{(\alpha)}) \Theta(t - t^{(\alpha)}) \frac{\delta^{n-1} \lambda_{j_\alpha}(\mathbf{x}^{(\alpha)}, t^{(\alpha)})}{\delta u_{j_1} \dots \delta u_{j_{\alpha-1}} \delta u_{j_{\alpha+1}} \dots \delta u_{j_n}} \end{aligned} \quad (4.87)$$

We average both sides of the above and use the Furutsu-Novikov theorem (equation

¹⁷Some authors (e.g. Novikov 1965) denote the functional derivative by $\delta R/(\delta f ds)$, in order to make its dimensions explicit.

¹⁸One might be confused about why there is no $1/n!$ or similar term on the RHS, but one can confirm this is correct by considering a functional $\int A(x_1, x_2) dx_1 dx_2$ and comparing it with the Taylor series expansion for a functional (equation 4.74).

4.15) to write

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left\langle \frac{\delta^n \lambda_i(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\delta u_{j_1} \dots \delta u_{j_n}} \right\rangle \\
&= -\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \int d\mathbf{q} d\mathbf{x}' dt' \int_{\max(t^{(1)}, \dots, t^{(n)})}^t d\tau G(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{q}, \tau) \langle u_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) u_a(\mathbf{x}', t') \rangle \left\langle \frac{\delta^{n+1} \lambda_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{\delta u_a(\mathbf{x}', t') \delta u_{j_1} \dots \delta u_{j_n}} \right\rangle \\
&\quad - \sum_{\alpha=1}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} G(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{x}^{(\alpha)}, t^{(\alpha)}) \Theta(t - t^{(\alpha)}) \left\langle \frac{\delta^{n-1} \lambda_{j_\alpha}(\mathbf{x}^{(\alpha)}, t^{(\alpha)})}{\delta u_{j_1} \dots \delta u_{j_{\alpha-1}} \delta u_{j_{\alpha+1}} \dots \delta u_{j_n}} \right\rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{4.88}$$

By taking causality into account ($\delta \lambda(t)/\delta u(t') = 0$ if $t' > t$) we can write the above more compactly as

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left\langle \frac{\delta^n \lambda_i(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\delta u_{j_1} \dots \delta u_{j_n}} \right\rangle \\
&= -\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \int d\mathbf{q} d\mathbf{x}' dt' d\tau G^c(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{q}, \tau) \langle u_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) u_a(\mathbf{x}', t') \rangle \left\langle \frac{\delta^{n+1} \lambda_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{\delta u_a(\mathbf{x}', t') \delta u_{j_1} \dots \delta u_{j_n}} \right\rangle \\
&\quad - \sum_{\alpha=1}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} G^c(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{x}^{(\alpha)}, t^{(\alpha)}) \left\langle \frac{\delta^{n-1} \lambda_{j_\alpha}(\mathbf{x}^{(\alpha)}, t^{(\alpha)})}{\delta u_{j_1} \dots \delta u_{j_{\alpha-1}} \delta u_{j_{\alpha+1}} \dots \delta u_{j_n}} \right\rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{4.89}$$

Note the superscript ‘c’ on the Green function, which denotes that it has been made causal:

$$G^c(x, t | x', t') = \begin{cases} G(x, t | x', t') & , t' \leq t \\ 0 & , \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{4.90}$$

4.D Higher-order terms of the series of functional derivatives

On applying the relation 4.26 thrice to the term $\langle \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \theta \rangle$, we obtain¹⁹

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \theta \rangle &= - \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_i(\boxtimes|1) \langle \lambda_{i_1} \textcircled{1} \rangle \\
&\quad - \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_i(\boxtimes|2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_2}(2|1) \partial_{i_1}(1|3) \langle \lambda_{i_3} \textcircled{3} \rangle \\
&\quad - \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_i(\boxtimes|2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_2}(2|1) \partial_{i_1}(1|4) \boxed{4_{i_4} 5_{i_5}} \boxed{\frac{4_{i_4}}{3_{i_3} 5_{i_5}}} \\
&\quad - \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_i(\boxtimes|2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_2}(2|3) \partial_{i_3}(3|1) \langle \lambda_{i_1} \textcircled{1} \rangle
\end{aligned}$$

¹⁹The recursion relation 4.26 can be easily coded into a set of rules in a CAS like SymPy. The following expression has been obtained from such a program.

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_i(\boxtimes|2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_2}(2|3) \partial_{i_3}(3|4) \boxed{4_{i_4} 5_{i_5}} \boxed{\frac{4_{i_4}}{1_{i_1} 5_{i_5}}} \quad (4.91) \\
& - \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_i(\boxtimes|2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_2}(2|4) \boxed{4_{i_4} 5_{i_5}} \partial_{i_4}(4|1) \boxed{\frac{1_{i_1}}{3_{i_3} 5_{i_5}}} \\
& - \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_i(\boxtimes|2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_2}(2|4) \boxed{4_{i_4} 5_{i_5}} \partial_{i_4}(4|3) \boxed{\frac{3_{i_3}}{1_{i_1} 5_{i_5}}} \\
& - \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_i(\boxtimes|2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_2}(2|4) \boxed{4_{i_4} 5_{i_5}} \partial_{i_4}(4|5) \boxed{\frac{5_{i_5}}{1_{i_1} 3_{i_3}}} \\
& - \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_i(\boxtimes|2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_2}(2|4) \boxed{4_{i_4} 5_{i_5}} \partial_{i_4}(4|6) \boxed{6_{i_6} 7_{i_7}} \boxed{\frac{6_{i_6}}{1_{i_1} 3_{i_3} 5_{i_5} 7_{i_7}}}
\end{aligned}$$

4.E Coefficients that depend on the temporal correlation function

Our results depend on the form of the temporal correlation function of the velocity field only through the following coefficients:

4.E.1 Definitions

$$g_1 \equiv \frac{1}{\tau_c} \int_{-\infty}^t dt' \int_{-\infty}^{t'} dt_1 \int_{-\infty}^{t_1} dt_2 \mathfrak{D}^{(t-t_1)} \mathfrak{D}^{(t'-t_2)} \quad (4.92a)$$

$$g_2 \equiv \frac{1}{\tau_c} \int_{-\infty}^t dt' \int_{-\infty}^{t'} dt_2 \int_{-\infty}^{t_2} dt_1 \mathfrak{D}^{(t-t_1)} \mathfrak{D}^{(t'-t_2)} \quad (4.92b)$$

The values of these coefficients depend on the form of the temporal correlation function; table 4.1 gives these values for some cases.

4.E.2 An identity

Recalling the definitions of g_1 and g_2 (equations 4.92), we note that

$$\begin{aligned}
g_1 + g_2 &= \frac{1}{\tau_c} \int_{-\infty}^t dt' \int_{-\infty}^{t'} dt_1 \int_{-\infty}^{t_1} dt_2 \mathfrak{D}^{(t-t_1)} \mathfrak{D}^{(t'-t_2)} \\
&+ \frac{1}{\tau_c} \int_{-\infty}^t dt' \int_{-\infty}^{t'} dt_2 \int_{-\infty}^{t_2} dt_1 \mathfrak{D}^{(t-t_1)} \mathfrak{D}^{(t'-t_2)} \quad (4.93)
\end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{1}{\tau_c} \int_{-\infty}^t dt' \int_{-\infty}^{t'} dt_1 \int_{-\infty}^{t'} dt_2 \mathfrak{D}^{(t-t_1)} \mathfrak{D}^{(t'-t_2)} \quad (4.94)$$

Name	$\mathfrak{D}(\tau)$	g_2
Exponential	$\frac{1}{2\tau_c} e^{- \tau /\tau_c}$	1/8
Top hat	$\frac{1}{4\tau_c} \Theta(2\tau_c - \tau) \Theta(\tau + 2\tau_c)$	1/12

Table 4.1: Values of g_2 for some temporal correlation functions. The corresponding values of g_1 can be calculated using equation 4.98. The constants in the correlation functions have been chosen to satisfy equations 4.33.

$$= \frac{1}{2\tau_c} \int_{-\infty}^t dt' \int_{-\infty}^{t'} dt_1 \mathfrak{D}^{(t-t_1)} \quad (4.95)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2\tau_c} \int_{-\infty}^t dt_1 \int_{t_1}^t dt' \mathfrak{D}^{(t-t_1)} \quad (4.96)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2\tau_c} \int_{-\infty}^t dt_1 (t - t_1) \mathfrak{D}^{(t-t_1)} \quad (4.97)$$

$$= \frac{1}{4} \quad (4.98)$$

where we have used the properties of $\mathfrak{D}(\tau)$, given by equations 4.33.

4.F Simplification of the $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ corrections to the evolution equation for the mean passive scalar

We now simplify the terms on the RHS of equation 4.F.

4.F.1 The first higher-order term

Let us assume $\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{0}$ and $\kappa = 0$ (the latter corresponds to neglecting $\mathcal{O}(\kappa\tau_c)$ terms in the final evolution equation for Φ). We then have $G^c(\mathbf{x}, t|\mathbf{q}, \tau) = \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{q}) \Theta(t - \tau)$. For convenience, we will use superscripts on the velocity fields to denote which ones are connected by averaging, such that velocity variables with matching superscripts are connected by averaging (e.g. $\langle uu \rangle \rightarrow u^{(1)}u^{(1)}$). Denoting $\oint \dots \equiv \int d\tau_1 d\tau_2 d\tau_3 \Theta(\tau_1 - \tau_3) \Theta(t - \tau_2) \Theta(\tau_2 - \tau_1) \dots$; assuming the velocity field is incompressible; and integrating by parts as required, we write

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \boxed{\mathfrak{X}_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_i(\mathfrak{X}|2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_2}(2|1) \partial_{i_1}(1|3) \langle \lambda_{i_3} \mathfrak{C} \rangle \\
& = - \boxed{\mathfrak{X}_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_i^{(\mathfrak{X})} \mathcal{G}(\mathfrak{X}|2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_2}^{(2)} \mathcal{G}(2|1) \partial_{i_1}^{(1)} \mathcal{G}(1|3) \langle \lambda_{i_3} \mathfrak{C} \rangle
\end{aligned} \quad (4.99)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= - \oint \int d\mathbf{q}^{(1)} d\mathbf{q}^{(2)} d\mathbf{q}^{(3)} \left[\langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_{i_1}(\mathbf{q}^{(1)}, \tau_1) \rangle \frac{\partial \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{q}^{(2)})}{\partial x_i} \right. \\
&\quad \times \langle u_{i_2}(\mathbf{q}^{(2)}, \tau_2) u_{i_3}(\mathbf{q}^{(3)}, \tau_3) \rangle \frac{\partial \delta(\mathbf{q}^{(2)} - \mathbf{q}^{(1)})}{\partial q_{i_2}^{(2)}} \frac{\partial \delta(\mathbf{q}^{(1)} - \mathbf{q}^{(3)})}{\partial q_{i_1}^{(1)}} \\
&\quad \left. \times \langle \lambda_{i_3}(\mathbf{q}^{(3)}, \tau_3) \rangle \right] \quad (4.100)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \oint u_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, t) \frac{\partial}{\partial x_{i_2}} \left(u_{i_1}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1) u_{i_2}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_2) \frac{\partial}{\partial x_{i_1}} \left[u_{i_3}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_3) \langle \lambda_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_3) \rangle \right] \right) \quad (4.101)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \oint \left\langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \frac{\partial u_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1)}{\partial x_{i_2}} \right\rangle \left\langle u_{i_2}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_2) \frac{\partial u_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_3)}{\partial x_{i_1}} \right\rangle \langle \lambda_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_3) \rangle \\
&\quad - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \oint \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1) \rangle \left\langle u_{i_2}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_2) \frac{\partial^2 u_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_3)}{\partial x_{i_1} \partial x_{i_2}} \right\rangle \langle \lambda_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_3) \rangle \\
&\quad - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \oint \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1) \rangle \left\langle u_{i_2}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_2) \frac{\partial u_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_3)}{\partial x_{i_1}} \right\rangle \frac{\partial \langle \lambda_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_3) \rangle}{\partial x_{i_2}} \\
&\quad - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \oint \left\langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \frac{\partial u_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1)}{\partial x_{i_2}} \right\rangle \langle u_{i_2}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_2) u_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_3) \rangle \frac{\partial \langle \lambda_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_3) \rangle}{\partial x_{i_1}} \\
&\quad - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \oint \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1) \rangle \left\langle u_{i_2}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_2) \frac{\partial u_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_3)}{\partial x_{i_2}} \right\rangle \frac{\partial \langle \lambda_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_3) \rangle}{\partial x_{i_1}} \\
&\quad - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \oint \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1) \rangle \langle u_{i_2}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_2) u_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_3) \rangle \frac{\partial^2 \langle \lambda_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_3) \rangle}{\partial x_{i_1} \partial x_{i_2}} \quad (4.102)
\end{aligned}$$

4.F.2 The second higher-order term

Denoting $\oint \dots \equiv \int d\tau_1 d\tau_2 d\tau_3 \Theta(t - \tau_2) \Theta(\tau_2 - \tau_3) \Theta(\tau_3 - \tau_1) \dots$ and following similar steps, we simplify the other term as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
&- \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_i(\boxtimes|2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_2}(2|3) \partial_{i_3}(3|1) \langle \lambda_{i_1} \textcircled{1} \rangle \\
&= - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \oint \left\langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \frac{\partial u_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1)}{\partial x_{i_3}} \right\rangle \left\langle u_{i_2}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_2) \frac{\partial u_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_3)}{\partial x_{i_2}} \right\rangle \langle \lambda_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1) \rangle \\
&\quad - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \oint \langle u_{i_2}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_2) u_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_3) \rangle \left\langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \frac{\partial^2 u_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1)}{\partial x_{i_3} \partial x_{i_2}} \right\rangle \langle \lambda_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1) \rangle \\
&\quad - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \oint \langle u_{i_2}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_2) u_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_3) \rangle \left\langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \frac{\partial u_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1)}{\partial x_{i_3}} \right\rangle \frac{\partial \langle \lambda_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1) \rangle}{\partial x_{i_2}} \\
&\quad - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \oint \left\langle u_{i_2}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_2) \frac{\partial u_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_3)}{\partial x_{i_2}} \right\rangle \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1) \rangle \frac{\partial \langle \lambda_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1) \rangle}{\partial x_{i_3}} \\
&\quad - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \oint \langle u_{i_2}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_2) u_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_3) \rangle \left\langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \frac{\partial u_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1)}{\partial x_{i_2}} \right\rangle \frac{\partial \langle \lambda_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1) \rangle}{\partial x_{i_3}} \\
&\quad - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \oint \langle u_{i_2}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_2) u_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_3) \rangle \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1) \rangle \frac{\partial^2 \langle \lambda_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, \tau_1) \rangle}{\partial x_{i_3} \partial x_{i_2}} \quad (4.103)
\end{aligned}$$

4.F.3 Taylor expansion of the quasilinear term

Expanding $\langle \lambda_i \rangle$ as indicated in equation 4.14 allows us to evaluate the contributions arising from the first term on the RHS of equation 4.28, neglecting $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c^2)$ terms:

$$\begin{aligned} & - \boxed{\mathbb{X}_i 1_{i_1}} \mathcal{D}_i(\mathbb{X}|1) \langle \lambda_{i_1} \mathbb{D} \rangle \\ &= - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau \int d\mathbf{q} \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{q}) \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_j(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \rangle \frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{q}, t)}{\partial q_j} \end{aligned} \quad (4.104)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau \int d\mathbf{q} \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{q}) \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_j(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \rangle (\tau - t) \frac{\partial^2 \Phi(\mathbf{q}, t)}{\partial q_j \partial t} \\ &= - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_j(\mathbf{x}, \tau) \rangle \frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial x_j} \\ & - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau \int_{-\infty}^t d\tau_2 \langle u_i(\mathbf{x}, t) u_j(\mathbf{x}, \tau) \rangle (\tau - t) \\ & \quad \times \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j \partial x_k} \left(\langle u_k(\mathbf{x}, t) u_l(\mathbf{x}, \tau_2) \rangle \frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial x_l} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (4.105)$$

where we have used equations 4.2 and 4.8 (discarding κ and \mathbf{U} as before).

4.F.4 Further simplification assuming separable correlations

To simplify the expressions obtained above, we assume the velocity correlations are separable (equation 4.32). From now on, we will discard terms which have more than two derivatives of the mean scalar (recall that $\langle \lambda_i \rangle = \partial_i \Phi$). The temporal integrals over the correlation functions in the terms of interest can be written in terms of the constants g_1 and g_2 , defined in equations 4.92. We write equation 4.102 as (omitting spatial and temporal arguments since they are the same for all terms)

$$\begin{aligned} & - \boxed{\mathbb{X}_i 1_{i_1}} \mathcal{D}_i(\mathbb{X}|2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \mathcal{D}_{i_2}(2|1) \mathcal{D}_{i_1}(1|3) \langle \lambda_{i_3} \mathbb{D} \rangle \\ &= - \tau_c g_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (C_{ii_1 i_2} C_{i_2 i_3 i_1} \langle \lambda_{i_3} \rangle) - \tau_c g_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (C_{ii_1} C_{i_2, i_3, i_1, i_2} \langle \lambda_{i_3} \rangle) \\ & - \tau_c g_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(C_{ii_1} C_{i_2 i_3 i_1} \frac{\partial \langle \lambda_{i_3} \rangle}{\partial x_{i_2}} \right) - \tau_c g_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(C_{ii_1 i_2} C_{i_2 i_3} \frac{\partial \langle \lambda_{i_3} \rangle}{\partial x_{i_1}} \right) \\ & - \tau_c g_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(C_{ii_1} C_{i_2 i_3 i_2} \frac{\partial \langle \lambda_{i_3} \rangle}{\partial x_{i_1}} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (4.106)$$

Similarly, equation 4.103 becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \boxed{\mathbf{\times}_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_i(\mathbf{\times}|2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_2}(2|3) \partial_{i_3}(3|1) \langle \lambda_{i_1} \textcircled{1} \rangle \\
& = - \tau_c g_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (C_{ii_1 i_3} C_{i_2 i_3 i_2} \langle \lambda_{i_1} \rangle) - \tau_c g_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (C_{i_2 i_3} C_{ii_1 i_3 i_2} \langle \lambda_{i_1} \rangle) \\
& \quad - \tau_c g_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(C_{i_2 i_3} C_{ii_1 i_3} \frac{\partial \langle \lambda_{i_1} \rangle}{\partial x_{i_2}} \right) - \tau_c g_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(C_{i_2 i_3 i_2} C_{ii_1} \frac{\partial \langle \lambda_{i_1} \rangle}{\partial x_{i_3}} \right) \\
& \quad - \tau_c g_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(C_{i_2 i_3} C_{ii_1 i_2} \frac{\partial \langle \lambda_{i_1} \rangle}{\partial x_{i_3}} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{4.107}$$

We will now keep up to one derivative of the turbulent quantities (E , H , and N), i.e. we will neglect terms like $\nabla^2 E$ or $(\nabla E)^2$. Equation 4.106 becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \boxed{\mathbf{\times}_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_i(\mathbf{\times}|2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_2}(2|1) \partial_{i_1}(1|3) \langle \lambda_{i_3} \textcircled{3} \rangle \\
& = - \frac{\tau_c g_1}{18} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[H^2 \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x_i} \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{4.108}$$

Equation 4.107 becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \boxed{\mathbf{\times}_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_i(\mathbf{\times}|2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_2}(2|3) \partial_{i_3}(3|1) \langle \lambda_{i_1} \textcircled{1} \rangle \\
& = \frac{2\tau_c g_2}{9} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[EN \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x_i} \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{4.109}$$

Equation 4.105 becomes

$$- \boxed{\mathbf{\times}_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_i(\mathbf{\times}|1) \langle \lambda_{i_1} \textcircled{1} \rangle = - \frac{1}{3} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[E \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x_i} \right] \tag{4.110}$$

One might get additional terms on keeping two spatial derivatives of the turbulent quantities, but for that, we would need expressions like those in appendix 4.H.3 up to the same order.

4.G Derivatives of the Dirac delta: a subtlety

Consider the integral

$$I \equiv \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x)g(y) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \delta(x-y) dx \tag{4.111}$$

There are two ways of evaluating this, both of which seem to lead to contradictory results.

Method 1 (correct)

$$I = - \int \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} g(y) \delta(x-y) dx = -f'(y)g(y) \tag{4.112}$$

Method 2 (wrong)

$$I = - \int \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [f(x)g(y)] \delta(x - y) dx = - \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [f(y)g(y)] \quad (4.113)$$

In equation 4.111, if we pull $g(y)$ out of the integral, the answer we get is the same as in method 1. Naively, one would expect both methods to give the same answer, but that is clearly not the case.

4.H Velocity correlations for locally isotropic, weakly inhomogeneous turbulence

4.H.1 Derivation of the equal-time correlation in Fourier-space

The technique used to derive the following expressions was first proposed by Roberts and Soward (1975), and they are well-known (e.g. Rädler, Kleorin, and Rogachevskii 2003; Brandenburg and Subramanian 2005b). However, we briefly outline the derivation for the sake of completeness.

We define $V_{ij}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{K}, t) \equiv \langle \tilde{v}_i(\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{K} + \mathbf{k}, t) \tilde{v}_j(\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{k}, t) \rangle$. If \mathbf{k}_1 and \mathbf{k}_2 denote the Fourier conjugates of the two positions between which the correlation is taken, $\mathbf{K} \equiv \mathbf{k}_1 + \mathbf{k}_2$, and $\mathbf{k} \equiv (\mathbf{k}_1 - \mathbf{k}_2)/2$. Henceforth, we will refer to \mathbf{K} as the ‘large scale’, and \mathbf{k} as the ‘small scale.’ Discarding all the large-scale dependence and assuming isotropy, we can write (Moffatt 1978, eq. 7.56; Lesieur 2008, eq. 5.84)^{20,21}

$$V_{ij}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{K}, t) = P_{ij}(\mathbf{k})E(k, t) - \frac{i}{k^2} \epsilon_{ijc} k_c F(k, t) \quad (4.114)$$

where $4\pi k^2 E(k, \mathbf{R})$ and $8\pi k^2 F(k, \mathbf{R})$ are the kinetic energy and kinetic helicity spectra respectively.²² Note that we have defined the Fourier transform as

$$\tilde{f}(\mathbf{k}) = \int \frac{d^3x}{(2\pi)^3} e^{-i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}} f(\mathbf{x}) \quad (4.115)$$

We assume that in the inhomogeneous case, the only additional quantities affecting the turbulence are spatial derivatives of the energy and helicity densities. The assumption of ‘weak inhomogeneity’ means that we will neglect $\mathcal{O}(K^2)$ terms. ‘Local isotropy’ means that anisotropy can only enter through the large scale. Now,

²⁰Batchelor (1953, eq. 3.4.12) gives the expression with the additional assumption of mirror symmetry.

²¹The differences between our expressions and those in the cited works are due to differences in the Fourier transform convention and in the definitions of E and F .

²² $\frac{1}{2} \langle v^2 \rangle = \int 4\pi k^2 E(k) dk$ and $\langle \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla \times \mathbf{v} \rangle = \int 8\pi k^2 F(k) dk$

to incorporate the large-scale dependence, we add some undetermined $O(K)$ terms to the above and write

$$V_{ij}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{K}, t) = P_{ij}(\mathbf{k})E(k, \mathbf{K}, t) - \frac{i}{k^2}\epsilon_{ijc}k_c F(k, \mathbf{K}, t) + A_{ijk}(\mathbf{k})K_k E(k, \mathbf{K}, t) + B_{ijk}(\mathbf{k})K_k F(k, \mathbf{K}, t) \quad (4.116)$$

If the velocity fields are incompressible, we require

$$\left(\frac{1}{2}K_i + k_i\right)V_{ij} = \left(\frac{1}{2}K_j - k_j\right)V_{ij} = 0 \quad (4.117)$$

A_{ijk} and B_{ijk} in equation 4.116 have to be chosen such that the above constraint is satisfied. We write

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{1}{2}K_i + k_i\right)V_{ij} &= \frac{k_i}{2k^2}(K_j k_i - k_j K_i)E(k, \mathbf{K}, t) \\ &\quad - \frac{i}{2k^4}\epsilon_{kjc}k_i k_c K_k F(k, \mathbf{K}, t) + k_i A_{ijk}(\mathbf{k})K_k E(k, \mathbf{K}, t) \\ &\quad + k_i B_{ijk}(\mathbf{k})K_k F(k, \mathbf{K}, t) + \mathcal{O}(K^2) \end{aligned} \quad (4.118)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{1}{2}K_j - k_j\right)V_{ij} &= \frac{k_j}{2k^2}(K_i k_j - k_i K_j)E(k, \mathbf{K}, t) \\ &\quad - \frac{i}{2k^4}\epsilon_{ikc}k_j k_c K_k F(k, \mathbf{K}, t) - k_j A_{ijk}(\mathbf{k})K_k E(k, \mathbf{K}, t) \\ &\quad - k_j B_{ijk}(\mathbf{k})K_k F(k, \mathbf{K}, t) + \mathcal{O}(K^2) \end{aligned} \quad (4.119)$$

We note that in constructing appropriate A_{ijk} and B_{ijk} , we may only use \mathbf{k} along with isotropic tensors. From equations 4.118 and 4.119, we infer

$$A_{ijk}(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{1}{2k^2}(k_j \delta_{ik} - k_i \delta_{jk}) + C_1 P_{ij}(\mathbf{k})k_k + C_2 \epsilon_{ijc}k_c k_k \quad (4.120)$$

$$B_{ijk}(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{i}{2k^4}(\epsilon_{kjc}k_i - \epsilon_{ikc}k_j)k_c + C_3 P_{ij}(\mathbf{k})k_k + C_4 \epsilon_{ijc}k_c k_k \quad (4.121)$$

where C_1 , C_2 , C_3 , and C_4 may be functions of k ($= |\mathbf{k}|$).

From the definition of $V_{ij}(\mathbf{k})$, one can see that it has the following symmetry: $V_{ij}(-\mathbf{k}) = V_{ji}(\mathbf{k})$. Imposing this symmetry on the above expressions gives us $C_1 = C_2 = C_3 = C_4 = 0$.

We thus write

$$\begin{aligned} V_{ij}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{K}, t) &= P_{ij}(\mathbf{k})E(k, \mathbf{K}, t) - \frac{i}{k^2}\epsilon_{ijc}k_c F(k, \mathbf{K}, t) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2k^2}(k_j \delta_{ik} - k_i \delta_{jk})K_k E(k, \mathbf{K}, t) \\ &\quad + \frac{i}{2k^4}(k_i \epsilon_{jck} + k_j \epsilon_{ick})k_c K_k F(k, \mathbf{K}, t) + \mathcal{O}(K^2) \end{aligned} \quad (4.122)$$

Performing one Fourier transform $\mathbf{K} \rightarrow \mathbf{R}$, we obtain²³

$$\begin{aligned} V_{ij}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{R}, t) &= P_{ij}(\mathbf{k})E(k, \mathbf{R}, t) - \frac{i}{k^2}\epsilon_{ijc}k_c F(k, \mathbf{R}, t) \\ &+ \frac{i}{2k^2}(k_i\delta_{jk} - k_j\delta_{ik})\partial_k E(k, \mathbf{R}, t) \\ &+ \frac{1}{2k^4}(k_i\epsilon_{jck} + k_j\epsilon_{ick})k_c\partial_k F(k, \mathbf{R}, t) + \mathcal{O}(\partial^2) \end{aligned} \quad (4.123)$$

where $\partial_i \equiv \partial/\partial R_i$. This matches the expression given by Roberts and Soward (1975, eqs. 2.19 & 2.23). As discussed by Gopalakrishnan and Subramanian (2023, appendix A), the analogous expressions used by Rädler, Kleeorin, and Rogachevskii (2003, eq. 71) and Brandenburg and Subramanian (2005b, eq. 10.40) are wrong.

4.H.2 Equal-time single-point correlations in real space

4.H.2.1 An example

As an example, we demonstrate how one can use equation 4.122 to derive an expression for $\langle v_i v_j \rangle$ (an equal-time single-point correlation).

$$\langle v_i(\mathbf{x})v_j(\mathbf{x}) \rangle = \int d^3p d^3q e^{i(\mathbf{p}+\mathbf{q})\cdot\mathbf{x}} \langle \tilde{v}_i(\mathbf{q})\tilde{v}_j(\mathbf{p}) \rangle \quad (4.124)$$

Defining $\mathbf{K} \equiv \mathbf{p} + \mathbf{q}$ and $\mathbf{k} \equiv \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{q})$,

$$\langle v_i(\mathbf{x})v_j(\mathbf{x}) \rangle = \int d^3K d^3k e^{i\mathbf{K}\cdot\mathbf{x}} \langle \tilde{v}_i(\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{k})\tilde{v}_j(\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{K} + \mathbf{k}) \rangle \quad (4.125)$$

Using equation 4.122,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle v_i(\mathbf{x})v_j(\mathbf{x}) \rangle &= \int d^3K k^2 dk d\Omega_k e^{i\mathbf{K}\cdot\mathbf{x}} \left(P_{ji}(\mathbf{k})E(k, \mathbf{K}, t) - \frac{i}{k^2}\epsilon_{jic}k_c F(k, \mathbf{K}, t) \right. \\ &- \frac{1}{2k^2}k_j K_i E(k, \mathbf{K}, t) + \frac{1}{2k^2}k_i K_j E(k, \mathbf{K}, t) \\ &\left. + \frac{i}{2k^4}k_j\epsilon_{icd}k_c K_d F(k, \mathbf{K}, t) + \frac{i}{2k^4}k_i\epsilon_{jcd}k_c K_d F(k, \mathbf{K}, t) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (4.126)$$

Performing the angular integral over \mathbf{k} , we obtain

$$\langle v_i(\mathbf{x})v_j(\mathbf{x}) \rangle = \frac{1}{3}\delta_{ji} \langle v^2(\mathbf{x}, t) \rangle \quad (4.127)$$

The steps to derive the other expressions that follow are similar to those above, so we shall omit the intermediate steps and just state the results.

²³Recall that the Fourier transform we use is defined in equation 4.115.

4.H.2.2 Results

$$\langle v_i v_j \rangle = \frac{1}{3} \delta_{ji} \langle v^2 \rangle + \mathcal{O}(\partial^2) \quad (4.128)$$

$$\left\langle v_i \frac{\partial v_j}{\partial x_k} \right\rangle = \left[\frac{1}{6} \delta_{ij} \partial_k + \frac{1}{12} (\delta_{ik} \partial_j - \delta_{jk} \partial_i) \right] \langle v^2 \rangle - \frac{1}{6} \epsilon_{ijk} h + \mathcal{O}(\partial^2) \quad (4.129)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle v_i \partial_a \partial_b v_j \rangle &= \frac{1}{12} \epsilon_{jia} \partial_b h + \frac{1}{12} \epsilon_{jib} \partial_a h + \left(\frac{1}{30} [\delta_{ai} \delta_{bj} + \delta_{aj} \delta_{bi}] - \frac{2}{15} \delta_{ab} \delta_{ij} \right) \langle \omega^2 \rangle \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{60} (2\delta_{ab} \epsilon_{ijk} + \delta_{jb} \epsilon_{iak} + \delta_{aj} \epsilon_{ibk} + \delta_{ib} \epsilon_{jak} + \delta_{ai} \epsilon_{jbk}) \partial_k h + \mathcal{O}(\partial^2) \end{aligned} \quad (4.130)$$

$$\langle v_i \partial_a \nabla^2 v_j \rangle = \left(-\frac{1}{20} \delta_{ai} \partial_j + \frac{7}{60} \delta_{aj} \partial_i - \frac{3}{10} \delta_{ij} \partial_a \right) \langle \omega^2 \rangle - \frac{1}{6} \epsilon_{jia} \mathcal{L} + \mathcal{O}(\partial^2) \quad (4.131)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\omega} \equiv \nabla \times \mathbf{v}$; $h \equiv \langle \mathbf{v} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega} \rangle$; and $\mathcal{L} \equiv \langle \boldsymbol{\omega} \cdot (\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\omega}) \rangle$. We have also used the relations $\langle \omega^2 \rangle(\mathbf{R}, t) = \int 8\pi k^4 E(k, \mathbf{R}, t) dk$ (Moffatt 1978, eq. 7.51); and $\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{R}, t) = \int dk 8\pi k^4 F(k, \mathbf{R}, t)$. Aside, we note that the expression given by Gopalakrishnan and Subramanian (2023, eq. A16) for $\langle v_i \partial_a \nabla^2 v_j \rangle$ is wrong.²⁴

4.H.3 Generalization to unequal-time correlations

Assuming the velocity correlations are separable (equation 4.32), the results in appendix 4.H.2 can be easily generalized as

$$C_{ij} = \frac{2}{3} \delta_{ij} E \quad (4.132)$$

$$C_{ijk} = \frac{1}{6} \epsilon_{ikj} H + \left[\frac{1}{3} \delta_{ij} \partial_k + \frac{1}{6} (\delta_{ik} \partial_j - \delta_{jk} \partial_i) \right] E \quad (4.133)$$

$$C_{ijkk} = -\frac{1}{3} \delta_{ij} N - \frac{1}{6} \epsilon_{ija} \partial_a H \quad (4.134)$$

$$\begin{aligned} C_{ijab} &= \left(\frac{1}{30} [\delta_{ai} \delta_{bj} + \delta_{aj} \delta_{bi}] - \frac{2}{15} \delta_{ab} \delta_{ij} \right) N + \frac{1}{12} \epsilon_{jia} \partial_b H + \frac{1}{12} \epsilon_{jib} \partial_a H \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{60} (2\delta_{ab} \epsilon_{ijk} + \delta_{jb} \epsilon_{iak} + \delta_{aj} \epsilon_{ibk} + \delta_{ib} \epsilon_{jak} + \delta_{ai} \epsilon_{jbk}) \partial_k H \end{aligned} \quad (4.135)$$

$$C_{ijabb} = -\frac{1}{6} \epsilon_{jia} L + \left(-\frac{1}{20} \delta_{ai} \partial_j + \frac{7}{60} \delta_{aj} \partial_i - \frac{3}{10} \delta_{ij} \partial_a \right) N \quad (4.136)$$

where

$$E(\mathbf{x}, t) \equiv \int_0^\infty \langle v_i(\mathbf{x}, t + \tau) v_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \rangle d\tau \quad (4.137a)$$

²⁴This can be checked by setting $i = a$ in equation 4.131 and comparing it with $\partial_i \langle v_i \nabla^2 v_j \rangle$ calculated using equation 4.130 (which is the same as eq. A13 of Gopalakrishnan and Subramanian 2023).

$$H(\mathbf{x}, t) \equiv 2 \int_0^\infty \langle v_i(\mathbf{x}, t + \tau) \omega_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \rangle d\tau \quad (4.137b)$$

$$N(\mathbf{x}, t) \equiv 2 \int_0^\infty \langle \omega_i(\mathbf{x}, t + \tau) \omega_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \rangle d\tau \quad (4.137c)$$

$$L(\mathbf{x}, t) \equiv 2 \int_0^\infty \langle \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{x}, t + \tau) \cdot [\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{x}, t)] \rangle d\tau \quad (4.137d)$$

4.I n -th functional derivative of B wrt. u

Following a similar procedure to that used in appendix 4.C, we wish to derive an expression for the n -th functional derivative of B with respect to \mathbf{u} . Denoting $\tilde{B}_i \equiv B_i[u_m + \epsilon \chi_m]$ (where χ_m is some test function), we may use equation 4.43 to write

$$\tilde{B}_i(\mathbf{x}, t) = \int d\tau d\mathbf{q} G^c(\mathbf{x}, t|\mathbf{q}, \tau) \epsilon_{ijk} \epsilon_{klm} \frac{\partial}{\partial q_j} \left[(u_l(\mathbf{q}, \tau) + \epsilon \chi_l(\mathbf{q}, \tau)) \tilde{B}_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \right] \quad (4.138)$$

which gives

$$\frac{d^n \tilde{B}_i(\mathbf{x}, t)}{d\epsilon^n} = \int d\tau d\mathbf{q} G^c(\mathbf{x}, t|\mathbf{q}, \tau) \epsilon_{ijk} \epsilon_{klm} \frac{\partial}{\partial q_j} \frac{d^n}{d\epsilon^n} \left[(u_l(\mathbf{q}, \tau) + \epsilon \chi_l(\mathbf{q}, \tau)) \tilde{B}_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \right] \quad (4.139)$$

$$= \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} \int d\tau d\mathbf{q} \left(G^c(\mathbf{x}, t|\mathbf{q}, \tau) \epsilon_{ijk} \epsilon_{klm} \right. \\ \left. \times \frac{\partial}{\partial q_j} \left[\frac{d^r}{d\epsilon^r} (u_l(\mathbf{q}, \tau) + \epsilon \chi_l(\mathbf{q}, \tau)) \frac{d^{n-r} \tilde{B}_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{d\epsilon^{n-r}} \right] \right) \quad (4.140)$$

$$= \int d\tau d\mathbf{q} G^c(\mathbf{x}, t|\mathbf{q}, \tau) \epsilon_{ijk} \epsilon_{klm} \frac{\partial}{\partial q_j} \left[(u_l(\mathbf{q}, \tau) + \epsilon \chi_l(\mathbf{q}, \tau)) \frac{d^n \tilde{B}_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{d\epsilon^n} \right] \\ + n \int d\tau d\mathbf{q} G^c(\mathbf{x}, t|\mathbf{q}, \tau) \epsilon_{ijk} \epsilon_{klm} \frac{\partial}{\partial q_j} \left[\chi_l(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \frac{d^{n-1} \tilde{B}_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{d\epsilon^{n-1}} \right] \quad (4.141)$$

$$= - \int d\tau d\mathbf{q} \epsilon_{ijk} \epsilon_{klm} \frac{\partial G^c(\mathbf{x}, t|\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{\partial q_j} [u_l(\mathbf{q}, \tau) + \epsilon \chi_l(\mathbf{q}, \tau)] \frac{d^n \tilde{B}_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{d\epsilon^n} \\ - n \int d\tau d\mathbf{q} \epsilon_{ijk} \epsilon_{klm} \frac{\partial G^c(\mathbf{x}, t|\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{\partial q_j} \chi_l(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \frac{d^{n-1} \tilde{B}_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{d\epsilon^{n-1}} \quad (4.142)$$

The functional derivatives of B_i are then related by (where we use the notation $u_{j_i} \equiv u_{j_i}(\mathbf{x}^{(i)}, t^{(i)})$)

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\delta^n B_i(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\delta u_{i_1} \dots \delta u_{i_n}} &= - \int d\tau d\mathbf{q} \epsilon_{ijk} \epsilon_{klm} \frac{\partial G^c(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{q}, \tau)}{\partial q_j} u_l(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \frac{\delta^n B_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{\delta u_{i_1} \dots \delta u_{i_n}} \\ &\quad - \sum_{\alpha=1}^n \epsilon_{ijk} \epsilon_{ki_\alpha m} \frac{\partial G^c(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{x}^{(\alpha)}, t^{(\alpha)})}{\partial x_j^{(\alpha)}} \frac{\delta^{n-1} B_m(\mathbf{x}^{(\alpha)}, t^{(\alpha)})}{\delta u_{i_1} \dots \delta u_{i_{\alpha-1}} \delta u_{i_{\alpha+1}} \dots \delta u_{i_n}} \end{aligned} \quad (4.143)$$

Now, we average both sides of the above and apply the Furutsu-Novikov theorem (appendix 4.B) to the first term of the RHS to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle \frac{\delta^n B_i(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\delta u_{i_1} \dots \delta u_{i_n}} \right\rangle &= - \int d\tau d\mathbf{q} \epsilon_{ijk} \epsilon_{klm} \frac{\partial G^c(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{q}, \tau)}{\partial q_j} \langle u_l(\mathbf{q}, \tau) \rangle \left\langle \frac{\delta^n B_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{\delta u_{i_1} \dots \delta u_{i_n}} \right\rangle \\ &\quad - \int d\tau d\mathbf{q} d\mathbf{x}^{(n+1)} dt^{(n+1)} \left[\epsilon_{ijk} \epsilon_{klm} \frac{\partial G^c(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{q}, \tau)}{\partial q_j} \right. \\ &\quad \quad \left. \times \langle u'_l(\mathbf{q}, \tau) u'_{i_{n+1}}(\mathbf{x}^{(n+1)}, t^{(n+1)}) \rangle \left\langle \frac{\delta^{n+1} B_m(\mathbf{q}, \tau)}{\delta u_{i_1} \dots \delta u_{i_n} \delta u_{i_{n+1}}} \right\rangle \right] \\ &\quad - \sum_{\alpha=1}^n \epsilon_{ijk} \epsilon_{ki_\alpha m} \frac{\partial G^c(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{x}^{(\alpha)}, t^{(\alpha)})}{\partial x_j^{(\alpha)}} \left\langle \frac{\delta^{n-1} B_m(\mathbf{x}^{(\alpha)}, t^{(\alpha)})}{\delta u_{i_1} \dots \delta u_{i_{\alpha-1}} \delta u_{i_{\alpha+1}} \dots \delta u_{i_n}} \right\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (4.144)$$

where $\mathbf{u}' \equiv \mathbf{u} - \langle \mathbf{u} \rangle$.

4.J Simplification of the EMF retaining $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ terms

For simplicity, we assume $\eta = 0$, in which case the diffusion Green function becomes a positional Dirac delta. As explained in appendix 4.G, one has to be a bit careful while evaluating derivatives of a Dirac delta.

4.J.1 Quasilinear term

We write (neglecting $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c^2)$ terms)²⁵

$$\begin{aligned} \boxed{\mathbf{x}_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_{i_2} (\mathbf{x} | 1) \bar{B}_{i_3} \textcircled{1} &= \boxed{\mathbf{x}_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_{i_2} (\mathbf{x} | 1) \bar{B}_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}^{(1)}, t) \\ &\quad + \boxed{\mathbf{x}_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_{i_2} (\mathbf{x} | 1) (t^{(1)} - t) \frac{\partial \bar{B}_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}^{(1)}, t)}{\partial t} \end{aligned} \quad (4.145)$$

We recall that neglecting $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ terms and setting $\eta = 0$, one can write (equations 4.55 and 4.41)

$$\frac{\partial B_a}{\partial t} = \epsilon_{abc} \left(-\frac{H}{6} \partial_b \bar{B}_c - \frac{E}{3} \epsilon_{cde} \partial_b \partial_d \bar{B}_e \right) \quad (4.146)$$

²⁵We are not Taylor-expanding the Green function since we plan to set $\eta = 0$, where we have $G(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{q}, \tau) = \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{q}) \Theta(t - \tau)$.

Using this and dropping terms with more than one spatial derivative of \bar{B} , we write

$$\begin{aligned} & \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_{i_2} (\boxtimes | 1) \bar{B}_{i_3} \textcircled{1} \\ &= \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_{i_2} (\boxtimes | 1) \bar{B}_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}^{(1)}, t) \\ & \quad - \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_{i_2} (\boxtimes | 1) (t^{(1)} - t) \epsilon_{i_3bc} \frac{H}{6} \frac{\partial \bar{B}_c(\mathbf{x}^{(1)}, t)}{\partial x_b^{(1)}} \end{aligned} \quad (4.147)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= - \int_{t^{(1)}} \left\langle v_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \frac{\partial v_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, t^{(1)})}{\partial x_{i_2}} \right\rangle \Theta(t - t^{(1)}) \bar{B}_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, t) \\ & \quad - \int_{t^{(1)}} \langle v_i(\mathbf{x}, t) v_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, t^{(1)}) \rangle \Theta(t - t^{(1)}) \frac{\partial \bar{B}_{i_3}(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial x_{i_2}} \\ & \quad - \frac{H}{6} \epsilon_{i_3bc} \int_{t^{(1)}} \left\langle v_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \frac{\partial v_{i_1}(\mathbf{x}, t^{(1)})}{\partial x_{i_2}} \right\rangle \Theta(t - t^{(1)}) (t^{(1)} - t) \frac{\partial \bar{B}_c(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial x_b} \end{aligned} \quad (4.148)$$

Assuming the velocity correlation is separable (equation 4.32), we write

$$\boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_{i_2} (\boxtimes | 1) \bar{B}_{i_3} \textcircled{1} = -\frac{1}{2} C_{ii_1 i_2} \bar{B}_{i_3} - \frac{1}{2} C_{ii_1} \frac{\partial \bar{B}_{i_3}}{\partial x_{i_2}} + \frac{\tau_c H}{12} \epsilon_{i_3bc} C_{ii_1 i_2} \frac{\partial \bar{B}_c}{\partial x_b} \quad (4.149)$$

Using the results of appendix 4.H.3, we then write the contribution to the EMF ($\mathcal{E}_k = \epsilon_{kij} \langle V_i B_j \rangle$) as

$$-\epsilon_{kij} \Upsilon_{ji_2 i_1 i_3} \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_{i_2} (\boxtimes | 1) \bar{B}_{i_3} \textcircled{1} = -\frac{H}{6} B_k + \left(\frac{E}{3} - \frac{H^2 \tau_c}{36} \right) \epsilon_{kr_0 r_1} B_{r_0, r_1} \quad (4.150)$$

where we have used a comma to denote differentiation.

4.J.2 First higher-order term

Denoting $\oint \dots \equiv \int d\tau_1 d\tau_2 d\tau_3 \Theta(t - \tau_2) \Theta(\tau_2 - \tau_3) \Theta(\tau_3 - \tau_1)$; dropping terms involving more than one spatial derivative of \bar{B} ,²⁶ and assuming we are only interested in

²⁶The term that appears in the induction equation is $\nabla \times \mathcal{E}$.

homogeneous turbulence, we write

$$\begin{aligned}
& \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_{j_3} (\boxtimes | 2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_4} (2|3) \partial_{i_6} (3|1) \bar{B}_{i_7} \textcircled{1} \\
&= - \oint v_i^{(1)}(t) v_{i_2}^{(2)}(\tau_2) \frac{\partial v_{i_3}^{(2)}(\tau_3)}{\partial x_{i_4}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_{j_3}} \left[\frac{\partial v_{i_1}^{(1)}(\tau_1)}{\partial x_{i_6}} \bar{B}_{i_7}(\tau_1) \right] \\
&\quad - \oint v_i^{(1)}(t) v_{i_2}^{(2)}(\tau_2) v_{i_3}^{(2)}(\tau_3) \frac{\partial}{\partial x_{j_3}} \left[\frac{\partial^2 v_{i_1}^{(1)}(\tau_1)}{\partial x_{i_6} \partial x_{i_4}} \bar{B}_{i_7}(\tau_1) \right] \\
&\quad - \oint v_i^{(1)}(t) v_{i_2}^{(2)}(\tau_2) v_{i_3}^{(2)}(\tau_3) \frac{\partial^2 v_{i_1}^{(1)}(\tau_1)}{\partial x_{i_6} \partial x_{j_3}} \frac{\partial \bar{B}_{i_7}(\tau_1)}{\partial x_{i_4}} \\
&\quad - \oint v_i^{(1)}(t) v_{i_2}^{(2)}(\tau_2) \frac{\partial v_{i_3}^{(2)}(\tau_3)}{\partial x_{i_4}} \frac{\partial v_{i_1}^{(1)}(\tau_1)}{\partial x_{j_3}} \frac{\partial \bar{B}_{i_7}(\tau_1)}{\partial x_{i_6}} \\
&\quad - \oint v_i^{(1)}(t) v_{i_2}^{(2)}(\tau_2) v_{i_3}^{(2)}(\tau_3) \frac{\partial^2 v_{i_1}^{(1)}(\tau_1)}{\partial x_{i_4} \partial x_{j_3}} \frac{\partial \bar{B}_{i_7}(\tau_1)}{\partial x_{i_6}}
\end{aligned} \tag{4.151}$$

where, since the position argument in all the terms of the final expression is \mathbf{x} , we have not indicated it explicitly. Above, as long as one is willing to ignore $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c^2)$ terms, one can replace the time arguments of all occurrences of \bar{B} by t . Assuming the correlation of the velocity field is separable (equation 4.32), we can write

$$\begin{aligned}
& \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_{j_3} (\boxtimes | 2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_4} (2|3) \partial_{i_6} (3|1) \bar{B}_{i_7} \textcircled{1} \\
&= - \tau_c g_2 C_{ii_1 j_3 i_6} C_{i_2 i_3 i_4} \bar{B}_{i_7} - \tau_c g_2 C_{ii_1 i_6} C_{i_2 i_3 i_4} \frac{\partial \bar{B}_{i_7}}{\partial x_{j_3}} \\
&\quad - \tau_c g_2 C_{ii_1 j_3 i_6 i_4} C_{i_2 i_3} \bar{B}_{i_7} - \tau_c g_2 C_{ii_1 i_6 i_4} C_{i_2 i_3} \frac{\partial \bar{B}_{i_7}}{\partial x_{j_3}} \\
&\quad - \tau_c g_2 C_{ii_1 i_6 j_3} C_{i_2 i_3} \frac{\partial \bar{B}_{i_7}}{\partial x_{i_4}} - \tau_c g_2 C_{ii_1 j_3} C_{i_2 i_3 i_4} \frac{\partial \bar{B}_{i_7}}{\partial x_{i_6}} \\
&\quad - \tau_c g_2 C_{ii_1 i_4 j_3} C_{i_2 i_3} \frac{\partial \bar{B}_{i_7}}{\partial x_{i_6}}
\end{aligned} \tag{4.152}$$

where g_2 is defined in equation 4.92. Using expressions for the tensors $C_{ij\dots}$ from appendix 4.H.3, we write the contribution to the EMF ($\mathcal{E}_k = \epsilon_{kij} \langle V_i B_j \rangle$) as

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \epsilon_{kij} \Upsilon_{i_5 i_6 i_1 i_7} \Upsilon_{j j_3 i_2 j_2} \Upsilon_{j_2 i_4 i_3 i_5} \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_{j_3} (\boxtimes | 2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_4} (2|3) \partial_{i_6} (3|1) \bar{B}_{i_7} \textcircled{1} \\
&= - \left(\frac{2\tau_c E N g_2}{9} + \frac{\tau_c H^2 g_2}{9} \right) \epsilon_{kr_0 r_1} B_{r_0, r_1} + \left(\frac{2\tau_c E L g_2}{9} + \frac{\tau_c H N g_2}{9} \right) B_k
\end{aligned} \tag{4.153}$$

4.J.3 Second higher-order term

Denoting $\oint \dots \equiv \int d\tau_1 d\tau_2 d\tau_3 \Theta(t - \tau_2) \Theta(\tau_2 - \tau_1) \Theta(\tau_1 - \tau_3) \dots$; dropping terms with more than one spatial derivative of \bar{B} ; and assuming we are interested in

homogeneous turbulence, we write

$$\begin{aligned}
& \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_{j_3} (\boxtimes | 2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_4} (2|1) \partial_{i_6} (1|3) \overline{B}_{i_7} \textcircled{3} \\
&= - \oint v_{i_2}^{(2)}(\tau_2) \frac{\partial v_{i_3}^{(2)}(\tau_3)}{\partial x_{i_6}} v_i^{(1)}(t) \frac{\partial}{\partial x_{j_3}} \left[\frac{\partial v_{i_1}^{(1)}(\tau_1)}{\partial x_{i_4}} \overline{B}_{i_7}(\tau_3) \right] \\
&\quad - \oint v_{i_2}^{(2)}(\tau_2) \frac{\partial^2 v_{i_3}^{(2)}(\tau_3)}{\partial x_{i_6} \partial x_{i_4}} v_i^{(1)}(t) \frac{\partial}{\partial x_{j_3}} \left[v_{i_1}^{(1)}(\tau_1) \overline{B}_{i_7}(\tau_3) \right] \\
&\quad - \oint v_{i_2}^{(2)}(\tau_2) \frac{\partial v_{i_3}^{(2)}(\tau_3)}{\partial x_{i_6}} v_i^{(1)}(t) \frac{\partial v_{i_1}^{(1)}(\tau_1)}{\partial x_{j_3}} \frac{\partial \overline{B}_{i_7}(\tau_3)}{\partial x_{i_4}} \\
&\quad - \oint v_i^{(1)}(t) v_{i_2}^{(2)}(\tau_2) v_{i_3}^{(2)}(\tau_3) \frac{\partial^2 v_{i_1}^{(1)}(\tau_1)}{\partial x_{i_4} \partial x_{j_3}} \frac{\partial \overline{B}_{i_7}(\tau_3)}{\partial x_{i_6}} \\
&\quad - \oint v_{i_2}^{(2)}(\tau_2) \frac{\partial v_{i_3}^{(2)}(\tau_3)}{\partial x_{i_4}} v_i^{(1)}(t) \frac{\partial v_{i_1}^{(1)}(\tau_1)}{\partial x_{j_3}} \frac{\partial \overline{B}_{i_7}(\tau_3)}{\partial x_{i_6}}
\end{aligned} \tag{4.154}$$

Above, as long as one is willing to ignore $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c^2)$ terms, one can replace the time arguments of all occurrences of \overline{B} by t . Assuming the correlation of the velocity field is separable (equation 4.32), we can write

$$\begin{aligned}
& \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_{j_3} (\boxtimes | 2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_4} (2|1) \partial_{i_6} (1|3) \overline{B}_{i_7} \textcircled{3} \\
&= - \tau_c g_1 C_{i_2 i_3 i_6} C_{i i_1 i_4 j_3} \overline{B}_{i_7} - \tau_c g_1 C_{i_2 i_3 i_6} C_{i i_1 i_4} \frac{\partial \overline{B}_{i_7}}{\partial x_{j_3}} \\
&\quad - \tau_c g_1 C_{i_2 i_3 i_6 i_4} C_{i i_1 j_3} \overline{B}_{i_7} - \tau_c g_1 C_{i_2 i_3 i_6 i_4} C_{i i_1} \frac{\partial \overline{B}_{i_7}}{\partial x_{j_3}} - \tau_c g_1 C_{i_2 i_3 i_6} C_{i i_1 j_3} \frac{\partial \overline{B}_{i_7}}{\partial x_{i_4}} \\
&\quad - \tau_c g_1 C_{i i_1 i_4 j_3} C_{i_2 i_3} \frac{\partial \overline{B}_{i_7}}{\partial x_{i_6}} - \tau_c g_1 C_{i_2 i_3 i_4} C_{i i_1 j_3} \frac{\partial \overline{B}_{i_7}}{\partial x_{i_6}}
\end{aligned} \tag{4.155}$$

where g_1 is defined in equation 4.92. Using expressions for the tensors $C_{ij\dots}$ from appendix 4.H.3, we write the contribution to the EMF ($\mathcal{E}_k = \epsilon_{kij} \langle V_i B_j \rangle$) as

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \epsilon_{kij} \Upsilon_{i_5 i_6 i_3 i_7} \Upsilon_{j j_3 i_2 j_2} \Upsilon_{j_2 i_4 i_1 i_5} \boxed{\boxtimes_i 1_{i_1}} \partial_{j_3} (\boxtimes | 2) \boxed{2_{i_2} 3_{i_3}} \partial_{i_4} (2|1) \partial_{i_6} (1|3) \overline{B}_{i_7} \textcircled{3} \\
&= - \left(\frac{\tau_c H^2 g_1}{18} \right) \epsilon_{kr_0 r_1} B_{r_0, r_1}
\end{aligned} \tag{4.156}$$

Chapter 5

Small-scale dynamo with nonzero correlation time

5.1 Introduction

Many astrophysical systems have values of Rm much larger than the threshold for excitation of the small-scale dynamo (SSD). The standard treatment of the SSD (Kazantsev 1968; Vainshtein and Kichatinov 1986; Schekochihin, Boldyrev, and Kulsrud 2002) is to model the velocity field as a Gaussian random field, such that all its higher moments can be expressed in terms of the first two moments.^{1,2} The resulting equations are still quite complicated, and so most analytical work (e.g. Kazantsev 1968; Schekochihin, Boldyrev, and Kulsrud 2002) has additionally assumed that the correlation time of the velocity field is zero (i.e. that it is white noise).³

Since, as discussed earlier, the Strouhal number is not expected to be small in real systems, it is natural to ask if one can relax the standard assumption of zero correlation time. Having dealt with the evolution of the mean magnetic field in chapter 4, we now turn to the SSD. The intermittency of the SSD manifests as the second moment, $\langle B^2 \rangle$, growing faster than $\langle B \rangle^2$. One thus needs to consider the evolution equation for the second moment of the magnetic field.

Bhat and Subramanian (2014)⁴ and Carteret, Schleicher, and Schober (2023)

¹Subramanian (1997), in a nonlinear treatment of the SSD, assumes the magnetic field is also a Gaussian random field, but this is not necessary for a kinematic treatment.

²Kopyev et al. (2022a,b) have studied the effect of a velocity field whose third cumulant is nonzero.

³Vainshtein and Kichatinov (1986) show that if the 4-particle distribution function follows a Fokker-Planck-like equation with diffusion tensor T_{ij} , the evolution equation for the longitudinal correlation function of the magnetic field takes a form similar to that in the case of zero correlation time, with the spatial correlation tensor of the velocity field replaced by T_{ij} . However, since they do not give an expression for T_{ij} when the correlation time is nonzero, the effects of a nonzero correlation time are still unclear. We simply note that such a Fokker-Planck equation can be derived using the methods outlined by Fox (1986).

⁴Bhat and Subramanian (2015) describe the same calculation in a more detailed manner.

have modelled a velocity field with a nonzero correlation time as a static, smooth flow which is randomly redrawn from an ensemble at fixed intervals of time, say τ (the ‘renovating flow’ model, first introduced by Zel’dovich et al. (1987)). They have analytically found that the growth rate is reduced, but the slope of the magnetic energy spectrum in the Kazantsev range (i.e. the range of wavenumbers much larger than the scale of the velocity field, but much smaller than the resistive scale) remains unchanged. The reduction of the growth rate is in qualitative agreement with simulations that use artificial velocity fields (Chandran 1997; Mason et al. 2011). On the other hand, Kleorin, Rogachevskii, and Sokoloff (2002), who also use a renovating flow but do not seem to have performed operator splitting, report that the growth rate is *increased* due to a nonzero correlation time.

While the approach used by Bhat and Subramanian (2014) and Carteret, Schleicher, and Schober (2023) leads to significant computational simplifications, it has a number of shortcomings which limit its generality. First, a smooth model for the velocity field is applicable only when $\text{Pr}_m \gg 1$ (Pr_m , the magnetic Prandtl number, is the ratio of the kinematic viscosity to the magnetic diffusivity). This is true in some astrophysical contexts (e.g., the interstellar medium), but not in others (e.g., stellar convection zones). Second, their use of operator splitting is at best justified only when Rm is large enough that one may neglect $\mathcal{O}(\eta\tau)$ terms in the evolution equation for the magnetic correlation function.⁵ This means that, e.g., their approach cannot be used to understand how the correlation time of the velocity field affects the threshold for onset of the SSD.

Assuming the velocity is a Gaussian random field as in chapter 4, one can use the Furutsu-Novikov theorem (appendix 4.B) to obtain the evolution equation for the two-point correlation function of the magnetic field as a series in the correlation time (say τ_c) of the velocity field. Schekochihin and Kulsrud (2001) have used the Furutsu-Novikov theorem to calculate the $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ corrections to the growth rates of the single-point moments of the magnetic field. However, they set the magnetic diffusivity (η) to zero, rather than taking the $\eta \rightarrow 0$ limit; this is known to drastically affect the growth rate of the magnetic field even when $\tau_c = 0$ (Kulsrud and Anderson 1992, eqs. 1.9, 1.16). The same problem arises in the work of Chandran (1997), who used a cumulant expansion to calculate the growth rate of the second moment. Using the Furutsu-Novikov theorem without setting $\eta = 0$, we find the $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ contributions to the evolution of the two-point correlation function of the magnetic field in Fourier space, under the additional assumption that the velocity field is incompressible.

Section 5.2 shows how the Furutsu-Novikov theorem can be used to derive the evolution equation for the Fourier-space two-point correlation of the magnetic field. Section 5.3 analyses the aforementioned evolution equation in the limit where the correlation time of the velocity field is zero, and verifies that we recover the Kazantsev equation in the limit of high Pr_m . In section 5.4, we derive evolution

⁵Bhat and Subramanian (2015) claim to show this in their appendix A (note that this appendix is present only in the version of record, not in the preprint).

equations, valid for arbitrary Pr_m , that describe the lowest-order corrections due to the correlation time of the velocity field being nonzero. Section 5.4.1 describes the evolution equation for the Fourier-space two-point correlation function of the magnetic field in a homogeneous and separable velocity field. Section 5.4.2 mentions how inverse Fourier transforms can be performed to obtain evolution equations in configuration space. In section 5.4.3, we describe the evolution equation for the longitudinal correlation function of the magnetic field in a homogeneous, isotropic, incompressible, and nonhelical velocity field. In section 5.4.4, we present the evolution equations for the longitudinal and modified-cross correlation functions of the magnetic field when the velocity field is helical. In section 5.5, we assume a particular form for the longitudinal correlation function of the velocity field (which corresponds to the limit $\text{Pr}_m \gg 1$), in order to simplify the evolution equation derived in section 5.4.3. Solving this equation using the WKBJ approximation tells us about the growth rate and the spectral slope of the magnetic field. We discuss how our results are related to those derived by other authors, and point out some mistakes in previous studies. Finally, in section 5.6, we summarize our findings and point out future directions of research.

The calculations in sections 5.4.3, 5.4.4, and 5.5 were performed using SymPy (Meurer et al. 2017). Some enhancements were required; we are currently in the process of getting these merged into the upstream repository.

5.2 Application of the Furutsu-Novikov theorem

5.2.1 Induction equation in sheared coordinates

The induction equation can be written as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{H}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times (\mathbf{V} \times \mathbf{H}) + \eta \nabla^2 \mathbf{H} \quad (5.1)$$

$$= (\mathbf{H} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{V} - (\mathbf{V} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{H} + \eta \nabla^2 \mathbf{H} \quad (5.2)$$

where \mathbf{H} is the magnetic field (conventionally denoted by \mathbf{B}), and we have assumed \mathbf{V} is incompressible. We split \mathbf{V} into mean and fluctuations as

$$\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{U} + \mathbf{u} \quad (5.3)$$

Let us consider a linear shear flow:

$$U_i(\mathbf{X}) = S_l \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{X} \quad (5.4)$$

where \mathbf{a} is a unit vector that determines the direction in which the shear flow varies, while \mathbf{S} determines the direction in which the velocity field points; we assume $\mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{a} = 0$. For future convenience, we define $S_{ij} \equiv S_i a_j$ and $S \equiv |\mathbf{S}|$. Using equation 5.4, equation 5.2 can be written as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{H}}{\partial t} = (\mathbf{H} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{U} + (\mathbf{H} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} - (\mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{H} - (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{H} + \eta \nabla^2 \mathbf{H} \quad (5.5)$$

$$= (\mathbf{H} \cdot \mathbf{a}) \mathbf{S} - (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{X}) (\mathbf{S} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{H} + (\mathbf{H} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} - (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{H} + \eta \nabla^2 \mathbf{H} \quad (5.6)$$

In this section, we define the Fourier transform such that

$$\tilde{f}(\mathbf{k}, t) \equiv \int \frac{d\mathbf{x}}{(2\pi)^3} e^{i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}} f(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (5.7)$$

with the convolution theorem taking the form

$$\int \frac{d\mathbf{x}}{(2\pi)^3} e^{i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}} f_1(\mathbf{x}) \dots f_{n+1}(\mathbf{x}) = \int d\mathbf{p}_1 \dots d\mathbf{p}_n \tilde{f}_1(\mathbf{p}) \dots \tilde{f}_n(\mathbf{p}_n) \tilde{f}_{n+1}(\mathbf{k} - \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{p}_i) \quad (5.8)$$

Shifting to Fourier space, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{H}}(\mathbf{K}, t)}{\partial t} &= \left(\tilde{\mathbf{H}}(\mathbf{K}, t) \cdot \mathbf{a} \right) \mathbf{S} + (\mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{K}) (\mathbf{a} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{K}}) \tilde{\mathbf{H}}(\mathbf{K}, t) \\ &\quad - i \int_{\mathbf{P}} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{H}}(\mathbf{K}-\mathbf{P}, t) \cdot \mathbf{P} \right) \tilde{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{P}, t) + i \int_{\mathbf{P}} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{K}-\mathbf{P}, t) \cdot \mathbf{P} \right) \tilde{\mathbf{H}}(\mathbf{P}, t) \\ &\quad - \eta K^2 \tilde{\mathbf{H}}(\mathbf{K}, t) \end{aligned} \quad (5.9)$$

Our goal is to derive an evolution equation for the two-point correlation of the magnetic field in terms of the statistical properties of the velocity field. The two-point correlation of the velocity field is a rank-two tensor: in three spatial dimensions, it has nine components. Imposing constraints like incompressibility, homogeneity, or isotropy allows us to reduce the number of independent functions that determine the two-point correlation tensor of the velocity field (e.g. appendix 4.H.1). While a shear profile such as that in equation 5.4 breaks homogeneity, it is possible to transform to ‘sheared coordinates’ (Pumir 1996, eq. 7; Sridhar and Subramanian 2009, p. 9; Singh 2012, sec. 3.2.1) where the velocity correlations become homogeneous again.⁶ We thus define sheared Fourier variables (appendix 5.A summarizes some properties of this transformation)

$$\mathbf{k} \equiv \mathbf{K} + t\mathbf{a} (\mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{K}) = e^{t\mathbf{a} \otimes \mathbf{S}} \cdot \mathbf{K}, \quad t' \equiv t \quad (5.10)$$

(recall that we assume $\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{S} = 0$) along with the new fields

$$\tilde{\mathbf{h}}(\mathbf{k}, t') \equiv \tilde{\mathbf{H}}(\mathbf{K}, t) \cdot e^{-t\mathbf{a} \otimes \mathbf{S}} \quad (5.11)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{w}}(\mathbf{k}, t') \equiv \tilde{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{K}, t) \cdot e^{-t\mathbf{a} \otimes \mathbf{S}} \quad (5.12)$$

Note that

- (i) the Jacobian of the transformation given in equation 5.10 is one;
- (ii) the inverse transformation is $\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{k} - t'\mathbf{a} (\mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{k})$;

⁶Singh (2012, eq. B.7) presents a proof.

(iii) the new fields are orthogonal to the transformed wavevectors; and

(iv) $\langle \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \rangle = \mathbf{0} \implies \langle \tilde{\mathbf{w}} \rangle = \mathbf{0}$.

We then write equation 5.9 as (adopting the convention that uppercase wavevectors are in the lab frame, while lowercase wavevectors are in the sheared coordinates; dropping the prime on the time variable; and denoting $\int_{\mathbf{p}} \equiv \int d\mathbf{p}$)

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{h}}^{(\mathbf{k},t)}}{\partial t} = -i \int_{\mathbf{p}} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p},t)} \cdot \mathbf{p} \right) \tilde{\mathbf{w}}^{(\mathbf{p},t)} + i \int_{\mathbf{p}} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{w}}^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p},t)} \cdot \mathbf{p} \right) \tilde{\mathbf{h}}^{(\mathbf{p},t)} - \eta K^2 \tilde{\mathbf{h}}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} \quad (5.13)$$

Integrating equation 5.13 gives us

$$\tilde{h}_i^{(\mathbf{k},t)} = -i \int_{t',\mathbf{p}} G^{(\mathbf{k},t,t')} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p},t')} \cdot \mathbf{p} \right) \tilde{w}_i^{(\mathbf{p},t')} + i \int_{t',\mathbf{p}} G^{(\mathbf{k},t,t')} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{w}}^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p},t')} \cdot \mathbf{p} \right) \tilde{h}_i^{(\mathbf{p},t')} \quad (5.14)$$

where

$$G(\mathbf{k}, t, \tau) \equiv \exp \left[- \int_{\tau}^t \eta K^2(\mathbf{k}, s) ds \right] \Theta(t - \tau) \quad (5.15)$$

with

$$\int_{\tau}^t K^2(\mathbf{k}, s) ds = k^2 (t - \tau) - (t^2 - \tau^2) (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{k}) (\mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{k}) + \frac{1}{3} (t^3 - \tau^3) (\mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{k})^2 \quad (5.16)$$

By defining

$$\lambda_m^{(\mathbf{k},t)} \equiv k_m - t a_m (\mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{k}) \quad (5.17)$$

$$\mathcal{A}_{ijk}^{(\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q})} \equiv -i \delta_{ij} p_k + i \delta_{ik} q_j \quad (5.18)$$

we can write equation 5.13 as

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{h}_i^{(\mathbf{k},t)}}{\partial t} = -\eta |\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{k},t)}|^2 \tilde{h}_i^{(\mathbf{k},t)} + \int_{\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{ijk}^{(\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q})} \tilde{w}_j^{(\mathbf{p},t)} \tilde{h}_k^{(\mathbf{q},t)} \quad (5.19)$$

5.2.2 The quantities of interest

Defining

$$\mathcal{B}_{ij}(\mathbf{k}, t; \mathbf{k}', t') \equiv \tilde{h}_i(\mathbf{k}, t) \tilde{h}_j(\mathbf{k}', t') \quad (5.20)$$

we use equation 5.19 to write

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t;\mathbf{k}',t')}}{\partial t} &= -\eta |\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{k},t)}|^2 \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t;\mathbf{k}',t')} + \int_{\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{jlm}^{(\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q})} \tilde{w}_l^{(\mathbf{p},t)} \mathcal{B}_{im}^{(\mathbf{k},t;\mathbf{q},t)} \\ &\quad + [i \leftrightarrow j; \mathbf{k} \leftrightarrow \mathbf{k}'] \end{aligned} \quad (5.21)$$

where we have used ‘ $[i \leftrightarrow j; \mathbf{k} \leftrightarrow \mathbf{k}']$ ’ at the end of the RHS to denote that all the preceding terms should be repeated under the indicated simultaneous relabelling.

We would like to obtain an evolution equation for $\langle \mathcal{B}_{ij} \rangle$. Averaging equation 5.21 gives us

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \langle \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t;\mathbf{k}',t)} \rangle}{\partial t} &= -\eta |\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{k},t)}|^2 \langle \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t;\mathbf{k}',t)} \rangle \\ &+ \int_{\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{jlm}^{(\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q})} \langle \tilde{w}_l^{(\mathbf{p},t)} \mathcal{B}_{im}^{(\mathbf{k},t;\mathbf{q},t)} \rangle \\ &+ [i \leftrightarrow j; \mathbf{k} \leftrightarrow \mathbf{k}'] \end{aligned} \quad (5.22)$$

The evolution equation for $\langle \mathcal{B} \rangle$ thus depends on correlations of the form $\langle \tilde{w} \mathcal{B} \rangle$. Similarly, the evolution equation for $\langle \tilde{w}_{i_1} \dots \tilde{w}_{i_n} \mathcal{B} \rangle$ would depend on correlations of the form $\langle \tilde{w}_{i_1} \dots \tilde{w}_{i_n} \tilde{w}_{i_{n+1}} \mathcal{B} \rangle$, where we have used the shorthand $\tilde{w}_{i_\alpha} \equiv \tilde{w}_{i_\alpha}(\mathbf{k}^{(\alpha)}, t^{(\alpha)})$.

To close the hierarchy, we assume \tilde{w} is a Gaussian random field. Since \mathcal{B} is a functional of this Gaussian random field (\mathcal{B} at a particular time can depend on \tilde{w} at all earlier times), we can use the Furutsu-Novikov theorem (appendix 4.B) to simplify the $\langle \tilde{w} \mathcal{B} \rangle$ terms. Assuming $\langle \tilde{w} \rangle = \mathbf{0}$ and applying the Furutsu-Novikov theorem, we write equation 5.22 as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \langle \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t;\mathbf{k}',t)} \rangle}{\partial t} &= -\eta |\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{k},t)}|^2 \langle \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t;\mathbf{k}',t)} \rangle \\ &+ \int_{\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q},\mathbf{k}^{(1)},t^{(1)}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q})} \langle \tilde{w}_r^{(\mathbf{p},t)} \tilde{w}_{i_1} \rangle \left\langle \frac{\delta \mathcal{B}_{is}^{(\mathbf{k},t;\mathbf{q},t)}}{\delta \tilde{w}_{i_1}} \right\rangle \\ &+ [i \leftrightarrow j; \mathbf{k} \leftrightarrow \mathbf{k}'] \end{aligned} \quad (5.23)$$

Our task is now to find an expression for $\langle \delta \mathcal{B} / \delta \tilde{w} \rangle$.

5.2.3 Recursion relation between functional derivatives

Integrating equation 5.21 wrt. time, we find

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t;\mathbf{k}',t)} &= \int_{t',\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{q})} G^{(\mathbf{k},t,t')} G^{(\mathbf{k}',t,t')} \mathcal{A}_{ilm}^{(\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q})} \tilde{w}_l^{(\mathbf{p},t')} \mathcal{B}_{mj}^{(\mathbf{q},t';\mathbf{k}',t')} \\ &+ \int_{t',\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{q})} G^{(\mathbf{k},t,t')} G^{(\mathbf{k}',t,t')} \mathcal{A}_{jlm}^{(\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q})} \tilde{w}_l^{(\mathbf{p},t')} \mathcal{B}_{im}^{(\mathbf{k},t';\mathbf{q},t')} \end{aligned} \quad (5.24)$$

We now use the above to obtain a recursion relation between functional derivatives of \mathcal{B} . For notational convenience, we define

$$A_{ijk}^{(\mathbf{k},\mathbf{k}';\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q};t,t')} \equiv G^{(\mathbf{k},t,t')} G^{(\mathbf{k}',t,t')} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{ijk}^{(\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q})} \quad (5.25)$$

Taking $\tilde{w}_i^{(\mathbf{k},t)} \rightarrow \tilde{w}_i^{(\mathbf{k},t)} + \epsilon \phi_i^{(\mathbf{k},t)}$ (with $\mathcal{B}_{ij} \rightarrow \mathcal{B}_{ij}[\tilde{w} + \epsilon\phi]$), we write

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\frac{d^n \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t;\mathbf{k}',t)}}{d\epsilon^n} \right]_{\epsilon=0} &= \int_{t',\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q}} A_{jmn}^{(\mathbf{k},\mathbf{k}';\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q};t,t')} \tilde{w}_m^{(\mathbf{p},t')} \left[\frac{d^n \mathcal{B}_{in}^{(\mathbf{k},t';\mathbf{q},t')}}{d\epsilon^n} \right]_{\epsilon=0} \\ &+ n \int_{t',\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q}} A_{jmn}^{(\mathbf{k},\mathbf{k}';\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q};t,t')} \phi_m^{(\mathbf{p},t')} \left[\frac{d^{n-1} \mathcal{B}_{in}^{(\mathbf{k},t';\mathbf{q},t')}}{d\epsilon^{n-1}} \right]_{\epsilon=0} \\ &+ [i \leftrightarrow j; \mathbf{k} \leftrightarrow \mathbf{k}'] \end{aligned} \quad (5.26)$$

which implies (using the shorthand $\tilde{w}_{i_\alpha} \equiv \tilde{w}_{i_\alpha}(\mathbf{k}^{(\alpha)}, t^{(\alpha)})$)

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\delta^n \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t;\mathbf{k}',t)}}{\delta \tilde{w}_{i_1} \dots \delta \tilde{w}_{i_n}} &= \int_{t',\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q}} A_{jmn}^{(\mathbf{k},\mathbf{k}';\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q};t,t')} \tilde{w}_m^{(\mathbf{p},t')} \frac{\delta^n \mathcal{B}_{in}^{(\mathbf{k},t';\mathbf{q},t')}}{\delta \tilde{w}_{i_1} \dots \delta \tilde{w}_{i_n}} \\ &+ \sum_{\alpha=1}^n \int_{\mathbf{q}} A_{ji_\alpha n}^{(\mathbf{k},\mathbf{k}';\mathbf{k}^{(\alpha)},\mathbf{q};t,t^{(\alpha)})} \frac{\delta^{n-1} \mathcal{B}_{in}^{(\mathbf{k},t^{(\alpha)};\mathbf{q},t^{(\alpha)})}}{\delta \tilde{w}_{i_1} \dots \delta \tilde{w}_{i_{\alpha-1}} \delta \tilde{w}_{i_{\alpha+1}} \dots \delta \tilde{w}_{i_n}} \\ &+ [i \leftrightarrow j; \mathbf{k} \leftrightarrow \mathbf{k}'] \end{aligned} \quad (5.27)$$

Averaging both sides of the above, using the Furutsu-Novikov theorem (equation 4.79), and recalling that $\langle \tilde{\mathbf{w}} \rangle = \mathbf{0}$, we write

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle \frac{\delta^n \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t;\mathbf{k}',t)}}{\delta \tilde{w}_{i_1} \dots \delta \tilde{w}_{i_n}} \right\rangle &= \int_{\substack{t',\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q}, \\ t^{(n+1)}, \\ \mathbf{k}^{(n+1)}}} A_{jmn}^{(\mathbf{k},\mathbf{k}';\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q};t,t')} \left\langle \tilde{w}_m^{(\mathbf{p},t')} \tilde{w}_{i_{n+1}} \right\rangle \left\langle \frac{\delta^{n+1} \mathcal{B}_{in}^{(\mathbf{k},t';\mathbf{q},t')}}{\delta \tilde{w}_{i_1} \dots \delta \tilde{w}_{i_{n+1}}} \right\rangle \\ &+ \sum_{\alpha=1}^n \int_{\mathbf{q}} A_{ji_\alpha n}^{(\mathbf{k},\mathbf{k}';\mathbf{k}^{(\alpha)},\mathbf{q};t,t^{(\alpha)})} \left\langle \frac{\delta^{n-1} \mathcal{B}_{in}^{(\mathbf{k},t^{(\alpha)};\mathbf{q},t^{(\alpha)})}}{\delta \tilde{w}_{i_1} \dots \delta \tilde{w}_{i_{\alpha-1}} \delta \tilde{w}_{i_{\alpha+1}} \dots \delta \tilde{w}_{i_n}} \right\rangle \\ &+ [i \leftrightarrow j; \mathbf{k} \leftrightarrow \mathbf{k}'] \end{aligned} \quad (5.28)$$

Defining

$$\Upsilon_{s;ij;mn}^{(\mathbf{p}';\mathbf{k},\mathbf{k}';\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q};t,t')} \equiv \delta_{is} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}')} A_{jmn}^{(\mathbf{k},\mathbf{k}';\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q};t,t')} + \delta_{js} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{p}')} A_{imn}^{(\mathbf{k}',\mathbf{k};\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q};t,t')} \quad (5.29)$$

we can write equation 5.28 as

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle \frac{\delta^n \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t;\mathbf{k}',t)}}{\delta \tilde{w}_{i_1} \dots \delta \tilde{w}_{i_n}} \right\rangle &= \int_{\substack{t',\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q},\mathbf{p}', \\ t^{(n+1)}, \\ \mathbf{k}^{(n+1)}}} \Upsilon_{s;ij;mn}^{(\mathbf{p}';\mathbf{k},\mathbf{k}';\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q};t,t')} \left\langle \tilde{w}_m^{(\mathbf{p},t')} \tilde{w}_{i_{n+1}} \right\rangle \left\langle \frac{\delta^{n+1} \mathcal{B}_{sn}^{(\mathbf{p}',t';\mathbf{q},t')}}{\delta \tilde{w}_{i_1} \dots \delta \tilde{w}_{i_{n+1}}} \right\rangle \\ &+ \sum_{\alpha=1}^n \int_{\mathbf{q},\mathbf{p}'} \Upsilon_{s;ij;i_\alpha n}^{(\mathbf{p}';\mathbf{k},\mathbf{k}';\mathbf{k}^{(\alpha)},\mathbf{q};t,t^{(\alpha)})} \left\langle \frac{\delta^{n-1} \mathcal{B}_{sn}^{(\mathbf{p}',t^{(\alpha)};\mathbf{q},t^{(\alpha)})}}{\delta \tilde{w}_{i_1} \dots \delta \tilde{w}_{i_{\alpha-1}} \delta \tilde{w}_{i_{\alpha+1}} \dots \delta \tilde{w}_{i_n}} \right\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (5.30)$$

Repeated application of the above to equation 5.23 allows us to write its RHS as a series in the correlation time (see the corresponding discussion for the evolution of the mean of a passive scalar in section 4.3).

5.3 The Kazantsev equation

5.3.1 Evolution equation in the white noise limit

Let us assume that there is no shear. Further assuming that the velocity field is statistically homogeneous and that its correlation time is zero, we can write

$$\langle \tilde{w}_i^{(\mathbf{k},t)} \tilde{w}_j^{(\mathbf{k}',t')} \rangle = T_{ij}(\mathbf{k}, t) \delta(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}') \delta(t - t') \quad (5.31)$$

Using equation 5.28, we write

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle \frac{\delta \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t;\mathbf{k}',t)}}{\delta \tilde{w}_{i_1}} \right\rangle &= G^{(\mathbf{k},t,t^{(1)})} G^{(\mathbf{k}',t,t^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{j i_1 n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{in}^{(\mathbf{k},t^{(1)}; \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t^{(1)})} \right\rangle \\ &+ [i \leftrightarrow j; \mathbf{k} \leftrightarrow \mathbf{k}'] + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (5.32)$$

where we have dropped terms that contribute only when the correlation time is nonzero. Putting these in equation 5.23, using equation 5.18, setting $\mathbf{k}' = -\mathbf{k}$, and noting that $\int_{-\infty}^t d\tau \delta^{(t-\tau)} f(\tau) = f(t)/2$ (for an arbitrary function f ; this may be thought of as the $\tau_c \rightarrow 0$ limit of equation 4.33a), we write

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \langle \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t; -\mathbf{k},t)} \rangle}{\partial t} &= -\eta |\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{k},t)}|^2 \langle \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t; -\mathbf{k},t)} \rangle \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{jeb}^{(\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} T_{ei_1}^{(\mathbf{p},t)} \mathcal{A}_{bi_1 n}^{(-\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{in}^{(\mathbf{k},t; -\mathbf{k},t)} \rangle \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{jeb}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} T_{ei_1}^{(\mathbf{p},t)} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1 n}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{bn}^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}, t; \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}, t)} \rangle \\ &+ [i \leftrightarrow j; \mathbf{k} \leftrightarrow -\mathbf{k}] \end{aligned} \quad (5.33)$$

5.3.2 Differential equation at high Pr_m

When $\text{Pr}_m \gg 1$, we can simplify the nonlocal integral in equation 5.33 by assuming that the integrand is significant only when $|\mathbf{p}| \ll |\mathbf{k}|$. The Taylor expansion of $\langle \mathcal{B} \rangle$ about \mathbf{k} is

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathcal{B}_{bn}^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}, t; \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}, t)} \rangle &= \langle \mathcal{B}_{bn}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; -\mathbf{k}, t)} \rangle - p_l \frac{\partial \langle \mathcal{B}_{bn}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; -\mathbf{k}, t)} \rangle}{\partial k_l} \\ &+ \frac{p_l p_m}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \langle \mathcal{B}_{bn}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; -\mathbf{k}, t)} \rangle}{\partial k_l \partial k_m} + \mathcal{O}(p^3) \end{aligned} \quad (5.34)$$

Note that although the magnetic field is divergence-free, the RHS of equation 5.34 is not. This may be seen by explicitly calculating $(k_b - p_b) \langle \mathcal{B}_{bn}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}) \rangle$ after performing the Taylor expansion; one is always left with a term that would've been cancelled by a neglected term in the next order of the Taylor expansion. This is

not a problem as long as one remembers that dropping $\mathcal{O}(p^3)$ terms in equation 5.34 requires us to drop all other terms of the same order in other expressions. For example, although we will be assuming the velocity field is nonhelical, we note that the quantity β that couples the evolution equations derived by Kulsrud and Anderson (1992, eqs. C17–C18) for the magnetic energy and magnetic helicity spectra should be neglected.

We further assume that the velocity field is nonhelical, homogeneous, and isotropic, with analogous assumptions for the magnetic field.

$$T_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k})} = E^{(k)} \mathbb{P}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k})} \quad (5.35)$$

$$\langle \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t;-\mathbf{k},t)} \rangle = M^{(k)} \mathbb{P}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k})} \delta^{(0)} \mathfrak{D}_B^{(0)} \quad (5.36)$$

where $\mathfrak{D}_B(t)$ is the temporal correlation function of the magnetic field. Let us keep in mind that as argued above, neglecting $\mathcal{O}(p^3)$ terms in equation 5.34 requires us to drop all terms containing $\int p^{4+n} E^{(p)} dp$ (with $n > 0$) in our final expressions. The derivatives of the magnetic correlation are

$$\frac{\partial \langle \mathcal{B}_{bn}^{(\mathbf{k},t;-\mathbf{k},t)} \rangle}{\partial k_n} = -\frac{2k_b}{k^2} M^{(k)} \delta^{(0)} \mathfrak{D}_B^{(0)} \quad (5.37)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \langle \mathcal{B}_{bn}^{(\mathbf{k},t;-\mathbf{k},t)} \rangle}{\partial k_b \partial k_n} = -\frac{2}{k} \frac{dM^{(k)}}{dk} \delta^{(0)} \mathfrak{D}_B^{(0)} - \frac{2}{k^2} M^{(k)} \delta^{(0)} \mathfrak{D}_B^{(0)} \quad (5.38)$$

Using these, we write

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{ieb}^{(\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} T_{ei_1}^{(\mathbf{p},t)} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1n}^{(-\mathbf{p},\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{k})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{bn}^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p},t;\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{k},t)} \rangle \\ &= \frac{8\pi}{3} k^2 M^{(k)} \delta^{(0)} \mathfrak{D}_B^{(0)} \int p^2 E^{(p)} dp + \frac{16\pi}{15} M^{(k)} \delta^{(0)} \mathfrak{D}_B^{(0)} \int p^4 E^{(p)} dp \\ &+ \frac{8\pi}{15} k \frac{dM^{(k)}}{dk} \delta^{(0)} \mathfrak{D}_B^{(0)} \int p^4 E^{(p)} dp + \frac{4\pi}{15} k^2 \frac{d^2 M^{(k)}}{dk^2} \delta^{(0)} \mathfrak{D}_B^{(0)} \int p^4 E^{(p)} dp \\ &+ \frac{4\pi}{15} \frac{d^2 M^{(k)}}{dk^2} \delta^{(0)} \mathfrak{D}_B^{(0)} \int p^6 E^{(p)} dp - \frac{8\pi}{15} \frac{M^{(k)}}{k^2} \delta^{(0)} \mathfrak{D}_B^{(0)} \int p^6 E^{(p)} dp \end{aligned} \quad (5.39)$$

We also find that

$$\frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{ieb}^{(\mathbf{p},-\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} T_{ei_1}^{(\mathbf{p},t)} \mathcal{A}_{bi_1n}^{(-\mathbf{p},-\mathbf{k})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{in}^{(\mathbf{k},t;-\mathbf{k},t)} \rangle = -\frac{8\pi}{3} k^2 M^{(k)} \delta^{(0)} \mathfrak{D}_B^{(0)} \int p^2 E^{(p)} dp \quad (5.40)$$

Contracting i with j in equation 5.33; using equations 5.39 and 5.40; recalling that $S = 0$; dropping terms involving $\int p^6 E^{(p)} dp$ (as discussed on page 94); and defining

$$v_2 \equiv \frac{4\pi}{6} \int k^4 E^{(k)} dk \quad (5.41)$$

we write

$$\frac{\partial M^{(k)}}{\partial t} = -2\eta k^2 M^{(k)} + \frac{8v_2}{5} M^{(k)} + \frac{4v_2}{5} k \frac{dM^{(k)}}{dk} + \frac{2v_2}{5} k^2 \frac{d^2 M^{(k)}}{dk^2} \quad (5.42)$$

This is consistent with the expressions derived by Kazantsev (1968, eq. 31) and Kulsrud and Anderson (1992, eq. 1.11).⁷

5.3.3 Solutions of the differential equation

5.3.3.1 General solutions

Taking

$$M(k, t) \equiv H(k)e^{\sigma t} \quad (5.43)$$

we write

$$k^2 \frac{d^2 H}{dk^2} + 2k \frac{dH}{dk} - \left[\frac{5\eta}{v_2} k^2 + \left(\frac{5\sigma}{2v_2} - 4 \right) \right] H = 0 \quad (5.44)$$

Defining

$$p \equiv k \sqrt{\frac{5\eta}{v_2}} \quad (5.45)$$

$$h(p) \equiv H(k)\sqrt{k} \quad (5.46)$$

we write

$$p^2 \frac{d^2 h}{dp^2} + p \frac{dh}{dp} - \left(p^2 + \frac{5\sigma}{2v_2} - \frac{15}{4} \right) h = 0 \quad (5.47)$$

which is a modified Bessel equation (Abramowitz and Stegun 1972, sec. 9.6; Olver et al. 2022, sec. 10.25). If we expect $h(p)$ to not diverge as $p \rightarrow \infty$, it needs to be a modified Bessel function of the second kind. The spectrum is a linear combination of functions of the form

$$M(k, t) \propto \frac{1}{\sqrt{p}} K_\mu(p) e^{\sigma t} \quad (5.48)$$

where

$$\mu = \sqrt{\frac{5\sigma}{2v_2} - \frac{15}{4}} \quad (5.49)$$

Note that it is possible for μ to be imaginary (Olver et al. 2022, sec. 10.45). We will soon see that the boundary conditions determine the allowed values of μ .

⁷Note that Kulsrud and Anderson (1992) define $\gamma = 2v_2$ (cf. Schekochihin, Boldyrev, and Kulsrud 2002, eq. 14) and write the evolution equation for $\mathcal{M}(k) \equiv k^2 M(k)$.

5.3.3.2 Boundary conditions

Using equation 5.42 and assuming $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} k^n \frac{d^m M}{dk^m} = 0$ for all $m, n > 0$, we can write the evolution equation for $E_B \equiv \int_{k_*}^{\infty} k^2 M(k) dk$ (at this stage, k_* is arbitrary) as

$$\frac{\partial E_B}{\partial t} = -2\eta \int_{k_*}^{\infty} k^4 M(k) dk + 4v_2 E_B + \frac{2v_2}{5} \left[k^4 \frac{dM(k)}{dk} - 2k^3 M(k) \right]_{k_*}^{\infty} \quad (5.50)$$

The last term may be interpreted as coupling scales $k < k_*$ to scales $k > k_*$. Now, suppose k_* is chosen small enough that scales $k < k_*$ do not contribute to the evolution of the magnetic spectrum at all. This means we need (Schekochihin et al. 2002, sec. 2.4)

$$\left[k^4 \frac{dM(k)}{dk} - 2k^3 M(k) \right]_{k=k_*} = 0 \quad (5.51)$$

Plugging equation 5.48 into this, the constraint becomes (with $p_* \equiv k_* \sqrt{5\eta/v_2}$)

$$p_* K'_\mu(p_*) - \frac{5}{2} K_\mu(p_*) = 0 \quad (5.52)$$

When $\mu^2, p > 0$, we have $K_\mu(p) > 0$ and $K'_\mu(p) < 0$. It is thus impossible for the above equation to be satisfied for real μ .

Recalling that k_* is supposed to represent a wavenumber below which the magnetic field is negligible, it seems reasonable to set $k_* \lesssim k_\nu$.⁸ Let us now assume the turbulence follows the Kolmogorov scaling: $E(k) \propto k^{-13/3}$ for $k_0 \lesssim k \lesssim k_\nu$ (recall that $T_{ij}(\mathbf{r})$ has dimensions of diffusivity, not energy) with $k_\nu \sim \text{Re}^{3/4} k_0$. We can then estimate

$$\frac{v_2}{\int_0^\infty k^2 E(k) dk} \sim k_\nu^{2/3} k_0^{4/3} \sim \text{Re}^{1/2} k_0^2 \quad (5.53)$$

Further defining

$$\text{Rm} \equiv \frac{1}{\eta} \int_0^\infty k^2 E(k) dk \quad (5.54)$$

we find that $\sqrt{v_2/\eta} \sim \text{Re}^{1/4} \text{Rm}^{1/2}$. Taking $k_* \sim k_\nu \sim \text{Re}^{3/4}$ then gives us

$$p_* \sim \text{Pr}^{-1/2} \quad (5.55)$$

For $p \ll 1$, we may expand (Olver et al. 2022, eq. 10.45.7)

$$K_{i\alpha}(p) = - \left(\frac{\pi}{\alpha \sinh(\pi\alpha)} \right)^{1/2} \sin(\alpha \ln(p/2) - \gamma_\alpha) + \mathcal{O}(p^2) \quad (5.56)$$

where

$$\gamma_\alpha \equiv -i \ln \left[\left(\frac{\sinh(\pi\alpha)}{\pi\alpha} \right)^{1/2} \Gamma(1 + i\alpha) \right] \quad (5.57)$$

⁸For $k \ll k_\nu$, equation 5.42 itself becomes invalid.

Plugging this into equation 5.52, the constraint becomes

$$\alpha \cos(\alpha \ln(p_*/2) - \gamma_\alpha) - \frac{5}{2} \sin(\alpha \ln(p_*/2) - \gamma_\alpha) = 0 \quad (5.58)$$

$$\implies \tan(\alpha \ln(p_*/2) - \gamma_\alpha) = \frac{2\alpha}{5} \quad (5.59)$$

5.3.3.3 Growth rate

We now note that when $\alpha, p > 0$, $K_{i\alpha}(p)$ has roots only in $0 < p < \alpha$ (Dunster 1990, eq. 2.18). Since $M(k) \geq 0$, we require that any zeros of $K_\mu(p)$ fall in the region $p < p_*$, i.e. we want $\alpha \leq p_*$. Further, from equation 5.49, we see that the highest possible growth rate (which is what we want to find) corresponds to the value of α that is closest to zero (but $\neq 0$). Keeping this in mind, we search for a solution to equation 5.59 such that $\alpha \ll 1$.

In the limit $\alpha \ll 1$, equation 5.57 becomes

$$\gamma_\alpha = -\gamma\alpha + \frac{\zeta(3)}{3} \alpha^3 + \mathcal{O}(\alpha^5) \quad (5.60)$$

where γ is the Euler-Mascheroni constant and ζ is the Riemann zeta function. Plugging this in equation 5.59, we the constraint becomes

$$\tan\left(\alpha \left[\ln(p_*/2) + \gamma - \frac{\zeta(3)}{3} \alpha^2\right]\right) = \frac{2\alpha}{5} \quad (5.61)$$

This is a transcendental equation that can only be solved numerically. Let us now assume $|\ln(p_*)| \gg 1$. We can then approximately write the constraint as^{9,10}

$$\tan(\alpha \ln(p_*)) = 0 \quad (5.62)$$

The smallest nonzero root of this equation corresponds to

$$\alpha = \frac{\pi}{\ln p_*} \quad (5.63)$$

Plugging this in equation 5.49, we find that the corresponding growth rate is

$$\sigma = \left(\frac{3}{2} - \frac{2\pi^2}{5(\ln p_*)^2}\right) v_2 \quad (5.64)$$

⁹A more obvious way to solve equation 5.57 would be to directly expand it as a series in α , discard $\mathcal{O}(\alpha^5)$ terms, and solve the resulting equation for α . Unfortunately, the nonzero roots of the resulting equation correspond to imaginary α . This seems to be a flaw in using series expansions about the origin to solve equations involving trigonometric functions. A similar issue arises when, e.g., we try to solve $\sin(x) = 0$ for its smallest nonzero solution.

¹⁰The roots of this equation are identical to those of $\sin(\alpha \ln(p_*/2)) = 0$, which results from requiring the spectrum itself to become zero at $k = k_*$ (see equation 5.56) (Schekochihin, Boldyrev, and Kulsrud 2002, p. 839; Schekochihin et al. 2002, eq. 17).

This matches the result obtained by Schekochihin et al. (2002, eq. 18) and Schekochihin, Boldyrev, and Kulsrud (2002, eq. 49).

Recalling equation 5.53, we see that when $\text{Pr}_m \gg 1$, the ratio of the growth rate to the integral-scale-turnover rate scales as $\text{Re}^{1/2}$.¹¹

5.4 Evolution equation when the correlation time is nonzero

5.4.1 The Fourier-space evolution equation

Repeatedly using equation 5.30 to eliminate all the functional derivatives in equation 5.23 and neglecting $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c^2)$ terms, one obtains an evolution equation for the double correlation of the magnetic field (see the corresponding discussion for mean passive scalar diffusion in section 4.3).

We further assume the velocity field is statistically homogeneous and separable (c.f. equations 4.32), i.e. that it can be written as¹²

$$\left\langle \tilde{w}_i^{(\mathbf{k},t)} \tilde{w}_j^{(\mathbf{k}',t')} \right\rangle = T_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k})} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}')} \mathfrak{D}^{(t-t')} \quad (5.65)$$

where \mathfrak{D} , the temporal correlation function of the velocity field, has the properties given in equations 4.33. We then obtain an extremely long evolution equation (equation 5.244), the details of which are relegated to appendix 5.C. Of note is that this evolution equation depends on \mathfrak{D} only through the constants g_1 and g_2 , defined in equations 4.92. Further simplification of this equation requires additional assumptions about the velocity field.

5.4.2 How to move to configuration space

While the Furutsu-Novikov theorem is easy to apply in Fourier space,¹³ the resulting evolution equations (equations 5.33 or 5.244) contain convolutions, and are thus difficult to simplify. Working in configuration space circumvents this issue. Using the convolution theorem (equation 5.8, with the Fourier transform defined by equation 5.7), we can transform the Fourier-space evolution equations to obtain the analogous equations in configuration space.

¹¹Taking $k^2 E(k) \sim k^{-5/3}$ in the derivation of equation 5.53 would have predicted that the growth rate scales as Re , which is not in agreement with DNS.

¹²Separability actually assumes that the correlation time of the velocity field is scale-independent. While the eddy turnover time is typically scale-dependent, Chandran (1997) argues that the smallest eddies randomize the direction of the magnetic field over a timescale of the order of their turnover time. Thus, at high Pr_m , one should supposedly consider the correlation time as the turnover time of the smallest eddies, regardless of the scale of interest.

¹³In configuration space, one would have to keep track of which objects each spatial derivative operates on. While this is doable for simpler problems (chapter 4), we expect it to be trickier for the problem studied in this chapter.

In this section, we describe how one can obtain such evolution equations in the absence of shear ($S = 0$), under the additional assumptions that the magnetic and velocity fields are statistically isotropic and that the velocity field is incompressible. The procedure described below will be applied for nonhelical velocity fields in section 5.4.3, and for helical velocity fields in section 5.4.4.

5.4.2.1 Identities

We use the following identities (assuming $f(k) \rightarrow f(r)$, with the arrow denoting inverse Fourier transformation from \mathbf{k} to \mathbf{r} ; note that some of these only hold when f is independent of the direction of \mathbf{k}):

$$k_i f(k) \rightarrow i \frac{\partial f(r)}{\partial r_i} \quad (5.66)$$

$$k^2 f(k) \rightarrow -\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^2 \frac{df(r)}{dr} \right) \quad (5.67)$$

Further assuming that $f(r = \infty) = 0$, we write¹⁴

$$\frac{f(k)}{k^2} \rightarrow -\int_r^\infty \left(\frac{dr}{r^2} \int_r^\infty dr r^2 f(r) \right) \quad (5.68)$$

5.4.2.2 Longitudinal and cross correlation functions

Definitions When the magnetic field is statistically homogeneous and isotropic, the double-correlation of the magnetic field in configuration space ($M_{ij}(\mathbf{r}) \equiv \langle B_i(\mathbf{r}) B_j(\mathbf{0}) \rangle$) can be written as (Lesieur 2008, eq. 5.63; Vainshtein and Kichatinov 1986, eq. 23)

$$M_{ij}(\mathbf{r}) = \left(\delta_{ij} - \frac{r_i r_j}{r^2} \right) M_N(r) + \frac{r_i r_j}{r^2} M_L(r) + \epsilon_{ijs} r_s M_C(r) \quad (5.69)$$

with

$$M_N = \frac{1}{2r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r^2 M_L) \quad (5.70)$$

where M_L is the *longitudinal correlation function*, and rM_C is the *cross correlation function* (Lesieur 2008, section 5.9). In what follows, we refer to M_C as the *modified cross correlation function*. If the velocity field is incompressible, the same relation holds for it (we denote its longitudinal correlation function by E_L and its modified cross correlation function by E_C). Authors who study the SSD in configuration space typically use the longitudinal and modified-cross correlation functions (e.g. Kazantsev 1968, eq. 16; Vainshtein and Kichatinov 1986, eq. 26–27; Subramanian 1997, eqs. 24–25).

¹⁴It may seem more natural to write

$$\frac{f(k)}{k^2} \rightarrow -\int_0^r \left(\frac{dr}{r^2} \int_0^r dr r^2 f(r) \right)$$

but this would leave behind extra terms involving $f(0)$ when applied to the Laplacian of $f(r)$.

Relations to the spectra On the other hand, in Fourier space, it is conventional to write the double-correlation of the magnetic field as¹⁵

$$M_{ij}(\mathbf{k}) = P_{ij}(\mathbf{k}) M(k) + \frac{i\epsilon_{ijc}k_c}{k^2} N(k) \quad (5.71)$$

We find that

$$2M(r) = M_{ii} = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r^3 M_L) \quad (5.72)$$

Inverting this, we have¹⁶

$$M_L = \frac{1}{r^3} \int_0^r r^2 M_{ii} dr \quad (5.73)$$

To find an analogous relation for the helical part, we note that in Fourier space, we have

$$2iN(k) = \epsilon_{ijs} k_s M_{ij}(\mathbf{k}) \quad (5.74)$$

Taking the inverse Fourier transform of both sides, we find

$$2N(r) = \epsilon_{ijs} \frac{\partial M_{ij}(\mathbf{r})}{\partial r_s} \quad (5.75)$$

Using the equation for $M_{ij}(\mathbf{r})$, we write

$$2N(r) = 2r \frac{\partial M_C}{\partial r} + 6M_C = \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r^3 M_C) \quad (5.76)$$

Inverting this, we have

$$M_C = \frac{1}{2r^3} \int_0^r 2N(r) r^2 dr \quad (5.77)$$

Performing an inverse Fourier transform (of the evolution equations we earlier derived) directly gives us the evolution equation for $M_{ij}(\mathbf{r})$, and thus those for $M(k)$ and $N(k)$. We then need to use the relations above to rewrite them in a more conventional form.

¹⁵For example, see equation 4.122, but note that the definition of the Fourier transform in that section is different from that used here, and so we have to complex-conjugate that expression before comparing it with the one here.

¹⁶The lower limit of the integral in equation 5.73 can be constrained by the following arguments. Let us denote the lower limit as $r = a$. Plugging equation 5.72 into the RHS of equation 5.73 and requiring the resulting equation to hold gives us $\lim_{r \rightarrow a} r^3 M_L(r) = 0$. In general, this is only expected to hold for $a = 0$ and $a = \infty$. Alternatively, taking the $r \rightarrow 0$ limit of equation 5.73 gives us $[r^3 M_L(r)]_{r \rightarrow 0} = \int_a^0 r^2 M_{ii} dr$. Equation 5.78 (which follows from equation 5.72 regardless of the value of a) tells us that $M_L(0)$ is finite. This means we need $\int_a^0 r^2 M_{ii} dr = 0$. This condition is satisfied for $a \rightarrow \infty$ only if there is no volume-averaged ($k = 0$) magnetic field (recall that $\int_0^\infty r^2 M_{ii} dr \propto M_{ii}(k = 0)$; see equation 5.247). As far as the evolution equation for $M_L(r)$ in nonhelical turbulence (equation 5.117 or 5.124) is concerned, the only effect of choosing $a = \infty$ rather than $a = 0$ is a change in the form of the extra terms given in equation 5.122. Elimination of these extra terms is possible in both cases: for $a = \infty$, one requires all the correlation functions to decay faster than any polynomial as $r \rightarrow \infty$; for $a = 0$, one requires $[dE_L(r)/dr]_{r=0} = 0$.

Useful single-point correlations in terms of longitudinal and modified-cross correlations To interpret the resulting equations, it is useful to note that

$$\langle H_i H_i \rangle = 2M(r=0) = 3M_L(0) \quad (5.78)$$

$$\epsilon_{ijk} \langle H_i \partial_j H_k \rangle = 2N(r=0) = 6M_C(0) \quad (5.79)$$

where we have assumed $[r dM_{L,C}/dr]_{r=0} = 0$.^{17,18,19}

Note that equation 5.79 gives the current helicity. To find an expression for the magnetic helicity, we note that its 3D spectrum (say $2\mathcal{N}(k)$) is related to the spectrum of the current helicity ($2N(k)$; see equation 5.74) by

$$\mathcal{N}(k) = \frac{N(k)}{k^2} \quad (5.80)$$

Using equations 5.68 and 5.76, we then write

$$\mathcal{N}(r) = - \int_r^\infty \left(\frac{dr}{r^2} \int_r^\infty dr r^2 N(r) \right) \quad (5.81)$$

$$= \int_r^\infty dr r M_C \quad (5.82)$$

We can then write

$$\text{magnetic helicity} = 2\mathcal{N}(r=0) = 2 \int_0^\infty dr r M_C \quad (5.83)$$

Note that equation 5.80 requires the divergence of the magnetic vector potential to be zero, and hence the above gives the magnetic helicity in the Coulomb gauge.

Similarly, the squared magnetic vector potential (needed to calculate the fractional magnetic helicity) is

$$\langle A_i A_i \rangle = \int_0^\infty dr r M_L \quad (5.84)$$

Similar relations hold for the velocity field, with its temporal correlation being inserted as needed. For example, the analogue of equation 5.78 is

$$\langle w_i(\mathbf{x}, t) w_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \rangle = 3 E_L(0) \mathfrak{D}(0) \quad (5.85)$$

¹⁷As discussed in appendix 5.E, one in fact expects $[dM_L/dr]_{r=0} = 0$.

¹⁸The RHS of our equation 5.78 differs from that given by Kim and Hughes (1997, p. 216) because their definition of the longitudinal correlation function differs from ours by a factor of 2 (compare their equation 35 with our equation 5.72).

¹⁹The sign of the RHS of equation 5.79 follows from our definition of $M_{ij}(\mathbf{r})$ as $\langle B_i(\mathbf{r}) B_j(0) \rangle$. Accounting for this, our result is consistent with that derived by Subramanian (1997, eq 15). Additionally accounting for the fact that Lesieur (2008, p. 173) define the helicity with an extra factor of 1/2 as compared to us, their equation 5.67 is consistent with our result.

5.4.2.3 The convolutions whose Fourier transforms we require

The terms on the RHS of equation 5.244 (appendix 5.C) can be rewritten as

$$[\mathcal{I}^{1.1}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} = \tau_c g_1 \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{iu}^{(\mathbf{k},t;-\mathbf{k},t)} \right\rangle \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jas}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\ \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{smn}^{(\mathbf{p},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_1l}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{li_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p},-\mathbf{k})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \quad (5.86)$$

$$[\mathcal{I}^{1.2}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} = \tau_c g_1 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)},\mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{jas}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{us}^{(\mathbf{q},t;-\mathbf{q},t)} \right\rangle \\ \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{imn}^{(\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_1l}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)},\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{li_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \quad (5.87)$$

$$[\mathcal{I}^{1.3}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} = \tau_c g_1 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)},\mathbf{q},\mathbf{p}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{jbs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1b}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{sma}^{(-\mathbf{p},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)}+\mathbf{p})} \\ \times \mathcal{A}_{ii_1l}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)},\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{li_2u}^{(\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{p})} T_{i_2m}^{(\mathbf{p})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{ua}^{(\mathbf{q},t;-\mathbf{q},t)} \right\rangle \quad (5.88)$$

$$[\mathcal{I}^{1.4}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} = \tau_c g_1 \int_{\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{ima}^{(\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{li_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{p})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{q},t;-\mathbf{q},t)} \right\rangle \\ \times \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jbs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{si_1l}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k})} T_{i_1b}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \quad (5.89)$$

$$[\mathcal{I}^{1.5}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} = \tau_c g_1 \int_{\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{ii_2u}^{(\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} T_{i_2m}^{(\mathbf{p})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{ua}^{(\mathbf{q},t;-\mathbf{q},t)} \right\rangle \\ \times \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{smn}^{(-\mathbf{p},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)}+\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_1a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{jbs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1b}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \quad (5.90)$$

$$[\mathcal{I}^{1.6}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} = \tau_c g_1 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)},\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{jbs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1b}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{imn}^{(\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} \\ \times \mathcal{A}_{ni_1a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)},\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{si_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)}+\mathbf{p})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{q},t;-\mathbf{q},t)} \right\rangle \quad (5.91)$$

$$[\mathcal{I}^{1.7}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} = \tau_c g_1 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)},\mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{jbs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1b}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{q},t;-\mathbf{q},t)} \right\rangle \\ \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{sml}^{(\mathbf{p},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)},\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{li_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \quad (5.92)$$

$$[\mathcal{I}^{1.8}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} = \tau_c g_1 \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{ua}^{(\mathbf{k},t;-\mathbf{k},t)} \right\rangle \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jbs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1b}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\ \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{iml}^{(\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{si_1a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k})} \mathcal{A}_{li_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \quad (5.93)$$

$$[\mathcal{I}^{2.1}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} = \tau_c g_2 \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{iu}^{(\mathbf{k},t;-\mathbf{k},t)} \right\rangle \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jas}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\ \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{smn}^{(\mathbf{p},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_2l}^{(-\mathbf{p},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{li_1u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \quad (5.94)$$

$$[\mathcal{I}^{2.2}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} = \tau_c g_2 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{jas}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{us}^{(\mathbf{q}, t; -\mathbf{q}, t)} \rangle$$

$$\times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{imn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_2 l}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k})} \mathcal{A}_{li_1 u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})}$$
(5.95)

$$[\mathcal{I}^{2.3}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} = \tau_c g_2 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{jbs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 b}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{sma}^{(-\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)}+\mathbf{p})}$$

$$\times \mathcal{A}_{i_2 l}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{li_1 u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_2 m}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{ua}^{(\mathbf{q}, t; -\mathbf{q}, t)} \rangle$$
(5.96)

$$[\mathcal{I}^{2.4}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} = \tau_c g_2 \int_{\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{ima}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{q}, t; -\mathbf{q}, t)} \rangle$$

$$\times \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{si_2 l}^{(-\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)}+\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{li_1 u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{jbs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 b}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})}$$
(5.97)

$$[\mathcal{I}^{2.5}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} = \tau_c g_2 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{jbs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 b}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{ua}^{(\mathbf{q}, t; -\mathbf{q}, t)} \rangle$$

$$\times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{smn}^{(\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_2 a}^{(-\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{i_1 u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})}$$
(5.98)

$$[\mathcal{I}^{2.6}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} = \tau_c g_2 \langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; -\mathbf{k}, t)} \rangle \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jbs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 b}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})}$$

$$\times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{imn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_2 a}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k})} \mathcal{A}_{si_1 u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})}$$
(5.99)

$$[\mathcal{I}^{2.7}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} = \tau_c g_2 \int_{\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{i_2 a}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} T_{i_2 m}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{q}, t; -\mathbf{q}, t)} \rangle$$

$$\times \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{sml}^{(-\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)}+\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{li_1 u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{jbs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 b}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})}$$
(5.100)

$$[\mathcal{I}^{2.8}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} = \tau_c g_2 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{jbs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 b}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})}$$

$$\times \mathcal{A}_{iml}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{si_2 a}^{(-\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)}+\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{li_1 u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{ua}^{(\mathbf{q}, t; -\mathbf{q}, t)} \rangle$$
(5.101)

$$[\mathcal{I}^{3.1}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} = \langle \mathcal{B}_{in}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; -\mathbf{k}, t)} \rangle \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jas}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{si_1 n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k})}$$

$$\times \left[\frac{1}{2} + \tau_c g_3 \eta \left(- \left| \boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \right|^2 + \left| \boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(-\mathbf{k}, t)} \right|^2 \right) \right]$$
(5.102)

$$[\mathcal{I}^{3.2}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} = \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{jas}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{i_1 n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})}$$

$$\times \left[\frac{1}{2} + \tau_c g_3 \eta \left(- \left| \boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{k}, t)} \right|^2 + \left| \boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \right|^2 \right) \right] \langle \mathcal{B}_{ns}^{(\mathbf{q}, t; -\mathbf{q}, t)} \rangle$$
(5.103)

$$\begin{aligned}
[\mathcal{I}^{4.1}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} &= -\frac{\tau_c g_3}{2} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{ib}^{(\mathbf{k},t;-\mathbf{k},t)} \right\rangle \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jms}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 m}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{s_{i_1 n}}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k})} \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{nla}^{(\mathbf{p},-\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} T_{li_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ai_2 b}^{(-\mathbf{p},-\mathbf{k})}
\end{aligned} \tag{5.104}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
[\mathcal{I}^{4.2}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} &= -\frac{\tau_c g_3}{2} \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)},\mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{jms}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 m}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{bs}^{(\mathbf{q},t;-\mathbf{q},t)} \right\rangle \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1 n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)},\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{nla}^{(\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{p})} T_{li_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ai_2 b}^{(-\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})}
\end{aligned} \tag{5.105}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
[\mathcal{I}^{4.3}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} &= -\frac{\tau_c g_3}{2} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{bm}^{(\mathbf{k},t;-\mathbf{k},t)} \right\rangle \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jns}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{s_{i_1 m}}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k})} \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{ila}^{(\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} T_{li_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ai_2 b}^{(-\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k})}
\end{aligned} \tag{5.106}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
[\mathcal{I}^{4.4}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} &= -\frac{\tau_c g_3}{2} \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)},\mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{jns}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1 m}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)},\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\
&\quad \times \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{mb}^{(\mathbf{q},t;-\mathbf{q},t)} \right\rangle \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{sla}^{(\mathbf{p},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{p})} T_{li_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ai_2 b}^{(-\mathbf{p},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})}
\end{aligned} \tag{5.107}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
[\mathcal{I}^{5.1}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} &= -\tau_c g_3 \int_{\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{nla}^{(-\mathbf{p},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{p})} T_{i_2 l}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ii_2 b}^{(\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{ba}^{(\mathbf{q},t;-\mathbf{q},t)} \right\rangle \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{s_{i_1 n}}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k})} \mathcal{A}_{jms}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 m}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})}
\end{aligned} \tag{5.108}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
[\mathcal{I}^{5.2}]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} &= -\tau_c g_3 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)},\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{jms}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 m}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1 n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)},\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\
&\quad \times \mathcal{A}_{nla}^{(\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{p})} T_{li_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{si_2 b}^{(-\mathbf{p},-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)}+\mathbf{p})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{ab}^{(\mathbf{q},t;-\mathbf{q},t)} \right\rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{5.109}$$

To simplify some of these terms, we have assumed $T_{ij}(\mathbf{k}) = T_{ji}(-\mathbf{k})$, which would follow from assuming $\mathfrak{D}(-t) = \mathfrak{D}(t)$. As discussed by Kopyev et al. (2022a,b), the time-asymmetry of the velocity field is closely related to its non-Gaussianity. Since we have already assumed the velocity field is Gaussian, this additional assumption does not seem very restrictive.

5.4.2.4 Obtaining the evolution equations

For the velocity correlation, we use an expression that follows from homogeneity, isotropy, and incompressibility (similar to equation 5.71):

$$T_{ij}(\mathbf{k}) = P_{ij}(\mathbf{k}) E(k) + \frac{i\epsilon_{ijc} k_c}{k^2} F(k) \tag{5.110}$$

The inverse Fourier transforms of the energy and helicity spectra can be related to the longitudinal and modified-cross correlation functions of the velocity field (denoted by E_L and E_C respectively) using the analogues of equations 5.72, 5.73, 5.77, and 5.76.

Substituting equation 5.110 into equation 5.244 and taking the inverse Fourier transform gives us the evolution equation for $M_{ij}(\mathbf{r}, t)$. The evolution equations for $M_L(r, t)$ and $M_C(r, t)$ can then be obtained by the relations

$$\frac{\partial M_L^{(r,t)}}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{r^3} \int_0^r dr r^2 \frac{\partial M_{ii}^{(r,t)}}{\partial t} \quad (5.111)$$

$$\frac{\partial M_C^{(r,t)}}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{2r^3} \int_0^r dr r^2 \epsilon_{ija} \frac{\partial^2 M_{ij}^{(r,t)}}{\partial t \partial r_a} \quad (5.112)$$

which follow from equations 5.73 and 5.77.

5.4.2.5 Some integrals over the velocity spectra

We will later find that the following integrals over the spectra of the velocity field make repeated appearances:

$$v_m \equiv \frac{4\pi}{6} \int_0^\infty p^{2+m} E(p) dp \quad (5.113a)$$

$$h_m \equiv \frac{4\pi}{6} \int_0^\infty p^{2+m} F(p) dp \quad (5.113b)$$

We would like to relate these to E_L and E_C . In terms of the inverse-Fourier-transformed spectra, we have

$$v_{2n} = \frac{(-1)^n}{6} [\nabla^{2n} E(r)]_{r=0}, \quad h_{2n} = \frac{(-1)^n}{6} [\nabla^{2n} F(r)]_{r=0} \quad (5.114)$$

We can then use equations 5.72 and 5.76 to write

$$v_{2n} = \frac{(-1)^n}{12} \left[\nabla^{2n} \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{d}{dr} (r^3 E_L) \right) \right]_{r=0} \quad (5.115)$$

$$h_{2n} = \frac{(-1)^n}{6} \left[\nabla^{2n} \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{d}{dr} (r^3 E_C) \right) \right]_{r=0} \quad (5.116)$$

5.4.3 Nonhelical velocity field

5.4.3.1 The evolution equation for the longitudinal correlation function

Assuming the velocity field is nonhelical ($E_C = 0$), the procedure outlined in section 5.4.2 gives us the following evolution equation for the longitudinal correlation function of the magnetic field:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial M_L}{\partial t} = & \frac{1}{r^4} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left([\kappa(r) + \tau_c \kappa_\tau(r)] r^4 \frac{\partial M_L}{\partial r} \right) + [G(r) + \tau_c G_\tau(r)] M_L \\ & + \tau_c A(r) \frac{\partial M_L}{\partial r} + 2\tau_c \left(\eta g_3 \frac{dS_2}{dr} + \frac{g}{r^4} \frac{d(r^4 S_2^2)}{dr} \right) \frac{\partial^3 M_L}{\partial r^3} \\ & + \tau_c g S_2^2(r) \frac{\partial^4 M_L}{\partial r^4} \end{aligned} \quad (5.117)$$

where we have defined

$$g \equiv g_1 + g_2 - \frac{g_3}{2} \quad (5.118)$$

$$S_2(r) \equiv 2(E_L(0) - E_L(r)) \quad (5.119)$$

$$\kappa(r) \equiv 2\eta + E_L(0) - E_L(r) \quad (5.120)$$

$$G(r) \equiv -\frac{d^2 E_L}{dr^2} - \frac{4}{r} \frac{dE_L}{dr} \quad (5.121)$$

The expressions for κ_τ , G_τ , and A are quite long, and so have been relegated to appendix 5.F.

In general, one obtains an additional term

$$-\frac{16}{r^3} (g_3\eta + g_2 E_L(0)) M_L(0) \left[\frac{dE_L}{dr} \right]_{r=0} \quad (5.122)$$

on the RHS of equation 5.117. We ignore this term since $E_L(r)$ is expected to have zero slope at the origin (appendix 5.E). If this term were nonzero, its $1/r^3$ dependence would always cause the τ_c expansion to break down at small enough r . This term seems to be related to the terms

$$\frac{16g_2 E_L(r) E'_L(r)}{r^3} - \frac{8g_3\eta S'_2(r)}{r^3} \quad (5.123)$$

in the expression for $G_\tau(r)$, in the sense that these arise from taking $r^{-3} \int_0^r r^2 \dots dr$ of the same terms in the expression for $M(r)$ (recall that $M_L(r)$ is related to $M(r)$ by equation 5.73; also see footnote 16). We have checked that the evolution equation for $M(r)$ itself does not contain any term involving $M(0)$.

Note that g_3 (equation 5.237c) is always 1/2. Further, by virtue of equation 4.98, it turns out that g (equation 5.118) is always zero. Taking these into account, equation 5.117 can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial M_L}{\partial t} = & \frac{1}{r^4} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left([\kappa(r) + \tau_c \kappa_\tau(r)] r^4 \frac{\partial M_L}{\partial r} \right) + [G(r) + \tau_c G_\tau(r)] M_L \\ & + \tau_c \eta \left[-\frac{4}{r^5} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^4 \frac{dS_2}{dr} \right) \frac{\partial M_L}{\partial r} + \frac{dS_2}{dr} \frac{\partial^3 M_L}{\partial r^3} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (5.124)$$

where κ , G , and S_2 are as defined in equations 5.120, 5.121, and 5.119 respectively, and

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa_\tau(r) = & g_2 \left[-8v_2 E_L(0) + (E'_L(r))^2 - \frac{1}{r^4} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^4 \frac{d(E_L^2)}{dr} \right) \right] \\ & - 4\eta v_2 + \frac{3\eta}{2r^4} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^4 \frac{dS_2}{dr} \right) + \frac{(S'_2(r))^2}{16} - \frac{1}{16r^4} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^4 \frac{d(S_2^2)}{dr} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (5.125)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_\tau(r) = g_2 & \left[-2E_L(r)E_L''''(r) - 6E_L'(r)E_L'''(r) - 4(E_L''(r))^2 \right. \\
& - \frac{16E_L(r)E_L'''(r)}{r} - \frac{40E_L'(r)E_L''(r)}{r} - \frac{16E_L(r)E_L''(r)}{r^2} \\
& \left. - \frac{16(E_L'(r))^2}{r^2} + \frac{16E_L(r)E_L'(r)}{r^3} \right] \\
& + \frac{\eta S_2''''(r)}{2} + \frac{4\eta S_2'''(r)}{r} + \frac{4\eta S_2''(r)}{r^2} - \frac{4\eta S_2'(r)}{r^3} - \frac{S_2(r)S_2''''(r)}{8} \\
& - \frac{3S_2'(r)S_2'''(r)}{8} - \frac{(S_2''(r))^2}{4} - \frac{S_2(r)S_2'''(r)}{r} - \frac{5S_2'(r)S_2''(r)}{2r} \\
& - \frac{S_2(r)S_2''(r)}{r^2} - \frac{(S_2'(r))^2}{r^2} + \frac{S_2(r)S_2'(r)}{r^3}
\end{aligned} \tag{5.126}$$

Note that g_2 is the only surviving parameter that depends on the form of the temporal correlation function.

5.4.3.2 Dimensionless form of the evolution equation

Given a wavenumber, k_f , and a diffusivity, E_0 , that characterize the scales of the velocity field, we change the temporal and spatial variables to

$$T \equiv E_0 k_f^2 t, \quad R \equiv k_f r \tag{5.127}$$

and define

$$\bar{\eta} \equiv \frac{\eta}{E_0}, \quad \bar{\tau} \equiv \tau_c k_f^2 E_0 \tag{5.128}$$

Equation 5.124 then becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial M_L}{\partial T} = \frac{1}{R^4} \frac{\partial}{\partial R} & \left([\tilde{\kappa}(R) + \bar{\tau} \tilde{\kappa}_\tau(R)] R^4 \frac{\partial M_L}{\partial R} \right) + [\tilde{G}(R) + \bar{\tau} \tilde{G}_\tau(R)] M_L \\
& + \bar{\tau} \bar{\eta} \left[-\frac{4}{R^5} \frac{d}{dR} \left(R^4 \frac{d\tilde{S}_2}{dR} \right) \frac{\partial M_L}{\partial R} + \frac{d\tilde{S}_2}{dR} \frac{\partial^3 M_L}{\partial R^3} \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{5.129a}$$

where

$$\tilde{S}_2(R) \equiv \frac{S_2(r)}{E_0} \tag{5.129b}$$

$$\tilde{\kappa}(R) \equiv \frac{\kappa(r)}{E_0} \tag{5.129c}$$

$$\tilde{G}(R) \equiv \frac{G(r)}{k_f^2 E_0} \tag{5.129d}$$

$$\tilde{\kappa}_\tau(R) \equiv \frac{\kappa_\tau(r)}{k_f^2 E_0^2} \tag{5.129e}$$

$$\tilde{G}_\tau(R) \equiv \frac{G_\tau(r)}{k_f^4 E_0^2} \tag{5.129f}$$

5.4.3.3 Comparison of the white-noise limit with previous results

Our evolution equation for the longitudinal correlation function (equation 5.117) agrees with that derived by Schekochihin, Boldyrev, and Kulsrud (2002, eq. 56) on setting $\tau_c = 0$. Accounting for the fact that Vainshtein and Kichatinov (1986, eq. 10) and Subramanian (1997) use a slightly different definition of the longitudinal correlation function of the velocity field (such that their $T_{LL, \text{VK86}} = E_L/2$), we also find that our equations are consistent with theirs (Vainshtein and Kichatinov 1986, eqs. 26–27; Subramanian 1997, eqs. 24–25).²⁰

5.4.3.4 Comparison of the $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ corrections with previous results

Bhat and Subramanian (2014, eq. 17) have derived an evolution equation for the longitudinal correlation of the magnetic field in a homogeneous, isotropic, and nonhelical renovating flow (explicitly neglecting $\mathcal{O}(\eta\tau_c)$ terms which we have retained). They use the Taylor expansion $f(\tau) = f(0) + \tau df/dt + \mathcal{O}(\tau^2)$ to evaluate the time derivative of a correlation function of the magnetic field (denoted here as f), given an expression for $f(\tau)$ in terms of $f(0)$ (see the discussions above equations 3.11 and 3.21 of Bhat and Subramanian 2015). However, the error in such an estimate of df/dt is proportional to $\tau d^2f/dt^2$, i.e. their final evolution equation misses some $\mathcal{O}(\tau)$ terms. The effect of this is similar to neglecting the second term on the RHS of our equation 5.217. This term is responsible for all the terms dependent on g_3 in section 5.4.2.3. Dropping these terms corresponds to setting $g = g_1 + g_2$ (which is nonzero) in equation 5.117. This suggests the reason for $\partial^4 M_L / \partial r^4$ appearing with a nonzero $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ coefficient in their final evolution equation, contrary to our result (equation 5.124). Additionally, they found no τ_c -dependent corrections to the coefficient of M_L , while we do.

Kleorin, Rogachevskii, and Sokoloff (2002, eq. 5) have also derived such an equation using a renovating flow, but without operator splitting (instead, they assume that the velocity field is Gaussian random).²¹ Just like us, they obtain τ_c -dependent corrections to the coefficient of M_L , and moreover do not obtain any terms dependent on $\partial^4 M_L / \partial r^4$. However, their coefficient of $\partial^3 M_L / \partial r^3$ seems to be independent of η , unlike in our case where the coefficient is $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c \eta)$.

5.4.4 Helical velocity field

5.4.4.1 The evolution equations

As in section 5.4.3, we recall that in general, $g_3 = 1/2$ (equation 5.237c) and $g = 0$ (by virtue of equation 4.98). When $E_C(r) \neq 0$, the procedure outlined in section

²⁰Subramanian (1997) points out a sign error in the equations given by Vainshtein and Kichatinov (1986).

²¹Note that Bhat and Subramanian (2014, p. 2) suggest that Kleorin, Rogachevskii, and Sokoloff (2002, cf. eq. B1) wrongly dropped some terms in a Taylor expansion.

5.4.2 gives us

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial M_L}{\partial t} = & \frac{1}{r^4} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left((\kappa + \tau_c \kappa_\tau) r^4 \frac{\partial M_L}{\partial r} \right) + (G + \tau_c G_\tau) M_L \\ & - 4(\alpha + \tau_c \alpha_\tau) M_C + 8\tau_c \eta \frac{dE_L}{dr^2} \frac{\partial M_C}{\partial r} \end{aligned} \quad (5.130)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & + \tau_c \eta \left[-\frac{4}{r^5} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^4 \frac{dS_2}{dr} \right) \frac{\partial M_L}{\partial r} + \frac{dS_2}{dr} \frac{\partial^3 M_L}{\partial r^3} \right] \\ \frac{\partial M_C}{\partial t} = & \frac{1}{r^4} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^4 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[(\kappa + \tau_c \kappa_\tau) M_C + (\alpha + \tau_c \alpha_\tau) M_L \right] \right) \\ & + \tau_c \eta \left[A_0^{(L)} M_C + A_1^{(L)} \frac{\partial M_C}{\partial r} - 2 \frac{d^2 E_L}{dr^2} \frac{\partial^2 M_C}{\partial r^2} \right. \\ & - 2 \frac{dE_L}{dr} \frac{\partial^3 M_C}{\partial r^3} + A_0^{(C)} M_L + A_1^{(C)} \frac{\partial M_L}{\partial r} \\ & \left. + \left(-4 \frac{d^2 E_C}{dr^2} - \frac{8}{r} \frac{dE_C}{dr} \right) \frac{\partial^2 M_L}{\partial r^2} - 2 \frac{dE_C}{dr} \frac{\partial^3 M_L}{\partial r^3} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (5.131)$$

where κ , G , and S_2 are as defined in equations 5.120, 5.121, and 5.119 respectively, and

$$\alpha(r) \equiv E_C(0) - E_C(r) \quad (5.132)$$

$$\kappa_\tau(r) \equiv \kappa_\tau^{(nh)}(r) + 4g_2 [E_C^2(r) - E_C^2(0)] + \frac{\alpha^2(r)}{4} \quad (5.133)$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_\tau(r) \equiv & \left[\frac{1}{r^4} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^4 \frac{d\kappa_\tau}{dr} \right) \right]_{\eta=0} \\ & + 2\eta \left(\frac{d^4 E_L}{dr^4} + \frac{8}{r} \frac{d^3 E_L}{dr^3} + \frac{8}{r^2} \frac{d^2 E_L}{dr^2} - \frac{8}{r^3} \frac{dE_L}{dr} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (5.134)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_\tau(r) \equiv & -g_2 \left[4h_2 E_L(0) + 8v_2 E_C(0) + 2 \frac{d^2}{dr^2} (E_C E_L) + \frac{8}{r} \frac{d}{dr} (E_C E_L) \right] \\ & - 2\eta h_2 + \frac{\eta}{2} \frac{d^2 \alpha}{dr^2} + \frac{2\eta}{r} \frac{d\alpha}{dr} - \frac{1}{8} \frac{d^2}{dr^2} (S_2 \alpha) - \frac{1}{2r} \frac{d}{dr} (S_2 \alpha) \end{aligned} \quad (5.135)$$

$$A_0^{(L,C)} \equiv 4 \frac{d^4 E_{L,C}}{dr^4} + \frac{24}{r} \frac{d^3 E_{L,C}}{dr^3} + \frac{16}{r^2} \frac{d^2 E_{L,C}}{dr^2} - \frac{16}{r^3} \frac{dE_{L,C}}{dr} \quad (5.136)$$

$$A_1^{(L,C)} \equiv 6 \frac{d^3 E_{L,C}}{dr^3} + \frac{24}{r} \frac{d^2 E_{L,C}}{dr^2} + \frac{16}{r^2} \frac{dE_{L,C}}{dr} \quad (5.137)$$

with $\kappa_\tau^{(nh)}$ being the corresponding term appearing in the nonhelical case (equation 5.124).

Similar to the nonhelical case, one obtains extra terms (not indicated above) which are zero if $E_C(r)$ and $E_L(r)$ have zero slope at the origin. As discussed in appendix 5.E, a sufficient condition for this is that there exists some wavenumber beyond which the energy and helicity spectra decay exponentially.

5.4.4.2 Comparison of the white-noise limit with previous work

As in the nonhelical case, accounting for the fact that Vainshtein and Kichatinov (1986, eq. 10) and Subramanian (1997) use slightly different definitions for the correlation functions of the velocity field (such that their $T_{LL, \text{VK86}} = E_L/2$ and $C_{\text{VK86}} = E_C/2$), we find that when $\tau_c = 0$, our equations 5.130 and 5.131 are consistent with theirs (Vainshtein and Kichatinov 1986, eqs. 26–27; Subramanian 1997, eqs. 24–25).²² Further, our equations are consistent with the assertion by Vainshtein and Kichatinov (1986) that the non-resistive $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ corrections do not change the forms of the evolution equations for M_L and M_C .

5.4.4.3 Conservation of magnetic helicity

As a sanity check, we follow Subramanian (1997, pp. 9–10) and verify that the equations we have derived are consistent with the conservation of magnetic helicity. Using equation 5.83, the evolution equations for the magnetic helicity (say $H(t)$) and $M_C(r, t)$ can be related as

$$\frac{dH}{dt} = 2 \int_0^\infty dr r \frac{\partial M_C(r, t)}{\partial t} \quad (5.138)$$

Motivated by appendix 5.E, we assume that near $r = 0$, we can expand

$$E_L(r) = C_1 + C_2 r^2 + \mathcal{O}(r^4) \quad (5.139)$$

$$E_C(r) = C_3 + C_4 r^2 + \mathcal{O}(r^4) \quad (5.140)$$

$$M_L(r, t) = C_5(t) + C_6(t) r^2 + \mathcal{O}(r^4) \quad (5.141)$$

$$M_C(r, t) = C_7(t) + C_8(t) r^2 + \mathcal{O}(r^4) \quad (5.142)$$

Substituting equation 5.131 into the RHS of equation 5.138; using the above; further using equations 5.115 and 5.116 for v_2 and h_2 ; and recalling that the current helicity is given by $H_J(t) \equiv 6M_C(0, t)$ (equation 5.79), we find that

$$\frac{dH}{dt} = -2\eta H_J \quad (5.143)$$

Note that all the $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ terms in this particular equation have disappeared in the $r \rightarrow 0$ limit. This is gratifying, as the usual derivation of the above equation (e.g. Brandenburg and Subramanian 2005b, section 3.4) makes no assumptions about the correlation time of the velocity field.

²²Subramanian (1997) points out a sign error in the equations given by Vainshtein and Kichatinov (1986).

5.5 Effects of nonzero correlation time at high Pr_m

5.5.1 Simplified evolution equation

We model $E_L(r) = E_0 \exp(-k_f^2 r^2/2)$.²³ We then find that (see equation 5.115)

$$v_2 = \frac{5k_f^2 E_0}{4} \quad (5.144)$$

In what follows, we work with the scaled variables and parameters defined in equations 5.127 and 5.128 (section 5.4.3.2). The evolution equation for M_L is then equation 5.129a.

To simplify the equation, we further assume that $\text{Rm} \gg 1$, so that the magnetic field grows the fastest on scales much smaller than the integral scale (i.e. $R \ll 1$). We thus expand all the coefficients as series in R and discard $\mathcal{O}(RM_L)$ terms (where $\partial M_L/\partial R \sim \mathcal{O}(R^{-1}M_L)$). Equation 5.129a then becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial M_L}{\partial T} = & \frac{1}{R^4} \frac{\partial}{\partial R} \left([\tilde{\kappa}(R) + \bar{\tau}\tilde{\kappa}_\tau(R)] R^4 \frac{\partial M_L}{\partial R} \right) + [\tilde{G}(R) + \bar{\tau}\tilde{G}_\tau(R)] M_L \\ & + \bar{\tau} \left(28\bar{\eta}R - \frac{40\bar{\eta}}{R} \right) \frac{\partial M_L}{\partial R} + \bar{\tau}\bar{\eta} (2R - R^3) \frac{\partial^3 M_L}{\partial R^3} \end{aligned} \quad (5.145)$$

with

$$\tilde{\kappa}(R) = \frac{R^2}{2} + 2\bar{\eta} \quad (5.146)$$

$$\tilde{G}(R) = 5 \quad (5.147)$$

$$\tilde{\kappa}_\tau(R) = 10\bar{\eta} - R^2 \left(\frac{21\bar{\eta}}{2} + 13g_2 + \frac{3}{2} \right) \quad (5.148)$$

$$\tilde{G}_\tau(R) = -35\bar{\eta} - 130g_2 - 15 \quad (5.149)$$

5.5.2 A heuristic perturbative treatment

We now solve equation 5.145 using the same heuristic method as Bhat and Subramanian (2014, p. 4). For simplicity, we assume the velocity field is exponentially correlated ($g_2 = 1/8$; table 4.1).

The first step is to set $\eta = 0$ and assume $M_L(r) \propto R^{-\lambda} \exp(\gamma T)$. Such a power law solution is only expected to hold at scales larger than the resistive scale but much smaller than the integral scale. Note that the general solution to equation 5.145 (with $\eta = 0$) is actually of the form $r^{-\lambda} (C_1 + C_2 \log(R))$. We do not see any obvious justification for discarding the $\log(R)$ term, since $R^{a+b\bar{\tau}} = R^a (1 + b\bar{\tau} \log(R) + \mathcal{O}(\bar{\tau}^2))$. However, it turns out that the growth rate and the

²³Since equation 5.124 contains fourth-order derivatives of E_L , this is different from simply taking $E_L(r) = E_L(0) (1 - k_f^2 r^2/2)$.

spectral slope obtained through this method are consistent with those obtained in the WKB approximation (to be described in section 5.5.3).

Ploughing ahead with the power-law ansatz, equation 5.145 becomes a quadratic equation for λ :²⁴

$$\frac{\lambda^2}{2} - \frac{5\lambda}{2} + \bar{\tau} \left(-\frac{25\lambda^2}{8} + \frac{125\lambda}{8} - \frac{125}{4} \right) + 5 = \gamma \quad (5.150)$$

While the above seems to suggest that $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$ as $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$, the eigenmodes need to satisfy certain boundary conditions.²⁵ Following Gruzinov, Cowley, and Sudan (1996, p. 2), we estimate the growth rate by taking the extremum²⁶ of the $\gamma(\lambda)$ curve.

Since equation 5.150 results from a series expansion in $\bar{\tau}$, we need to solve it perturbatively (order by order). When $\bar{\tau} = 0$, we find $\gamma = 15/8$, for which $\lambda = 5/2$. Plugging this value of λ into the $\mathcal{O}(\bar{\tau})$ terms, we obtain

$$\gamma = \frac{15}{8} - \frac{375}{32} \bar{\tau}, \quad \lambda = \frac{5}{2} \quad (5.151)$$

Note that when $\bar{\tau} = 0$, this agrees with equation 5.64.²⁷ In agreement with Bhat and Subramanian (2014) and Carteret, Schleicher, and Schober (2023), we find that the Kazantsev spectrum is unaffected, at least when $\bar{\tau}$ is small. This seems to be a general feature of the perturbative method we are using; any $\mathcal{O}(\bar{\tau})$ correction only changes the value of γ at the extremum, but not the position of the extremum.

5.5.3 WKB treatment

In the heuristic treatment described above (section 5.5.2), the boundary conditions were accounted for in a fashion whose justification is unclear to us. Here, we describe a more rigorous WKB treatment (following Carteret, Schleicher, and Schober 2023, appendix C).

5.5.3.1 Elimination of higher derivatives

To apply the WKB method, we need to express the derivatives of order greater than two in equation 5.145 in terms of lower derivatives. Since such higher derivatives

²⁴Bhat and Subramanian (2014) had to use a perturbative approach to eliminate the third and fourth spatial derivatives of $M_L(r, t)$. Since we do not have a fourth derivative in equation 5.124, and the third derivative only appears multiplied with η , such an approach is not necessary here. However, we use their approach in section 5.5.3, where we keep $\eta \neq 0$.

²⁵Since our ansatz for $M_L(r)$ blows up at $r = 0$ regardless of the value of λ , it is not clear what boundary conditions should be appealed to. Despite not understanding the argument given by Gruzinov, Cowley, and Sudan (1996, p. 2), we shall proceed with their method, following Bhat and Subramanian (2014) and Carteret, Schleicher, and Schober (2023). A detailed WKB analysis (section 5.5.3) turns out to give the same answer as this method, so we feel reluctant to completely dismiss it.

²⁶This actually turns out to be a minimum.

²⁷Recall that setting $k_f = E_0 = 1$ implies $v_2 = 5/4$.

only appear multiplied by $\bar{\tau}$, one can use the ‘Landau-Lifshitz’ approach (Landau and Lifshitz 1980, sec. 75; Bhat and Subramanian 2014, p. 4) and eliminate them perturbatively as follows. Assuming $M_L(r, t) = \widetilde{M}_L(R) \exp(\gamma T)$, setting $\bar{\tau} = 0$, and taking derivatives wrt. R of equation 5.145, we obtain an expression for the third derivative of \widetilde{M}_L in terms of the lower-order derivatives. Substituting this expression in equation 5.145 and discarding $\mathcal{O}(\bar{\eta}^2)$ terms, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[2\bar{\eta} + \frac{R^2}{2} + \bar{\tau} \left(-6\bar{\eta} + R^2 \left(-\frac{5\bar{\eta}}{2} - 13g_2 - \frac{3}{2} \right) \right) \right] \frac{d^2 \widetilde{M}_L}{dR^2} \\ & + \left[\frac{8\bar{\eta}}{R} + 3R + \bar{\tau} \left(\frac{\bar{\eta}(4\gamma - 32)}{R} + R(\bar{\eta}(-2\gamma - 19) - 78g_2 - 9) \right) \right] \frac{d\widetilde{M}_L}{dR} \\ & + [5 - \gamma + \bar{\tau}(-35\bar{\eta} - 130g_2 - 15)] \widetilde{M}_L(R) = 0 \quad (5.152) \end{aligned}$$

5.5.3.2 Change of variables

We change the variable of differentiation to

$$x \equiv \log(R/\sqrt{\bar{\eta}}) \quad (5.153)$$

with $\Upsilon(x) \equiv \widetilde{M}_L(R)$ and obtain

$$A_2(x) \frac{d^2 \Upsilon}{dx^2} + A_1(x) \frac{d\Upsilon}{dx} + A_0(x) \Upsilon(x) = 0 \quad (5.154)$$

with

$$A_0(x) \equiv 5 - \gamma + \bar{\tau}(-35\bar{\eta} - 130g_2 - 15) \quad (5.155a)$$

$$A_1(x) \equiv \frac{5}{2} + 6e^{-2x} + \bar{\tau} \left(-\bar{\eta} \left[2\gamma + \frac{33}{2} \right] - 65g_2 + 4\gamma e^{-2x} - \frac{15}{2} - 26e^{-2x} \right) \quad (5.155b)$$

$$A_2(x) \equiv \frac{1}{2} + 2e^{-2x} + \bar{\tau} \left(-\frac{5\bar{\eta}}{2} - 13g_2 - \frac{3}{2} - 6e^{-2x} \right) \quad (5.155c)$$

5.5.3.3 Conversion to Schrödinger-like form

Further substituting $\Upsilon(x) = \beta(x) \Theta(x)$, we find that imposing

$$\frac{d\beta}{dx} = -\beta(x) \frac{A_1(x)}{2A_2(x)} \quad (5.156)$$

gives us

$$\frac{d^2 \Theta}{dx^2} + p(x) \Theta(x) = 0 \quad (5.157)$$

with

$$p(x) \equiv \frac{A_0(x)}{A_2(x)} - \frac{A_1^2(x)}{4A_2^2(x)} + \frac{A_1(x)}{2A_2^2(x)} \frac{dA_2}{dx} - \frac{1}{2A_2(x)} \frac{dA_1}{dx} \quad (5.158)$$

The WKBJ solutions for $\Theta(x)$ are then

$$\Theta(x) \propto |p(x)|^{-1/4} \exp\left(\pm i \int^x \sqrt{p(x)} dx\right) \quad (5.159)$$

5.5.3.4 Asymptotic solution at $x \rightarrow -\infty$

We first note that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow -\infty} \frac{A_1(x)}{A_2(x)} = 3 + \mathcal{O}(\tau_c) \quad (5.160)$$

Equation 5.156 then implies

$$\beta(x) \propto e^{-3x/2 + \mathcal{O}(\tau_c)}, \quad x \rightarrow -\infty \quad (5.161)$$

Physically, we expect $\widetilde{M}_L(r) = \Upsilon(x)$ to approach a constant value as $r \rightarrow 0$ ($x \rightarrow -\infty$). Since

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow -\infty} p(x) = -\frac{9}{4} + \mathcal{O}(\tau_c) \quad (5.162)$$

we need to pick the $\exp(-i \int \dots)$ branch, which gives us

$$\Theta(x) \propto e^{3x/2 + \mathcal{O}(\tau_c)}, \quad x \rightarrow -\infty \quad (5.163)$$

5.5.3.5 Asymptotic solution at $x \rightarrow \infty$

On the other hand, at $x \rightarrow \infty$, equation 5.145 (which we used to derive equation 5.152) becomes invalid, and so we have to go back to equation 5.129a. Replacing $E_L(r \neq 0) = 0$, setting $\bar{\tau} = 0$, and taking $M_L(r, t) = \widetilde{M}_L(R) \exp(\gamma T)$, equation 5.129a reduces to

$$(1 + 2\bar{\eta}) \frac{d^2 \widetilde{M}_L}{dR^2} + \frac{4(1 + 2\bar{\eta})}{R} \frac{d\widetilde{M}_L}{dR} - \gamma \widetilde{M}_L(R) = 0 \quad (5.164)$$

$p(x)$ (equation 5.158) is then given by

$$p(x) = -\frac{\bar{\eta}\gamma}{2\bar{\eta} + 1} e^{2x} + \mathcal{O}(1, x \rightarrow \infty) \quad (5.165)$$

We have (setting $\tau_c = 0$)

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{A_1(x)}{A_2(x)} = 3 \quad (5.166)$$

This implies

$$\beta(x) \propto e^{-3x/2}, \quad x \rightarrow \infty \quad (5.167)$$

Recall that equation 5.145 (the evolution equation which we are analysing) is valid when $\text{Rm} \gg 1$. It is thus reasonable to assume $\gamma > 0$ (i.e. that there exists a growing solution). Since we require $\widetilde{M}_L(r) \equiv \beta(x) \Theta(x)$ to approach zero as $r \rightarrow \infty$ ($x \rightarrow \infty$), we need to pick the $\exp(+i \int \dots)$ branch, which gives us

$$\Theta(x) \propto \exp\left(-e^x \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\eta}\gamma}{2\bar{\eta} + 1}}\right), \quad x \rightarrow \infty \quad (5.168)$$

5.5.3.6 Connection formulae

Above, we saw that different solution branches need to be chosen at $\pm\infty$ in order to satisfy the boundary conditions. This means we must have a turning point. Since $\lim_{x \rightarrow -\infty} p(x) < 0$ and $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} p(x) < 0$, there must be at least two turning points (say x_1 and x_2), between which $p(x) > 0$.

Let us write the general solution as

$$\Theta(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{C_1}{|p|^{1/4}} e^{-i \int_{x_1}^x \sqrt{p} dx} & x < x_1 \\ \frac{C_+}{|p|^{1/4}} e^{i \int_{x_1}^x \sqrt{p} dx} + \frac{C_-}{|p|^{1/4}} e^{-i \int_{x_1}^x \sqrt{p} dx} & x_1 < x < x_2 \\ \frac{C_2}{|p|^{1/4}} e^{i \int_{x_2}^x \sqrt{p} dx} & x_2 < x \end{cases} \quad (5.169)$$

and number the regions above as I, II, and III respectively. Going from II to I, we find (see Landau and Lifshitz 1977, sec. 47)

$$C_1 = C_+ e^{-i\pi/4} = C_- e^{i\pi/4} \quad (5.170)$$

We thus write

$$\Theta(x) = \frac{C_1 \sqrt{2}}{|p|^{1/4}} \cos\left(\int_{x_1}^x \sqrt{p} dx\right), \quad x_1 < x < x_2 \quad (5.171)$$

Now, considering this near x_2 , defining $P \equiv \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \sqrt{p} dx$, and going from II to III, we find

$$C_2 = C_+ e^{iP+i\pi/4} = C_- e^{-iP-i\pi/4} \quad (5.172)$$

Recalling that $C_1 = C_+ e^{-i\pi/4}$, we write the first equality above as

$$C_2 = C_1 e^{iP+i\pi/2} \quad (5.173)$$

By requiring that C_1 and C_2 be real, we find that we need

$$\int_{x_1}^{x_2} \sqrt{p(x)} dx = \frac{(2n+1)\pi}{2} \quad (5.174)$$

where n can be any nonnegative integer.

5.5.3.7 Estimate of the growth rate

If we are interested in scales much above the resistive scale (but still below the integral scale, since we have already assumed $R \ll 1$), we can assume $e^{-2x} \ll 1$. We thus expand $p(x)$ (equation 5.158) about $x = \infty$ and neglect $\mathcal{O}(e^{-2x}, x \rightarrow \infty)$ terms. In what follows, we define

$$\Delta \equiv x_2 - x_1 = \log(R_2/R_1) > 0 \quad (5.175)$$

where R_1 and R_2 are the values of R corresponding to x_1 and x_2 . The square of the integral on the RHS of equation 5.174 can then be estimated as²⁸

$$\left(\int_{x_1}^{x_2} \sqrt{p(x)} dx \right)^2 = \frac{\Delta^2 (15 - 8\gamma + \bar{\tau}\gamma(-208g_2 - 24))}{4} \quad (5.176)$$

Squaring both sides of equation 5.174, choosing $n = 0$,²⁹ and iteratively solving for γ , we find

$$\gamma = \frac{15}{8} - \bar{\tau} \left(\frac{195g_2}{4} + \frac{45}{8} \right) + \mathcal{O}(\Delta^{-2}) + \mathcal{O}(\bar{\tau}^2) \quad (5.177)$$

If the velocity field's temporal correlation function is exponential,³⁰ the growth rate obtained above matches that in equation 5.151.

5.5.3.8 WKBJ solution for the correlation function

As in the estimation of the growth rate, we assume $e^{-2x} \ll 1$ and thus neglect $\mathcal{O}(e^{-2x}, x \rightarrow \infty)$ terms below. This allows us to write

$$\int_{x_1}^x \sqrt{p(x)} dx = \frac{\pi(x - x_1)}{2\Delta} + \mathcal{O}(\bar{\tau}^2) + \mathcal{O}(e^{-2x}, x \rightarrow \infty) \quad (5.178)$$

$$p(x) = \frac{\pi^2}{4\Delta^2} + \mathcal{O}(\bar{\tau}^2) + \mathcal{O}(e^{-2x}, x \rightarrow \infty) \quad (5.179)$$

Equation 5.171 then implies that for $x_1 < x < x_2$, we have

$$\Theta(x) \propto \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2\Delta} \log(R/R_1) + \mathcal{O}(\bar{\tau}^2)\right) \quad (5.180)$$

Using equation 5.177 for γ and recalling the definitions of A_1 (equation 5.155b) and A_2 (equation 5.155c), we write

$$\frac{A_1(x)}{A_2(x)} = 5 + \bar{\eta}\bar{\tau} \left(\frac{\pi^2}{2\Delta^2} - \frac{31}{2} \right) + \mathcal{O}(\bar{\tau}^2) \quad (5.181)$$

²⁸While estimating the integral, it is convenient to change the variable of integration to $y \equiv \exp(-2x)$ (such that $y = \bar{\eta}/R^2$).

²⁹The value of n only affects the $\mathcal{O}(\Delta^{-2})$ corrections to the growth rate.

³⁰ $g_1 = g_2 = 1/8$ (see table 4.1), and $g_3 = 1/2$.

Equation 5.156 then tells us that

$$\beta(x) = \exp\{-[5/2 + \mathcal{O}(\bar{\eta}\bar{\tau})]x\} \propto R^{-5/2 + \mathcal{O}(\bar{\eta}\bar{\tau})} \quad (5.182)$$

Recalling that $M_L(r) = \beta(x) \Theta(x) e^{\gamma T}$, we write

$$M_L(r, t) = e^{\gamma T} R^{-5/2} \cos\left(\frac{\pi \log(R/R_1)}{2 \log(R_2/R_1)}\right), \quad R_1 \ll R \ll R_2 \quad (5.183)$$

where γ is given by equation 5.177.

5.5.3.9 Estimates of the turning points

Recall that equation 5.145 (which we are analysing) is valid only for $R \ll 1$. Further, our act of linearizing in $\bar{\eta}$ while substituting for the higher derivatives means that we require $R \gg \sqrt{\bar{\eta}}$. Carteret, Schleicher, and Schober (2023, appendix C) assume these scales are good estimates for the turning points, i.e.

$$R_1 \approx \sqrt{\bar{\eta}} \quad (5.184a)$$

$$R_2 \approx 1 \quad (5.184b)$$

Under these assumptions, we have

$$\Delta \approx -\frac{\log \bar{\eta}}{2} \sim \frac{\log \text{Rm}}{2} \quad (5.185)$$

where we have used the relation between $\bar{\eta}$ and Rm , given in appendix 5.B. These estimates suggest that the neglected $\mathcal{O}(\Delta^{-2})$ terms in equation 5.177 for γ become small when $(\log \text{Rm})^2 \gg 1$.

To convince oneself of these estimates, it is helpful to plot $p(x)$. However, as noted earlier, the approach we used to derive $p(x)$ above becomes invalid as $x \rightarrow \infty$. To find an expression for $p(x)$ that is valid for arbitrary x , we need to go back to the general evolution equation (equation 5.129a), and rewrite it in WKBJ form following the same procedure as we did for its high- Pr_m limit: substitute our chosen form for $E_L(r)$; assume the solution grows exponentially with time; use the Landau-Lifshitz approximation to eliminate the third derivative; and then use equation 5.158 to obtain an expression for $p(x)$ that is valid for all x . To evaluate this expression for given Rm and St , we use equation 5.177 for the growth rate, and assume the temporal correlation function is exponential. Since our estimate for the growth rate depends on Δ (which itself depends on the roots of $p(x)$), the obtained expression for $p(x)$ contains Δ as a parameter. Figure 5.1 shows $p(x)$ for different choices of Δ . We find that regardless of the choice of Δ , the two turning points of $p(x)$ scale like the resistive and the integral scales respectively for high-enough Rm . This justifies estimating the turning points according to equations 5.184.

Figure 5.1: The WKB coefficient, $p(x)$, as a function of x for various combinations of Rm and St . Each panel shows a different choice for Δ . Recall that the resistive and the integral scales correspond to $-2x/\log(\bar{\eta}) = 0, 1$ respectively.

5.5.3.10 Validity of the WKB approximation

As pointed out by Carteret, Schleicher, and Schober (2023, eq. C16), substituting equation 5.159 into equation 5.157 gives us

$$\frac{d^2\Theta}{dx^2} = -p(x)\Theta(x) \left(1 + \frac{p''(x)}{4[p(x)]^2} - \frac{5[p'(x)]^2}{16[p(x)]^3} \right) \quad (5.186)$$

Comparing this with equation 5.157, we find the following consistency condition for the validity of the WKB approximation:³¹

$$\epsilon \equiv \left| \frac{p''(x)}{4[p(x)]^2} - \frac{5[p'(x)]^2}{16[p(x)]^3} \right| \ll 1 \quad (5.187)$$

Note that a similar condition has been given by Northover (1969, eq. 31).

The LHS of this condition (ϵ) is dependent on x . Carteret, Schleicher, and Schober (2023, appendix C.3) evaluate it at the arithmetic mean of the resistive and the integral scales. However, judging from the form of $p(x)$ (figure 5.1), we believe it is more appropriate to choose the geometric mean of the resistive and the integral scales (i.e. the arithmetic mean of the logarithms of these scales; recall

³¹One of the numerical prefactors here is different from the corresponding factor mentioned by Carteret, Schleicher, and Schober (2023, eq. C16).

Figure 5.2: Plot of ϵ (the LHS of equation 5.187) as a function of Rm for different St . The panel on the left shows ϵ evaluated at $x = -\log(\bar{\eta})/4$ (the geometric mean of the integral and resistive scales); the panel on the right shows it at $x = \log[(1 + 1/\sqrt{\bar{\eta}})/2]$ (the choice made by Carteret, Schleicher, and Schober (2023, appendix C.3)).

that x is related to the logarithm of R through equation 5.153). In figure 5.2, we compare both these choices by using equations 5.155 and 5.158 to evaluate $p(x)$. Our choice seems much more conservative. Further, regardless of the choice made, increasing St decreases the value of Rm above which the WKB approximation becomes valid.

5.5.4 Growth rates for different temporal correlation functions

Let us now simplify the corrections to the growth rate for the two temporal correlation functions described in table 4.1. For exponential temporal correlation, equation 5.208 gives us $\bar{\tau} = 2\text{St}^2/3$. Equation 5.177 for the growth rate (which also assumes a particular form for $E_L(r)$) then becomes

$$\gamma = \frac{15}{8} - \frac{375}{32} \bar{\tau} = \gamma_0 \left(1 - \frac{25\text{St}^2}{6} \right) \approx \gamma_0 (1 - 4.2\text{St}^2) \quad (5.188)$$

On the other hand, for the top hat temporal correlation function, we have $\bar{\tau} = 4\text{St}^2/3$. The corresponding growth rate can be written as

$$\gamma = \frac{15}{8} - \frac{155}{16} \bar{\tau} = \gamma_0 \left(1 - \frac{155\text{St}^2}{12} \right) \approx \gamma_0 (1 - 12.9\text{St}^2) \quad (5.189)$$

5.5.5 Comparison with previous work

5.5.5.1 Non-resistive calculations

Schekochihin and Kulsrud (2001, eq. 85) have derived an expression for the growth rates of the single-point moments of the magnetic field at $\text{Pr}_m \gg 1$ when $\tau_c \neq 0$. Their result is superficially similar to ours, in that it contains constants parametrizing the temporal correlation properties of the velocity field. However, we note that they set $\eta = 0$ at the starting of their calculations,³² while we have taken the limit $\eta \rightarrow 0$ only towards the end. Even when $\tau_c = 0$, this is known to significantly affect the predicted growth rate (Kulsrud and Anderson 1992, eqs. 1.9, 1.16), and hence we do not expect our $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ corrections to match theirs.

For the sake of completeness, we note the correspondences between our formulae and theirs. Their equation 47 for the two-point correlation of the velocity field is

$$\begin{aligned} \langle u_i^{(\mathbf{x}+r, t+\tau)} u_j^{(\mathbf{x}, t)} \rangle &= \kappa_0^{(\tau)} \delta_{ij} - \frac{1}{2} \kappa_2^{(\tau)} [r^2 \delta_{ij} + 2a r_i r_j] \\ &+ \frac{1}{4} \kappa_4^{(\tau)} r^2 [r^2 \delta_{ij} + 2b r_i r_j] + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (5.190)$$

which is more general than the form we have assumed. Incompressibility can be imposed by choosing $a = -1/4$, $b = -2/5$. Specializing to three spatial dimensions, we obtain (see equation 5.73)

$$E_L(r) \mathfrak{D}(\tau) = \kappa_0 - \frac{r^2}{4} \kappa_2(\tau) + \frac{11r^4}{140} \kappa_4(\tau) + \dots \quad (5.191)$$

On the other hand, we have taken

$$E_L(r) = E_0 e^{-k_f^2 r^2 / 2} = E_0 \left(1 - \frac{k_f^2 r^2}{2} + \frac{k_f^4 r^4}{8} + \dots \right) \quad (5.192)$$

Comparing both these expressions, we write

$$\kappa_0(\tau) = E_0 \mathfrak{D}(\tau) \quad (5.193)$$

$$\kappa_2(\tau) = 2E_0 k_f^2 \mathfrak{D}(\tau) \quad (5.194)$$

$$\kappa_4(\tau) = \frac{35}{22} E_0 k_f^4 \mathfrak{D}(\tau) \quad (5.195)$$

which gives us $\bar{\kappa}_2 = 2E_0 k_f^2$. Using these, one may calculate the constants K_1 , K_2 , and \tilde{K}_2 appearing in their equation for the growth rate. Choosing units where $k_f = E_0 = 1$, their expression for the growth rate of the second moment in incompressible turbulence in three spatial dimensions gives

$$\gamma_{\text{SK01}} = 5 + \mathcal{O}(\bar{\tau}) \quad (5.196)$$

³²See the discussion in their endnote 40.

which is related to our result (equation 5.177) when $\bar{\tau} = 0$ by

$$\gamma_0 = \frac{3}{8} \gamma_{0,SK01} \quad (5.197)$$

This is exactly the expected relation between the resistive and non-resistive growth rates (Kulsrud and Anderson 1992, eqs. 1.9, 1.16). Since we have no reason to expect a neat relation between their $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c)$ corrections and ours, we shall not bother explicitly working out how they are related.

5.5.5.2 Renovating flows

In section 5.4.3.4, we commented on some differences between our evolution equation and that derived by Bhat and Subramanian (2014). We now turn our attention to the predicted growth rate. The velocity field they chose corresponds to the longitudinal correlation function (see Bhat and Subramanian 2014, eq. 12)³³

$$E_L^{\text{BS14}}(r) = \frac{A^2\tau}{6} \left[1 + \frac{1}{q^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} \right] j_0(qr) \quad (5.198)$$

where τ is the renovation time of the velocity field, q is a characteristic wavenumber, A is related to the amplitude of the velocity field, and j_0 is the spherical Bessel function of the first kind of order 0 (recall that $j_0(z) = \text{sinc}(z)$). We identify $q \equiv k_f$. Bhat and Subramanian (2014, p. 3) define

$$\eta_t \equiv \frac{E_L^{\text{BS14}}(0)}{2} = \frac{A^2\tau}{18} \quad (5.199)$$

$$\bar{\tau}^{\text{BS14}} \equiv \tau\eta_t q^2 = \frac{\bar{\tau}}{2} = \frac{2\text{St}^2}{3} \quad (5.200)$$

Note that for the last equality, we have used the relation between $\bar{\tau}$ to St corresponding to the temporal correlation function being a top hat (see equation 5.208). The growth rate found by Bhat and Subramanian (2014, p. 4) is

$$\gamma = \gamma_0 \left(1 - \frac{15\text{St}^2}{28} \right) \approx \gamma_0 (1 - 0.5\text{St}^2) \quad (5.201)$$

Note that the suppression of the growth rate here is much weaker than what we obtained earlier. It is unclear how much of this difference can be attributed to the fact that the longitudinal correlation function of the velocity field chosen by Bhat and Subramanian (2014) is different from that assumed by us.

Figure 5.3 compares the growth rates for various temporal correlation functions with the result reported by Bhat and Subramanian (2014).

³³We have accounted for the fact that their definition of the longitudinal correlation function differs from ours by a factor of 2 (see section 5.4.3.3).

Figure 5.3: Growth rate as a function of St for two different temporal correlation functions, along with the expression obtained by Bhat and Subramanian (2014, p. 4).

5.6 Conclusions

By assuming that the velocity field is an incompressible separable Gaussian random field, we have derived the Fourier-space evolution equation for the two-point correlation function of the magnetic field (section 5.4.1). Using the equation we derived and further assuming that the velocity field is nonhelical, we have derived the evolution equation for the longitudinal correlation function of the magnetic field (M_L) in configuration space, valid for arbitrary Pr_m and Rm (equation 5.124 in section 5.4.3). Unlike in previous work, setting $\eta = 0$ gives an evolution equation with at most two spatial derivatives of M_L .

By choosing an appropriate form for the longitudinal correlation function of the velocity field, we have studied the $Pr_m \gg 1$ limit (section 5.5). In agreement with previous work (Chandran 1997; Mason et al. 2011; Bhat and Subramanian 2014; Carteret, Schleicher, and Schober 2023; Schekochihin and Kulsrud 2001), we have found that the growth rate of the magnetic field decreases when the correlation time is nonzero. The growth rate is suppressed much more strongly than in the renovating flow model (Bhat and Subramanian 2014; Carteret, Schleicher, and Schober 2023). However, the corrections to the spectral slope of the magnetic field are still negligible when $Rm \gg 1$.

While our equation 5.124 can also be used to study the limit $Pr_m \ll 1$ (which has been studied in the white-noise case by, e.g. Vincenzi 2002; Arponen and Horvai 2007; Schober et al. 2012; and using a renovating model by Kleorin and Rogachevskii 2012), this seems to be more complicated than the calculations we have presented so far; we intend to do this in the future.

We have also derived the equations describing the evolution of the correlation functions of the magnetic field in a helical velocity field with nonzero correlation time (section 5.4.4). It would be interesting to see if a nonzero correlation time modifies the effects of kinetic helicity on the SSD (Malyshkin and Boldyrev 2007, 2010).

Equation 5.244 (appendix 5.C) can be used as a starting point to analytically study the effect of shear on the SSD; such effects have only been studied in simulations so far (Singh, Rogachevskii, and Brandenburg 2017). Work along this direction is in progress, and will be reported elsewhere.

Appendices to chapter 5

5.A Sheared coordinates

5.A.1 Fourier and configuration space

In a linear shear flow ($\mathbf{U} = (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{X}) \mathbf{S}$), the sheared coordinates (lowercase) are related to the normal coordinates (uppercase) by

$$\mathbf{x} = \exp(-t\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{a}) \cdot \mathbf{X} \quad (5.202a)$$

$$\mathbf{k} = \exp(t\mathbf{a} \otimes \mathbf{S}) \cdot \mathbf{K} \quad (5.202b)$$

If \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{K} are Fourier-conjugate, so are \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{k} .

5.A.2 Oblique axes

The sheared coordinates (equations 5.202) still use the same basis vectors as the lab frame. At the cost of introducing a nontrivial metric (and thus having to distinguish co- and contra-variant indices), it is possible to work in oblique axes (Singh 2022). Jingade and Singh (2020, eq. 14) have shown that this makes the induction equation look identical to that in the unsheared case.

5.A.3 Galilean invariance and homogeneity

When measured by an observer moving at a constant (and nonrelativistic) velocity wrt. the lab frame, the mean and fluctuating magnetic fields and the fluctuating velocity field are the same as in the lab frame (Galilean invariance; see Sridhar and Subramanian 2009, p. 5). Sridhar and Subramanian (2009, sec. IV.A) and Singh (2012, appendix B) show that Galilean invariance of any vector field implies homogeneity of its double-correlation in sheared coordinates. This holds regardless of whether one uses sheared basis vectors or the lab-frame ones.

5.A.4 Single-time correlations

In general, homogeneity in the sheared coordinates does not imply homogeneity in the unsheared coordinates, but this difference ceases to be relevant for single-time correlations. Consider a correlation which is homogeneous in the sheared

coordinates:

$$\langle w_i(\mathbf{x}, t) w_j(\mathbf{x}', t') \rangle = \langle w_i(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{y}, t) w_j(\mathbf{x}' + \mathbf{y}, t') \rangle \quad (5.203)$$

We define $v_i(\mathbf{X}, t) \equiv w_i(\mathbf{x}, t)$. By definition,

$$\langle v_i(\mathbf{X} + \mathbf{Y}, t) v_j(\mathbf{X}' + \mathbf{Y}, t') \rangle = \left\langle w_i(\mathbf{x} + e^{-t\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{a}} \cdot \mathbf{Y}, t) w_j(\mathbf{x}' + e^{-t'\mathbf{S} \otimes \mathbf{a}} \cdot \mathbf{Y}, t') \right\rangle \quad (5.204)$$

If $t = t'$, we obtain

$$\langle v_i(\mathbf{X} + \mathbf{Y}, t) v_j(\mathbf{X}' + \mathbf{Y}, t) \rangle = \langle v_i(\mathbf{X}, t) v_j(\mathbf{X}', t) \rangle \quad (5.205)$$

but in general,

$$\langle v_i(\mathbf{X} + \mathbf{Y}, t) v_j(\mathbf{X}' + \mathbf{Y}, t') \rangle \neq \langle v_i(\mathbf{X}, t) v_j(\mathbf{X}', t') \rangle \quad (5.206)$$

Note that the correlation need not be invariant under time translations.

5.B Dimensionless numbers for a separable velocity correlation function

Given a separable velocity correlation function (see equation 5.65) with longitudinal correlation function $E_L(r)$ and temporal correlation function $\mathfrak{D}(t)$, equation 5.85 can be written as

$$u_{\text{rms}}^2 = 3 E_L(0) \mathfrak{D}(0) \quad (5.207)$$

Let us assume the velocity correlation is characterized by a length scale $1/k_f$. We then write

$$\text{St} = \tau_c u_{\text{rms}} k_f = \tau_c k_f \sqrt{3 E_L(0) \mathfrak{D}(0)} \quad (5.208)$$

and

$$\text{Rm} = \frac{u_{\text{rms}}}{\eta k_f} = \frac{\sqrt{3 E_L(0) \mathfrak{D}(0)}}{\eta k_f} \quad (5.209)$$

For example, exponential temporal correlation (table 4.1) would give us

$$\tau_c = \frac{2 \text{St}^2}{3 k_f^2 E_L(0)}, \quad \eta = \frac{3 E_L(0)}{2 \text{Rm St}} \quad (5.210)$$

While the numerical factors above depend on the functional form of $\mathfrak{D}(t)$, we expect $\tau_c \sim \text{St}^2$ and $\eta \sim 1/(\text{Rm St})$ to always be valid. Schekochihin and Kulsrud (2001, eq. 95) and Bhat and Subramanian (2014, p. 3) agree that $\bar{\tau} \propto \text{St}^2$.

5.C Derivation of the Fourier-space evolution equation

We now simplify equation 5.23 neglecting $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c^2)$ terms, where τ_c is the correlation time of the velocity field (see the corresponding discussion for mean passive scalar diffusion in section 4.3).

5.C.1 Expression for the first functional derivative

Repeatedly applying equation 5.30, we write

$$\begin{aligned}
\left\langle \frac{\delta \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; \mathbf{k}', t)}}{\delta \tilde{w}_{i_1}} \right\rangle &= \int_{t^{(2)}, \mathbf{k}^{(2)}} \int_{t', \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}'} \Upsilon_{s;ij;mn}^{(\mathbf{p}'; \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'; \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}; t, t')} \left\langle \tilde{w}_m^{(\mathbf{p}, t')} \tilde{w}_{i_2} \right\rangle \left\langle \frac{\delta^2 \mathcal{B}_{sn}^{(\mathbf{p}', t'; \mathbf{q}, t')}}{\delta \tilde{w}_{i_1} \delta \tilde{w}_{i_2}} \right\rangle \\
&+ \int_{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}'} \Upsilon_{s;ij;i_1 n}^{(\mathbf{p}'; \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'; \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}; t, t^{(1)})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{sn}^{(\mathbf{p}', t^{(1)}; \mathbf{q}, t^{(1)})} \right\rangle \\
&= \int_{t^{(2)}, \mathbf{k}^{(2)}} \int_{t', \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}'} \left[\Upsilon_{s;ij;mn}^{(\mathbf{p}'; \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'; \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}; t, t')} \left\langle \tilde{w}_m^{(\mathbf{p}, t')} \tilde{w}_{i_2} \right\rangle \Upsilon_{r;sn;i_1 l}^{(\mathbf{p}''; \mathbf{p}', \mathbf{q}; \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}'; t', t^{(1)})} \right. \\
&\quad \left. \times \Upsilon_{a;rl;i_2 u}^{(\mathbf{p}'''; \mathbf{p}'', \mathbf{q}'; \mathbf{k}^{(2)}, \mathbf{q}'', t^{(1)}, t^{(2)})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{p}''', t^{(2)}; \mathbf{q}'', t^{(2)})} \right\rangle \right] \\
&+ \int_{t^{(2)}, \mathbf{k}^{(2)}} \int_{t', \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}'} \left[\Upsilon_{s;ij;mn}^{(\mathbf{p}'; \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'; \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}; t, t')} \left\langle \tilde{w}_m^{(\mathbf{p}, t')} \tilde{w}_{i_2} \right\rangle \Upsilon_{r;sn;i_2 l}^{(\mathbf{p}''; \mathbf{p}', \mathbf{q}; \mathbf{k}^{(2)}, \mathbf{q}'; t', t^{(2)})} \right. \\
&\quad \left. \times \Upsilon_{a;rl;i_1 u}^{(\mathbf{p}'''; \mathbf{p}'', \mathbf{q}'; \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}'', t^{(2)}, t^{(1)})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{p}''', t^{(1)}; \mathbf{q}'', t^{(1)})} \right\rangle \right] \\
&+ \int_{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}'} \Upsilon_{s;ij;i_1 n}^{(\mathbf{p}'; \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'; \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}; t, t^{(1)})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{sn}^{(\mathbf{p}', t^{(1)}; \mathbf{q}, t^{(1)})} \right\rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{5.211}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \tag{5.212}
\end{aligned}$$

where we have discarded terms which will lead to $\mathcal{O}(\tau_c^2)$ contributions (τ_c is the correlation time of the velocity field).

In what follows, we will assume that the velocity field is statistically homogeneous and separable (equation 5.65). We also expand (G is defined in equation 5.15)

$$G^{(\mathbf{k}, t, \tau)} = \left(1 - (t - \tau) \eta |\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{k}, t)}|^2 \right) \Theta^{(t-\tau)} + \mathcal{O}((t - \tau)^2) \tag{5.213}$$

and (A_{ijk} is defined in equation 5.25)

$$\begin{aligned}
A_{ijk}^{(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'; \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}; t, t')} &= \Theta^{(t-t')} \left[1 - (t - t') \eta |\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{k}, t)}|^2 - (t - t') \eta |\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{k}', t)}|^2 \right] \\
&\times \delta^{(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{ijk}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q})} + \mathcal{O}((t - \tau)^2)
\end{aligned} \tag{5.214}$$

where \mathcal{A}_{ijk} has been defined in equation 5.18. Defining

$$\Lambda_{s;ij;mn}^{(\mathbf{p}'; \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'; \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q})} \equiv \delta^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}')} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{q})} \delta_{is} \mathcal{A}_{jmn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q})} + \delta^{(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p}')} \delta^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{q})} \delta_{js} \mathcal{A}_{imn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q})} \tag{5.215}$$

we expand $\Upsilon_{s;ij;mn}$ (equation 5.29) as

$$\begin{aligned}
\Upsilon_{s;ij;mn}^{(\mathbf{p}'; \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'; \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}; t, t')} &= \Theta^{(t-t')} \left[1 - (t - t') \eta |\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{k}, t)}|^2 - (t - t') \eta |\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{k}', t)}|^2 \right] \\
&\times \Lambda_{s;ij;mn}^{(\mathbf{p}'; \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'; \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q})} + \mathcal{O}((t - \tau)^2)
\end{aligned} \tag{5.216}$$

Using equation 5.23 and then equations 5.65, 5.32, and 4.33a, we write

$$\langle \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k}, t'; \mathbf{k}', t')} \rangle = \langle \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; \mathbf{k}', t)} \rangle + (t' - t) \frac{\partial \langle \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; \mathbf{k}', t)} \rangle}{\partial t} \quad (5.217)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left[1 - (t' - t) \eta \left| \boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{k}, t)} \right|^2 - (t' - t) \eta \left| \boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{k}', t)} \right|^2 \right] \langle \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; \mathbf{k}', t)} \rangle \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} (t' - t) \int_{\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}'} \Lambda_{m;ij;rs}^{(\mathbf{p}'; \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'; \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q})} T_{ri_1}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{si_1n}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q} + \mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{mn}^{(\mathbf{p}', t; \mathbf{q} + \mathbf{p}, t)} \rangle \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} (t' - t) \int_{\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}'} \Lambda_{m;ij;rs}^{(\mathbf{p}'; \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'; \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q})} T_{ri_1}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{mi_1n}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}' + \mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{sn}^{(\mathbf{q}, t; \mathbf{p}' + \mathbf{p}, t)} \rangle \\ &\quad + (t' - t) \mathcal{O}(\tau_c) \end{aligned} \quad (5.218)$$

We now define

$$f_1^{(t, t^{(1)})} \equiv \int_{t'', t^{(2)}} \Theta^{(t-t'')} \mathfrak{D}^{(t''-t^{(2)})} \Theta^{(t''-t^{(1)})} \Theta^{(t^{(1)}-t^{(2)})} \quad (5.219)$$

$$f_2^{(t, t^{(1)})} \equiv \int_{t'', t^{(2)}} \Theta^{(t-t'')} \mathfrak{D}^{(t''-t^{(2)})} \Theta^{(t''-t^{(2)})} \Theta^{(t^{(2)}-t^{(1)})} \quad (5.220)$$

$$f_3^{(t, t^{(1)})} \equiv (t - t^{(1)}) \Theta^{(t-t^{(1)})} \quad (5.221)$$

and use equations 5.65, 5.218, 5.214, and 5.216 to write equation 5.212 as

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle \frac{\delta \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; \mathbf{k}', t)}}{\delta \tilde{w}_{i_1}} \right\rangle &= [\mathcal{T}^1] + [\mathcal{T}^2] + [\mathcal{T}^3] + [\mathcal{T}^4] + [\mathcal{T}^5] \\ &\quad + (t - t^{(1)}) \mathcal{O}(\tau_c) + \mathcal{O}\left([t - t^{(1)}]^2\right) \end{aligned} \quad (5.222)$$

where

$$[\mathcal{T}^1] \equiv f_1^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\substack{\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}' \\ \mathbf{q}', \mathbf{p}'' \\ \mathbf{q}'', \mathbf{p}'''}} \Lambda_{s;ij;mn}^{(\mathbf{p}'; \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'; \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \Lambda_{r;sn;i_1l}^{(\mathbf{p}'': \mathbf{p}', \mathbf{q}; \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}')} \Lambda_{a;rl;i_2u}^{(\mathbf{p}''': \mathbf{p}'', \mathbf{q}'; -\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}'')} \langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{p}''', t; \mathbf{q}'', t)} \rangle \quad (5.223)$$

$$[\mathcal{T}^2] \equiv f_2^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\substack{\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}' \\ \mathbf{q}', \mathbf{p}'' \\ \mathbf{q}'', \mathbf{p}'''}} \Lambda_{s;ij;mn}^{(\mathbf{p}'; \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'; \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \Lambda_{r;sn;i_2l}^{(\mathbf{p}'': \mathbf{p}', \mathbf{q}; -\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}')} \Lambda_{a;rl;i_1u}^{(\mathbf{p}''': \mathbf{p}'', \mathbf{q}'; \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}'')} \langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{p}''', t; \mathbf{q}'', t)} \rangle \quad (5.224)$$

$$\begin{aligned} [\mathcal{T}^3] &\equiv \int_{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}'} \left\{ \left[\Theta^{(t-t^{(1)})} + f_3^{(t, t^{(1)})} \eta \left(- \left| \boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{k}, t)} \right|^2 - \left| \boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{k}', t)} \right|^2 + \left| \boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{p}', t)} \right|^2 + \left| \boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{q}, t)} \right|^2 \right) \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. \times \Lambda_{s;ij;i_1n}^{(\mathbf{p}'; \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'; \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{sn}^{(\mathbf{p}', t; \mathbf{q}, t)} \rangle \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (5.225)$$

$$[\mathcal{T}^4] \equiv -\frac{1}{2} f_3^{(t,t^{(1)})} \int_{\substack{\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}', \mathbf{p}'' \\ \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}'}} \Lambda_{s;ij;i_1n}^{(\mathbf{p}'; \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'; \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q})} \Lambda_{m;sn;ra}^{(\mathbf{p}''; \mathbf{p}', \mathbf{q}; \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}')} T_{ri_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ai_2b}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}' + \mathbf{p})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{mb}^{(\mathbf{p}'', t; \mathbf{q}' + \mathbf{p}, t)} \right\rangle \quad (5.226)$$

$$[\mathcal{T}^5] \equiv -\frac{1}{2} f_3^{(t,t^{(1)})} \int_{\substack{\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}', \mathbf{p}'' \\ \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}'}} \Lambda_{s;ij;i_1n}^{(\mathbf{p}'; \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'; \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q})} \Lambda_{m;sn;ra}^{(\mathbf{p}''; \mathbf{p}', \mathbf{q}; \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}')} T_{ri_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{mi_2b}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}'' + \mathbf{p})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{ab}^{(\mathbf{q}', t; \mathbf{p}'' + \mathbf{p}, t)} \right\rangle \quad (5.227)$$

To simplify the above, we use the following results:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\substack{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}' \\ \mathbf{q}', \mathbf{p}''}} \Lambda_{s;ij;mn}^{(\mathbf{p}'; \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'; \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q})} \Lambda_{r;sn;i_1l}^{(\mathbf{p}''; \mathbf{p}', \mathbf{q}; \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}')} \Lambda_{a;rl;i_2u}^{(\mathbf{p}'''; \mathbf{p}'', \mathbf{q}'; -\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}'')} \\ &= \delta_{ia} \mathcal{A}_{jmn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_1l}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \delta(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}''') \delta(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{q}'') \mathcal{A}_{li_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}'')} \\ &+ \delta_{ja} \mathcal{A}_{imn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_1l}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \delta(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p}''') \delta(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{q}'') \mathcal{A}_{li_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}'')} \\ &+ \mathcal{A}_{jma}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1l}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \delta(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}''') \delta(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} + \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{q}'') \mathcal{A}_{li_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}'')} \\ &+ \mathcal{A}_{ima}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ji_1l}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \delta(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}''') \delta(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} + \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{q}'') \mathcal{A}_{li_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}'')} \\ &+ \mathcal{A}_{jmn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p})} \delta(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p}''') \mathcal{A}_{ni_1a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{p}''')} \delta(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{q}'') \mathcal{A}_{ii_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}'')} \\ &+ \mathcal{A}_{imn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \delta(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p}''') \mathcal{A}_{ni_1a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{p}''')} \delta(\mathbf{k}' + \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{q}'') \mathcal{A}_{ji_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}'')} \\ &+ \mathcal{A}_{jmr}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p})} \delta(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p}''') \mathcal{A}_{ii_1a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{p}''')} \delta(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{q}'') \mathcal{A}_{ri_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}'')} \\ &+ \mathcal{A}_{imr}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \delta(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p}''') \mathcal{A}_{ji_1a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{p}''')} \delta(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{q}'') \mathcal{A}_{ri_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}'')} \end{aligned} \quad (5.228)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\substack{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}' \\ \mathbf{q}', \mathbf{p}''}} \Lambda_{s;ij;mn}^{(\mathbf{p}'; \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'; \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q})} \Lambda_{r;sn;i_2l}^{(\mathbf{p}''; \mathbf{p}', \mathbf{q}; -\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}')} \Lambda_{a;rl;i_1u}^{(\mathbf{p}'''; \mathbf{p}'', \mathbf{q}'; \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}'')} \\ &= \delta_{ia} \mathcal{A}_{jmn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_2l}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}')} \delta(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}''') \delta(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{q}'') \mathcal{A}_{li_1u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}'')} \\ &+ \delta_{ja} \mathcal{A}_{imn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_2l}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k})} \delta(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p}''') \delta(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{q}'') \mathcal{A}_{li_1u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}'')} \\ &+ \delta(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}''') \mathcal{A}_{jma}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}''')} \mathcal{A}_{ii_2l}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p})} \delta(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{q}'') \mathcal{A}_{li_1u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}'')} \\ &+ \mathcal{A}_{ima}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ji_2l}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}' + \mathbf{p})} \delta(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}''') \delta(\mathbf{k}' + \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{q}'') \mathcal{A}_{li_1u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}'')} \\ &+ \mathcal{A}_{jmn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p})} \delta(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p}''') \mathcal{A}_{ni_2a}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}''')} \delta(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{q}'') \mathcal{A}_{ii_1u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}'')} \\ &+ \mathcal{A}_{imn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \delta(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}''') \mathcal{A}_{ni_2a}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}''')} \delta(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{q}'') \mathcal{A}_{ji_1u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}'')} \\ &+ \mathcal{A}_{jmr}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p})} \delta(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}''') \mathcal{A}_{ii_2a}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}''')} \delta(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{q}'') \mathcal{A}_{ri_1u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}'')} \\ &+ \mathcal{A}_{imr}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \delta(\mathbf{k}' + \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}''') \mathcal{A}_{ji_2a}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}''')} \delta(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{q}'') \mathcal{A}_{ri_1u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}'')} \end{aligned} \quad (5.229)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}'} \Lambda_{s;ij;i_1n}^{(\mathbf{p}'; \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'; \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q})} \Lambda_{m;sn;ra}^{(\mathbf{p}''; \mathbf{p}', \mathbf{q}; \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}') } \\
&= \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}'')} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{q}')} \delta_{im} \mathcal{A}_{ji_1n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{nra}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}')} \\
&+ \delta^{(\mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{p}'')} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{q}')} \delta_{jm} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{nra}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}')} \\
&+ \delta^{(\mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{p}'')} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{q}')} \mathcal{A}_{ji_1m}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{p}'')} \mathcal{A}_{ira}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}')} \\
&+ \delta^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{p}'')} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{q}')} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1m}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{p}'')} \mathcal{A}_{jra}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}')}
\end{aligned} \tag{5.230}$$

The terms on the RHS of equation 5.222 can then be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
& [\mathcal{T}^1]_{iji_1}^{(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k}^{(1)}; t, t^{(1)})} \\
&= f_1^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{jmn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_1l}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{li_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{iu}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; \mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \right\rangle \\
&+ f_1^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{imn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_1l}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{li_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{ju}^{(\mathbf{k}', t; \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \right\rangle \\
&+ f_1^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{jma}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1l}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{li_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}+\mathbf{p})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{p}, t; \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}+\mathbf{p}, t)} \right\rangle \\
&+ f_1^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{ima}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ji_1l}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{li_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}+\mathbf{p})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}, t; \mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}+\mathbf{p}, t)} \right\rangle \\
&+ f_1^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{jmn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_1a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{ii_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}+\mathbf{p})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t; \mathbf{k}+\mathbf{p}, t)} \right\rangle \\
&+ f_1^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{imn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_1a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{ji_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}'+\mathbf{p})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t; \mathbf{k}'+\mathbf{p}, t)} \right\rangle \\
&+ f_1^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{jmr}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{ri_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}')} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t; \mathbf{k}', t)} \right\rangle \\
&+ f_1^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{imr}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}-\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ji_1a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{ri_2u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{k}'-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t; \mathbf{k}, t)} \right\rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{5.231}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& [\mathcal{T}^2]_{ijj_1}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k}^{(1)}; t, t^{(1)}) \\
&= f_2^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{jmn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_2l}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}')} \mathcal{A}_{li_1u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{iu}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \rangle \\
&\quad + f_2^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{imn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_2l}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k})} \mathcal{A}_{li_1u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{ju}^{(\mathbf{k}', t; \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \rangle \\
&\quad + f_2^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{jma}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ii_2l}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{li_1u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p}, t; \mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \rangle \\
&\quad + f_2^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{ima}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ji_2l}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}' + \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{li_1u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}' + \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}, t; \mathbf{k}' + \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \rangle \\
&\quad + f_2^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{jmn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_2a}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}')} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{k}', t; \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \rangle \\
&\quad + f_2^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{imn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_2a}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k})} \mathcal{A}_{ji_1u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \rangle \\
&\quad + f_2^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{jmr}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ii_2a}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ri_1u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p}, t; \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \rangle \\
&\quad + f_2^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{imr}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ji_2a}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}' + \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ri_1u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{k}' + \mathbf{p}, t; \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{5.232}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& [\mathcal{T}^3]_{ijj_1}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k}^{(1)}; t, t^{(1)}) \\
&= \left[\Theta^{(t-t^{(1)})} + f_3^{(t, t^{(1)})} \eta \left(-|\boldsymbol{\lambda}(\mathbf{k}', t)|^2 + |\boldsymbol{\lambda}(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)|^2 \right) \right] \mathcal{A}_{ji_1n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{in}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \rangle \\
&\quad + \left[\Theta^{(t-t^{(1)})} + f_3^{(t, t^{(1)})} \eta \left(-|\boldsymbol{\lambda}(\mathbf{k}, t)|^2 + |\boldsymbol{\lambda}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)|^2 \right) \right] \mathcal{A}_{ii_1n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{jn}^{(\mathbf{k}', t; \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{5.233}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& [\mathcal{T}^4]_{ijj_1}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k}^{(1)}; t, t^{(1)}) \\
&= -\frac{1}{2} f_3^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{ji_1n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{nra}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p})} T_{ri_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ai_2b}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{ib}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \rangle \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} f_3^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{nra}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p})} T_{ri_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ai_2b}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{jb}^{(\mathbf{k}', t; \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \rangle \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} f_3^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{ji_1m}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{ira}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} T_{ri_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ai_2b}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{mb}^{(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t; \mathbf{k}, t)} \rangle \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} f_3^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1m}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{jra}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p})} T_{ri_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ai_2b}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}')} \langle \mathcal{B}_{mb}^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t; \mathbf{k}', t)} \rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{5.234}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& [\mathcal{T}^5]_{iji_1}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k}^{(1)}; t, t^{(1)}) \\
&= -f_3^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{ji_1 n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{nra}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p})} T_{ri_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ii_2 b}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{ab}^{(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p}, t; \mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p}, t)} \right\rangle \\
&\quad - f_3^{(t, t^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1 n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{nra}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p})} T_{ri_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ji_2 b}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}' + \mathbf{p})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{ab}^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p}, t; \mathbf{k}' + \mathbf{p}, t)} \right\rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{5.235}$$

5.C.2 The required integral over the functional derivative

The non-resistive term on the RHS of equation 5.23 can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t^{(1)}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q})} \langle \tilde{w}_r^{(\mathbf{p}, t)} \tilde{w}_{i_1} \rangle \left\langle \frac{\delta \mathcal{B}_{is}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; \mathbf{q}, t)}}{\delta \tilde{w}_{i_1}} \right\rangle \\
&= \int_{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t^{(1)}} \delta^{(\mathbf{k}' + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{q})} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{q})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathfrak{D}^{(t - t^{(1)})} \left\langle \frac{\delta \mathcal{B}_{is}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; \mathbf{q}, t)}}{\delta \tilde{w}_{i_1}} \right\rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{5.236}$$

We now note that (equations 4.92 and 4.33b)

$$g_1 = \frac{1}{\tau_c} \int_{t^{(1)}} \mathfrak{D}^{(t - t^{(1)})} f_1^{(t, t^{(1)})} \tag{5.237a}$$

$$g_2 = \frac{1}{\tau_c} \int_{t^{(1)}} \mathfrak{D}^{(t - t^{(1)})} f_2^{(t, t^{(1)})} \tag{5.237b}$$

$$g_3 \equiv \frac{1}{\tau_c} \int_{t^{(1)}} \mathfrak{D}^{(t - t^{(1)})} f_3^{(t, t^{(1)})} = \frac{1}{2} \tag{5.237c}$$

The five contributions to the first functional derivative (equation 5.222), which are given by equations 5.231, 5.232, 5.233, 5.234, and 5.235, lead to the following

five contributions to the integral in equation 5.236:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{\mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t^{(1)}} \delta^{(-\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{k}')} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}')} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathfrak{D}^{(t-t^{(1)})} [\mathcal{T}^1]_{isi_1}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k}^{(1)}; t, t^{(1)}) \\
&= \tau_c g_1 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{smn}^{(\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_1 l}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{li_2 u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{iu}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; -\mathbf{k}, t)} \rangle \\
&+ \tau_c g_1 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{imn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_1 l}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{li_2 u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{us}^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t; -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \rangle \\
&+ \tau_c g_1 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{sma}^{(\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1 l}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{li_2 u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} + \mathbf{p})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{ua}^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} + \mathbf{p}, t; -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p}, t)} \rangle \\
&+ \tau_c g_1 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{ima}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{si_1 l}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k})} \mathcal{A}_{li_2 u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}, t; -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p}, t)} \rangle \\
&+ \tau_c g_1 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{smn}^{(\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_1 a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ii_2 u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{ua}^{(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p}, t; -\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}, t)} \rangle \\
&+ \tau_c g_1 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{imn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_1 a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{si_2 u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} + \mathbf{p})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t; -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} + \mathbf{p}, t)} \rangle \\
&+ \tau_c g_1 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{sml}^{(\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1 a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{li_2 u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t; -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \rangle \\
&+ \tau_c g_1 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{iml}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{si_1 a}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k})} \mathcal{A}_{li_2 u}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{ua}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; -\mathbf{k}, t)} \rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{5.238}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{\mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t^{(1)}} \delta^{(-\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{k}')} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}')} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{D}^{(t-t^{(1)})} [\mathcal{T}^2]_{isi_1}^{(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k}^{(1)}; t, t^{(1)})} \\
&= \tau_c g_2 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{smn}^{(\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_2 l}^{(-\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{li_1 u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{iu}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; -\mathbf{k}, t)} \rangle \\
&+ \tau_c g_2 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{imn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_2 l}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k})} \mathcal{A}_{li_1 u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{us}^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t; -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \rangle \\
&+ \tau_c g_2 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{sma}^{(\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ii_2 l}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{li_1 u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{ua}^{(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t; -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p}, t)} \rangle \\
&+ \tau_c g_2 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{ima}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{si_2 l}^{(-\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} + \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{li_1 u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}, t; -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p}, t)} \rangle \\
&+ \tau_c g_2 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{smn}^{(\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_2 a}^{(-\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1 u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{ua}^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t; -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \rangle \\
&+ \tau_c g_2 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{imn}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ni_2 a}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k})} \mathcal{A}_{si_1 u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; -\mathbf{k}, t)} \rangle \\
&+ \tau_c g_2 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{sml}^{(\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ii_2 a}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{li_1 u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{au}^{(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p}, t; -\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}, t)} \rangle \\
&+ \tau_c g_2 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{iml}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{si_2 a}^{(-\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} + \mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{li_1 u}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{mi_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \langle \mathcal{B}_{ua}^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t; -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} + \mathbf{p}, t)} \rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{5.239}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{\mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t^{(1)}} \delta^{(-\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{k}')} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}')} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{D}^{(t-t^{(1)})} [\mathcal{T}^3]_{isi_1}^{(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k}^{(1)}; t, t^{(1)})} \\
&= \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \left[\frac{1}{2} + \tau_c g_3 \eta \left(-|\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(-\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)}|^2 + |\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(-\mathbf{k}, t)}|^2 \right) \right] \\
&\quad \times \mathcal{A}_{si_1 n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{in}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; -\mathbf{k}, t)} \right\rangle \\
&+ \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \left[\frac{1}{2} + \tau_c g_3 \eta \left(-|\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{k}, t)}|^2 + |\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)}|^2 \right) \right] \\
&\quad \times \mathcal{A}_{ii_1 n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{ns}^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t; -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \right\rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{5.240}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{\mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t^{(1)}} \delta^{(-\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{k}')} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}')} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{D}^{(t-t^{(1)})} [\mathcal{T}^4]_{isi_1}^{(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k}^{(1)}; t, t^{(1)})} \\
&= -\frac{\tau_c g_3}{2} \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{si_1 n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k})} \mathcal{A}_{nla}^{(\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} T_{li_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ai_2 b}^{(-\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{ib}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; -\mathbf{k}, t)} \right\rangle \\
&- \frac{\tau_c g_3}{2} \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1 n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{nla}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p})} T_{li_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ai_2 b}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{bs}^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t; -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \right\rangle \\
&- \frac{\tau_c g_3}{2} \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{si_1 m}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k})} \mathcal{A}_{ila}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} T_{li_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ai_2 b}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{bm}^{(\mathbf{k}, t; -\mathbf{k}, t)} \right\rangle \\
&- \frac{\tau_c g_3}{2} \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1 m}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{sla}^{(\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p})} T_{li_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ai_2 b}^{(-\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{mb}^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t; -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t)} \right\rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{5.241}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{\mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k}^{(1)}, t^{(1)}} \delta^{(-\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{k}')} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k}')} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{D}^{(t-t^{(1)})} [\mathcal{T}^5]_{isi_1}^{(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k}^{(1)}; t, t^{(1)})} \\
&= -\tau_c g_3 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{si_1 n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k})} \mathcal{A}_{nla}^{(\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p})} T_{li_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{ii_2 b}^{(-\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{ba}^{(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{p}, t; -\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p}, t)} \right\rangle \\
&- \tau_c g_3 \int_{\mathbf{k}^{(1)}} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \\
&\quad \times \int_{\mathbf{p}} \mathcal{A}_{ii_1 n}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathcal{A}_{nla}^{(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p})} T_{li_2}^{(\mathbf{p})} \mathcal{A}_{si_2 b}^{(-\mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} + \mathbf{p})} \left\langle \mathcal{B}_{ab}^{(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}^{(1)} - \mathbf{p}, t; -\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}^{(1)} + \mathbf{p}, t)} \right\rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{5.242}$$

For notational convenience, we denote the quantities given by equations 5.238, 5.239, 5.240, 5.241, and 5.242 as

$$[\mathcal{I}^N]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} \equiv \int_{\mathbf{k}',\mathbf{k}^{(1)},t^{(1)}} \delta^{(-\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}^{(1)}-\mathbf{k}')} \mathcal{A}_{jrs}^{(-\mathbf{k}^{(1)},\mathbf{k}')} T_{i_1 r}^{(\mathbf{k}^{(1)})} \mathfrak{D}^{(t-t^{(1)})} [\mathcal{I}^N]_{isi_1}^{(\mathbf{k},\mathbf{k}',\mathbf{k}^{(1)};t,t^{(1)})} \quad (5.243)$$

Setting $\mathbf{k}' = -\mathbf{k}$ in equation 5.23, one obtains the following evolution equation for the double-correlation of the magnetic field in Fourier space:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \langle \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t;-\mathbf{k},t)} \rangle}{\partial t} = & -\eta |\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(\mathbf{k},t)}|^2 \langle \mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t;-\mathbf{k},t)} \rangle + [\mathcal{I}^1]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} + [\mathcal{I}^2]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} + [\mathcal{I}^3]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} \\ & + [\mathcal{I}^4]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} + [\mathcal{I}^5]_{ij}^{(\mathbf{k},t)} + [i \leftrightarrow j; \mathbf{k} \rightarrow -\mathbf{k}] + \mathcal{O}(\tau_c^2) \end{aligned} \quad (5.244)$$

Simplification of this equation requires the use of equations 5.238, 5.239, 5.240, 5.241, and 5.242 along with further assumptions about the velocity field.

We use the convention that, e.g., $[\mathcal{I}^{1..3}]$ refers to the third term on the RHS of equation 5.238.

5.D Fourier transform of a spherically symmetric function

Consider a spherically symmetric function $f(r)$. Its Fourier transform can be evaluated as

$$f(k) = \int \frac{d\mathbf{r}}{(2\pi)^3} e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{r}} f(r) \quad (5.245)$$

Choosing coordinates such that \mathbf{k} is parallel to the z -axis, we write

$$f(k) = (2\pi)^{-3} \int_0^\infty dr \int_0^\pi d\theta \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi e^{ikr \cos \theta} f(r) r^2 \sin \theta \quad (5.246)$$

The integrals over ϕ and θ can be performed to obtain (Monin and Yaglom 1975, eq 12.2)

$$f(k) = \frac{2}{k(2\pi)^2} \int_0^\infty dr f(r) r \sin(kr) \quad (5.247)$$

$$= \frac{1}{k(2\pi)^2} \text{Im} \left(\int_{-\infty}^\infty dr f(|r|) r e^{ikr} \right) \quad (5.248)$$

The inverse expression is (Monin and Yaglom 1975, eq 12.4)

$$f(r) = \frac{4\pi}{r} \int_0^\infty dk f(k) k \sin(kr) \quad (5.249)$$

5.E On the slope of the longitudinal correlation function near the origin

Using equations 5.73 and 5.249, one can relate the longitudinal correlation function to the spectrum as (Monin and Yaglom 1975, eq. 12.75)³⁴

$$E_L(r) = \frac{2}{r^3} \int_0^r r^2 E(r) dr \quad (5.250)$$

$$= \frac{8\pi}{r^3} \int_0^\infty dk E(k) \int_0^r dr kr \sin(kr) \quad (5.251)$$

$$= 8\pi \int_0^\infty dk \left(-\frac{\cos(kr)}{(kr)^2} + \frac{\sin(kr)}{(kr)^3} \right) k^2 E(k) \quad (5.252)$$

Taking the $r \rightarrow 0$ limit, we write

$$E_L(r) = 8\pi \int_0^\infty dk \left(\frac{1}{3} - \frac{k^2 r^2}{30} + \mathcal{O}(k^4 r^4) \right) k^2 E(k) \quad (5.253)$$

$$= \frac{1}{3} \int_0^\infty 8\pi k^2 E(k) dk - \frac{r^2}{30} \int_0^\infty 8\pi k^4 E(k) dk + \mathcal{O}(r^4) \quad (5.254)$$

The series above converges if $\int_0^\infty k^{2m} E(k) dk$ is finite for all positive integers m . One way to ensure the convergence of these integrals is to require the existence of some wavenumber k_ν such that $E(k)$ decays exponentially for $k \gg k_\nu$.

Similarly, we can use equations 5.77 and 5.249 to write

$$E_C(r) = 4\pi \int_0^\infty dk \left(-\frac{\cos(kr)}{(kr)^2} + \frac{\sin(kr)}{(kr)^3} \right) k^2 F(k) \quad (5.255)$$

which allows us to draw a similar conclusion about the behaviour of $E_C(r)$ when $r \rightarrow 0$.

³⁴Monin and Yaglom (1975, p. 31) give some examples of $E(k)$ for which $E_L(r)$ has a closed form.

5.F Coefficients in the evolution equation for the longitudinal correlation function when g is nonzero

The following coefficients appear on the RHS of equation 5.117.

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa_\tau(r) \equiv & g \left[-\frac{11}{4} \left(\frac{dS_2}{dr} \right)^2 + \frac{9}{4} \frac{d^2(S_2^2)}{dr^2} + \frac{13}{r} \frac{d(S_2^2)}{dr} + \frac{8}{r^2} S_2^2(r) \right] \\ & + g_2 \left[-8v_2 E_L(0) + \left(\frac{dE_L}{dr} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{r^4} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^4 \frac{d(E_L^2)}{dr} \right) \right] \\ & + g_3 \left[-8\eta v_2 + \frac{3\eta}{r^4} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^4 \frac{dS_2}{dr} \right) + \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{dS_2}{dr} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{8r^4} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^4 \frac{d(S_2^2)}{dr} \right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (5.256)$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_\tau(r) \equiv & g \left[\frac{S_2(r)S_2''''(r)}{2} - \frac{S_2'(r)S_2'''(r)}{2} + \frac{4S_2(r)S_2''''(r)}{r} + \frac{2S_2'(r)S_2''(r)}{r} \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{4S_2(r)S_2''(r)}{r^2} + \frac{8(S_2'(r))^2}{r^2} - \frac{4S_2(r)S_2'(r)}{r^3} \right] \\ & + g_2 \left[-2E_L(r)E_L''''(r) - 6E_L'(r)E_L'''(r) - 4(E_L''(r))^2 \right. \\ & - \frac{16E_L(r)E_L'''(r)}{r} - \frac{40E_L'(r)E_L''(r)}{r} - \frac{16E_L(r)E_L''(r)}{r^2} \\ & \left. - \frac{16(E_L'(r))^2}{r^2} + \frac{16E_L(r)E_L'(r)}{r^3} \right] \quad (5.257) \\ & + g_3 \left[\eta S_2''''(r) + \frac{8\eta S_2''''(r)}{r} + \frac{8\eta S_2''(r)}{r^2} - \frac{8\eta S_2'(r)}{r^3} - \frac{S_2(r)S_2''''(r)}{4} \right. \\ & - \frac{3S_2'(r)S_2''''(r)}{4} - \frac{(S_2''(r))^2}{2} - \frac{2S_2(r)S_2''''(r)}{r} - \frac{5S_2'(r)S_2''(r)}{r} \\ & \left. - \frac{2S_2(r)S_2''(r)}{r^2} - \frac{2(S_2'(r))^2}{r^2} + \frac{2S_2(r)S_2'(r)}{r^3} \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} A(r) \equiv & -\frac{8\eta g_3}{r^5} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^4 \frac{dS_2}{dr} \right) \\ & - g \left(\frac{d^3(S_2^2)}{dr^3} + \frac{12}{r} \frac{d^2(S_2^2)}{dr^2} + \frac{36}{r^2} \frac{d(S_2^2)}{dr} + \frac{24}{r^3} S_2^2(r) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (5.258)$$

Part III
Nonlinear dynamo

Chapter 6

Effects of anisotropy and rotation on the small-scale dynamo

6.1 Introduction

Convective flows are anisotropic, with the RMS value of the vertical component being larger than those of the other two components. Further, most astrophysical bodies rotate. In a spherical body, the angle between the local vertical and the rotation axis depends on the latitude. It is thus natural to ask how rotation and the anisotropy of convection affect the small-scale dynamo (SSD).

Favier and Bushby (2012) have studied the effect of rotation on SSD action in compressible (i.e. non-Boussinesq) convection. Needless to say, such a setup contains both rotation and anisotropic flows. However, they considered only two different rotational rates, which does not tell us much about how the SSD is affected by rotation.¹ Moreover, they only considered cases where the rotational axis was aligned with the direction of stratification. The same holds for the work of Bushby et al. (2018), whose focus was on a different phenomenon (see chapters 2 and 10).

Since astrophysical parameter regimes are computationally inaccessible, one typically relies on finding out how quantities of interest scale with dimensionless numbers that characterize the system. Optimistic extrapolation of such scaling laws then allows one to make astrophysically relevant predictions. In simulations of rotating convection, the obvious length scales often themselves scale with the rotation rate (Käpylä 2024), complicating the interpretation of parameter studies. Convective flows in stratified domains are known to be highly anisotropic, and so it seems reasonable to use an anisotropically forced velocity field as a controllable model for convective flows (e.g. Kitchatinov and Rüdiger 2005; Käpylä and Brandenburg 2008). Such simplified models may aid the interpretation of simulations of rotating convection such as those we describe in chapter 10. The effect of anisotropy

¹They claim “there is weak evidence to suggest that the rotating cases are saturating at a slightly higher level”, but closer examination of their figure 6 suggests that this may just be a stochastic fluctuation.

of the velocity field on the SSD is itself not well-studied.²

In chapter 2, we saw that even when the forcing function is isotropic, rotation can cause the velocity field to become anisotropic at small scales. Given the importance of the small scales for the growth of the SSD (see section 5.3.3), one expects rotation to affect the growth rate and the saturation level of the SSD.

The combined effects of rotation and anisotropic forcing on the velocity field have been studied in the context of the Λ effect, which gives rise to non-diffusive contributions to angular momentum transport (Kichatinov 1986; Kichatinov and Rudiger 1993; Pipin, Rüdiger, and Kitchatinov 1996; Kitchatinov and Rüdiger 2005; Käpylä and Brandenburg 2008).³ This effect is thought to maintain the Sun's differential rotation profile. Magnetic contributions to this effect have also been studied (Käpylä 2019a,b). More relevant to our focus in this chapter is the work of Käpylä (2019a), who has studied the effect of the SSD on the Lambda effect. However, they do not report how the growth rate or the saturation level of the SSD vary with latitude or the rotation rate. We are not aware of any other studies of the combined effects of rotation and anisotropy on the SSD.

We are interested in the following questions. (i) How does rotation affect the SSD? (ii) How does the anisotropy of the velocity field affect the SSD? (iii) If we have both anisotropy and rotation, does the angle between the rotational axis and the direction of anisotropy affect the SSD?

Section 6.2 specifies our numerical setup. Section 6.3 describes how we analyse the output of our simulations. In section 6.4, we study the effect of rotation on the SSD in isotropically forced simulations. In section 6.5, we study the effect of the anisotropy of the forcing function on the SSD in non-rotating simulations. In section 6.6, we describe a series of rotating, anisotropically forced simulations where the angle between the rotational axis and the direction of anisotropy is varied. Finally, we summarize our findings in section 6.7.

6.2 Setup

We consider isothermal forced turbulence in a cubical periodic box of side L . Rotation is added in the f -plane approximation, i.e. spatial variation of the Coriolis force is ignored, and there is no centrifugal force. We choose units in which the sound speed c , the initial (uniform) density ρ_0 , and the magnetic permeability μ_0 are 1; and $L = 2\pi$. These choices mean that if we define $k_0 \equiv 2\pi/L$, the unit for time is $(ck_0)^{-1}$; length is k_0^{-1} ; mass is $\rho_0 k_0^{-3}$; and magnetic field is $\sqrt{\mu_0 \rho_0 c^2}$. We solve the continuity, momentum, and induction equations:

$$\frac{D \ln \rho}{dt} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \quad (6.1)$$

²Bhat (2021) have studied the effect of anisotropy on the large-scale dynamo. Aside, we note that their comparison involves two very different forcing functions, and it is unclear to what extent anisotropy alone accounts for their results.

³As we explain in appendix 6.A, anisotropy is essential for the Λ effect.

$$\rho \frac{D\mathbf{u}}{dt} = -c^2 \nabla \rho + \mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B} - 2\rho \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{u} + \nabla \cdot (2\rho \nu \overleftrightarrow{S}) + \rho \mathbf{F} \quad (6.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial t} = \mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{B} + \eta \nabla^2 \mathbf{A} \quad (6.3)$$

where

$$\mathbf{B} \equiv \nabla \times \mathbf{A} \quad (6.4)$$

$$\mathbf{J} \equiv \frac{\nabla \times \mathbf{B}}{\mu_0} \quad (6.5)$$

$$S_{ij} \equiv \frac{1}{2} \left(\partial_i u_j + \partial_j u_i - \frac{2}{3} \delta_{ij} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \right) \quad (6.6)$$

with ρ being the density; \mathbf{u} the velocity; $D/dt \equiv \partial/\partial t + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla$ the convective derivative; c the speed of sound; $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ the rotational rate; ν the kinematic viscosity; \mathbf{F} a forcing function; \mathbf{A} the magnetic vector potential; μ_0 the magnetic permeability; and η the magnetic diffusivity. The forcing function is chosen as (Käpylä 2019b,a)

$$F_i = \left(\delta_{ij} + \delta_{i3} \delta_{j3} \epsilon (\hat{\mathbf{k}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{z}})^2 \right) F_j^{(\text{iso})} \quad (6.7)$$

where a hat denotes a unit vector, and $\mathbf{F}^{(\text{iso})}$ is the isotropic solenoidal forcing given by equation 2.22 (with a mean wavenumber $k_f \approx 3.13$). When $\epsilon \neq 0$, this preferentially forces the $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$ component of the velocity field.⁴

The equations described above are solved using the PENCIL code (Pencil Code Collaboration et al. 2021).⁵ Spatial derivatives are discretized using a sixth-order finite difference scheme, while the equations are evolved in time using a third-order Runge-Kutta method. Upwinding is used for advection of the density, the velocity, and the magnetic vector potential.

The initial velocity is set to zero, while the initial density is set to ρ_0 . Each component of the magnetic vector potential at each grid point is initially drawn from a Gaussian distribution with mean 0 and standard deviation $4 \times 10^{-6} \sqrt{\mu_0 \rho_0} c/k_0$. The timestep is chosen to keep the Courant numbers based on the advective and diffusive terms less than 0.6 and 0.25 respectively.

For all the simulations presented in this chapter, we use a grid with an equal number of grid points (say N) in each direction and set $\eta = \nu$. To completely specify the setup, one needs to specify the following parameters (in addition to those whose values are mentioned above): $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$, ν , f_0 , ϵ , and N .

⁴Note that the amplitude of the forcing depends on both f_0 (which appears in $\mathbf{F}^{(\text{iso})}$) and ϵ . The value of u_{rms} remains roughly the same (but still changes a bit, nevertheless) if one keeps $f_0(1 + \epsilon/9)$ constant while changing ϵ . This condition ensures the trace of the angular average of $f_0 \left(\delta_{ij} + \delta_{i3} \delta_{j3} \epsilon (\hat{\mathbf{k}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{z}})^2 \right)$ remains unchanged.

⁵<http://pencil-code.org>

6.3 Data analysis

In the context of the SSD, we are interested in comparing quantities across the kinematic and saturated phases. It is thus useful to have an automated way of computing averages over the kinematic and saturated phases given a particular simulation.

The first issue is that since we start from a fluid at rest, the velocity field takes some time to reach steady state under the influence of the forcing function. We thus exclude the first five turnover times while computing averages. The turnover time is estimated as $2\pi / (u_{\text{rms,full}} k_f)$, where $u_{\text{rms,full}}$ is the average over the entire time series.

To compute averages over the kinematic phase, we consider times after the first five turnover times, but before the volume-averaged magnetic energy reaches 10^{-2} of the volume-averaged kinetic energy. This is further divided into five chunks, the average over each of which is treated as an independent realization. The average of the quantity of interest is then estimated by averaging the chunked averages, while the associated error is estimated as σ / \sqrt{n} , where σ is the standard deviation of the chunked averages, and n is the number of chunks. In particular, the growth rate is estimated by fitting a straight line to the time series of the logarithm of the volume averaged magnetic energy in each chunk.

The beginning of the saturated phase is estimated to be the point where the extrapolated kinematic fit to the volume-averaged magnetic energy exceeds the time average (excluding the first five turnover times) of the volume-averaged kinetic energy.

6.4 Rotation

Even when the forcing is isotropic, rotation can induce anisotropy of the velocity field (chapter 2). Let us consider the simulations listed in table 6.1, which vary only in the rotation rate. The left panel of figure 6.1 shows that the flow is almost isotropic below $\text{Co} = 2$. For faster rotation rates, the flow becomes highly two-dimensionalized, as discussed in (chapter 2). Recall that this is due to the formation of a large-scale vortex. The right panel of figure 6.1 shows that in this regime, the fraction of the kinetic energy⁶ above the forcing scale is much larger than in the slowly rotating regime.

For notational convenience, we use $\tilde{\gamma}$ to denote the product of the growth rate of the magnetic energy and the turnover time, while \tilde{E} denotes the ratio of the magnetic energy to the kinetic energy. Figure 6.2 shows that for slow rotation, both the growth rate and the saturation level of the magnetic field decrease with increasing rotation rate. However, once the rotation is fast enough to cause the formation of large-scale vortices, the growth rate and the saturation level increase

⁶This was actually calculated from the velocity power spectrum. Since these simulations are at low Mach number, we do not expect our results to be affected by neglecting density fluctuations.

$\Omega/(ck_0)$	$\nu k_0/c$	f_0	N	Re	Co	Ma
0	1×10^{-3}	3×10^{-2}	128	306	0.00	0.153
0.02	1×10^{-3}	3×10^{-2}	128	306	0.27	0.153
0.05	1×10^{-3}	3×10^{-2}	128	308	0.67	0.154
0.075	1×10^{-3}	3×10^{-2}	128	310	0.99	0.154
0.1	1×10^{-3}	3×10^{-2}	128	311	1.31	0.155
0.125	1×10^{-3}	3×10^{-2}	128	315	1.62	0.157
0.15	1×10^{-3}	3×10^{-2}	128	319	1.91	0.159
0.175	1×10^{-3}	3×10^{-2}	128	324	2.19	0.162
0	5×10^{-4}	2.6×10^{-2}	256	581	0.00	0.145
0.025	5×10^{-4}	2.6×10^{-2}	256	582	0.38	0.145
0.05	5×10^{-4}	2.6×10^{-2}	256	583	0.74	0.145
0.075	5×10^{-4}	2.6×10^{-2}	256	588	1.11	0.147
0.1	5×10^{-4}	2.6×10^{-2}	256	593	1.45	0.148
0.125	5×10^{-4}	2.6×10^{-2}	256	596	1.78	0.149
0.15	5×10^{-4}	2.6×10^{-2}	256	605	2.10	0.151
0	2.5×10^{-4}	2.6×10^{-2}	512	1190	0.00	0.148
0.05	2.5×10^{-4}	2.6×10^{-2}	512	1190	0.75	0.148
0.1	2.5×10^{-4}	2.6×10^{-2}	512	1212	1.45	0.151
0.15	2.5×10^{-4}	2.6×10^{-2}	512	1241	2.10	0.155

Table 6.1: Parameter values and diagnostics (computed by averaging over the kinematic phase) for the isotropically forced rotating simulations. All of these simulations were run with $\epsilon = 0$. For the fastest rotational rates (where a large-scale vortex was formed) u_{rms} did not reach a statistically steady state within the kinematic phase; this affects the quoted values of Re, Co, and Ma.

Figure 6.1: Left: level of anisotropy induced by rotation in simulations with isotropic forcing. The inset on the left shows a zoomed-in view of the low- Co region. Right: at high rotation rates, a large fraction of the kinetic energy resides at spatial scales larger than the forcing scale.

Figure 6.2: Left: growth rate (scaled by the turnover time) of the magnetic energy for different rotation rates. Right: the ratio of magnetic to kinetic energies in the saturated phase for different rotation rates.

Figure 6.3: The fraction of the magnetic energy at spatial scales smaller than the forcing scale, as a function of the rotation rate.

with rotation. Note from table 6.1 that Re increases monotonically with the rotation rate. Figure 6.3 shows that in the regime of fast rotation, a larger fraction of the magnetic energy lives at scales larger than the forcing scale (suggesting large-scale dynamo action which coexists with the SSD).

Figure 6.4 shows the growth rate and the saturation level of the magnetic field as a function of the Coriolis number, but this time for different values of Re . We restrict ourselves to rotation rates where the large-scale vortex instability is not excited. Since both the growth rate and the saturation level of the magnetic field are known to be functions of Re and Pr_m (Schekochihin et al. 2004, fig. 14; Federrath et al. 2014), we express these quantities in the rotating simulations as fractions of their values in otherwise identical non-rotating simulations.

At the highest Re considered, the growth rate of the SSD does not vary much with rotation, being suppressed by only around 15% at $Co \approx 2$. Further, the strength of this effect seems to decrease as Re increases, suggesting that rotation does not affect the growth rate of the SSD in the astrophysically relevant limit of high Re . However, the steady-state ratio of magnetic to kinetic energies behaves somewhat differently: for a particular rotational rate, at the two highest values of Re considered, this ratio remains the same fraction of its non-rotating value. This raises the possibility that the rotational effect on the saturation level of the magnetic field remains significant at high Re . Quantitatively, at the highest Re considered, the ratio of magnetic to kinetic energies is suppressed by about 35% at $Co \approx 2$ as compared to its non-rotating value.

A possible explanation for why the growth rate and the saturation level behave differently is the fact that the correlation length of the magnetic field generated

Figure 6.4: Kinematic growth rate (left) and the ratio of magnetic to kinetic energies in the saturated phase (right) as a function of the Coriolis number for different Reynolds numbers. Each set of simulations has been labelled by the Reynolds number of its non-rotating case. The subscript ‘rel’ denotes that the quantity plotted has been normalized by the corresponding value in the absence of rotation.

by the SSD is larger in the saturated phase than in the kinematic phase (e.g. Seta et al. 2020, table 1). This would mean that at high Re (with $\text{Pr}_m = 1$), SSD action takes place closer to the rotationally affected scales in the nonlinear phase than in the kinematic phase. Alternatively, vorticity generated by the Lorentz force (Brandenburg and Scannapieco 2025) may play a role.

	f_0	ϵ	A_V	Re	Ma
	3×10^{-2}	0	0.00	306	0.153
	2.7×10^{-2}	1	-0.05	300	0.150
	2.25×10^{-2}	3	-0.14	302	0.150
	1.8×10^{-2}	6	-0.24	309	0.154
	1.5×10^{-2}	9	-0.28	315	0.157
	2.3×10^{-3}	81	-0.41	297	0.148

Table 6.2: Parameter values and diagnostics (computed by averaging over the kinematic phase) for the anisotropically forced non-rotating simulations. All of these simulations were run with $\nu = 10^{-3} c/k_0$, $\Omega = 0$, and a 128^3 grid.

Figure 6.5: Left: growth rate (scaled by the turnover time) of the magnetic energy in anisotropically forced simulations. Right: ratio of the magnetic energy to the kinetic energy in the saturated phase of anisotropically forced simulations. The error in A_V (which has been calculated by averaging over the kinematic phase) is less than 10^{-2} (absolute value), and so is not indicated.

Figure 6.6: Left: regardless of the level of anisotropy, the magnetic energy is predominantly at small scales. Right: anisotropic forcing does not seem to induce significant large-scale flows. The error in A_V (which has been calculated by averaging over the kinematic phase) is less than 10^{-2} (absolute value), and so is not indicated.

θ	f_0	ϵ	Re	Co	Ma	A_V
0	1.5×10^{-2}	9	319	1.26	0.159	-0.21
30	1.5×10^{-2}	9	320	1.26	0.160	-0.20
60	1.5×10^{-2}	9	320	1.25	0.160	-0.16
90	1.5×10^{-2}	9	321	1.25	0.160	-0.16

Table 6.3: Parameter values and diagnostics (computed by averaging over the kinematic phase) for the anisotropically forced rotating simulations. All of these simulations were run with $\nu = 10^{-3} c/k_0$, $\Omega = 0.1 ck_0$, and a 128^3 grid.

6.5 Anisotropy

Now, we look at a series of non-rotating simulations (listed in table 6.2) where we set $\epsilon \neq 0$ to make the forcing function anisotropic. Both the growth rate and the saturation level (figures 6.5) of the magnetic energy are reduced when the degree of anisotropy (as measured by the absolute value of the anisotropy parameter A_V , defined in equation 2.17) increases. Note that the relative change in the growth rate with A_V is roughly the same as that in the saturation level. Figure 6.6 shows that the kind of anisotropic forcing used here does not induce any significant large-scale flows or lead to large-scale magnetic fields.

6.6 Rotation and anisotropy

Now, we consider the simulations listed in table 6.3, where the turbulence is anisotropically forced such that $A_V < 0$, and the domain is simultaneously rotated about an axis inclined at an angle θ with the \hat{z} axis. If one insists on placing this study in the stellar context, the value of θ corresponds to the colatitude at which the box is placed. Figure 6.7 shows that both the growth rate and the saturation level of the magnetic field increase as θ increases (albeit with the increase in the growth rate not being very significant). Figure 6.8 shows that while the fraction of magnetic energy at small scales is θ -independent in the kinematic phase, its value in the saturated state decreases weakly as θ increases. Figure 6.9 shows that despite ϵ being the same, the degree of anisotropy of the flow varies with θ ; it is unclear to what extent this variation is responsible for the changes in the growth rate and the saturation value (see section 6.5).

The simulations described here have Coriolis numbers in the range where the Λ effect (wherein rotation acts on anisotropic flows to give off-diagonal contributions to the Reynolds stress) is expected to be significant (Käpylä 2019b, fig. 4). Indeed, in figure 6.10, we see that the off-diagonal components of the Reynolds stress are nonzero. However, there are no major differences between the kinematic and saturated phases. The hypothesis that the θ -dependence of the SSD is due to the Λ effect would be consistent with the fact that the growth rate is much less sensitive

Figure 6.7: Left: the growth rate (scaled by the turnover time) of the magnetic energy increases marginally with θ . Right: the ratio of the magnetic energy to the kinetic energy in the saturated phase varies significantly with θ .

Figure 6.8: In the kinematic phase, the fraction of the magnetic energy at small scales is independent of θ . However, it becomes θ -dependent in the saturated phase.

Figure 6.9: Even when ϵ remains the same, the degree of anisotropy of the velocity field varies with θ . Further, the velocity field becomes more anisotropic in the saturated phase.

Figure 6.10: Normalized off-diagonal components of the Reynolds stress, $\tilde{Q}_{ij} \equiv \langle u_i u_j \rangle / \langle u_k u_k \rangle$, as a function of θ in the kinematic and saturated phases. The faint grey vertical lines mark the values of θ for which simulations were performed.

than the saturation level to θ only if the Λ effect were to affect large scales more than small scales (recall section 6.4). Whether this is really the case is not clear.

6.7 Summary

We have used simulations of anisotropically forced rotating turbulence to understand the effects of rotation and anisotropy on the SSD.

First, considering isotropically forced cases with rotation (section 6.4), we have found that when the rotational rate is below a certain threshold, the growth rate and the saturation level of the magnetic field decrease as the rotational rate increases. This is consistent with the fact that rotation induces anisotropy of the velocity field at scales smaller than the forcing scale (chapter 2). While the rotational effect on the growth rate becomes weak at the highest Re considered, the suppression of the saturation level is less sensitive to Re , with the saturation level at $Co \approx 2$ being 35% lower than that in an otherwise equivalent non-rotating case. It is unclear why the growth rate and the saturation level are affected differently. At higher rotation rates, the large-scale vortex instability sets in, causing the growth rate and the saturation level to increase with increasing rotation rate.

Second, we have performed a set of non-rotating anisotropically forced simulations (section 6.5) to confirm the role of anisotropy in suppressing the SSD. Just as in the rotating case, both the growth rate and the saturation level decrease as the velocity field becomes more anisotropic.

To understand whether the SSD would behave differently at different latitudes in a rotating spherical system with convection, we have also considered a set of rotating anisotropically forced simulations, where the angle between the rotational axis and the direction of anisotropy is varied (section 6.6). While the growth rate does not increase much with the colatitude, there is a much larger relative increase in the saturation level. Keeping in mind our earlier study of the effect of rotation on the SSD, we suggest that whether this latitudinal dependence can be explained by the Λ effect depends on which scales of the velocity field are predominantly affected by the Λ effect. This should be dealt with in future work.

Appendices to chapter 6

6.A Comparison of two calculations: is anisotropy required for the Λ effect?

Kitchatinov and Rüdiger (2005, appendix A) suggest that a Λ effect (i.e. nonzero off-diagonal components of the Reynolds stress tensor) is possible even when the original turbulence (i.e. the turbulence which would have been driven by the imposed forcing function in the absence of rotation) is isotropic. In fact, they even find that for fast rotation, the Λ effect is independent of the degree of anisotropy of the original turbulence. On the other hand, Käpylä and Brandenburg (2008, eqs. A.7–9) find that all the off-diagonal components of the Reynolds stress become zero when the original turbulence is isotropic. We now explain the main difference between the two calculations, which we believe is responsible for this apparent disagreement.

Kichatinov and Rudiger (1993) and Kitchatinov and Rüdiger (2005) assume that the original turbulence would be isotropic in the absence of stratification. They then perform a weakly inhomogeneous expansion, where one expands the velocity correlation in a series with respect to a ‘large-scale’ wavenumber (Roberts and Soward 1975).⁷ This approach does not seem relevant to stratified convection, where the anisotropy of turbulence can be unrelated to the local stratification: plumes at a particular depth may have originated at a very different depth.

On the other hand, the terms obtained by Käpylä and Brandenburg (2008, eqs. A.7–9) correspond to an intermediate step in the calculation presented by Kichatinov and Rudiger (1993) and Kitchatinov and Rüdiger (2005). While Käpylä and Brandenburg (2008) allow the ‘original turbulence’ to remain anisotropic in the unstratified limit (and thus avoid the need to consider inhomogeneities), we believe that substituting the weakly inhomogeneous expressions for the original turbulence (Kitchatinov and Rüdiger 2005, eq. A9) in their expressions would lead to results consistent with those of Kitchatinov and Rüdiger (2005). Nevertheless, the point we would like to make is that the final results reported by Kitchatinov and Rüdiger (2005) and Käpylä and Brandenburg (2008) represent different scenarios.

⁷Aside, note that as explained in section 4.H, the velocity correlation tensor for incompressible turbulence is uniquely determined to the first order in the inhomogeneity; one has to go to the second order to obtain a free parameter.

Käpylä and Brandenburg (2008) attempt to compare their results with those of Kitchatinov and Rüdiger (2005) by setting the scale ratio in the latter's expressions to 1. Any agreement obtained in this manner must be regarded as a happy coincidence. Käpylä and Brandenburg (2008) wrongly suggest that the differences between these two calculations reflect differences between the closures used (FOSA; and MTA, the Minimal Tau Approximation).

Aside, the reason why Kichatinov and Rudiger (1993) and Kitchatinov and Rüdiger (2005) had to go to the second order in the inhomogeneity to get a nontrivial effect is clear when one looks at an intermediate expression derived by Kichatinov (1986, eq. 11) in conjunction with the expressions obtained by Käpylä and Brandenburg (2008, eqs. A.7–9): the relation in Fourier space between the velocity correlation tensors of the actual turbulence and of the original turbulence is linear, with a coefficient that is even in the small-scale wavevector, \mathbf{k} . Evaluating the Reynolds stress of the rotating turbulence (i.e. the real-space correlation at zero separation) corresponds to taking the integral over all wavenumbers of its Fourier-space correlation. In the weakly inhomogeneous expansion for the original turbulence (recall this is this supposed to be independent of $\mathbf{\Omega}$), the n -th order terms in the large-scale wavevector have parity $(-1)^n$ wrt. reflections of \mathbf{k} . The angular integral over \mathbf{k} would eliminate all terms which are odd in \mathbf{k} . This leads to the vanishing of contributions to the Reynolds stress of the rotating turbulence that are of the first order in the inhomogeneity.

Part IV

Solar magnetic fields

Chapter 7

On the observational evidence for bihelical magnetic fields

7.1 Introduction

Magnetic helicity, a measure of the topological linkage between magnetic field lines, is conserved at high Rm (Brandenburg and Subramanian 2005b, section 3.4 **ParValDem**). In idealized situations (e.g. simulations in periodic boxes), the conservation of magnetic helicity can drastically quench the growth rate of the large-scale dynamo, to the extent that it grows only on resistive timescales (i.e. too slowly to explain astrophysical magnetic fields). This is known as *catastrophic quenching*.

How, then, can one explain large-scale magnetic fields in astrophysical systems? The conventional answer is to first note that when one separately writes evolution equations for the helicities of the mean and fluctuating magnetic fields, $\boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}} \cdot \overline{\boldsymbol{B}}$ appears with opposite signs in the two equations. The interpretation of this is that while the α effect (see equation 4.56) generates a helical mean magnetic field, it also generates fluctuating fields with helicity of the opposite sign, such that the helicity of the total magnetic field is conserved. Another problem arises here: one can show that helical small-scale magnetic fields affect the mean magnetic field in such a way that counteracts the α effect (e.g. Vainshtein and Kichatinov 1983, eq. 12). This is resolved by appealing to fluxes of the small-scale magnetic helicity (Kleorin et al. 2000; Vishniac and Cho 2001; Subramanian and Brandenburg 2004, 2006; Vishniac and Shapovalov 2014; Shukurov and Subramanian 2022; Kleorin and Rogachevskii 2022; Gopalakrishnan and Subramanian 2023), which can allow helicity to leave the system through its boundaries.

If the solar magnetic field is indeed generated by a large-scale dynamo involving the α effect, one thus expects the large-scale magnetic fields to have a sign opposite that of the small-scale magnetic fields (i.e. the magnetic field should have a *bihelical* spectrum). Further, the fact that the kinetic helicity induced by the alpha effect is expected to switch sign across the Sun's equator (Roberts and Stix 1971, p. 156)

leads one to expect the magnetic helicities of the mean and fluctuating fields to obey a *hemispheric sign rule*, wherein the large-scale magnetic helicity is positive in the northern hemisphere. On the other hand, in a mean-field model that also includes differential rotation, Pipin et al. (2013) have found reversals of the hemispheric sign rule near cycle minima. Various attempts have thus been made to observationally constrain the spatiotemporal variation and spectral distribution of the magnetic helicity in the Sun.

By using the Zeeman effect, information on solar magnetic fields can be obtained by polarimetric measurements of spectral lines. The observed spectrum can, in principle, be affected by absorption by and emission from atoms all along the line of sight. Nevertheless, by using the fact that the temperature, density, and elemental abundances vary with the distance from the center of the Sun, one can constrain the range of depths whose contribution to a particular spectral line dominates. This can be quantified by calculating a ‘contribution function’ as a function of the radius. For photospheric lines, such contribution functions have widths of the order of tens to hundreds of kilometres (e.g. Holzreuter and Solanki 2012, fig. 7). Magnetic effects on spectral lines are thus determined not by the magnetic field at a particular depth, but by some sort of weighted average over all depths at which the contribution function of the line of interest is not negligible. This is further complicated if an instrument combines observations of multiple lines, since their contribution functions may peak at different heights (e.g., see Faurobert et al. 2009).

If one assumes that the magnetic field is uniform in a particular region, one can find an analytical relation between the magnetic field vector and the Stokes parameters at a particular wavelength (Unno 1956; Rachkovsky 1962, 1963, 1967).¹ Using the observed Stokes parameters as a function of wavelength in a band containing the line of interest, one can estimate the magnetic field at a particular location by inverting the aforementioned analytical relation (e.g. Harker 2017). Doing this for each observed pixel gives us a vector magnetogram on the observed solar disk.

The fact that we cannot observe the entire surface of the Sun simultaneously means that full-disk magnetograms are themselves still not convenient to use for studies that are interested in the global properties of the magnetic field. This motivates further reduction of the data by constructing *synoptic* magnetograms, which cover the entire surface of the Sun. In such magnetograms, the magnetic field in each pixel is a weighted average of the magnetic field at the same latitude and longitude in a number of full-disk magnetograms. The contributing full-disk magnetograms for each pixel are typically chosen such that the corresponding longitude is near the observed central meridian, the justification being that measurements near the disk center are more reliable than those near the disk edge. While this means that different pixels of a synoptic magnetogram are determined by observations

¹We were not able to access the papers by Rachkovsky (1962, 1963, 1967); however, they are often cited alongside the work of Unno (1956).

taken at different times, this complication is invariably ignored.

Recalling the interpretation of the magnetic helicity as the topological interlinking of magnetic field lines, it seems foolhardy to attempt to estimate it from a magnetogram which, ignoring the complications discussed above, only gives the configuration of the magnetic field in a two-dimensional plane. Nevertheless, given the dim prospects of getting anything better in the foreseeable future, various authors have attempted to use magnetograms to study the helicity of photospheric magnetic fields.

The magnetic helicity density ($\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{B}$) depends on the magnetic vector potential, and is thus gauge-dependent. Some authors circumvent this by considering the current helicity ($\mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{B}$) instead (e.g. Seehafer 1990; Pevtsov and Latushko 2000; Zhang et al. 2010; Yang et al. 2011). Other authors choose a specific gauge and use a poloidal-toroidal decomposition to determine the vector potential (e.g. Pipin et al. 2019). In conjunction with longitudinal averaging, this approach allows one to associate magnetic helicities with the mean and fluctuating fields.

Motivated by the theoretical expectation of a bihelical spectrum, Zhang, Brandenburg, and Sokoloff (2014) studied the spectral distribution of the magnetic helicity in active regions. For this, they used a heuristic analogy with the expressions for the magnetic energy and helicity spectra in homogeneous and isotropic turbulence (see equation 5.71). By a similar analogy with the expressions for the magnetic energy and helicity in weakly inhomogeneous turbulence (appendix 4.H discusses these expressions), Brandenburg, Petrie, and Singh (2017) and Singh et al. (2018) introduced a ‘two-scale method’, which treats the photosphere as a flat surface. Prabhu et al. (2021) have shown that using spherical harmonics does not qualitatively change the results.

In this chapter, we apply the two-scale method introduced by Brandenburg, Petrie, and Singh (2017) and Singh et al. (2018). Section 7.2 describes the two-scale method. Section 7.3 gives the details of our data analysis. In section 7.4, we verify the two-scale method by applying it to simulations. Section 7.5 describes some errors in previous work (which nevertheless do not change the final results due to the fortuitous cancellation of multiple spurious minus signs). In section 7.6, we show that near the minimum between solar cycles 24 and 25, one can find large-scale magnetic fields at high latitudes in SDO/HMI synoptic magnetograms, but not in cotemporal SOLIS/VSM synoptic magnetograms. Section 7.7 shows that, as reported earlier, neither apodization nor masking of weak-field regions brings the helicity spectra from HMI and SOLIS magnetograms into agreement. Finally, section 7.8 summarizes our conclusions. The scripts used in this chapter can be downloaded from <https://github.com/Kishore96in/bihelical-mag-fields>.

7.2 Description of the two-scale method

7.2.1 Locally isotropic, weakly inhomogeneous turbulence

Let us consider the Fourier-space two-point correlation function of the magnetic field:

$$M_{ij}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{K}) \equiv \langle B_i(\mathbf{k} + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{K}) B_j^*(\mathbf{k} - \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{K}) \rangle \quad (7.1)$$

For turbulence that is locally isotropic and weakly inhomogeneous (see equation 4.122 in appendix 4.H.1), we can write the spectra of the magnetic energy and the magnetic helicity (using expressions from appendix 7.A) as

$$8\pi M(k, K) = \int M_{ii}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{K}) d\Omega_k \quad (7.2)$$

$$8\pi N(k, K) = \int i k_i \epsilon_{ijk} M_{jk}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{K}) d\Omega_k \quad (7.3)$$

respectively. The quantities M and N are related to the quantities \tilde{E}_M and \tilde{H}_M (defined by Zhang, Brandenburg, and Sokoloff 2014; Brandenburg, Petrie, and Singh 2017; Singh et al. 2018) by

$$\tilde{E}_{M,3D}(k, \mathbf{K}) = 4\pi k^2 M(k, \mathbf{K}) = \frac{1}{2} \int M_{ii}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{K}) k^2 d\Omega_k \quad (7.4a)$$

$$\tilde{H}_{M,3D}(k, \mathbf{K}) = 8\pi N(k, \mathbf{K}) = \int i \epsilon_{ijk} \frac{k_i}{k^2} M_{jk}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{K}) k^2 d\Omega_k \quad (7.4b)$$

Note that the magnetic energy and the magnetic helicity are proportional to $\int \tilde{E}_{M,3D} dk$ and $\int \tilde{H}_{M,3D} dk$ respectively.

7.2.2 A leap of faith

One would like a method that can be applied to solar magnetograms. The expressions above are not directly useful, since they require information about the magnetic field in a three-dimensional volume. We are not aware of any rigorous derivation of the two-scale method introduced by Brandenburg, Petrie, and Singh (2017). Zhang, Brandenburg, and Sokoloff (2014, p. 3) and Brandenburg, Petrie, and Singh (2017, p. 2) seem to have heuristically derived their expressions by making the replacement $4\pi k^2 d\Omega_{3D} \rightarrow 2\pi k d\Omega_{2D}$ in equations 7.4.

7.2.3 Definitions of the energy and helicity spectra

While our reasoning so far has been in terms of the continuous Fourier transform, it is conventional in observational work to use the discrete Fourier transform (appendix 7.C discusses how these differ). If we define M_{ij} (equation 7.1) in terms of the discrete Fourier transform of the magnetic field, we find that it has the same dimensions as the square of the magnetic field.

Paralleling the heuristic procedure described by Zhang, Brandenburg, and Sokoloff (2014, p. 3) and Brandenburg, Petrie, and Singh (2017, p. 2), we define (analogous to equations 7.4)

$$\tilde{E}_M(k, \mathbf{K}) \equiv \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \frac{1}{2} M_{ii}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{K}) \mathbb{1}\left(k - \frac{\Delta}{2} \leq |\mathbf{k}| < k + \frac{\Delta}{2}\right) \quad (7.5)$$

$$\tilde{H}_M(k, \mathbf{K}) \equiv \sum_{\mathbf{k}} i \epsilon_{ijk} \frac{k_i}{k^2} M_{jk}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{K}) \mathbb{1}\left(k - \frac{\Delta}{2} \leq |\mathbf{k}| < k + \frac{\Delta}{2}\right) \quad (7.6)$$

where Δ is the spacing between adjacent values of k , and $\mathbb{1}$ denotes the indicator function (which is 1 when its argument is true, and 0 otherwise); note that the indicator function has replaced the 3D angular element $k^2 d\Omega_k$. In equation 7.6, \mathbf{k} is treated as a three-dimensional vector whose third component is zero. Note that \tilde{E}_M and $k\tilde{H}_M$ have units of G^2 , which is equivalent to erg cm^{-3} .^{2,3}

7.3 Data analysis

7.3.1 The magnetograms used

7.3.1.1 HMI

HMI (Helioseismic and Magnetic Imager) is an instrument on SDO (Solar Dynamics Observatory, a geosynchronous satellite) which observes the 617.3 nm line of Fe I in absorption.⁴ After computing the Stokes parameters from these measurements, the vector magnetic field is obtained using a Milne-Eddington-based inversion algorithm. Azimuth disambiguation is done using the minimum-energy algorithm in strong-field ($|\mathbf{B}| > 150 \text{ G}$) regions, while the sign of the transverse component is randomly assigned in weak-field regions. Synoptic maps are then constructed by, for each combination of Carrington longitude and latitude, averaging over magnetograms where that particular location is closest to the observed central meridian. Liu et al. (2017) describe the production of both full-disk and synoptic vector magnetograms in more detail.⁵

We use 360×720 pixel (sine-latitude vs longitude) vector synoptic maps (series `b_synoptic_small`) downloaded from JSOC. We rebin these using cubic spline interpolation to a grid equispaced in latitude, preserving the number of pixels.

²Brandenburg, Petrie, and Singh (2017), Singh et al. (2018), and Prabhu et al. (2021) mention dimensionally different units ($\text{G}^2 \text{ Mm}$). Their expressions would follow if the spectra were defined using the continuous Fourier transform, as opposed to the discrete one used here. We note that at least Brandenburg, Petrie, and Singh (2017) used the discrete Fourier transform in their scripts.

³For conversion to SI units, it is useful to note that $1 \text{ erg cm}^{-3} = 10^{-1} \text{ J m}^{-3}$.

⁴For more details on this particular line, we direct the reader to Norton et al. (2006).

⁵The work of Liu et al. (2017) is also described at <http://hmi.stanford.edu/hminuggets/?p=1689>.

7.3.1.2 SOLIS

The VSM (Vector Spectro-Magnetograph) instrument on SOLIS (Synoptic Optical Long-term Investigations of the Sun) observes a pair of Fe I lines around 630.2 nm in absorption (Keller, Harvey, and Giampapa 2003, section 2).⁶ The vector magnetic field is obtained from the Stokes parameters using a Milne-Eddington-based inversion algorithm (Harker 2017). Azimuthal disambiguation has supposedly been done using the ‘Very Fast Disambiguation method’ proposed by Rudenko and Anfinogentov (2014).⁷ Synoptic maps are constructed by averaging over multiple magnetograms, with a weighting factor ensuring that the dominant contributions to a particular Carrington longitude come from magnetograms where that longitude is near the central meridian. We use 180×360 pixel (latitude vs longitude) vector synoptic maps.⁸

7.3.2 Coordinate system and domain

Using $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$, and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\phi}}$ to denote the radial, colatitudinal, and azimuthal unit vectors on the Sun’s surface, we note that $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\phi}}$, and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ form a left-handed coordinate system. A right-handed coordinate system can then be formed by taking one’s unit vectors as $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\phi}}$, and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}$, where $\hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} \equiv -\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$. The components of the magnetic field are given by $(B_r, B_\phi, B_\lambda) = (B_r, B_\phi, -B_\theta)$ (Brandenburg, Petrie, and Singh 2017, eq. 20; Singh et al. 2018, eq. 10).

We unwrap the surface of the Sun to form a Cartesian 2D domain, such that the position vector is $\mathbf{X} = (X_\phi, X_\lambda)$; and the domain has size $L_\phi \times L_\lambda = 2\pi R_\odot \times \pi R_\odot$ (where $\lambda \equiv \pi/2 - \theta$ is the latitude).

7.3.3 The important part of the helicity spectrum

The hemispheric sign rule predicts that the large-scale magnetic fields have helicities of opposite signs in the northern and southern hemispheres. If one is searching for signs of large-scale dynamo action, one should thus look at the parts of the helicity spectrum that change sign about the equator.

We thus search for large-scale latitudinal modulation of the form $\sin(2\lambda)$ (with λ being the latitude in radians). In the domain described in section 7.3.2, the mode we are interested in would correspond to $\sin(\mathbf{Q} \cdot \mathbf{X})$, with $\mathbf{Q} \equiv (0, 2/R_\odot) = (0, 2\pi/L_\lambda)$. The Fourier transform of this is

$$\sin(\mathbf{Q} \cdot \mathbf{X}) \rightarrow \frac{1}{2i} [\delta(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{Q}) - \delta(\mathbf{K} + \mathbf{Q})] \quad (7.7)$$

⁶See <https://solarnews.nso.edu/solis-vsm-vector-magnetograms/>.

⁷We have not been able to confirm this through primary sources, and so rely on secondary sources such as Singh et al. (2018, section 3).

⁸Downloaded from <https://magmap.nso.edu/> (series kcv9g). These files are described as “level 3 SOLIS data processed by GONG pipeline”. Gosain et al. (2013) appear to describe the creation of these synoptic maps in more detail, but also see <https://solarnews.nso.edu/solis-vsm-vector-magnetograms> and <https://solis.nso.edu/0/vsm/aboutmaps.html>.

To obtain the contribution proportional to this with a sign corresponding to the sign of the helicity in the northern hemisphere, one has to take the *negative imaginary part* of $\tilde{H}_M(k, \mathbf{Q})$.

7.3.4 Averaging

Talking about a ‘double correlation’ implies that some sort of averaging (e.g. an ensemble average) is being done. However, we work with synoptic vector magnetograms, and the only averaging we perform is over the azimuthal large-scale coordinate (due to our choice of the large-scale wavevector) and time (in some cases).⁹

7.3.5 Error estimates

Spectra calculated from single magnetograms are expected to be affected by stochastic fluctuations. To suppress these fluctuations, we average spectra over a number of contiguous magnetograms. We then estimate the stochastic errors in these averaged spectra by using the jackknife method: given N realizations of a random variable X (denoted by X_1, \dots, X_N), the error in their mean is estimated as the standard deviation of μ_1, \dots, μ_N , where

$$\mu_i \equiv \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^N \frac{X_j}{N-1} \quad (7.8)$$

The procedure chosen for azimuth disambiguation is expected to affect the helicity spectrum. In particular, for the HMI magnetograms, the sign of the transverse field is randomly chosen in weak-field regions. Since the random signs chosen for different magnetograms are uncorrelated, the error estimated using equation 7.8 also includes the error due to this specific disambiguation procedure. We show this in appendix 7.B.

No attempt is made to estimate other sources of systematic error, e.g. due to the model atmospheres used in the inversion process.

7.4 Verification of the two-scale method

We consider a simulation setup similar to that used by Brandenburg, Petrie, and Singh (2017, sec. 3.2), with the grid having 512^3 points. Given the magnetic field at a particular instant of time, we consider its values in a single yz plane, and

⁹The magnetic field in a synoptic chart may have been averaged over multiple observations, and further may also be thought of as a weighted average over radius (depending on the particular spectral line being observed). However, this is not relevant for our discussion.

Figure 7.1: Recovery of the correct sign of the helicity from a simulation where there is no sign change across $z = 0$. The helicity on the left, calculated directly from \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} , has been averaged over x and y . The helicity spectrum on the right is the average of the spectra calculated from \mathbf{B} in six yz planes. None of the quantities has been averaged over time.

calculate the energy and helicity spectra.¹⁰ This coordinate system is similar to the one we use for synoptic maps (section 7.3.2).

7.4.1 No sign change of helicity

First, we consider a case where the sign of the helical forcing is the same throughout the domain. In this case, we are interested in the real part of the $K = 0$ part of the helicity spectrum. Figure 7.1 shows that we recover the correct sign of the helicity spectrum (the sign of the mean helicity in the left panel is consistent with the sign in the low-wavenumber region of the right panel).

7.4.2 Helicity changing sign across the equator

Next, we consider a case where the helicity flips sign across $z = 0$, and the domain itself has extent $-L_z/2 < z < L_z/2$. In this case, we expect the strongest contribution to be proportional to $\sin(2\pi z/L_z)$ (see section 7.3.3).

7.4.2.1 The problem

Formally, the expressions for the energy and helicity spectra (equations 7.5 and 7.6) involve $M_{ij}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{K}) \equiv \langle B_i(\mathbf{k} + \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{K}) B_j^*(\mathbf{k} - \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{K}) \rangle$. If one wishes to recover

¹⁰Taking xz planes, like Brandenburg, Petrie, and Singh (2017, sec. 3.2), forces one to use a left-handed coordinate system (also see section 7.5.1).

Figure 7.2: Recovery of the wrong sign of the helicity when one takes $M_{ij}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{K}) \equiv \langle \tilde{B}_i(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{K}) \tilde{B}_j^*(\mathbf{k}) \rangle$. The helicity on the left, calculated directly from \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} , has been averaged over x and y . The helicity spectrum on the right is the average of the spectra calculated from \mathbf{B} in six yz planes. None of the quantities has been averaged over time.

a mode with $K_z = 2\pi/L_z$, a problem arises: $2\pi/L_z$ is the smallest wavenumber present in the domain, and so it is difficult to make sense of $\mathbf{K}/2$.

7.4.2.2 The traditional method

To circumvent this issue, Brandenburg, Petrie, and Singh (2017) and Singh et al. (2018) treat the quantity $\langle \tilde{B}_i(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{K}) B_j^*(\mathbf{k}) \rangle$ as being equivalent to $M_{ij}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{K})$. If one uses this definition, various tricks (sections 7.5.1 and 7.5.2) are required to recover the correct sign of the helicity spectrum from simulations. In figure 7.2, we show that the wrong sign of the helicity is recovered using this method (the sign of the mean helicity in the $z > 0$ region on the left panel is inconsistent with the sign in the low-wavenumber region of the right panel).

7.4.2.3 The correct method

An alternative¹¹ is to double the length of the domain (keeping the equator, if any, still at the middle); this is consistent with the assumption of periodicity that goes into expanding a function (in a finite domain) as a Fourier series. In this particular

¹¹We later found that Axel Brandenburg had written a routine (`helspec_double.pro`) that does something similar (without, however, preserving the position of the equator). This was not used by Brandenburg, Petrie, and Singh (2017) and Singh et al. (2018).

Figure 7.3: Recovery of the correct sign of the helicity when one takes $M_{ij}(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{K}) \equiv \langle \tilde{B}_i(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{K}/2) \tilde{B}_j^*(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{K}/2) \rangle$. The helicity on the left, calculated directly from \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} , has been averaged over x and y . The helicity spectrum on the right is the average of the spectra calculated from \mathbf{B} in six yz planes after doubling the extent of the domain as described in the text. None of the quantities has been averaged over time.

case, we extend the definition of \mathbf{B} as (omitting the other arguments for brevity)

$$\mathbf{B}(z) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{B}(z + L_z), & -L_z < z < -L_z/2 \\ \mathbf{B}(z), & -L_z/2 < z < L_z/2 \\ \mathbf{B}(z - L_z), & L_z/2 < z < L_z \end{cases} \quad (7.9)$$

To keep the spacing between the wavevectors the same in both the directions, we also double the domain along the y direction (recall that the domain was initially cubical).¹² After calculating the spectra, we rebin them in terms of the wavenumbers of the original domain (since doubling the domain halves the spacing between the wavenumbers). In figure 7.3, we show that this method allows us to recover the correct sign of the helicity spectrum.

7.5 Issues with previous applications of the two-scale method

7.5.1 Comparison with simulations

Brandenburg, Petrie, and Singh (2017, p. 5) claim to apply their scripts to slices saved from a simulation and recover the correct sign of the helicity spectrum.

¹²In the y direction, we can simply stack the domain, since there is no equator to worry about.

However what they plot in their figure 6b is actually the *positive* imaginary part of the helicity spectrum (and not the relevant negative imaginary part as claimed).¹³

7.5.2 A spurious sign flip

We now describe the source of a spurious minus sign in the IDL scripts used by Singh et al. (2018) to analyse SOLIS vector magnetograms.¹⁴ Denoting the latitudinal extent by L_θ , we note that in their `helspec_two.pro` (lines 15–17), they apply a shift of $L_\theta/2$ along the latitudinal direction to each component of the magnetic field before taking the Fourier transform. This means that the double correlation $\langle B_i(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{K})B_j^*(\mathbf{k}) \rangle$, which they calculate, gains an extra multiplicative factor of $e^{i\pi} = -1$ when $\mathbf{K} = (2\pi/L_\theta)\hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}$. The shift applied in `helspec_two.pro` is unnecessary because the HMI vector magnetograms already have the equator at the middle.

Since the minus sign introduced here is cancelled by the minus sign described in section 7.4.2.2, we believe their results are not affected by this issue. However, this is something future reproducers of their work need to be aware of.

7.5.3 Error estimates

Singh et al. (2018, eq. 11) claim that they estimate errors in a spectrum $P_{k,t}$ as

$$\sigma_k^{(P)} = \sqrt{\left\langle \left(P_{k,t} - \langle P_{k,t} \rangle_t \right)^2 \right\rangle_t} \quad (7.10)$$

where t is a discrete coordinate meant to represent the Carrington rotation number of the corresponding synoptic map. However, examination of their IDL routine `pavgfew_spec.pro` suggests that they have in fact estimated the error as

$$\sigma_k^{(P)} = \sqrt{\left\langle \left(\tilde{P}_{k,t} - \langle \tilde{P}_{k,t} \rangle_t \right)^2 \right\rangle_t} \quad (7.11)$$

where¹⁵

$$\tilde{P}_{k,t} \equiv \frac{P_{k,t-1} + P_{k,t}}{2} \quad (7.12)$$

\tilde{P} at the beginning of the time slice is defined to be equal to the one at the next time.

Note that equation 7.10 is an estimator of the sample standard deviation, while we are interested in the error in the sample mean. Equation 7.11 appears to be an attempt to estimate the latter and seems to be a variant of the ‘jackknife’ method.

¹³The script they used to plot this figure is available at <https://lcd-www.colorado.edu/~axbr9098/projects/LShelicityspec/576b/ptst.pro> (accessed 26-Aug-2023, 11:16 AM IST).

¹⁴We obtained a copy of these scripts from Nishant Singh.

¹⁵In IDL, the smoothing was done using `gdkHk1=smooth(gdkHk1, [0,2], /edge_mirror)`.

Figure 7.4: Energy spectra calculated from HMI magnetograms, averaged over the indicated Carrington rotations. Errors are indicated by shaded regions of the same colour as the corresponding lines, but are too small to be clearly visible.

7.6 Large-scale fields in HMI magnetograms

Figure 7.4 shows the magnetic energy spectra calculated from HMI synoptic vector magnetograms at different phases of solar cycle 24. Near the peak of solar cycle 24 (Carrington rotations 2143–2152), we find that the magnetic energy spectrum peaks at a single scale. However, closer to the minimum between cycles 24–25, we find that the magnetic energy spectrum has a second peak at around $6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ Mm}^{-1}$. We are not aware of any other reports of such a feature.

Let us now investigate what exactly these large-scale features correspond to. The left panel of figure 7.5 shows a low-pass-filtered HMI synoptic map from a single Carrington rotation. The large-scale features we saw in the spectra show up as a dipolar component, strongest at latitudes $|\lambda| > 50^\circ$. The sign of this large-scale dipolar field is consistent with that expected for the polar fields at this stage of the solar cycle (see Hathaway 2015, figure 17), and so it is difficult to dismiss it as a spurious feature.

The right panel of figure 7.5 shows a low-pass-filtered SOLIS magnetogram. While the magnetograms from HMI and SOLIS are comparable near the equator, they are completely different at high latitudes. In particular, the SOLIS magnetograms do not have a prominent dipolar component at high latitudes. Given the complex process through which synoptic magnetograms are derived from the observed line profiles, it is difficult to immediately point out why the two magnetograms differ so drastically.

Many authors consider vector magnetograms unreliable at high latitudes (e.g. Brandenburg, Petrie, and Singh 2017, p. 5; Luo, Jiang, and Wang 2023, p. 2) and in

Figure 7.5: Low-pass-filtered ($k < 10^{-2} \text{ Mm}^{-1}$) synoptic HMI and SOLIS maps of the radial magnetic field in Carrington rotation 2180 (30-Jul-2016 – 26-Aug-2016).

Figure 7.6: The effect, of removing high latitudes or weak-field regions from HMI magnetograms, on the magnetic energy spectrum (averaged over Carrington rotations 2197–2206). The legend indicates which region of each magnetogram was used to compute the spectrum.

Figure 7.7: Magnetic energy and helicity spectra calculated from apodized ($|\lambda| < 60^\circ$) HMI and SOLIS magnetograms, averaged over Carrington rotations 2143–2153. Errors have been indicated by shaded regions of the same colour as the corresponding lines.

regions where the magnetic field is weak. The former is related to projection effects, while the latter is due to magnetic effects on the observed lines being overpowered by noise. The simplest way of obtaining results that do not depend on these regions is to set the magnetic field to zero there. ‘Apodization’ refers to removing the effect of high-latitude regions by either setting them to zero or using some sort of windowing function. More complicated approaches (which we do not explore here) involve using an extrapolation scheme to ‘fill in’ the data at high latitudes (e.g. Luo, Jiang, and Wang 2023, p. 2). In figure 7.6 we show that the peak at low wavenumbers is suppressed when the magnetic field is set to zero, either at high latitudes or in weak-field regions.

Note that the suppression of the low-wavenumber peak by apodization or masking has no bearing on whether it is spurious. Given that many authors (e.g. Brandenburg, Petrie, and Singh 2017; Pipin et al. 2019) use HMI magnetograms without any apodization or masking, it is important to understand why HMI and SOLIS magnetograms disagree.

7.7 Disagreement between cotemporal HMI and SOLIS magnetograms

Despite the issues we noted at large scales, one may still hope that the magnetograms are more reliable at high wavenumbers (which are presumably dominated by active

regions, where the strength of the magnetic field allows more accurate inversions). Figure 7.7 compares energy and helicity spectra from apodized ($|\lambda| < 60^\circ$) HMI and SOLIS magnetograms (Carrington rotations 2143–2153). As noted by Singh et al. (2018), we find that the sign of the helicity spectrum is instrument-dependent. While the interval compared by Singh et al. (2018, fig. 9) (Carrington rotations 2160–2162) showed disagreement between HMI and SOLIS only at the largest wavenumbers, the particular interval we have compared here shows disagreement at both large and small wavenumbers.

7.8 Conclusions

While the two-scale method introduced by Brandenburg, Petrie, and Singh (2017) and Singh et al. (2018) may allow one to extract much more information from magnetograms than competing methods, it has certain subtle implementation issues which were not discussed in the original papers. To aid application of this method, we have discussed these problems and their solutions.

Application of this method to HMI magnetograms reveals that throughout the solar cycle, the magnetic energy spectrum peaks at a wavenumber of roughly 0.1 Mm^{-1} . Near the cycle minimum, a second peak appears at a lower wavenumber (roughly $6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ Mm}^{-1}$). Examining a low-pass-filtered magnetogram of the radial magnetic field indicates that the second peak is associated with large-scale fields concentrated at high latitudes. These fields have a sign consistent with that expected from the sign of the longitudinally averaged polar fields.

Somewhat surprisingly, the feature described above is absent from cotemporal SOLIS magnetograms. Previous applications of the two-scale method (Brandenburg, Petrie, and Singh 2017; Singh et al. 2018) only used magnetograms from the declining phase of solar the solar cycle (where the magnetic energy spectrum has a single peak), and hence this discrepancy was not noticed. Further, we find that even after excluding high-latitude regions where the magnetograms are expected to be unreliable, the SOLIS and HMI data can differ on the sign of the magnetic helicity spectrum at both large and small scales.

Part of the disagreement between HMI and SOLIS could, in principle, be attributed to the fact that they observe different spectral lines. However, the differences between the respective contribution functions are comparable to their widths and to changes due to the presence of a magnetic field — see Faurobert et al. (2009) and Grec et al. (2010) for the formation heights of the lines used by SOLIS; Holzreuter and Solanki (2012, fig. 7) for magnetic effects on these lines; and Norton et al. (2006, table 1) and Fleck, Couvidat, and Straus (2011, fig. 11) for the formation height of the line used by HMI. This makes it difficult to argue that HMI and SOLIS magnetograms sample magnetic fields at very different depths. In fact, Norton et al. (2006, section 3.2), comparing magnetic field strengths inferred from the line pair used by SOLIS with those from the line used by HMI,¹⁶ find

¹⁶They observed these lines simultaneously using the Advanced Stokes Polarimeter (Elmore

reasonably good agreement.

Other possible explanations for the disagreement are differences in the way the synoptic magnetograms are assembled, including differences in the observation times of the underlying full-disk magnetograms; and differences in the inversion procedure used to obtain the magnetic field (for a comparison of different inversion procedures, see Borrero et al. 2014, fig. 2). Directly analysing full-disk magnetograms would allow one to find out which of these is the dominant source of systematic error in the helicity spectrum. Using full-disk magnetograms would also avoid the loss of information, on two-point correlations, which is inherent to the process of producing synoptic magnetograms (heuristically, the magnetic field present in synoptic magnetograms is already an average over multiple full-disk observations).

In light of our analysis of the two-scale method, the instrument-dependence of other ways of constraining the magnetic helicity should also be critically examined.

Appendices to chapter 7

7.A Angular integrals over unit vectors

One often needs to perform angular integrals of the form

$$\frac{1}{k^n} \int d\Omega_k k_{i_1} k_{i_2} \dots k_{i_n} \quad (7.13)$$

where $d\Omega_k$ denotes an integral over the angular part of \mathbf{k} . It is possible to guess the answer without actually performing the calculation. The integral needs to be an isotropic tensor, since all the angular dependence has already been integrated out. Isotropic tensors of even rank can be expressed completely in terms of Kronecker deltas, while those of odd rank can be expressed as a sum of terms containing one Levi-Civita multiplied by the required number of Kronecker deltas (Boyle and Matthews 1971, p. 382).^{17,18} There is no isotropic one-index tensor; the only isotropic two-index tensor is δ_{ij} ; while the only isotropic three-index tensor is ϵ_{ijk} .¹⁹

We then find that

$$\frac{1}{k} \int d\Omega_k k_{i_1} = 0 \quad (7.14)$$

Further, the integral needs to be symmetric under interchange of any two of its indices. Then we have

$$\frac{1}{k^3} \int d\Omega_k k_{i_1} k_{i_2} k_{i_3} = 0 \quad (7.15)$$

To see that the higher-order integrals of odd rank are also zero, we simply need to note that under $\mathbf{k} \rightarrow -\mathbf{k}$, we have

$$\int d\Omega_k k_{i_1} k_{i_2} \dots k_{i_{2n+1}} \rightarrow - \int d\Omega_k k_{i_1} k_{i_2} \dots k_{i_{2n+1}} \quad (7.16)$$

which implies

$$\frac{1}{k^{2n+1}} \int d\Omega_k k_{i_1} k_{i_2} \dots k_{i_{2n+1}} = 0 \quad (7.17)$$

¹⁷Boyle and Matthews (1971) attribute this result to Weyl, but we were not able to verify the paper they cite, it being in German.

¹⁸We are not sure if this result holds in spaces with dimension different from 3.

¹⁹<https://mathworld.wolfram.com/IsotropicTensor.html> lists the number of isotropic tensors of various ranks, along with a recurrence relation for those numbers.

Again using the symmetry under interchange of any two indices, we can write the angular integrals of even numbers of unit vectors as

$$\frac{1}{k^2} \int d\Omega_k k_{i_1} k_{i_2} \propto \delta_{i_1 i_2} \quad (7.18)$$

$$\frac{1}{k^4} \int d\Omega_k k_{i_1} k_{i_2} k_{i_3} k_{i_4} \propto \delta_{i_1 i_2} \delta_{i_3 i_4} + \delta_{i_1 i_3} \delta_{i_2 i_4} + \delta_{i_1 i_4} \delta_{i_2 i_3} \quad (7.19)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{k^6} \int d\Omega_k k_{i_1} k_{i_2} k_{i_3} k_{i_4} k_{i_5} k_{i_6} \propto & \delta_{i_1 i_2} \delta_{i_3 i_4} \delta_{i_5 i_6} + \delta_{i_1 i_2} \delta_{i_3 i_5} \delta_{i_4 i_6} + \delta_{i_1 i_2} \delta_{i_3 i_6} \delta_{i_4 i_5} \\ & + \delta_{i_1 i_3} \delta_{i_2 i_4} \delta_{i_5 i_6} + \delta_{i_1 i_3} \delta_{i_2 i_5} \delta_{i_4 i_6} + \delta_{i_1 i_3} \delta_{i_2 i_6} \delta_{i_4 i_5} \\ & + \delta_{i_1 i_4} \delta_{i_2 i_3} \delta_{i_5 i_6} + \delta_{i_1 i_4} \delta_{i_2 i_5} \delta_{i_3 i_6} + \delta_{i_1 i_4} \delta_{i_2 i_6} \delta_{i_3 i_5} \\ & + \delta_{i_1 i_5} \delta_{i_2 i_3} \delta_{i_4 i_6} + \delta_{i_1 i_5} \delta_{i_2 i_4} \delta_{i_3 i_6} + \delta_{i_1 i_5} \delta_{i_2 i_6} \delta_{i_3 i_4} \\ & + \delta_{i_1 i_6} \delta_{i_2 i_3} \delta_{i_4 i_5} + \delta_{i_1 i_6} \delta_{i_2 i_4} \delta_{i_3 i_5} + \delta_{i_1 i_6} \delta_{i_2 i_5} \delta_{i_3 i_4} \end{aligned} \quad (7.20)$$

The normalization can be fixed by contracting all the indices in pairs and recalling that in three dimensions, $\int d\Omega_k = 4\pi$. We then find

$$\int d\Omega_k \frac{k_{i_1} k_{i_2}}{k^2} = \frac{4\pi}{3} \delta_{i_1 i_2} \quad (7.21)$$

$$\int d\Omega_k \frac{k_{i_1} k_{i_2} k_{i_3} k_{i_4}}{k^4} = \frac{4\pi}{15} (\delta_{i_1 i_2} \delta_{i_3 i_4} + \delta_{i_1 i_3} \delta_{i_2 i_4} + \delta_{i_1 i_4} \delta_{i_2 i_3}) \quad (7.22)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int d\Omega_k \frac{k_{i_1} k_{i_2} k_{i_3} k_{i_4} k_{i_5} k_{i_6}}{k^6} = & \frac{4\pi}{105} \left(\delta_{i_1 i_2} \delta_{i_3 i_4} \delta_{i_5 i_6} + \delta_{i_1 i_2} \delta_{i_3 i_5} \delta_{i_4 i_6} + \delta_{i_1 i_2} \delta_{i_3 i_6} \delta_{i_4 i_5} \right. \\ & + \delta_{i_1 i_3} \delta_{i_2 i_4} \delta_{i_5 i_6} + \delta_{i_1 i_3} \delta_{i_2 i_5} \delta_{i_4 i_6} \\ & + \delta_{i_1 i_3} \delta_{i_2 i_6} \delta_{i_4 i_5} + \delta_{i_1 i_4} \delta_{i_2 i_3} \delta_{i_5 i_6} \\ & + \delta_{i_1 i_4} \delta_{i_2 i_5} \delta_{i_3 i_6} + \delta_{i_1 i_4} \delta_{i_2 i_6} \delta_{i_3 i_5} \\ & + \delta_{i_1 i_5} \delta_{i_2 i_3} \delta_{i_4 i_6} + \delta_{i_1 i_5} \delta_{i_2 i_4} \delta_{i_3 i_6} \\ & + \delta_{i_1 i_5} \delta_{i_2 i_6} \delta_{i_3 i_4} + \delta_{i_1 i_6} \delta_{i_2 i_3} \delta_{i_4 i_5} \\ & \left. + \delta_{i_1 i_6} \delta_{i_2 i_4} \delta_{i_3 i_5} + \delta_{i_1 i_6} \delta_{i_2 i_5} \delta_{i_3 i_4} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (7.23)$$

7.B The error due to azimuthal disambiguation

Recall that in HMI magnetograms (section 7.3.1.1), the sign of the transverse component of the magnetic field (i.e. the component normal to the line of sight) is chosen randomly in weak-field regions. One way to estimate the effect of this on the helicity spectra is to construct different realizations of each magnetogram by randomly flipping the sign of the transverse component at each position where the magnitude of the magnetic field is below 150 G (the same threshold used to generate the HMI magnetograms).

Since each pixel in a synoptic magnetogram is computed by taking contributions from full-disk magnetograms where the corresponding pixels are close to the central

Figure 7.8: Magnetic helicity spectra calculated from different realizations of HMI magnetograms (in each case, the helicity spectra are averaged over Carrington rotations 2143–2153). Errors have been indicated by shaded regions of the same colour as the corresponding lines.

meridian (Liu et al. 2017), it seems reasonable to assign to each pixel an effective line of sight that points in the direction $(\cos \lambda) \hat{\mathbf{r}} - (\sin \lambda) \hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}$. At each weak-field pixel, we then randomly flip the direction of the component transverse to the corresponding effective line of sight.

Figure 7.8 compares helicity spectra from two such realizations, showing that the changes in the helicity spectrum are consistent with the error estimated using equation 7.8.

7.C On the dimensions of the Fourier transform

Consider a function $f(x)$, defined on $0 < x < L$. The discrete Fourier transform expands it in a series, such that

$$f(x) = \sum_n f_n e^{2\pi i n x / L} \quad (7.24)$$

where n ranges over the integers, and

$$f_n = \frac{1}{L} \int_{-L/2}^{L/2} f(x) e^{-2\pi i n x / L} dx \quad (7.25)$$

To relate this to the continuous Fourier transform, we define $k \equiv 2\pi n / L$, so that the spacing between consecutive k values is $\Delta k = 2\pi / L$. Equation 7.24 can be

written as

$$f(x) = \sum_k f(k) e^{ikx} \Delta k \quad (7.26)$$

where

$$f(k) \equiv \frac{L}{2\pi} f_n \quad (7.27)$$

Taking the $L \rightarrow \infty$ limit of equation 7.25, we write

$$f(k) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x) e^{-ikx} dx \quad (7.28)$$

In this limit, k becomes a continuous variable, and so equation 7.26 becomes

$$f(x) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(k) e^{ikx} dk \quad (7.29)$$

We also note that equation 7.27 can be rewritten as

$$f_n = \int_{2\pi n/L}^{2\pi(n+1)/L} f(k) dk \quad (7.30)$$

IDL²⁰ uses the definition 7.25 for the discrete Fourier transform; equation 7.27 then tells us that the discrete Fourier transform calculated by IDL (f_n) has different dimensions from the continuous Fourier transform ($f(k)$). By default, SciPy²¹ and NumPy²² define the discrete Fourier transform as $Lf_n/\Delta x$, and so a similar conclusion holds for them.

²⁰<https://www.nv5geospatialsoftware.com/docs/fft.html>

²¹<https://docs.scipy.org/doc/scipy/reference/generated/scipy.fft.fft.html>

²²<https://numpy.org/doc/stable/reference/routines.fft.html>

Part V

Convection and plumes

Chapter 8

The penetration depth of a thermal

8.1 Introduction

The simplest treatments of stellar convection (including mixing length theory, MLT) are local, in the sense that the convective flux at a particular location is related to background properties (such as the entropy gradient) at that location alone. Convection is assumed to occur in regions which are unstably stratified. For a chemically homogeneous star, this gives rise to the *Schwarzschild criterion*, while in the presence of chemical inhomogeneities, one obtains the *Ledoux criterion* (Kippenhahn, Weigert, and Weiss 2012, section 6.1). From a dynamical point of view, it is not reasonable to assume that fluid elements immediately stop at the radius where the background stratification becomes stable. In principle, the fluid elements could be carried a bit into the stably stratified region before coming to rest. This leads to extension of the convective zone (penetration/overshoot)¹, and mixing with layers above or below the convection zone. Such extra mixing can influence elemental abundances and stellar lifetimes.

To deal with overshoot in the framework of MLT, one either assumes that overshoot is always a fixed fraction of the scale height, or assumes that overshoot can be modelled as a diffusive process (Kippenhahn, Weigert, and Weiss 2012, page 352). In either approach, one ends up introducing an extra free parameter (in addition to the mixing length).

Simple upper bounds on the extent of penetration show that the penetration region under a convective envelope may be of the order of a scale height (Zahn 1991). On the other hand, from helioseismic constraints, we have reason to believe that the overshoot region in the Sun is only a few percent of the scale height (Basu 1997). We note that naive models of overshoot in the framework of MLT often give contradictory or unphysical results, which arise from limitations of the latter

¹In the literature, the persistence of convection outside the zone predicted by static stability criteria (applied to a non-convecting reference model) is sometimes called *entrainment* if such a region becomes unstably stratified due to convection; *penetration* if it remains stably stratified but becomes close to adiabatic; and *overshoot* otherwise (Zahn 1991; Anders et al. 2022). In this chapter, we will not need to make such distinctions.

(Renzini 1987).

As an alternative to the MLT picture of the convective flux being carried by blobs whose size is of the order of a scale height and which retain their coherence over a similar length scale, it has been suggested that in convective envelopes such as the Sun's, the flux is carried by threads of cool material which descend from the surface to the bottom of the convective zone (Spruit 1997; Stein and Nordlund 1989). This reasoning was based on structures observed in simulations of the near-surface layers of the solar convection zone; recent numerical results (Käpylä et al. 2017) also support it. The idea that the convective flux is mainly carried by cool threads of material descending from the solar surface is referred to as *entropy rain*. It is worth noting that such a picture would lead to a velocity spectrum and profile different from that expected in the usual local (MLT) picture, and thus may help resolve the convective conundrum (discussed in section 1.1).

The addition of a term, unrelated to the local entropy gradient, to the convective flux was suggested decades ago in the context of meteorology (Deardorff 1966, 1972; Priestley and Swinbank 1947). Brandenburg (2016) has shown that extending MLT with a term similar to that proposed by Deardorff (1972) can still lead to a sharp boundary between the radiative and convective zones, as required by helioseismic constraints (Basu 1997). The extra term added was physically interpreted by Brandenburg (2016) as being a consequence of entropy rain. The idea of entropy rain is thus not incompatible with helioseismic constraints.

Schmitt, Rosner, and Bohn (1984) and Rempel (2004) have studied overshoot at the bottom of a convective envelope by making semi-analytic models which assume that the convective flux is carried by plumes which extend throughout the convective layer. The dynamics of entrainment by plumes in stratified backgrounds is still not well-understood, and so they had to specify the variation of the filling factor of the plumes with depth. In both these studies, the properties of the overshoot region turned out to be strongly dependent on the filling factor. In this scenario, it would be interesting to see if a simpler model can reproduce their findings while reducing the number of unknowns. In addition, there are indications that the downflow plumes are subject to various instabilities (Rast 1998). It is thus possible that one might end up with *thermals* (isolated blobs of material), and not plumes (continuous streams of material), at the base of the convection zone. The propagation of thermals in an adiabatically stratified domain (i.e. with the entropy gradient being zero) has been studied by Anders, Lecoanet, and Brown (2019), who concluded that thermals formed near the surface of the Sun can reach the base of its convection zone without being appreciably affected by conduction.

In this chapter, we will describe some simple models which we tried to use to constrain the extent of convective overshoot. These models are based on the idea that convective fluxes are carried by isolated blobs of cool material, rather than by continuous plumes. An advantage of working with thermals is that entrainment (the process by which fluid from the surroundings is drawn into a plume or a thermal) is better understood in thermals than in plumes.

Section 8.2 describes some of our definitions and assumptions, while some

thermodynamic relations we use are derived in appendix 8.A. In section 8.3, we obtain analytical expressions for the maximum depth reached by an insulated sphere descending in a stratified medium in the absence of drag. In section 8.4, we include the effects of drag. In section 8.5, we include the effects of thermal conduction on the maximum depth attained by the sphere. In section 8.6, we formulate the equations describing a vortex ring which interacts with its surroundings by entraining fluid. Finally, we summarize our conclusions in section 8.7.

8.2 Setup

In this chapter, \square_{surr} denotes a property of the surroundings; \square_{drop} denotes a property of the drop; $\dot{\square}$ denotes the total derivative of \square with respect to time; s , z , V , m , ρ , T , and k denote specific entropy, depth, volume, mass, density, temperature, and thermal conductivity respectively; z_{max} is the maximum depth reached by the blob; v_0 is the initial velocity of the drop; C_P is the specific heat at constant pressure; g is the acceleration due to gravity; H_{P0} denotes the scale height at the base of the convection zone; γ is the ratio of specific heats at constant pressure and constant volume; the letters α , β , κ , and C with numerical subscripts denote various constants; $v \equiv \dot{z}$; $s' \equiv s_{\text{surr}} - s_{\text{drop}}$; $s'_0 \equiv s'(z = 0)$;

Since we are interested in overshoot at the bottom of the Sun's convective envelope, we consider a blob of cool material ($s' > 0$) released at the base of the Sun's convective envelope (taken to be at $0.7R_{\odot}$ wherever a numerical value is required). The depth z is taken to be zero at the base of the convection zone, and increases towards the center of the star. The surroundings are treated as plane-parallel, and are assumed to be stably stratified ($ds/dz < 0$). Since we do not expect the overshoot to exceed a scale height (Zahn 1991), we assume g is constant. We do not include the effects of magnetic fields, rotation, or shear. We also assume the convective blob always has the same pressure as its surroundings, since the pressure is equalized on timescales much shorter than the ones we are interested in.

8.3 Dragless insulated sphere

We consider a droplet descending in a constant stable background stratification without drag or heat exchange.

The acceleration of the droplet is

$$\ddot{z} = \frac{\rho_{\text{drop}} - \rho_{\text{surr}}}{\rho_{\text{drop}}} g = \left(1 - \frac{\rho_{\text{surr}}}{\rho_{\text{drop}}}\right) g \quad (8.1)$$

$$\implies v \frac{dv}{dz} = \left(1 - \frac{\rho_{\text{surr}}}{\rho_{\text{drop}}}\right) g \quad (8.2)$$

$$\implies v^2 - v_0^2 = \int_0^z 2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_{\text{surr}}}{\rho_{\text{drop}}} \right) g dz \quad (8.3)$$

Recall that we assume that the surroundings are stably stratified ($ds_{\text{surr}}/dz < 0$) for $z > 0$. The entropy of the surroundings will keep on decreasing, and fall below that of the drop at some point. Beyond this, the drop will be decelerated, and soon come to rest. The maximum depth reached is given by setting $v = 0$ in the above and finding the corresponding z .

We now use equation 8.45 (appendix 8.A) to write the density ratio in equation 8.3 in terms of the entropy difference as

$$v_0^2 = \int_0^{z_{\text{max}}} 2g \left[\exp \left(\frac{s_0 - s_{\text{surr}}(z)}{C_P} \right) - 1 \right] dz \quad (8.4)$$

As an aside, we note that if $s_0 < s_{\text{surr}}(z)$, the integrand in the above is negative. For a stable stratification, $s_{\text{surr}}(z)$ decreases with depth, and the integrand will change sign at the depth of neutral buoyancy (z_n). Since the LHS is manifestly positive, we see that $z_{\text{max}} > z_n$ if $s_0 < s_{\text{surr}}(0)$.

8.3.1 Small entropy perturbations

Assuming $|s_0 - s_{\text{surr}}| \ll C_P$, we obtain

$$v_0^2 = \frac{2gs_0}{C_P} z_{\text{max}} - \frac{2g}{C_P} \int_0^{z_{\text{max}}} s_{\text{surr}}(z) dz \quad (8.5)$$

$$= \frac{2gs_0}{C_P} z_{\text{max}} - \frac{2g}{C_P} [s_{\text{surr}}z]_0^{z_{\text{max}}} + \frac{2g}{C_P} \int_0^{z_{\text{max}}} z \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} dz \quad (8.6)$$

If we assume the background entropy gradient in the stably stratified region is independent of depth, we obtain

$$v_0^2 = \frac{g}{C_P} \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} z_{\text{max}}^2 + \frac{2g}{C_P} \left(s_0 - s_{\text{surr}}(0) - \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} z_{\text{max}} \right) z_{\text{max}} \quad (8.7)$$

where $s'_0 \equiv s_{\text{surr}}(0) - s_0$. Assuming stable stratification ($ds_{\text{surr}}/dz < 0$), we write

$$\left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| z_{\text{max}}^2 - 2s'_0 z_{\text{max}} - \frac{v_0^2 C_P}{g} = 0 \quad (8.8)$$

$$\implies z_{\text{max}} = \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right|^{-1} \left(s'_0 + \sqrt{s_0'^2 + \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| \frac{v_0^2 C_P}{g}} \right) \quad (8.9)$$

Assuming a constant background entropy gradient as before, we note that the depth of neutral buoyancy (the depth at which the surroundings have an entropy equal to the initial entropy of the blob) is given by

$$s_0 = s_{\text{surr}}(0) + \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} z_n \quad (8.10)$$

$$\implies z_n = s'_0 \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right|^{-1} \quad (8.11)$$

Thus, $z_{\text{max}} > z_n$, as expected. The maximum depth approaches infinity for an isentropic stratification, which is also expected. Note that if we set $v_0 = 0$, we find that $z_{\text{max}} = 2z_n$. This is a manifestation of the fact that if the background entropy gradient is constant, the acceleration and deceleration phases of the blob are symmetric.

8.3.2 Arbitrary entropy perturbations

If we just assume a constant background entropy gradient without assuming $|s'_0| \ll C_P$, we can write equation 8.4 as

$$v_0^2 = \int_0^{z_{\text{max}}} 2g \left[\exp \left(\frac{-s'_0 - z ds_{\text{surr}}/dz}{C_P} \right) - 1 \right] dz \quad (8.12)$$

$$= 2ge^{-s'_0/C_P} \int_0^{z_{\text{max}}} \exp \left(-\frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \frac{z}{C_P} \right) dz - 2gz_{\text{max}} \quad (8.13)$$

$$= -\frac{2gC_P}{ds_{\text{surr}}/dz} e^{-s'_0/C_P} \left[\exp \left(-\frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \frac{z_{\text{max}}}{C_P} \right) - 1 \right] - 2gz_{\text{max}} \quad (8.14)$$

Using the assumption that the medium is stably stratified ($ds_{\text{surr}}/dz < 0$), we write the above as

$$e^{-s'_0/C_P} \left[\exp \left(\left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| \frac{z_{\text{max}}}{C_P} \right) - 1 \right] - \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| \frac{z_{\text{max}}}{C_P} = \frac{v_0^2}{2gC_P} \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| \quad (8.15)$$

$$\implies -y + e^y = A \quad (8.16)$$

where

$$y \equiv \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| \frac{z_{\text{max}}}{C_P} - \frac{s'_0}{C_P} \quad (8.17a)$$

$$A \equiv \frac{v_0^2}{2gC_P} \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| + e^{-s'_0/C_P} + \frac{s'_0}{C_P} \quad (8.17b)$$

The solution to the above equation is

$$y = -A - W_{-1}(-e^{-A}) ; \quad A > 1 \quad (8.18)$$

Figure 8.1: Plot of the function $y(A)$, defined in equation 8.18.

where we have chosen the branch of the Lambert W function² such that z_{\max} increases with increasing v_0 . The condition on A ensures that W remains real. We note that $A = 1$ corresponds to $v_0 = s'_0 = 0$, in which case the prediction is that $z_{\max} = 0$. The condition $A > 1$ is thus satisfied in the situations we are interested in. Figure 8.1 shows that $y > 0$; this ensures that $z_{\max} > z_n$.

8.3.3 Consistency with previously obtained scaling relations

Multiple authors (Schmitt, Rosner, and Bohn 1984; Zahn 1991; Rempel 2004) have found the scaling relation $z_{\max} \sim v_0^{3/2}$ in their models. This scaling is not apparent in our solutions. However, the relation obtained by Rempel (2004, eq. 84) is

$$z_{\max} \sim \frac{v_0^{3/2}}{F_{\text{conv}}^{1/2}} \quad (8.19)$$

where F_{conv} is the convective flux. If we write $F_{\text{conv}} \sim \rho T v_0 s'_0$, we find that the overall scaling of z_{\max} with v_0 is linear, consistent with what we obtained in equation 8.9.

8.3.4 Estimate of z_{\max} in the Sun

At the surface of the sun, Anders, Lecoanet, and Brown (2019, page 7) estimate $s'_0/C_P \sim 5 \times 10^{-2}$ for the downflows. Since there is no mechanism for the downflows to gain entropy during their downward journey, it is safe to assume $s'_0 \ll C_P$ at the base of the CZ; this allows us to use equation 8.9. We do not attempt to estimate

²See, for example, Olver et al. (2020, section 4.13).

Figure 8.2: z_{\max} and z_n as a function of the background entropy gradient. The leftmost value plotted corresponds to a polytropic index $n = 3$ with $\gamma = 5/3$. Recall that the z -axis points downwards, and so a negative entropy gradient is stable.

the entropy perturbation of the downflows at the base of the CZ; rather, we just use the aforementioned value. As the velocity of the downflows at the base of the CZ, we take $v_0 = 3 \times 10^{-2} \text{ Mm s}^{-1}$ (Anders, Lecoanet, and Brown 2019, fig. 6).

We also need an estimate of the acceleration due to gravity at the base of the CZ. Let us say the convective zone of the Sun ends at $0.7R_{\odot}$, and that inside this radius, the density distribution of the Sun is well-approximated by an $n = 3$ polytrope. Numerically integrating the corresponding solution of the Lane-Emden equation suggests that approximately 99% of the Sun’s mass lies within this radius. We can then estimate

$$g \approx \frac{GM_{\odot}}{(0.7R_{\odot})^2} = 5.6 \times 10^2 \text{ m s}^{-2} \quad (8.20)$$

We take the scale height at the base of the convection zone as 60 Mm .³ We will also assume a background polytropic index $n = 3$ (this, along with the scale height, fixes the background entropy gradient as per equation 8.42).

Using equation 8.9, we obtain $z_{\max} \approx 0.87H_P$. For the same parameters, $z_n \approx 0.33H_P$. The predicted maximum depth reached is thus significantly larger than the depth of neutral buoyancy. In figure 8.2, we plot z_{\max} and z_n as a function of the background entropy gradient, with the other parameters as above.

³This is close to the value 58 Mm , calculated from ‘Solar Model S’ (Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 1996).

8.4 Insulated sphere with drag

We consider two kinds of drag laws: Stokes drag ($\propto v$), and a drag $\propto v^2$.

8.4.1 Stokes drag

When the drag is given by Stokes' law, assuming small entropy perturbations and a constant background entropy gradient results in an equation of motion identical with a damped harmonic oscillator. Explicitly, if we suppose that the drag is given by $a_{\text{drag}} = -\mu v$, we can write

$$\ddot{z} = \left[1 - \exp\left(\frac{s_0 - s_{\text{surr}}(z)}{C_P}\right) \right] g - \mu \dot{z} \quad (8.21)$$

$$= -\mu \dot{z} + \left[\frac{s'_0}{C_P} - \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| \frac{z}{C_P} \right] g \quad (8.22)$$

$$= -\mu \dot{z} - \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| \frac{g}{C_P} (z - z_n) = 0 \quad (8.23)$$

Assuming a constant drag coefficient (μ), the above equation tells us that the droplet oscillates about the position of neutral buoyancy (z_n , defined in equation 8.11) as expected.

8.4.2 v^2 drag

While Stokes drag is appropriate at low Re, the Re associated with flows in the Sun is very high. For example, Schumacher and Sreenivasan (2020, table 1) estimate $\text{Re} \sim 10^{12}$ at the base of the solar convection zone. This estimate is based on treating the depth of the convection zone as the relevant length scale. A more relevant estimate may be one based on the length and velocity scales characterizing thermals at the base of the convection zone. For example, taking a length scale of 2×10^{-3} Mm and a velocity scale of 3×10^{-2} Mm s $^{-1}$ (Anders, Lecoanet, and Brown 2019, fig. 6), along with a viscosity $\nu = 10^{-3}$ m 2 s $^{-1}$ (Schumacher and Sreenivasan 2020, fig. 4) gives us $\text{Re} = 6 \times 10^{10}$, which is still very large. At such high Re, one expects drag to be better modelled as quadratic in the velocity.

If we include a drag given by $a_{\text{drag}} = \mu(z)v^2$ and assume the droplet is moving down, the acceleration of the droplet is given by

$$\ddot{z} = v \frac{dv}{dz} = \left[1 - \exp\left(\frac{s_0 - s_{\text{surr}}(z)}{C_P}\right) \right] g - \mu v^2 \quad (8.24)$$

Recall that we assume the stratification is stable ($ds/dz < 0$) for $z > 0$, where the z -axis points downwards; the droplet will come to rest for the first time at some depth z_{max} , at which we set $v = 0$. We then write

$$v_0^2 = \int_0^{z_{\text{max}}} 2ge^{2M(z)} \left[\exp\left(\frac{s_0 - s_{\text{surr}}(z)}{C_P}\right) - 1 \right] dz \quad (8.25)$$

where $M(z) \equiv \int_0^z \mu dz$. We note that we were only able to find analytical expressions for the case where μ is depth-independent. We will hence proceed with this assumption. While, in principle, the drag coefficient could depend on the density, recall that even without drag, the penetration depth is only of the order of the scale height.

8.4.2.1 Small entropy perturbations

In appendix 8.B.1, we show that the maximum depth is given by

$$z_{\max} = \frac{1}{2\mu} [A_2 + W_0(A_1 e^{-A_2})] \quad (8.26)$$

where

$$A_1 \equiv \frac{2v_0^2 \mu^2 C_P}{g \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right|} - \frac{2\mu s'_0}{\left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right|} - 1 \quad (8.27a)$$

$$A_2 \equiv 1 + \frac{2\mu s'_0}{\left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right|} \quad (8.27b)$$

8.4.2.2 Arbitrary entropy perturbations

Relaxing our earlier assumption that $s' \ll C_P$, we show in appendix 8.B.2 that the maximum depth is obtained by solving the following implicit equation.

$$x^{A_2/2\mu} - A_3 x = A_1 \quad (8.28)$$

where

$$A_1 \equiv \left(\frac{v_0^2}{2g} - \frac{1}{2\mu} \right) \left(\frac{1}{C_P} \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| + 2\mu \right) e^{s'_0/C_P} + 1 \quad (8.29a)$$

$$A_2 \equiv \frac{1}{C_P} \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| + 2\mu > 2\mu \quad (8.29b)$$

$$A_3 \equiv \frac{1}{2\mu} \left(\frac{1}{C_P} \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| + 2\mu \right) e^{s'_0/C_P} > 1 \quad (8.29c)$$

$$x \equiv e^{2\mu z_{\max}} \quad (8.29d)$$

We see that the analytical expressions are quite complicated, even with the addition of only a simplified drag force. In the absence of tractable analytical expressions, we now move on to semi-analytic models.

8.5 A sphere with conduction and drag

8.5.1 Evolution equations

We now consider a blob of material moving in an arbitrary background entropy gradient, which experiences a drag $\propto v^2$, and exchanges heat with the surroundings.

In appendix 8.C, we show that one obtains the following set of equations, in which the tildes denote scaled variables defined in appendix 8.D.

$$\dot{\tilde{z}} = \tilde{v} \quad (8.30a)$$

$$\dot{\tilde{v}} = 1 - \exp(-\tilde{s}') - \frac{\alpha_2}{\tilde{l}_{\text{drop}}} \text{sgn}(\tilde{v})\tilde{v}^2 \exp(-\tilde{s}') \quad (8.30b)$$

$$\dot{\tilde{s}'} = \tilde{v} \frac{\partial \tilde{s}_{\text{surr}}}{\partial \tilde{z}} - \dot{\tilde{s}}_{\text{drop}} \quad (8.30c)$$

$$\frac{d\tilde{T}_{\text{surr}}}{d\tilde{z}} = \tilde{T}_{\text{surr}} \frac{d\tilde{s}_{\text{surr}}}{d\tilde{z}} + (\gamma - 1) C_2 \tilde{T}_{\text{surr}} \tilde{\rho}_{\text{drop}}^{1-\gamma} \exp(-\tilde{s}' - \gamma \Delta \tilde{s}_{\text{drop}}) \quad (8.30d)$$

$$\dot{\tilde{s}}_{\text{drop}} = \frac{\alpha_1 C_1}{(\gamma C_2)^{\beta_2}} \frac{\tilde{T}_{\text{surr}}^{\beta_1} \tilde{s}'}{\tilde{\rho}_{\text{drop}}^{1+\beta_2} \tilde{l}_{\text{drop}}^2} \exp(\beta_2 \tilde{s}') \quad (8.30e)$$

$$\dot{\tilde{\rho}}_{\text{drop}} = C_2 \tilde{v} \tilde{\rho}_{\text{drop}}^{2-\gamma} \exp(-\tilde{s}' - \gamma \Delta \tilde{s}_{\text{drop}}) - \dot{\tilde{s}}_{\text{drop}} \tilde{\rho}_{\text{drop}} \quad (8.30f)$$

$$\dot{\tilde{l}}_{\text{drop}} = -\frac{\tilde{l}_{\text{drop}}}{3\tilde{\rho}_{\text{drop}}} \dot{\tilde{\rho}}_{\text{drop}} \quad (8.30g)$$

where we have defined

$$C_1 \equiv \frac{k_0}{\rho_0 C_P} \frac{1}{\sqrt{g H_{P0}^3}} \quad (8.31)$$

$$C_2 \equiv \frac{\exp(\tilde{s}'_0)}{\gamma} \quad (8.32)$$

$$\Delta \tilde{s}_{\text{drop}} \equiv \tilde{s}_{\text{drop}}(z) - \tilde{s}_{\text{drop}}(0) \quad (8.33)$$

Recall that here, ρ_0 refers to the density of the drop at $z = 0$. We have written the equations in terms of $\Delta \tilde{s}_{\text{drop}}$ in order to avoid numerical issues due to the largeness of \tilde{s}_{drop} with our choice of origin and units. l_{drop} denotes a characteristic length scale of the falling drop (see appendix 8.C).

8.5.2 Initial conditions and parameters required

For the initial conditions, we need to specify \tilde{v} , \tilde{s}' , and \tilde{l}_{drop} (the initial values of the other variables are, by definition, $\tilde{z} = \Delta \tilde{s}_{\text{drop}} = 0$ and $\tilde{T}_{\text{surr}} = \tilde{\rho}_{\text{drop}} = 1$). The free parameters we need to specify are α_1 , α_2 , C_1 , γ , β_1 and β_2 (C_2 is completely specified by the choice of γ and $\tilde{s}'(0)$). To fix C_1 , we need to specify C_P , g , $H_P(0)$, $\rho_{\text{drop}}(0)$, and $k(0)$ in addition to the initial conditions mentioned earlier. We also need to specify a background entropy gradient.

If we assume thermal conduction is negligible, we can set $C_1 = 0$,⁴ and simply specify \tilde{v} , \tilde{s}' , and \tilde{l}_{drop} at $z = 0$, along with a choice of α_2 and the background entropy gradient. If there is also no drag, we can set $\alpha_2 = 0$.

⁴Equivalently, ignore the equation for $\dot{\tilde{s}}_{\text{drop}}$ and set it to zero everywhere it occurs.

Figure 8.3: The effect of conduction without drag. The red dotted line denotes the depth of neutral buoyancy, z_n . We set $\tilde{l}_{\text{drop}}(0) = 10^{-4}$, $\alpha_2 = 0$, $\alpha_1 = 1$, $\beta_1 = 5/2$, and $\beta_2 = 0$. C_1 was set to 10^{-8} for the case with conduction. Other parameters and initial conditions are as in section 8.3.4.

8.5.3 Is conduction important in the Sun?

We now estimate the value of C_1 to judge if the thermal conductivity is important in the Sun. Using Solar Model S (Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 1996), we find $H_{P0} = 58 \text{ Mm}$, $g = 5.46 \times 10^2 \text{ m s}^{-2}$, $\rho_0 = 200 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, $T_0 = 2.2 \times 10^6 \text{ K}$ and $C_P = 3.6 \times 10^4 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. In the stellar context, the dominant contribution to thermal conduction is the radiative conductivity (Kippenhahn, Weigert, and Weiss 2012, chapter 5), which is given by equation 8.74. Taking an opacity of $\kappa = 2 \text{ m}^2 \text{ kg}^{-1}$ (Schumacher and Sreenivasan 2020, fig. 4), we find $C_1 = 2 \times 10^{-11}$. We thus might as well set $C_1 = 0$ while applying this model to the Sun's convective zone.

8.5.4 Results

When drag is negligible, thermal conduction enhances penetration (figure 8.3). In this regime, we have $z_{\text{max}} \geq z_n$ (recall that z_n is the depth of neutral buoyancy, defined in equation 8.11). For solar parameters, $z_n \approx 0.3H_P$. On the other hand, if both the drag and the thermal conductivity are large enough, the blob can come to rest much before the depth of neutral buoyancy (figure 8.4). Essentially, the thermal conductivity needs to be large enough for the blob to lose its entropy signature within a few percent of the scale height.

In summary, with non-negligible drag and a thermal conductivity much higher than that expected in the Sun, this model predicts penetration depths a few percent

Figure 8.4: The effect of conduction with drag. The red dotted line denotes the depth of neutral buoyancy, z_n . We set $\alpha_2 = 10^{-2}$; other parameters and initial conditions are as in figure 8.3.

of a scale height. However, for reasonable values of the thermal conductivity, the penetration depth remains of the order of the scale height.

8.6 An entraining vortex ring

The model constructed in section 8.5 had a large number of free parameters. It also required unrealistic parameter values to obtain reasonable overshoot depths. We now present a more physically motivated model which drastically reduces the number of free parameters and predicts reasonable overshoot depths for reasonable parameter values.

8.6.1 Entrainment rate

The entrainment rate of a thermal is given by

$$\epsilon \equiv \frac{\dot{V}_{\text{drop}}}{V_{\text{drop}}} \frac{1}{v} = \frac{\kappa_3}{l_{\text{drop}}} \quad (8.34)$$

where κ_3 is a constant, called the entrainment efficiency; l_{drop} denotes the radius of the thermal; and the last equality is called the *entrainment assumption* (Lecoanet and Jeevanjee 2019). Since the entrained fluid is at density ρ_{surr} , we can write

$$\epsilon = \frac{\rho_{\text{drop}}}{\rho_{\text{surr}}} \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{drop}}}{m_{\text{drop}}} \frac{1}{v} = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{drop}}}{m_{\text{drop}}} \frac{e^{s'/C_p}}{v} \quad (8.35)$$

Figure 8.5: Plot of κ_2 as a function of the aspect ratio of an ellipsoidal thermal, using equation 31 of Tarshish, Jeevanjee, and Lecoanet (2018).

$$\implies \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{drop}}}{m_{\text{drop}}} = v \frac{\kappa_3}{l_{\text{drop}}} e^{-s'/C_P} \quad (8.36)$$

where we have used equation 8.45 (appendix 8.A).

The entropy of the drop changes due to entrainment at a rate⁵

$$\dot{s}_{\text{drop}} = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{drop}}}{m_{\text{drop}}} s' \quad (8.37)$$

while entrainment changes the momentum of the drop at a rate

$$F_{\text{entrainment}} = -\dot{m}_{\text{drop}} v \quad (8.38)$$

Note that this leads to a drag $\propto v^2$.

8.6.2 Virtual mass

When a body moves in a fluid, it also sets into motion some of the surrounding fluid. This means a body of mass m_{drop} acts like it has an inertial mass $(1 + \kappa_2) m_{\text{drop}}$, where κ_2 is called the virtual mass coefficient. For a spherical thermal, $\kappa_2 = 1/2$, while for ellipsoidal thermals, it is a known function of the aspect ratio (Tarshish, Jeevanjee, and Lecoanet 2018), plotted in figure 8.5.⁶

⁵ $m s_{\text{drop}} + s_{\text{surr}} \dot{m} dt = (m + \dot{m} dt)(s_{\text{drop}} + \dot{s}_{\text{drop}} dt)$. Note that $\dot{m}_{\text{drop}} \geq 0$ in this model.

⁶Tarshish, Jeevanjee, and Lecoanet (2018) write the virtual mass in terms of a function $f(\alpha)$, where $1 - f(\alpha) = 1/(1 + \kappa_2)$ and α is the aspect ratio.

8.6.3 Scaled equations

Putting all these effects together and performing the variable transformations given in appendix 8.D, we obtain the following set of coupled equations.

$$\dot{\tilde{z}} = \tilde{v} \quad (8.39a)$$

$$\dot{\tilde{v}} = \frac{1 - \exp(-\tilde{s}')}{1 + \kappa_2} - \text{sgn}(\tilde{v}) \frac{\kappa_3}{\tilde{l}_{\text{drop}}} \tilde{v}^2 \exp(-\tilde{s}') \quad (8.39b)$$

$$\dot{\tilde{s}'} = \tilde{v} \frac{d\tilde{s}_{\text{surr}}}{d\tilde{z}} - \frac{\kappa_3}{\tilde{l}_{\text{drop}}} \tilde{s}' \tilde{v} \exp(-\tilde{s}') \quad (8.39c)$$

$$\dot{\tilde{l}_{\text{drop}}} = -\frac{\tilde{l}_{\text{drop}}}{\tilde{v}} \dot{\tilde{v}} \quad (8.39d)$$

The last equation is a consequence of assuming the circulation of the vortex ring is conserved (see equation 8.106 in appendix 8.E.2), which holds for thin vortex rings (appendix 8.E.1).

8.6.4 Initial conditions and parameters

We need to specify \tilde{l}_{drop} , \tilde{v} , \tilde{s}' at $z = t = 0$. Additionally, we need to specify the background entropy gradient and values for κ_3 and κ_2 .

8.6.5 Value of the entrainment coefficient

The value of κ_3 depends on the initial conditions of the blob from which the vortex ring has spun up (McKim, Jeevanjee, and Lecoanet 2020, eq. 17).⁷ Lecoanet and Jeevanjee (2019) find $0.3 \lesssim \kappa_3 \lesssim 0.6$ in simulations, while they note that other people have found $\kappa_3 \approx 0.75$ and $\kappa_3 \approx 0.5$ in different laboratory experiments.

8.6.6 Sensitivity of z_{max} to κ_2

Figure 8.6 shows that varying the droplet aspect ratio between 0 and 2 only changes the penetration depth by $\approx 10\%$.

8.6.7 Relation between z_{max} and l_{drop}

We see from figure 8.7 that as long as $l_{\text{drop}} \ll H_P$, we can take $z_{\text{max}} \propto l_{\text{drop}}^{1/2}$ (with the latter being the initial value). The asymptote at the higher end is related to the fact that the addition of entrainment cannot result in a higher penetration than in the ideal (no drag or entropy loss) case.

⁷Note that McKim, Jeevanjee, and Lecoanet (2020) derive their expression for a constant background density. It is not clear if the same expression carries over to the case of a stratified atmosphere.

Figure 8.6: A plot of z_{\max} for various values of κ_2 , corresponding to droplet aspect ratios $0 \lesssim W/H \lesssim 2$. We took $\kappa_3 = 0.1$; other parameters are as in section 8.3.4.

Figure 8.7: A scaling relation between z_{\max} and the initial value of l_{drop}/H_P . The blue circles are obtained by solving equations 8.39 with $\kappa_3 = 0.1$, $\kappa_2 = 0.5$; other parameters are as in section 8.3.4. The black dashed line is arbitrarily normalized to make it coincide with the numerical results at the lower end. The orange dashed line shows the penetration obtained without entrainment ($\kappa_3 = 0$).

Morton, Taylor, and Turner (1956, see p. 16) found that the maximum height attained by an instantaneously created buoyancy perturbation in a medium with a constant density gradient is proportional to $b_0^{3/4}$, where b_0 is the initial radius of the perturbation;⁸ this is different from what we find. The reason for the difference is that Morton, Taylor, and Turner (1956) did not treat the circulation of the thermal as a conserved quantity, while we, following Anders, Lecoanet, and Brown (2019), do. While the results obtained by Morton, Taylor, and Turner (1956, fig. 9) agree with experiments where a volume of light fluid is released into saltwater tanks with a stratification in the salinity, we believe this is due to the experiments being dominated by the initial phase of vortex ring formation, where the circulation is not conserved. On the other hand, in the context of the Sun's CZ, we expect thermals which reach the bottom to already have fully developed vortex rings, for which the conservation of circulation is a good approximation.

Aside, the scaling law that we find is the same as that obtained by Morton, Taylor, and Turner (1956, see p. 7 and equation 14) for the maximum height attained by a *plume* driven by a maintained source of buoyancy in a medium with a constant density gradient.

8.6.8 Indicative numerical results

For reasonable values of parameters, we seem to obtain z_{\max} a few percent of H_P . For example, with a background polytropic index $n = 3$, $v_0 = 3 \times 10^{-2} \text{ Mm s}^{-2}$, and $s'_0/C_P = 5 \times 10^{-2}$, taking $\kappa_3 = 0.3$ and $l_{\text{drop}}/H_P = 10^{-4}$ gives $z_{\max}/H_P \approx 0.02$.

8.7 Conclusions

We have studied a number of models for the penetration of a fluid element (referred to as a thermal) into a stably stratified region. For the simplest case where drag, entrainment, and heat exchange are neglected, we have derived analytical expressions for the penetration depth. These expressions predict a penetration depth of the order of the scale height. On the other hand, in the Sun, helioseismic constraints suggest the penetration depth is a few percent of the scale height.

Including heat conduction and drag, we found that obtaining acceptable penetration depths requires these effects to be much stronger than in the Sun. Moreover, this model suffers from a profusion of free parameters.

In search of a simpler model, we considered a thin vortex ring which interacts with the surroundings by entraining fluid. We found that despite having fewer free parameters than the previously considered model, reasonable values of these parameters were able to predict penetration depths of the order of a few percent of a scale height. Interestingly, we found that the penetration depth is related to the initial size of the fluid element as $z_{\max} \propto \sqrt{l_{\text{drop}}}$. While most studies assume the

⁸They found that the maximum height is $\propto F_0^{1/4}$, with $F_0 \propto b_0^3$.

dynamics of a thermal is not very sensitive to the details of its internal structure (being determined, to the lowest order, only by volume-integrated quantities), comparison of our scaling relation with that obtained by Morton, Taylor, and Turner (1956) suggests that the internal structure plays a crucial role by determining whether the fluid circulation is a conserved quantity.

In principle, one can estimate the value of the entrainment coefficient (one of the two free parameters in the vortex ring model) at the base of the Sun's convection zone using the analytical expressions given by McKim, Jeevanjee, and Lecoanet (2020). It is not straightforward to do, as the aforementioned expression depends, for example, on the circulation of the vortex ring formed in the entropy perturbation. We are not aware of any simple way to relate this to solar observables. If possible, it would be interesting to see if the resulting entrainment coefficient predicts overshoot depths that match observations.

In our model, we have put in entrainment 'by hand', and used a few expressions plucked from the dynamics of vortex rings. It would be interesting to see if similar effects arise in a model derived from first principles. A natural progression of this work would be to incorporate the effects of shear, rotation, and magnetic fields on a propagating thermal.

Appendices to chapter 8

8.A Some thermodynamic relations

Applying the first law of thermodynamics to a perfect gas, one can show that

$$ds = C_P \left(\frac{1}{\gamma} d \ln P - d \ln \rho \right) \quad (8.40)$$

$$\implies P \rho^{-\gamma} = e^{s/C_V} \quad (8.41)$$

Now, we note that we can write the entropy gradient in terms of the polytropic index (n) and the pressure scale height (H_P) as⁹

$$\frac{ds}{dz} = \frac{C_P}{H_P} \left(\frac{1}{\gamma} - \frac{n}{n+1} \right) \quad (8.42)$$

where we have taken z pointing to the interior of the star.

If we assume the drop is composed of a perfect gas, we can write

$$\rho_{\text{drop}} = P_{\text{drop}}^{1/\gamma} e^{-s_{\text{drop}}/C_P} = P_{\text{surr}}^{1/\gamma} e^{-s_{\text{drop}}/C_P} \quad (8.43)$$

On the other hand,

$$\frac{\rho_{\text{surr}}}{P_{\text{surr}}^{1/\gamma}} = (P_{\text{surr}} \rho_{\text{surr}}^{-\gamma})^{-1/\gamma} = \exp \left(-\frac{s_{\text{surr}}}{C_P} \right) \quad (8.44)$$

$$\implies \frac{\rho_{\text{surr}}}{\rho_{\text{drop}}} = \exp \left(\frac{s_{\text{drop}} - s_{\text{surr}}}{C_P} \right) \quad (8.45)$$

8.B Calculations for an insulated sphere with v^2 drag

This appendix contains derivations of the results in section 8.4.2.

⁹ $P \propto \rho^{1+\frac{1}{n}}$; $\frac{\partial \ln P}{\partial z} \equiv \frac{1}{H_P}$

8.B.1 Small entropy perturbations

We assume μ is independent of depth, assume a constant stable (< 0) background entropy gradient, and write equation 8.25 as

$$v_0^2 = \int_0^{z_{\max}} 2ge^{2\mu z} \left[\exp \left(\frac{s_0 - s_{\text{surr}}(0) - \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} z}{C_P} \right) - 1 \right] dz \quad (8.46)$$

$$\implies \frac{v_0^2}{2g} = \int_0^{z_{\max}} \left[e^{-s'_0/C_P} \exp \left(\left\{ \frac{1}{C_P} \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| + 2\mu \right\} z \right) - e^{2\mu z} \right] dz \quad (8.47)$$

$$\implies \frac{v_0^2}{2g} = e^{-s'_0/C_P} \frac{\exp \left(\left\{ \frac{1}{C_P} \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| + 2\mu \right\} z_{\max} \right) - 1}{\frac{1}{C_P} \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| + 2\mu} - \frac{e^{2\mu z_{\max}} - 1}{2\mu} \quad (8.48)$$

$$\implies \frac{v_0^2}{2g} - \frac{1}{2\mu} = e^{-s'_0/C_P} \frac{e^{\left\{ \frac{1}{C_P} \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| + 2\mu \right\} z_{\max}}}{\frac{1}{C_P} \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| + 2\mu} - \frac{e^{-s'_0/C_P}}{\frac{1}{C_P} \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| + 2\mu} - \frac{e^{2\mu z_{\max}}}{2\mu} \quad (8.49)$$

$$\implies A_1 = e^{A_2 z_{\max}} - A_3 e^{2\mu z_{\max}} \quad (8.50)$$

$$\implies x^{A_2/2\mu} - A_3 x = A_1 \quad (8.51)$$

where

$$A_1 \equiv \left(\frac{v_0^2}{2g} - \frac{1}{2\mu} \right) \left(\frac{1}{C_P} \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| + 2\mu \right) e^{s'_0/C_P} + 1 \quad (8.52a)$$

$$A_2 \equiv \frac{1}{C_P} \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| + 2\mu > 2\mu \quad (8.52b)$$

$$A_3 \equiv \frac{1}{2\mu} \left(\frac{1}{C_P} \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| + 2\mu \right) e^{s'_0/C_P} > 1 \quad (8.52c)$$

$$x \equiv e^{2\mu z_{\max}} \quad (8.52d)$$

Note that the inequality indicated above for A_3 requires $s'_0 > 0$. We also note that $A_1 + A_3 > 1$.

The inequalities given above ensure that equation 8.51 has exactly one root corresponding to $z_{\max} > 0$.¹⁰ While we could not find a way of analytically solving equation 8.51, it is easy to numerically solve.

¹⁰The root of equation 8.51 is the intersection of the curves x^n and $A_3 x + A_1$. Note that at $x = 1$, $A_3 x + A_1 > x^n$. On the other hand, for large enough x and $n > 1$, x^n will always exceed a linear function. The two curves thus have to intersect at some $x > 1$. They cannot intersect at more than one point since the slope of x^n monotonically increases and is $> A_3$ at the intersection (it crosses the line from below).

8.B.2 Arbitrary entropy perturbations

Assuming $s'_0 \ll C_P$ and $z/z_n \sim 1$, we write¹¹

$$v_0^2 = \int_0^{z_{\max}} 2ge^{2\mu z} \left[e^{-s'_0/C_P} \exp \left(\left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| \frac{z}{C_P} \right) - 1 \right] dz \quad (8.53)$$

$$= \int_0^{z_{\max}} 2ge^{2\mu z} \left[\left(1 - \frac{s'_0}{C_P} \right) \left(1 + \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| \frac{z}{C_P} \right) - 1 \right] dz \quad (8.54)$$

$$= \int_0^{z_{\max}} 2ge^{2\mu z} \left(\left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| \frac{z}{C_P} - \frac{s'_0}{C_P} \right) dz \quad (8.55)$$

$$\implies \frac{v_0^2}{2g} = \frac{1}{C_P} \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| \frac{(2\mu z_{\max} - 1)e^{2\mu z_{\max}} + 1}{4\mu^2} - \frac{s'_0}{C_P} \frac{e^{2\mu z_{\max}} - 1}{2\mu} \quad (8.56)$$

$$\implies \frac{v_0^2 \mu C_P}{g} = \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| \frac{(2\mu z_{\max} - 1)e^{2\mu z_{\max}} + 1}{2\mu} - s'_0 (e^{2\mu z_{\max}} - 1) \quad (8.57)$$

$$\implies \frac{v_0^2 \mu C_P}{g} - s'_0 - \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| \frac{1}{2\mu} = \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| z_{\max} e^{2\mu z_{\max}} - \left(\frac{1}{2\mu} \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right| + s'_0 \right) e^{2\mu z_{\max}} \quad (8.58)$$

$$\implies A_1 = ye^y - A_2 e^y \quad (8.59)$$

where

$$A_1 \equiv \frac{2v_0^2 \mu^2 C_P}{g \left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right|} - \frac{2\mu s'_0}{\left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right|} - 1 \quad (8.60a)$$

$$A_2 \equiv 1 + \frac{2\mu s'_0}{\left| \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} \right|} \quad (8.60b)$$

$$y \equiv 2\mu z_{\max} \quad (8.60c)$$

We note that $A_2 > 1$ and $A_1 + A_2 > 0$. The solution to equation 8.59 is

$$y = A_2 + W_0(A_1 e^{-A_2}) \quad (8.61)$$

We have used the fact that $A_1 e^{-A_2} \geq -e^{-1}$ (for $A_2 > 1$) to choose the appropriate branch of the Lambert W function.

8.C Calculations for a conducting sphere with drag

This appendix contains derivations of the equations used in section section 8.5.

¹¹Note that we still assume constant μ and a constant stable background entropy gradient.

Change of the background temperature with depth We plug equation 8.41 into the hydrostatic equilibrium equation to write (here, all quantities refer to the surroundings)

$$\frac{d \ln P_{\text{surr}}}{dz} = \frac{\rho_{\text{surr}} g}{P_{\text{surr}}} \quad (8.62)$$

$$= \rho_{\text{surr}}^{1-\gamma} g e^{-s_{\text{surr}}/C_V} \quad (8.63)$$

$$= \rho_{\text{drop}}^{1-\gamma} g \exp \left[\frac{s_{\text{drop}} - s_{\text{surr}}}{C_P} (1 - \gamma) \right] e^{-s_{\text{surr}}/C_V} \quad (8.64)$$

$$= \rho_{\text{drop}}^{1-\gamma} g \exp \left(-\frac{s'}{C_P} - \gamma \frac{s_{\text{drop}}}{C_P} \right) \quad (8.65)$$

where we have used equation 8.45 (appendix 8.A). Using the ideal gas law, equation 8.40 can be written as

$$\frac{ds}{dz} = C_P \frac{d \ln T}{dz} - R \frac{d \ln P}{dz} \quad (8.66)$$

Plugging equation 8.65 into this, we obtain the following equation for the temperature gradient.

$$\frac{d \ln T_{\text{surr}}}{dz} = \frac{1}{C_P} \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} + \frac{R}{C_P} \left[\rho_{\text{drop}}^{1-\gamma} g \exp \left(-\frac{s'}{C_P} - \gamma \frac{s_{\text{drop}}}{C_P} \right) \right] \quad (8.67)$$

$$\implies \frac{dT_{\text{surr}}}{dz} = \frac{T_{\text{surr}}}{C_P} \frac{ds_{\text{surr}}}{dz} + T_{\text{surr}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\gamma} \right) \left[\rho_{\text{drop}}^{1-\gamma} g \exp \left(-\frac{s'}{C_P} - \gamma \frac{s_{\text{drop}}}{C_P} \right) \right] \quad (8.68)$$

Change in entropy of the drop due to conduction

$$\text{heat flux} = -k \nabla T \quad (8.69)$$

$$\implies \dot{q} \approx -\frac{S_{\text{drop}}}{m_{\text{drop}}} k \nabla T \quad (8.70)$$

$$\implies \dot{s}_{\text{drop}} \approx -\frac{S_{\text{drop}}}{m_{\text{drop}}} k \nabla \ln T \quad (8.71)$$

$$\implies \dot{s}_{\text{drop}} \approx -\frac{S_{\text{drop}} k}{C_P m_{\text{drop}}} \nabla s \quad (8.72)$$

$$\implies \dot{s}_{\text{drop}} \approx \frac{\alpha_1 k}{\rho_{\text{drop}} l_{\text{drop}}^2} \frac{s'}{C_P} \quad (8.73)$$

where k is the thermal conductivity of the medium, S_{drop} is the surface area of the drop, l_{drop} is some characteristic length scale of the drop, α_1 is a $\mathcal{O}(1)$ factor that depends on the geometry of the drop, and $s' \equiv s_{\text{surr}} - s_{\text{drop}}$. In the above, \dot{q} denotes the heat gain rate of the drop per unit mass. We have assumed the drop and the surroundings are at the same pressure, and that the drop is composed of a perfect gas.

We note that as mentioned in the main text, we can write the equations in terms of $\Delta s_{\text{drop}} \equiv s_{\text{drop}} - s_{\text{drop}}(0)$, which means we actually do not need to worry about specifying an initial value for s_{drop} .

For an ideal gas, we expect the thermal conductivity to be $\propto \rho v_{\text{rms}} \lambda$. This leads to the scaling $k \propto \sqrt{T}$. On the other hand, for a fully ionized plasma, we have $k \propto T^{5/2}$ in the absence of a magnetic field (Choudhuri et al. 1998, eq. 13.40). The radiative conductivity is given by (Kippenhahn, Weigert, and Weiss 2012, eq. 5.10)

$$k_{\text{rad}} = \frac{16\sigma T^3}{3c \kappa \rho} \propto \frac{T^{13/2}}{\rho^2} \quad (8.74)$$

where σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant, and κ is the opacity of the material. We have assumed the opacity goes as $\kappa \propto \rho T^{-7/2}$ (Kramers opacity law).

We write equation 8.73 as

$$\dot{s}_{\text{drop}} = \frac{\alpha_1 k_0}{\rho_{\text{drop}} l_{\text{drop}}^2} \left(\frac{T_{\text{surr}}}{T_0} \right)^{\beta_1} \left(\frac{\rho_0}{\rho_{\text{drop}}} \right)^{\beta_2} \frac{s'}{C_P} e^{\beta_2[s' - s'(0)]/C_P} \quad (8.75)$$

where k_0 , ρ_0 and T_0 denote the conductivity, drop density, and background temperature at $z = 0$. The values of β_1 and β_2 can be changed to account for different types of heat loss. For example, $\beta_1 = 6.5$ and $\beta_2 = 2$ correspond to heat loss by radiation. Note that T_{surr} is given by equation 8.68, and we have used equation 8.45 (appendix 8.A) to relate the densities of the drop and the surroundings.

Relation between drop size and density Let us assume

$$\frac{l_{\text{drop}}(z)}{l_{\text{drop}}(0)} = \left[\frac{\rho_{\text{drop}}(0)}{\rho_{\text{drop}}(z)} \right]^{1/3} \quad (8.76)$$

Evolution of drop density with time We plug

$$P_{\text{surr}} = P_{\text{drop}} = \rho_{\text{drop}}^\gamma e^{\gamma s_{\text{drop}}/C_P} \quad (8.77)$$

into the hydrostatic equilibrium equation to obtain

$$\frac{d}{dz} (\rho_{\text{drop}}^\gamma e^{\gamma s_{\text{drop}}/C_P}) = \rho_{\text{surr}} g \quad (8.78)$$

$$\implies \frac{d\rho_{\text{drop}}}{dz} \gamma \rho_{\text{drop}}^{\gamma-1} e^{\gamma s_{\text{drop}}/C_P} + \frac{\gamma}{C_P} \frac{ds_{\text{drop}}}{dz} \rho_{\text{drop}}^\gamma e^{\gamma s_{\text{drop}}/C_P} = \rho_{\text{surr}} g \quad (8.79)$$

$$\implies \frac{d\rho_{\text{drop}}}{dz} = \frac{g}{\gamma} \rho_{\text{surr}} \rho_{\text{drop}}^{1-\gamma} e^{-\gamma s_{\text{drop}}/C_P} - \frac{\rho_{\text{drop}}}{C_P} \frac{ds_{\text{drop}}}{dz} \quad (8.80)$$

$$\implies \frac{d\rho_{\text{drop}}}{dt} = \frac{g}{\gamma} v \rho_{\text{surr}} \rho_{\text{drop}}^{1-\gamma} e^{-\gamma s_{\text{drop}}/C_P} - \frac{\dot{s}_{\text{drop}}}{C_P} \rho_{\text{drop}} \quad (8.81)$$

$$\implies \frac{d\rho_{\text{drop}}}{dt} = \frac{g}{\gamma} v e^{-s'/C_P} \rho_{\text{drop}}^{2-\gamma} e^{-\gamma s_{\text{drop}}/C_P} - \frac{\dot{s}_{\text{drop}}}{C_P} \rho_{\text{drop}} \quad (8.82)$$

where we have used equation 8.45 (appendix 8.A) in the last step. Note that \dot{s}_{drop} is given by equation 8.75.

Coefficient for v^2 drag Let us assume that up to a dimensionless multiplicative constant,

$$\mu = \frac{\rho_{\text{surr}} A_{\text{drop}}}{m_{\text{drop}}} = \frac{\rho_{\text{surr}} A_{\text{drop}}}{\rho_{\text{drop}} V_{\text{drop}}} \quad (8.83)$$

where A_{drop} is a characteristic cross-sectional area of the drop. We plug equation 8.45 (appendix 8.A) into the above and write

$$\mu = \frac{\alpha_2}{l_{\text{drop}}} e^{-s'/C_P} \quad (8.84)$$

where α_2 is an $\mathcal{O}(1)$ factor that depends on the drop geometry.

Equation of motion for the drop We use the above expression for the drag coefficient and equation 8.45 to write

$$\dot{v} = \left(1 - e^{-s'/C_P}\right) g - \text{sgn}(v) \mu v^2 \quad (8.85)$$

$$= \left(1 - e^{-s'/C_P}\right) g - \frac{\alpha_2}{l_{\text{drop}}} \text{sgn}(v) v^2 e^{-s'/C_P} \quad (8.86)$$

where $v \equiv \dot{z}$, and $\text{sgn}(x) \equiv x/|x|$.

Evolution of the entropy perturbation We write

$$\dot{s}' = \dot{s}_{\text{surr}} - \dot{s}_{\text{drop}} = v \frac{\partial s_{\text{surr}}}{\partial z} - \dot{s}_{\text{drop}} \quad (8.87)$$

Note that \dot{s}_{drop} is given by equation 8.75.

We assume the overshoot zone is small enough that it is justified to assume $g = \text{constant}$. We perform the transformations given in appendix 8.D, and obtain the equations given in the main text.

8.D Definition of scaled variables

$$\tilde{s} \equiv \frac{s}{C_P} \quad (8.88)$$

$$\tilde{\rho}_{\text{drop}} \equiv \frac{\rho_{\text{drop}}}{\rho_0} \quad (8.91)$$

$$\tilde{z} \equiv \frac{z}{H_{P0}} \quad (8.89)$$

$$\tilde{T}_{\text{surr}} \equiv \frac{T_{\text{surr}}}{T_0} \quad (8.92)$$

$$\tilde{l}_{\text{drop}} \equiv \frac{l_{\text{drop}}}{H_{P0}} \quad (8.90)$$

where H_{P0} and ρ_0 denote the pressure scale height and drop density at $z = 0$. In equations where these scaled variables are used, we redefine the dot to denote derivatives wrt. $\tilde{t} \equiv t\sqrt{g/H_P}$.

8.E Evolution of vortex rings

8.E.1 Conservation of circulation for a thin vortex ring

We note that

$$\mathbf{u} \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{u}) = \nabla \left(\frac{u^2}{2} \right) - (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} \quad (8.93)$$

The momentum equation can be rewritten as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} = -\frac{\nabla P}{\rho} + \mathbf{g} \quad (8.94)$$

$$\implies \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \nabla \left(\frac{u^2}{2} \right) - \mathbf{u} \times \boldsymbol{\omega} = -\nabla \left(\frac{P}{\rho} \right) + P \nabla \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \right) - \nabla \phi_{\text{grav}} \quad (8.95)$$

$$\implies \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}}{\partial t} - \nabla \times (\mathbf{u} \times \boldsymbol{\omega}) = \nabla P \times \nabla \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \right) \quad (8.96)$$

$$\implies \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times (\mathbf{u} \times \boldsymbol{\omega}) - \frac{\bar{\rho} \mathbf{g} \times \nabla \rho}{\rho^2} \quad (8.97)$$

$$\implies \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times (\mathbf{u} \times \boldsymbol{\omega}) - \frac{\mathbf{g} \times \nabla \rho'}{\bar{\rho}} \quad (8.98)$$

$$\implies \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times \left[\mathbf{u} \times \boldsymbol{\omega} + \frac{\mathbf{g} \rho'}{\bar{\rho}} \right] \quad (8.99)$$

where we have taken $\nabla P = \bar{\rho} \mathbf{g}$ and assumed the following: small density perturbations; the variation of the mean density is parallel to \mathbf{g} ; \mathbf{g} is position-independent. Note that we have also assumed there are no pressure perturbations, since we are interested in timescales much larger than that of sound.

Consider the time derivative of the circulation about an arbitrary contour ∂S

$$\frac{d\Gamma}{dt} = \int_S \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}}{\partial t} \cdot d\mathbf{A} \quad (8.100)$$

$$= \oint_{\partial S} \left[\mathbf{u} \times \boldsymbol{\omega} + \frac{\mathbf{g} \rho'}{\bar{\rho}} \right] \cdot d\mathbf{l} \quad (8.101)$$

$$= \oint_{\partial S} \left[\mathbf{u} \times \boldsymbol{\omega} - \frac{\mathbf{g} s'}{C_P} \right] \cdot d\mathbf{l} \quad (8.102)$$

where we have used equation 8.40 in the form $s' = -C_P \rho' / \bar{\rho}$, assuming the pressure perturbations are not dynamically important. Let us assume S is a large-enough cross-section of a thin¹² vortex ring such that $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ and s' are both zero on ∂S . This then tells us that neglecting viscous effects, one can expect the circulation of a thin buoyant vortex ring evolving in a stratified atmosphere to be conserved.

¹²The thinness is required to allow the following conditions to be satisfied for a ∂S passing inside the vortex ring. If ∂S does not pass inside the vortex ring, the circulation is trivially zero, and this result doesn't tell us much. Note that this result does not forbid vortex ring spin-up from an initial perturbation.

8.E.2 Radius of a vortex ring travelling in a stratified medium

For a thin vortex ring, the impulse is given by (Batchelor 2000, eq. 7.2.14)

$$I = \pi \rho r^2 \Gamma \quad (8.103)$$

$$= \pi \Gamma r^2 \frac{m_{\text{drop}}}{V_{\text{drop}}} = \frac{\pi \Gamma m_{\text{drop}}}{\kappa_1 r} \quad (8.104)$$

where we have taken $V_{\text{drop}} \equiv \kappa_1 r^3$. κ_1 is some constant which we assume does not vary as the vortex ring evolves. We assume the z-axis points down.

We also assume that the velocity of a vortex ring is related to its impulse by

$$I = (1 + \kappa_2) m_{\text{drop}} v \quad (8.105)$$

where κ_2 is the virtual mass coefficient.

We note that putting equations 8.104 and 8.105 together gives us

$$vr = \frac{\pi \Gamma}{\kappa_1 (1 + \kappa_2)} \quad (8.106)$$

Note that this holds even if m_{drop} varies with time. If we assume the vortex ring is thin, the circulation will be conserved (see section 8.E.1). This equation then tells us that $vr = \text{constant}$. Equation 8.106 can also be obtained from equations 7 and 8 of Lecoanet and Jeevanjee (2019), although they have not explicitly noted this relation.

Chapter 9

Shell models for convection

9.1 Introduction

In section 1.1, we described the problems with the current paradigm of convection. As we saw there, some proposed resolutions of these problems appeal to the fact that the dimensionless numbers characterizing solar convection are much more extreme than what can be achieved in simulations. For example, the Rayleigh number (Ra, which characterizes the strength of the convective driving) is 10^{20} in the Sun (Schumacher and Sreenivasan 2020, table 1), while current simulations reach 10^9 at best (e.g. Käpylä 2021).

Geophysical and laboratory flows are typically at Prandtl numbers (Pr) close to or much larger than one. On the other hand, stellar convection takes place at very low Pr; e.g. in the solar convection zone, $\text{Pr} \sim 10^{-6}$ (Schumacher and Sreenivasan 2020). It is difficult to perform simulations with Pr significantly different from unity, due to the wide range of scales that need to be simultaneously resolved. Most 3D simulations of stellar convection are run with enhanced diffusivities and $\text{Pr} \sim 1$; e.g. the ASH simulations (Miesch et al. 2008) use $\text{Pr} = 0.25$. Others (Hotta and Kusano 2021; Hotta, Iijima, and Kusano 2019) use artificial diffusion schemes, but still seem to have $\text{Pr} \sim 1$.

Orvedahl et al. (2018) have examined the effects of changes in Pr on the amplitude and spectral distribution of convective flows. While they find faster flows in simulations with a lower Pr, the spectral distribution of the velocity remains similar to the $\text{Pr} = 1$ cases (Featherstone and Hindman 2016b), thus suggesting that the spectra are rather insensitive to changes in Pr. For a similar range of Pr, Käpylä (2021) finds that despite the velocity spectra being rather insensitive to Pr, the nature of convection changes significantly, with stronger downflows and larger overshoot depths at low Pr. Convection at low Pr appears very turbulent, yet less efficient: with decreasing Pr, larger velocity amplitudes are needed to convect the same amount of energy.

It seems to be common to make assertions about the nature of low-Pr convection based on the simplified system of equations derived by Spiegel (1962). However,

we note (as recognized by Lignières (1999)) that the aforementioned equations are only valid at low Peclet number (Pe, the ratio of the thermal diffusion timescale to the advection timescale); they are thus not applicable to the solar convection zone, where $Pe = Re Pr \sim 10^7$ (Schumacher and Sreenivasan 2020). We are not aware of any simplified versions of the equations governing convection in the simultaneous limit of high Peclet number and low Prandtl number.

Given the complexity of solar convection and the infeasibility of fully resolved simulations, simplified models of convection may help us understand which effects are important. We present one such simplified model, based on a generalization of ‘shell models’. Shell models (Yamada and Ohkitani 1987; Brandenburg 1992; L’vov et al. 1998) are simplified models of turbulence that have proved successful in deepening our understanding of energy cascades in homogeneous, isotropic turbulence (for a review, see Biferale 2003). Shell models representing convection in a thin layer (the Boussinesq approximation) have been studied in the past (Brandenburg 1992; Kumar and Verma 2015). While shell models are themselves quite interesting, our attitude towards them is that they are relatively simple systems that nevertheless qualitatively capture some aspects of turbulent energy cascades.

Section 9.2 describes how the notion of a shell model can be generalized to a stratified system. Section 9.3 gives the parameters and dimensionless numbers characterizing the constructed model. We analyse some numerical solutions of the resulting model in section 9.4. Finally, we summarize our conclusions in section 9.5.

9.2 Construction of the shell model

9.2.1 Simplifying the equations of motion

Let us start with the following equations of motion for an ideal gas in a nonrotating plane-parallel domain without magnetic fields:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v}) \quad (9.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} = -(\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} - \frac{\nabla p}{\rho} + \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{g} \quad (9.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial s}{\partial t} = -\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla s + \frac{\kappa C_P}{T} \nabla^2 T \quad (9.3)$$

$$T \propto \rho^{\gamma-1} \exp\left(\frac{s}{C_V}\right) \quad (9.4)$$

$$p = \rho RT \quad (9.5)$$

where ρ is the density; \mathbf{v} is the velocity; p is the pressure; ν is the kinematic viscosity; \mathbf{g} is the acceleration due to gravity; s is the specific entropy; κ is the thermal diffusivity (which may include both conduction and radiation); T is the

temperature; C_P is the specific heat at constant pressure; C_V is the specific heat at constant volume; $\gamma \equiv C_P/C_V$; $R \equiv C_P - C_V$; and t is the time. We have neglected the effects of compressibility on viscous dissipation; neglected viscous heating; neglected the effect of density variations on the thermal conductivity; neglected internal heat sources/sinks; and assumed ν , κ , R , and C_P are constant throughout the domain.

For every quantity \square , we perform the split

$$\square = \square_0 + \square' \quad (9.6)$$

where \square_0 represents a ‘background’, and \square' represents deviations from this background. \square' may be a function of both a ‘small-scale coordinate’ and a ‘large-scale’ vertical coordinate. We assume $\mathbf{v}_0 = 0$, so that $\mathbf{v}' = \mathbf{v}$. Further, we assume the background quantities are prescribed solutions of the equations of motion, and do not evolve with time (i.e. the background state is in hydrostatic equilibrium, and satisfies the ideal gas equation).

The equations of motion are

$$\frac{\partial \rho'}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (\rho_0 \mathbf{v}) - \nabla \cdot (\rho' \mathbf{v}) \quad (9.7)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} = -(\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} - \frac{\nabla p}{\rho} + \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{g} \quad (9.8)$$

$$\frac{\partial s'}{\partial t} = -\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla s_0 - \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla s' + \frac{\kappa C_P}{T} \nabla^2 T + \kappa C_P (\nabla \ln \rho) \cdot (\nabla \ln T) \quad (9.9)$$

$$T' = T_0 \left[(\gamma - 1) \frac{\rho'}{\rho_0} + \frac{s'}{C_V} \right] \quad (9.10)$$

$$p' = \rho' R T_0 + \rho_0 R T' + \rho' R T' \quad (9.11)$$

where we have used the incompressible form of viscous dissipation for the momentum equation, and neglected viscous heating in the entropy equation.^{1,2} Note that the dynamical variables are ρ' , \mathbf{v} , and s' (T' and p' are just auxiliary variables that allow us to write the equations more compactly).

Dropping various terms which we expect to be nonessential, recalling that the background is in hydrostatic equilibrium, and simplifying some of the more complicated terms, we write the equations of motion as

$$\frac{\partial \rho'}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (\rho_0 \mathbf{v}) - \nabla \cdot (\rho' \mathbf{v}) \quad (9.12)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} = -(\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} - \frac{\nabla p'}{\rho_0} + \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{v} + \frac{\rho' \mathbf{g}}{\rho_0} \quad (9.13)$$

¹The $\nabla \ln \rho$ term in the momentum equation comes because we have assumed κ (and not k) is constant. Anyway, we will soon discard this term, so the reader need not worry about it.

²Brandenburg (1992) also drop the viscous heating term, so at least it seems to be a standard thing to do while studying convection.

$$\frac{\partial s'}{\partial t} = -\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla s_0 - \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla s' + \frac{\kappa C_P}{T_0} \nabla^2 T' \quad (9.14)$$

$$T' = T_0 \left[(\gamma - 1) \frac{\rho'}{\rho_0} + \frac{s'}{C_V} \right] \quad (9.15)$$

$$p' = \rho' R T_0 + \rho_0 R T' \quad (9.16)$$

9.2.2 Shellification

We now Fourier-transform the small-scale variable (say \mathbf{r}) to the wavevector \mathbf{k} , and restrict the allowed values of k to

$$k_n = k_1 h^{n-1} \quad , \text{ where } n = 1, 2, 3, \dots N \quad (9.17)$$

We further assume everything depends only on the magnitude of the small-scale wavenumber, and replace convolutions over the small-scale wavenumber by summations over neighbouring shells. The Fourier transform of every quantity $\square'(\mathbf{r}, Z)$ is now denoted by $\square_n(Z)$ (where Z is the large-scale coordinate). We will use $\square_0(Z)$ to denote the (prescribed) background quantities, as before. The equations of motion are then (for $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots N$)

$$\frac{\partial \rho_n}{\partial t} = -ik_n v_n \rho_0 - \bar{\partial}(v_n \rho_0) - ik_n \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p} \rho_{n+q} - \bar{\partial} \left(\sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p} \rho_{n+q} \right) \quad (9.18a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial v_n}{\partial t} = & - \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} i v_{n+p} k_{n+q} v_{n+q} - \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p} \bar{\partial} v_{n+q} \\ & - \frac{ik_n p_n}{\rho_0} - \frac{\bar{\partial} p_n}{\rho_0} - \nu k_n^2 v_n + \frac{\rho_n g}{\rho_0} \end{aligned} \quad (9.18b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial t} = & - v_n \bar{\partial} s_0 - \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} i v_{n+p} k_{n+q} s_{n+q} - \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p} \bar{\partial} s_{n+q} \\ & - \frac{\kappa C_P}{T_0} k_n^2 T_n + \frac{\kappa C_P}{T_0} \bar{\partial}^2 T_n \end{aligned} \quad (9.18c)$$

$$T_n = T_0 \left[(\gamma - 1) \frac{\rho_n}{\rho_0} + \frac{s_n}{C_V} \right] \quad (9.18d)$$

$$p_n = \rho_n R T_0 + \rho_0 R T_n \quad (9.18e)$$

where we have used $\bar{\partial}$ to denote d/dZ , and we do not use the summation convention. The symbol ‘*, ∞ ’ on top of the summations denotes that we also sum over complex conjugates of the arguments and that each term in the sum may be multiplied by a different constant. The velocity vector has been replaced by a scalar field to further simplify the model. Shell models have been constructed in the past with both complex (Yamada and Ohkitani 1987; L’vov et al. 1998) and real (Brandenburg 1992) variables. We note that while in principle, linkages only need be allowed

between adjacent shells (i.e. between, say, n and $n+1$), many models allow linkages with next-neighbour shells as well (Yamada and Ohkitani 1987; L’vov et al. 1998).³

Aside, in the GOY model (L’vov et al. 1998, eq. 1), the advection term has a part of the kind that doesn’t seem to be explicitly written here ($k_n u_{n+1} u_{n-1}$). However, such terms can be included by multiplying some of the terms in the summation by powers of h .

9.2.3 Vertical discretization

Above, the ‘shell variables’ (e.g. ρ_n) are still continuous functions of Z (the large-scale coordinate). We now discretize the vertical direction, assuming that all quantities are defined only on a discrete set of ‘levels’ which are indexed by $m = 1, 2, 3, \dots, M$. For all variables \square , we take $\square_n(Z) \rightarrow \square_{n,m}$. The ‘vertical derivatives’ ∂ above can be approximated by finite differences (i.e. summations over neighbouring levels). Denoting the spacing between levels by ΔZ_m and assuming this is a constant, vertical derivatives can be written as, e.g.,

$$\partial \rho_0 \rightarrow \frac{\rho_{0,m+1} - \rho_{0,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} \quad (9.19)$$

We then write (for $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$ and $m = 1, 2, 3, \dots, M$)

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\rho_{n,m}}{dt} = & -ik_n v_{n,m} \rho_{0,m} - \frac{v_{n,m+1} \rho_{0,m+1} - v_{n,m-1} \rho_{0,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} \\ & - ik_n \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} \rho_{n+q,m} - \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} \frac{v_{n+p,m+1} \rho_{n+q,m+1} - v_{n+p,m-1} \rho_{n+q,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} \end{aligned} \quad (9.20)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dv_{n,m}}{dt} = & -i \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} k_{n+q} v_{n+q,m} - \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} \frac{v_{n+q,m+1} - v_{n+q,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} \\ & - \frac{ik_n p_{n,m}}{\rho_{0,m}} - \frac{p_{n,m+1} - p_{n,m-1}}{2\rho_{0,m} \Delta Z_m} - \nu k_n^2 v_{n,m} + g \frac{\rho_{n,m}}{\rho_{0,m}} \end{aligned} \quad (9.21)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{ds_{n,m}}{dt} = & -v_{n,m} \frac{s_{0,m+1} - s_{0,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} - i \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p} k_{n+q} s_{n+q} \\ & - \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} \frac{s_{n+q,m+1} - s_{n+q,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} - \frac{\kappa C_P}{T_{0,m}} k_n^2 T_{n,m} \\ & + \frac{\kappa C_P}{T_{0,m}} \frac{T_{n,m+1} - 2T_{n,m} + T_{n,m-1}}{\Delta Z_m^2} \end{aligned} \quad (9.22)$$

$$T_{n,m} = T_{0,m} \left[(\gamma - 1) \frac{\rho_{n,m}}{\rho_{0,m}} + \frac{s_{n,m}}{C_V} \right] \quad (9.23)$$

³The penultimate paragraph of Brandenburg (1992) discusses the importance of such terms.

$$p_{n,m} = \rho_{n,m}RT_{0,m} + \rho_{0,m}RT_{n,m} \quad (9.24)$$

The condition of hydrostatic equilibrium leads to the following constraint on the background profile:

$$\Delta Z_m = \frac{p_{0,m+1} - p_{0,m}}{2\rho_{0,m}g} \quad (9.25)$$

A rule of thumb in 3D simulations of stratified convection is to have at least 5 grid points per scale height. However, given the drastic simplifications inherent in shell models (all angular dependence in wavenumber-space is dropped, and further one typically chooses the ratio between the wavenumbers of successive shells as $h = 2$), we do not see any reason to hew to such a criterion. To qualitatively understand the effect of stratification on convection, we consider it enough to take a very small number of levels.

9.2.4 Nondimensionalization

We now choose units such that $C_P = \kappa = \rho_{0,1} = k_1 = 1$. More explicitly, length is measured in units of k_1^{-1} ; mass in units of $\rho_{0,1}k_1^{-3}$; time in units of $\kappa^{-1}k_1^{-2}$; entropy in units of C_P ; and temperature in units of $\kappa^2k_1^2C_P^{-1}$. In these units, the equations of the model become

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\rho_{n,m}}{dt} = & -ik_n v_{n,m}\rho_{0,m} - \frac{v_{n,m+1}\rho_{0,m+1} - v_{n,m-1}\rho_{0,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} \\ & - ik_n \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m}\rho_{n+q,m} - \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} \frac{v_{n+p,m+1}\rho_{n+q,m+1} - v_{n+p,m-1}\rho_{n+q,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} \end{aligned} \quad (9.26a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dv_{n,m}}{dt} = & -i \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m}k_{n+q}v_{n+q,m} - \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} \frac{v_{n+q,m+1} - v_{n+q,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} \\ & - \frac{ik_n p_{n,m}}{\rho_{0,m}} - \frac{p_{n,m+1} - p_{n,m-1}}{2\rho_{0,m}\Delta Z_m} - \nu k_n^2 v_{n,m} + g \frac{\rho_{n,m}}{\rho_{0,m}} \end{aligned} \quad (9.26b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{ds_{n,m}}{dt} = & -v_{n,m} \frac{s_{0,m+1} - s_{0,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} - i \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m}k_{n+q}s_{n+q,m} \\ & - \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} \frac{s_{n+q,m+1} - s_{n+q,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} - \frac{k_n^2 T_{n,m}}{T_{0,m}} \\ & + \frac{T_{n,m+1} - 2T_{n,m} + T_{n,m-1}}{T_{0,m}\Delta Z_m^2} \end{aligned} \quad (9.26c)$$

$$T_{n,m} = T_{0,m} \left[(\gamma - 1) \frac{\rho_{n,m}}{\rho_{0,m}} + \gamma s_{n,m} \right] \quad (9.26d)$$

$$p_{n,m} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{\gamma} \right) (\rho_{n,m}T_{0,m} + \rho_{0,m}T_{n,m}) \quad (9.26e)$$

where ν is now the Prandtl number.

9.2.5 Consistency checks

9.2.5.1 Momentum density

Consider the evolution equation for $\rho\mathbf{v}$ for an inviscid fluid (which follows from equations 9.1 and 9.2):

$$\frac{\partial(\rho\mathbf{v})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho\mathbf{v} \otimes \mathbf{v}) = -\nabla p + \rho\mathbf{g} \quad (9.27)$$

$$= -\nabla p' + \rho'\mathbf{g} \quad (9.28)$$

where in the last step, we have assumed the background is in hydrostatic equilibrium. If we require $\mathbf{v} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} = 0$ on the boundaries (where $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ is the outward normal), integrating the above over the domain gives us

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int \rho\mathbf{v} \, dV = \int (-\nabla p' + \rho'\mathbf{g}) \, dV \quad (9.29)$$

$$\implies \frac{d}{dt} \int \rho'\mathbf{v} \, dV = \int (-\nabla p' + \rho'\mathbf{g}) \, dV - \frac{d}{dt} \int \rho_0\mathbf{v} \, dV \quad (9.30)$$

We now note (using equation 9.2 with $\nu = 0$) that

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int \rho_0\mathbf{v} \, dV = \int \rho_0 \frac{\partial\mathbf{v}}{\partial t} \, dV \quad (9.31)$$

$$= \int \rho_0 \left(-(\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{v} - \frac{\nabla p}{\rho} + \mathbf{g} \right) \, dV \quad (9.32)$$

$$= \int \rho_0 \left[-(\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{v} - \frac{\nabla p_0}{\rho_0} \left(1 - \frac{\rho'}{\rho_0} + \frac{\rho'\rho'}{\rho_0^2} \right) - \frac{\nabla p'}{\rho_0} \left(1 - \frac{\rho'}{\rho_0} \right) + \mathbf{g} \right] \, dV \quad (9.33)$$

$$= \int \left[-(\rho_0\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{v} + \rho'\mathbf{g} - \frac{\rho'\rho'\mathbf{g}}{\rho_0} - \nabla p' + \frac{\rho'\nabla p'}{\rho_0} \right] \, dV \quad (9.34)$$

$$= \int \left[\mathbf{v} [\nabla \cdot (\rho_0\mathbf{v})] + \rho'\mathbf{g} - \frac{\rho'\rho'\mathbf{g}}{\rho_0} - \nabla p' + \frac{\rho'\nabla p'}{\rho_0} \right] \, dV \quad (9.35)$$

Putting this in equation 9.30, we obtain

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int \rho'\mathbf{v} \, dV = \int \left(-\mathbf{v} [\nabla \cdot (\rho_0\mathbf{v})] + \frac{\rho'\rho'\mathbf{g}}{\rho_0} - \frac{\rho'\nabla p'}{\rho_0} \right) \, dV \quad (9.36)$$

Analogous to the above, we require a shell model to satisfy the following equation

whenever $v_{n,1} = v_{n,M} = 0$:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{d}{dt} \sum_{m,n} \rho_{n,m} v_{n,m}^* \Delta Z_m \\
&= - \sum_{m,n} i k_n v_{n,m}^* v_{n,m} \rho_{0,m} \Delta Z_m - \sum_{m,n} v_{n,m}^* \frac{v_{n,m+1} \rho_{0,m+1} - v_{n,m-1} \rho_{0,m-1}}{2} \\
&+ \sum_{m,n} \rho_{n,m} \frac{i k_n p_{n,m}^*}{\rho_{0,m}} \Delta Z_m - \sum_{m,n} \rho_{n,m} \frac{p_{n,m+1}^* - p_{n,m-1}^*}{2 \rho_{0,m}} \\
&+ \sum_{m,n} \frac{\rho_{n,m}^* \rho_{n,m} g}{\rho_{0,m}} \Delta Z_m
\end{aligned} \tag{9.37}$$

which can be written using equations 9.26a and 9.26b (dropping the viscous terms) as

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{m,n} \Delta Z_m \left\{ - i k_n v_{n,m}^* \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} \rho_{n+q,m} \right. \\
&\quad - v_{n,m}^* \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} \frac{v_{n+p,m+1} \rho_{n+q,m+1} - v_{n+p,m-1} \rho_{n+q,m-1}}{2 \Delta Z_m} \\
&\quad + i \rho_{n,m} \left(\sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} k_{n+q} v_{n+q,m} \right)^* \\
&\quad \left. - \rho_{n,m} \left(\sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} \frac{v_{n+q,m+1} - v_{n+q,m-1}}{2 \Delta Z_m} \right)^* \right\} = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{9.38}$$

A set of sufficient (but not necessary) conditions for the above to be satisfied is

$$\sum_n \left\{ - i k_n v_{n,m}^* \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} \rho_{n+q,m} + i \rho_{n,m} \left(\sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} k_{n+q} v_{n+q,m} \right)^* \right\} = 0 \tag{9.39}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{m,n} \left\{ - v_{n,m}^* \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} \frac{v_{n+p,m+1} \rho_{n+q,m+1} - v_{n+p,m-1} \rho_{n+q,m-1}}{2} \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \rho_{n,m} \left(\sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} \frac{v_{n+q,m+1} - v_{n+q,m-1}}{2} \right)^* \right\} = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{9.40}$$

9.2.5.2 Entropy conservation

In the inviscid, insulating case (i.e. when $\nu = \kappa = 0$), the cascade process should also conserve entropy. Equation 9.3 can be written (using the continuity equation) as

$$\rho T \frac{\partial s}{\partial t} + \rho T \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla s = 0 \tag{9.41}$$

$$\implies \rho \frac{\partial s}{\partial t} + \rho \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla s = 0 \quad (9.42)$$

$$\implies \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho s) + \nabla \cdot (\rho s \mathbf{v}) = 0 \quad (9.43)$$

If we require $\mathbf{v} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} = 0$ on the boundaries (where $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ is the outward normal), integrating the above over the domain gives us

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int \rho s \, dV = 0 \quad (9.44)$$

$$\implies \frac{d}{dt} \int \rho' s' \, dV = -\frac{d}{dt} \int \rho_0 s' \, dV - \frac{d}{dt} \int \rho' s_0 \, dV \quad (9.45)$$

We now note (using equation 9.3 with $\nu = \kappa = 0$) that

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int \rho_0 s' \, dV = \int \rho_0 \frac{\partial s'}{\partial t} \, dV \quad (9.46)$$

$$= - \int \rho_0 (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) s \, dV \quad (9.47)$$

$$= - \int \rho_0 (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) s_0 \, dV - \int \rho_0 (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) s' \, dV \quad (9.48)$$

$$= - \int \rho_0 (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) s_0 \, dV + \int s' [\nabla \cdot (\rho_0 \mathbf{v})] \, dV \quad (9.49)$$

and (using equation 9.1)

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int \rho' s_0 \, dV = \int \frac{\partial \rho'}{\partial t} s_0 \, dV \quad (9.50)$$

$$= - \int s_0 \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v}) \, dV \quad (9.51)$$

$$= - \int s_0 \nabla \cdot (\rho_0 \mathbf{v}) \, dV - \int s_0 \nabla \cdot (\rho' \mathbf{v}) \, dV \quad (9.52)$$

$$= - \int s_0 \nabla \cdot (\rho_0 \mathbf{v}) \, dV + \int \rho' (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) s_0 \, dV \quad (9.53)$$

Putting equations 9.49 and 9.53 in equation 9.45, we find that

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int \rho' s' \, dV = - \int s' [\nabla \cdot (\rho_0 \mathbf{v})] \, dV - \int \rho' (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) s_0 \, dV \quad (9.54)$$

Analogous to the above, we require a shell model to satisfy the following equation whenever $v_{n,1} = v_{n,M} = 0$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dt} \sum_{m,n} \rho_{n,m} s_{n,m}^* \Delta Z_m \\ &= -i \sum_{m,n} k_n v_{n,m} \rho_{0,m} s_{n,m}^* \Delta Z_m - \sum_{m,n} s_{n,m}^* \frac{v_{n,m+1} \rho_{0,m+1} - v_{n,m-1} \rho_{0,m-1}}{2} \\ & \quad - \sum_{m,n} \rho_{n,m} v_{n,m}^* \frac{s_{0,m+1} - s_{0,m-1}}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (9.55)$$

which can be written using equations 9.26a and 9.26c (dropping the conductive terms) as

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{m,n} \Delta Z_m \left\{ -ik_n s_{n,m}^* \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} \rho_{n+q,m} \right. \\ - s_{n,m}^* \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} \frac{v_{n+p,m+1} \rho_{n+q,m+1} - v_{n+p,m-1} \rho_{n+q,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} \\ + i\rho_{n,m} \left(\sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} k_{n+q} s_{n+q,m} \right)^* \\ \left. - \rho_{n,m} \left(\sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} \frac{s_{n+q,m+1} - s_{n+q,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} \right)^* \right\} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9.56)$$

A set of sufficient (but not necessary) conditions for the above to be satisfied is

$$\sum_n \left[-ik_n s_{n,m}^* \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} \rho_{n+q,m} + i\rho_{n,m} \left(\sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} k_{n+q} s_{n+q,m} \right)^* \right] = 0 \quad (9.57)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{m,n} \left[-s_{n,m}^* \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} \frac{v_{n+p,m+1} \rho_{n+q,m+1} - v_{n+p,m-1} \rho_{n+q,m-1}}{2} \right. \\ \left. - \rho_{n,m} \left(\sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} \frac{s_{n+q,m+1} - s_{n+q,m-1}}{2} \right)^* \right] = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9.58)$$

9.2.6 A choice of coefficients

Equations 9.26 still contain various undefined sums (denoted by $\sum^{*,\infty}$); the specification of the terms in these summations is part of the specification of a shell model. The choice made needs to be in accordance with equations 9.39, 9.40, 9.57, and 9.58 (section 9.2.5). We make the following choices for the shell-linkage terms in equation 9.26b:

$$\begin{aligned} -i \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} k_{n+q} v_{n+q,m} \longrightarrow iC_1 k_{n+1} v_{n+2,m} v_{n+1,m}^* + iC_2 k_n v_{n+1,m} v_{n-1,m}^* \\ - iC_3 k_{n-1} v_{n-1,m} v_{n-2,m} \end{aligned} \quad (9.59)$$

$$- \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} \frac{v_{n+q,m+1} - v_{n+q,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} \longrightarrow 0 \quad (9.60)$$

The first relation above has been directly taken from a model for homogeneous, isotropic turbulence (L'vov et al. 1998, eq. 21). To satisfy the constraints (equations

9.39 and 9.40), the shell linkages in equation 9.26a may be

$$-ik_n \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} \rho_{n+q,m} \longrightarrow iC_1^* k_{n-1} \rho_{n-2,m} v_{n-1,m} + iC_2^* k_{n-1} \rho_{n-1,m} v_{n-2,m} - iC_3^* k_{n+1} \rho_{n+2,m} v_{n+1,m} \quad (9.61)$$

$$- \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} \frac{v_{n+p,m+1} \rho_{n+q,m+1} - v_{n+p,m-1} \rho_{n+q,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} \longrightarrow 0 \quad (9.62)$$

This implies (via equations 9.57 and 9.58) the following is a possible choice of linkages in equation 9.26c:

$$-i \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} k_{n+q} s_{n+q,m} \longrightarrow iC_1 k_{n+1} v_{n+1,m}^* s_{n+2,m} + iC_2 k_n v_{n-1,m}^* s_{n+1,m} - iC_3 k_{n-1} v_{n-1,m} s_{n-2,m} \quad (9.63)$$

$$- \sum_{p,q}^{*,\infty} v_{n+p,m} \frac{s_{n+q,m+1} - s_{n+q,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} \longrightarrow 0 \quad (9.64)$$

Equations 9.26 then become

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\rho_{n,m}}{dt} = & -ik_n v_{n,m} \rho_{0,m} - \frac{v_{n,m+1} \rho_{0,m+1} - v_{n,m-1} \rho_{0,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} \\ & + iC_1^* k_{n-1} \rho_{n-2,m} v_{n-1,m} + iC_2^* k_{n-1} \rho_{n-1,m} v_{n-2,m} \\ & - iC_3^* k_{n+1} \rho_{n+2,m} v_{n+1,m} \end{aligned} \quad (9.65a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dv_{n,m}}{dt} = & iC_1 k_{n+1} v_{n+2,m} v_{n+1,m}^* + iC_2 k_n v_{n+1,m} v_{n-1,m}^* \\ & - iC_3 k_{n-1} v_{n-1,m} v_{n-2,m} - \frac{ik_n p_{n,m}}{\rho_{0,m}} - \frac{p_{n,m+1} - p_{n,m-1}}{2\rho_{0,m} \Delta Z_m} \\ & - \nu k_n^2 v_{n,m} + g \frac{\rho_{n,m}}{\rho_{0,m}} \end{aligned} \quad (9.65b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{ds_{n,m}}{dt} = & -v_{n,m} \frac{s_{0,m+1} - s_{0,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} + iC_1 k_{n+1} v_{n+1,m}^* s_{n+2,m} \\ & + iC_2 k_n v_{n-1,m}^* s_{n+1,m} - iC_3 k_{n-1} v_{n-1,m} s_{n-2,m} \\ & - \frac{k_n^2 T_{n,m}}{T_{0,m}} + \frac{T_{n,m+1} - 2T_{n,m} + T_{n,m-1}}{T_{0,m} \Delta Z_m^2} \end{aligned} \quad (9.65c)$$

$$T_{n,m} = T_{0,m} \left[(\gamma - 1) \frac{\rho_{n,m}}{\rho_{0,m}} + \gamma s_{n,m} \right] \quad (9.65d)$$

$$p_{n,m} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{\gamma} \right) (\rho_{n,m} T_{0,m} + \rho_{0,m} T_{n,m}) \quad (9.65e)$$

where ΔZ_m (equation 9.25) is a constant, and $1 \leq n \leq N$.

9.2.7 Background specification

The equations above involve the background quantities $s_{0,m}$, $\rho_{0,m}$, $T_{0,m}$, and $p_{0,m}$. If the background quantities satisfy the ideal gas equation, the first law of thermodynamics, and the equation of hydrostatic equilibrium (equation 9.25; recall that we have assumed ΔZ_m is a constant), we need to specify the profile of one quantity, along with the values of two quantities at a single point. To this end, we will specify $s_{0,m}$, $\rho_{0,1}$, and $T_{0,1}$.

The equation of hydrostatic equilibrium can be written (using the ideal gas equation) in the form

$$\nabla \ln T_0 + \nabla \ln \rho_0 = \frac{g}{RT_0} \quad (9.66)$$

while the first law of thermodynamics is

$$\nabla s_0 = C_V \nabla \ln T_0 - R \nabla \ln \rho_0 \quad (9.67)$$

Combining these, we write

$$C_P \nabla \ln T_0 = \frac{g}{T_0} + \nabla s_0 \quad (9.68)$$

$$\implies \nabla T_0 = \frac{g}{C_P} + \frac{T_0}{C_P} \nabla s_0 \quad (9.69)$$

Discretizing as before, we find

$$\frac{T_{0,m+1} - T_{0,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} = \frac{g}{C_P} + \frac{T_{0,m}}{C_P} \frac{s_{0,m+1} - s_{0,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} \quad (9.70)$$

$$\implies T_{0,m+1} = T_{0,m-1} + \frac{2g\Delta Z_m}{C_P} + \frac{T_{0,m}}{C_P} (s_{0,m+1} - s_{0,m-1}) \quad (9.71)$$

Equation 9.67 can be rewritten as

$$\nabla \rho_0 = \frac{C_V \rho_0}{RT_0} \nabla T_0 - \frac{\rho_0}{R} \nabla s_0 \quad (9.72)$$

Discretizing it, we find

$$\rho_{0,m+1} = \rho_{0,m-1} + \frac{C_V \rho_{0,m}}{RT_{0,m}} (T_{0,m+1} - T_{0,m-1}) - \frac{\rho_{0,m}}{R} (s_{0,m+1} - s_{0,m-1}) \quad (9.73)$$

The ideal gas equation can be written as

$$p_{0,m+1} = R \rho_{0,m+1} T_{0,m+1} \quad (9.74)$$

Setting $C_P = 1$, we write equations 9.71, 9.73, and 9.74 as

$$T_{0,m+1} = T_{0,m-1} + 2g\Delta Z_m + T_{0,m} (s_{0,m+1} - s_{0,m-1}) \quad (9.75a)$$

$$\rho_{0,m+1} = \rho_{0,m-1} + \frac{1}{\gamma - 1} \frac{\rho_{0,m}}{T_{0,m}} (T_{0,m+1} - T_{0,m-1}) - \left(1 - \frac{1}{\gamma}\right) \rho_{0,m} (s_{0,m+1} - s_{0,m-1}) \quad (9.75b)$$

$$p_{0,m+1} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{\gamma}\right) \rho_{0,m+1} T_{0,m+1} \quad (9.75c)$$

These equations determine the values of $\rho_{0,m}$, $T_{0,m}$, and $p_{0,m}$ (given $s_{0,m}$, $\rho_{0,1}$, $T_{0,1}$, g , and ΔZ_m).

9.2.8 Reduction to the limit of infinite sound speed

The shell model described by equations 9.65 turns out to be numerically unstable unless an extra dissipation term is added to the continuity equation.⁴ The addition of such terms would complicate the interpretation of the resulting shell model; in fact, it is suspected (e.g. Brandenburg 2016, p. 2) that such artificially enhanced diffusivities are the reason numerical simulations of the deep solar convection zone don't agree with helioseismic observations.

To simplify the obtained equations, let us assume the sound speed is infinite. This means we will neglect pressure fluctuations in the equation of state. We write the ideal gas equation as

$$\frac{\rho'}{\rho_0} \approx -\frac{T'}{T_0} \quad (9.76)$$

Using this, equation 9.10 becomes

$$T' \approx \frac{T_0 s'}{C_P} \quad (9.77)$$

If we use equations 9.76 and 9.77 to eliminate ρ' from the equations of motion, we can proceed without solving the continuity equation.

To obtain a shell model in this limit, we can simply perform the following replacements (motivated by equations 9.76 and 9.77) in equations 9.65 (recall that we have set $C_P = 1$):

$$\frac{\rho_{n,m}}{\rho_{0,m}} \rightarrow -\frac{T_{n,m}}{T_{0,m}} \quad (9.78)$$

$$T_{n,m} \rightarrow T_{0,m} s_{n,m} \quad (9.79)$$

Further making the conventional choice of modelling the pressure term in the momentum equation by a term quadratic in the velocity (Ditlevsen 2010, pp. 48, 53), one then obtains

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial v_{n,m}}{\partial t} = & iC_1 k_{n+1} v_{n+2,m} v_{n+1,m}^* + iC_2 k_n v_{n+1,m} v_{n-1,m}^* \\ & - iC_3 k_{n-1} v_{n-1,m} v_{n-2,m} - \nu k_n^2 v_{n,m} - \frac{s_{n,m} g}{C_P} \end{aligned} \quad (9.80a)$$

⁴Such a 'mass dissipation' term has been used by Gent et al. (2021).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial s_{n,m}}{\partial t} = & iC_1 k_{n+1} v_{n+1,m}^* s_{n+2,m} + iC_2 k_n v_{n-1,m}^* s_{n+1,m} \\ & - iC_3 k_{n-1} v_{n-1,m} s_{n-2,m} - k_n^2 s_{n,m} \end{aligned} \quad (9.80b)$$

$$+ \frac{T_{n,m+1} - 2T_{n,m} + T_{n,m-1}}{T_{0,m} \Delta Z_m^2} - v_{n,m} \frac{s_{0,m+1} - s_{0,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} \quad (9.80c)$$

$$T_{n,m} = T_{0,m} s_{n,m}$$

where we have set $\kappa = 1$.

9.2.9 Further simplification

On examining numerical solutions of equations 9.80 (not presented here), it turns out that the qualitative results are not much affected by neglecting the variation of T_0 ; we thus further simplify equations 9.80 to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial v_{n,m}}{\partial t} = & iC_1 k_{n+1} v_{n+2,m} v_{n+1,m}^* + iC_2 k_n v_{n+1,m} v_{n-1,m}^* \\ & - iC_3 k_{n-1} v_{n-1,m} v_{n-2,m} - \nu k_n^2 v_{n,m} - \frac{s_{n,m} g}{C_P} \end{aligned} \quad (9.81a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial s_{n,m}}{\partial t} = & iC_1 k_{n+1} v_{n+1,m}^* s_{n+2,m} + iC_2 k_n v_{n-1,m}^* s_{n+1,m} - iC_3 k_{n-1} v_{n-1,m} s_{n-2,m} \\ & - \underbrace{\kappa k_n^2 s_{n,m} + \kappa \frac{s_{n,m+1} - 2s_{n,m} + s_{n,m-1}}{\Delta Z_m^2}}_{\text{level coupling}} - v_{n,m} \frac{s_{0,m+1} - s_{0,m-1}}{2\Delta Z_m} \end{aligned} \quad (9.81b)$$

9.2.10 Boundary conditions

To specify the boundary conditions, we may think of ‘ghost levels’ for which $m = 0, M + 1$. On these ghost levels, all the fluctuating quantities are set to zero, while the background quantities are set such that their gradient at the boundary is constant. For example,

$$\rho_{n,0} = \begin{cases} 0 & , n \neq 0 \\ 2\rho_{n,1} - \rho_{n,2} & , n = 0 \end{cases} \quad (9.82)$$

In the shell linkage terms, any terms which probe fluctuating quantities with $n > N$ or $n < 1$ are set to zero.

9.3 Quantities characterizing the solutions

9.3.1 Parameters and background

To solve equations 9.81, we need to specify $N, M, h, C_1, C_2, C_3, \nu, \gamma, g$, and ΔZ_m . The background is completely specified by the arbitrary choice of $s_{0,m}$. Further,

initial values of $s_{n,m}$ and $v_{n,m}$ need to be specified. Henceforth, we set $C_1 = 1$, $C_2 = -0.5$, $C_3 = -0.5$, and $h = 2$; this choice of coefficients was used to represent 3D homogeneous isotropic turbulence by L'vov et al. (1998).

9.3.2 Dimensionless numbers

In the nondimensional units described earlier, we have

$$\text{Pr} = \nu \quad (9.83)$$

The Rayleigh number may be estimated as

$$\text{Ra} = \frac{g(s_{0,M} - s_{0,1})(M\Delta Z_m)^3}{\nu} \quad (9.84)$$

assuming that $s_{0,M} > s_{0,1}$ (i.e. that the domain is unstably stratified). Recalling that $\text{Ra} = \text{Gr Pr}$ and $\text{Gr} = \text{Re}^2$ (for buoyancy driven flows; see Schumacher and Sreenivasan 2020, eq. 17), we can estimate the Reynolds number as

$$\text{Re} = \sqrt{\frac{\text{Ra}}{\text{Pr}}} \quad (9.85)$$

9.3.3 Varying the Prandtl number

We vary ν to change Pr . However, this also changes Ra . To vary Pr while keeping Ra unchanged, we simultaneously modify

$$\text{Pr} \rightarrow K \text{Pr} \quad (9.86)$$

$$g \rightarrow K g \quad (9.87)$$

where K is some positive constant.

Empirically, we find that with the above modifications, the timescale over which the solutions evolve roughly scales as

$$\tau \rightarrow K^{-1/2} \tau \quad (9.88)$$

which is consistent with estimating it from the free-fall velocity:

$$\tau \sim \left(\frac{g \nabla s_0}{C_P} \right)^{-1/2} \quad (9.89)$$

9.4 Results

We now present some solutions of equations 9.81. To solve them, we use the BDF solver (Byrne and Hindmarsh 1975; Shampine and Reichelt 1997) from SciPy (Virtanen et al. 2020); this is an implicit solver for stiff equations that can work

Figure 9.1: Depth dependence of the background entropy used for all the cases presented ($m = 1$: top layer; $m = 15$: bottom layer).

in the complex domain. We evolve the equations starting from a nonzero initial condition, and average the required quantities (e.g. $|v_n|^2$) over a time interval much larger than the correlation time of the shell variables.

For all the solutions presented here, we set the background entropy profile (figure 9.1) to have a thin unstable layer with a large entropy gradient, on top of a thick unstable layer with a smaller entropy gradient; additional thin and stably stratified layers are placed at the top and bottom boundaries in order to maintain consistency with the boundary conditions. Initially, we set $s = 1$ for the first four shells at $m = 3$, with the remaining dynamical variables being set to zero. We set $N = 30$, $M = 15$, $\gamma = 5/3$, and $\Delta Z_m = 1$. Further, we choose units such that $C_P = 1$, $\kappa = 1$, and $k_1 = 1$. As described in section 9.3.2, the remaining parameters (ν and g) can be used to control Ra and Pr . For the $\text{Pr} = 1$ case, we set $g = 10^6$ and $\nu = 1$. For the other cases, ν and g are varied as described in section 9.3.3.

First of all, we note that in an unstratified shell model (that represents homogeneous, isotropic, incompressible turbulence), one expects $\langle |v_n|^2 \rangle \sim k_n^{-2/3}$ (Biferale 2003, eq. 14),⁵ where the angle bracket denotes a time average. We find that the velocity spectra follow the same scaling with wavenumber that is expected in the unstratified case (e.g. all three panels of figure 9.2). This is perhaps not too surprising, as we have intentionally kept the shell couplings similar to those in the unstratified case. It is possible that a more careful consideration of symmetries and conservation laws suggests a different form of the shell coupling, which could lead to a different power-spectral slope.

In figure 9.2, we see that simply decreasing Pr (keeping Ra fixed) is enough to cause convective amplitudes to decrease with depth. What we observe in this model is that the spectra remain roughly Kolmogorov at all depths, but that their

⁵Since the shells are logarithmically spaced, the KE spectrum is actually $\langle |v_n|^2 / k_n \rangle$, which indeed scales as $k_n^{-5/3}$.

Figure 9.2: Spectra at various vertical levels for $Ra = 8.6 \times 10^7$. Larger values of m are deeper in the domain; Pr decreases from left to right. Only relative magnitudes of the spectra at various depths are important here, as their absolute values are affected by the process of varying Pr while keeping Ra constant; see appendix 9.3.3.

Figure 9.3: Effect of the level coupling term (see equation 9.81b) at $Pr = 10^{-6}$ and $Ra = 8.6 \times 10^7$.

amplitudes depend on the depth at which they reside.

In figure 9.3, we see that when the ‘level coupling’ term is dropped from equation 9.81b, lowering Pr does not result in suppression of large scales. This suggests that along with low Pr , nonlocality is also crucial to the effect we observe.

A comparison of the three panels in figure 9.2 suggests that the effect of low Pr is to boost the spectra at intermediate depths, rather than to suppress convection in deeper layers. However, note that in all these cases, the background entropy gradient is the same. In simulations or real systems where the total energy transport needs to be constant, the effect observed here may manifest as an apparent suppression of the spectra with depth.

The behaviour described here (enhanced influence of surface layers at low Pr) is not affected by whether the lower layers are stable or unstable; it is sufficient for the absolute value of the entropy gradient in the lower layers to be much less than that in the upper layers.

A caveat is in order: note that all the spectra exhibit oscillations (in the wavenumber-domain) at small wavenumbers. These oscillations are due to the flux of a conserved quantity with dimensions of kinetic helicity (L’vov et al. 1998, p. 1813; Ditlevsen 2010, p. 101). In forced shell models, one typically eliminates these oscillations by choosing a particular kind of forcing; however, we do not have the freedom to do that in our system. Such (presumably spurious) features are also seen in previous shell models for Boussinesq convection (Brandenburg 1992, fig. 1; Kumar and Verma 2015, fig. 4)^{6,7}. We consider these oscillations (along with the fact that the spectra invariably peak at the largest scale rather than the local scale height) as artefacts of the shell model, rather than as relevant to full-fledged convection.

On a more speculative note, we see similarities between the behaviour of our shell model and that expected from the entropy rain picture. If convection in the Sun were indeed driven by downflowing plumes or thermals, the effect of low Pr could be understood in two ways: (i) a low viscosity leads to less dissipation of the downflows’ momentum, allowing them to persist longer (ii) a high thermal diffusivity leads to downflows losing their entropy signature very quickly, leading to a suppression of buoyant braking. These seem to be consistent with the suggestion of Käpylä (2021) that as Pr is lowered, the kinetic energy of the flows increases.

Recently, Fuentes, Cumming, and Anders (2022) have found that at low Pr , convective layers in simulated gas giant planets start merging. The reason for their observation is unclear, but it may be related to the mechanism at play in the Sun’s convection zone.

We also note that Vlaykov et al. (2022), in 2D simulations of a solar-like convective region, have found that the near-surface layers affect even the bottom of the convection zone. The apparent disagreement between their results and those

⁶Interestingly, it seems that the introduction of a magnetic field gets rid of such oscillations (Brandenburg 1992, fig. 2). This may be related to the fact that the kinetic helicity is not conserved in the presence of magnetic fields.

⁷Kumar and Verma (2015) seem to dismiss these oscillations as “systematic error”.

of Hotta, Iijima, and Kusano (2019) can be explained as follows: Hotta, Iijima, and Kusano (2019) used a slope-limited diffusion scheme which dissipates both the momentum and the entropy in a similar fashion. Their results thus represent convection at $\text{Pr} \sim 1$. On the other hand, Vlaykov et al. (2022) performed an implicit LES of the momentum equation, while retaining an explicit thermal diffusivity. Their results then seem to represent convection at low Pr (Bricteux et al. 2012). This supports our finding that a low Pr enhances the effect of a strongly stratified unstable layer on the convective velocities in deeper layers.

9.5 Conclusions

We have generalized the notion of a shell model (used to study unstratified or weakly stratified turbulence) to stratified systems. By numerically solving one such model, we have tried to shed light on the convective conundrum.

In this framework, we find that a low value of Pr , along with a thermal-diffusion-induced coupling between different depths, is sufficient to cause suppression of convective spectra as one goes deeper into a convecting domain underneath a strongly unstable surface layer. This suggests that low Pr is at least as important as magnetic fields and rotation for a complete explanation of the convective conundrum.

Given that Featherstone and Hindman (2016b) report suppression of large scales in their simulations as Ra increases, we note the possibility that large Ra and low Pr are degenerate, and that, as suggested by Orvedahl et al. (2018), some combination of the two serves as a better control parameter. In light of our findings, the effects of low Pr on the stability and dynamics of convective structures (such as the plumes invoked in the entropy rain picture) should be studied. These will be taken up in the future.

Chapter 10

Dynamo saturation and cycles in rotating convection

10.1 Introduction

Given the problems with the standard picture of sunspot formation (discussed in section 1.3), one would like to understand if various observational properties of sunspots can be explained without appealing to rising flux tubes. In this chapter, we will perform simulations of rotating convection with the axis of rotation inclined with the vertical. Such boxes are meant to model convection at a particular latitude on the Sun. We will study the effects of rotation and latitude on the small-scale dynamo (SSD) in such simulations, motivated by the existence of active latitudes on the Sun.

While a connection between sunspots and the SSD may seem somewhat far-fetched, we note that even within the framework of large-scale dynamo theory, mechanisms such as the magnetic shear-current effect (Rogachevskii and Kleeorin 2004; Squire and Bhattacharjee 2015, 2016) can supposedly produce large-scale magnetic fields from small-scale magnetic fluctuations. Alternatively, in the presence of shear, it is possible for large-scale fields to be generated from strong-enough fields at a smaller scale simply by stretching of the magnetic field, without the need for a dynamo mechanism to actually operate. Such arguments dovetail with recent ideas of the solar dynamo being seated in or shaped by the near-surface shear layer (Brandenburg 2005).

In simulations of rotating Boussinesq convection with the rotational axis aligned with the gravitational axis, Guervilly, Hughes, and Jones (2017) observed a dynamo induced by the formation of large-scale vortices.¹ Interaction between the large-scale vortices and the magnetic field generated by them led to cycles in the horizontally averaged magnetic field. They found that the SSD suppresses this effect by suppressing the large-scale vortices. In similar simulations of compressible

¹Recall that such vortices were also formed in the forced-turbulence simulations described in chapter 2 and section 6.4.

convection, Masada and Sano (2014) and Bushby et al. (2018) found that while the kinematic stage of the dynamo depends on the formation of large-scale vortices, the nonlinear stage can show nontrivial behaviour even without periodic regeneration of the vortices. They were able to show the operation of such a dynamo even for Rm larger than the threshold for the onset of the SSD.

All the studies above considered a vertical rotation axis. In a rotating spherical body, the angle between the rotational axis and the acceleration due to gravity is a function of latitude. Rotvig and Jones (2002) have studied magnetoconvection with the rotational axis inclined at an angle of 45° to the vertical. However, their focus was on the geodynamo, and so they worked in the limit of infinite Pr and strong rotation. Further, they did not find any magnetic cycles. We are not aware of any published studies that use Cartesian simulations of convection to study dynamo cycles when the rotational axis is inclined to the vertical.

Spherical simulations of convection have been used in the past to study convective dynamos and the latitudinal dependence of the resulting magnetic field (e.g. Käpylä, Mantere, and Brandenburg 2012; Brun et al. 2022). However, most such simulations are in a regime where the SSD is not excited. While spherical simulations of convection can be used to study latitudinal effects on the SSD, simulating a large segment of a spherical shell at the high Rm required for excitation of the SSD is computationally demanding. For exploratory work, we find it more convenient to use Cartesian simulations such as those described in this chapter.

Section 10.2 describes our simulation setup. In section 10.3, we describe the non-rotating case. In section 10.4, we study how the saturation level of the SSD varies with the latitude and the rotation rate. In section 10.5, we describe magnetic cycles in a case with a higher rotational rate. Finally, we summarize our conclusions in section 10.6.

10.2 Setup

10.2.1 Domain and evolution equations

We consider a Cartesian domain, periodic in the x and y directions. Rotation is modelled using the f-plane approximation. Gravity points along the $-\hat{z}$ direction. The domain extends vertically between $0 < z < L$.

We solve the following evolution equations:

$$\frac{D \ln \rho}{dt} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \quad (10.1)$$

$$\rho \frac{D \mathbf{u}}{dt} = -\nabla p - \rho g \hat{z} + \mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B} - 2\rho \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{u} + \nabla \cdot (2\rho \nu \overleftrightarrow{S}) \quad (10.2)$$

$$\rho T \frac{Ds}{dt} = q + \nabla \cdot (\chi \nabla T) + 2\rho \nu S_{ij} S_{ij} + \mu_0 \eta |\mathbf{J}|^2 \quad (10.3)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial t} = \mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{B} + \eta \nabla^2 \mathbf{A} \quad (10.4)$$

where

$$\mathbf{B} \equiv \nabla \times \mathbf{A} \quad (10.5)$$

$$\mathbf{J} \equiv \frac{\nabla \times \mathbf{B}}{\mu_0} \quad (10.6)$$

$$S_{ij} \equiv \frac{1}{2} \left(\partial_i u_j + \partial_j u_i - \frac{2}{3} \delta_{ij} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \right) \quad (10.7)$$

with ρ being the density; \mathbf{u} the velocity; $D/dt \equiv \partial/\partial t + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla$ the convective derivative; p the pressure; g the acceleration due to gravity; $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ the rotation rate; ν the kinematic viscosity; s the specific entropy; T the temperature; χ the thermal conductivity; \mathbf{A} the magnetic vector potential; η the magnetic diffusivity; and μ_0 the magnetic permeability.

We choose units such that $c_0 = C_P = L = \rho_0 = 1$, where c_0 is the sound speed at the top of the domain, C_P is the specific heat at constant pressure, and ρ_0 is the initial density at the top of the domain. With these choices, the unit for length is L ; mass is $\rho_0 L^3$; time is L/c_0 ; temperature is c_0^2/C_P ; and magnetic field is $\sqrt{\mu_0 \rho_0 c_0^2}$. We assume the kinematic viscosity, the magnetic diffusivity, and the thermal conductivity are constants ($\nu = \chi = \eta = 10^{-4} c_0 L$), and neglect the bulk viscosity (omitted from the expressions above). Further, we set $g = 10 c_0^2/L$.

A cooling function, q , of the form

$$q = -\kappa \frac{(c_s^2 - c_0^2)}{c_0^2} \Theta \left(\frac{z - z_{\text{cool}}}{w_{\text{cool}}} \right) \quad (10.8)$$

with $\Theta(z) \equiv (1 + \text{erf}(z))/2$, $z_{\text{cool}} = 0.98 L$, $w_{\text{cool}} = 0.01 L$, and $\kappa = 100 \rho_0 c_0^3/L$ has also been added to the entropy equation. This forces the sound speed in $z > z_{\text{cool}}$ to c_0 .

The fluid is chosen to be an ideal gas, whose equation of state is

$$p = \rho R T = \rho_0 R T_0 \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right)^\gamma e^{\gamma s/C_P} \quad (10.9)$$

where $R \equiv C_P - C_V$ and $\gamma \equiv C_P/C_V$, with C_V being the specific heat at constant volume. We set $\gamma = 5/3$, corresponding to a monoatomic gas. Note that the zero point of the entropy is determined by the constant T_0 , which we choose such that $(\gamma - 1) C_P T_0 = c_0^2$.

These evolution equations are solved using the PENCIL code (Pencil Code Collaboration et al. 2021).² Spatial derivatives are discretized using a sixth-order finite difference scheme, while the equations are evolved in time using a third-order Runge-Kutta method. Upwinding is used for advection of the density, the velocity, and the entropy. We use $N_x \times N_y \times N_z = 384^3$ grid points with $L_x = L_y = 4L$.

²<http://pencil-code.org>

10.2.2 Vertical boundary conditions

The vertical boundaries are made free-slip and impenetrable. The enthalpy flux at the bottom is constrained to be $10^{-2} \rho_0 c_0^3$, while the temperature at the top is constrained to be T_0 . The boundary conditions for the vector potential are chosen to ensure a vertical magnetic field at the boundaries. At the vertical boundaries, the second derivative of $\ln \rho$ is set to zero.

10.2.3 Initial conditions

Convection simulations need to be run for a timespan of the order of the diffusion timescale (l^2/χ , where l is the size of the convecting region) to reach steady state. Further, in our setup, the growth rate of the SSD is quite slow, such that the magnetic field takes a similarly long time to reach saturation. To save computational resources, we initialized all our rotating simulations from a snapshot of a nonrotating simulation which had been run for a timespan $3 \times 10^3 L/c_0$.

In the non-rotating simulation, we initially set an adiabatically stratified profile for the density and entropy, such that the density and sound speed were ρ_0 and c_0 respectively at $z = L$. At each grid point, each velocity component was randomly chosen from a uniform distribution between $\pm 10^{-6} c_0$. Each component of the vector potential was chosen at each grid point from a Gaussian distribution of mean 0 and standard deviation $10^{-6} \sqrt{\mu_0 \rho_0 c_0^2 L^2}$.

10.2.4 Fluxes and diagnostics

The averaged total energy density (kinetic + internal + gravitational) is transported by the following fluxes:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{conv}} \equiv \langle \rho C_P \mathbf{u} T \rangle \quad (10.10)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{kin}} \equiv \langle \rho \mathbf{u}^2 \mathbf{u} / 2 \rangle \quad (10.11)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{visc}} \equiv - \left\langle 2\rho \nu \mathbf{u} \cdot \overset{\leftrightarrow}{S} \right\rangle \quad (10.12)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{cool}} \equiv - \hat{\mathbf{z}} \int_{z_{\text{bot}}}^z \langle q \rangle dz \quad (10.13)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{rad}} \equiv - \chi \nabla T \quad (10.14)$$

where q has been defined in equation 10.8. Note that the expression for \mathbf{F}_{cool} above assumes $\langle q \rangle$ is independent of the horizontal coordinates (this is guaranteed if we are using horizontal averages).

We define the Rayleigh number (Ra), which describes the degree of supercriticality of convection, as

$$\text{Ra} \equiv \frac{g |\Delta s| L_{\text{CZ}}^3}{C_P \nu \chi} \quad (10.15)$$

where L_{CZ} is the depth over which the entropy gradient remains negative (i.e. excluding the stably stratified layers at the top and the bottom of the domain);

$\Omega L/c_0$	θ [deg]	Re	Co	Ra	Nu	Ma _{max}	L_{CZ}/L
0	0	557	0.00	3.2×10^6	2.9	0.13	0.35
0.1	0	610	0.23	3.8×10^6	2.8	0.14	0.38
0.1	30	604	0.23	3.7×10^6	2.8	0.14	0.37
0.1	60	587	0.22	3.4×10^6	2.8	0.14	0.36
0.1	90	564	0.22	3.3×10^6	2.9	0.14	0.36
0.5	0	798	1.26	6.1×10^6	2.4	0.17	0.45
0.5	60	830	1.30	6.8×10^6	2.3	0.17	0.46
0.5	90	661	1.42	5.5×10^6	2.4	0.30	0.43
1	0	858	2.63	7.2×10^6	2.3	0.18	0.48
1	30	882	2.65	7.9×10^6	2.2	0.18	0.48
1	60	924	2.55	8.3×10^6	2.2	0.19	0.49
1	90	890	1.77	4.3×10^6	2.6	0.31	0.40
2	0	929	5.64	1.0×10^7	2.1	0.18	0.51
2	60	975	5.05	1.1×10^7	2.1	0.20	0.50

Table 10.1: Parameter values and diagnostics (computed in the saturated state) for the simulations discussed in this chapter. The diagnostics have been computed from temporal averages over a timespan $500L/c_0$ from the end of each simulation. The Mach number is based on the total velocity (both mean and fluctuations). Note that the diagnostics quoted for $\Omega = 2$ with $\theta = 60^\circ$ are probably affected by the cyclic behaviour of the horizontal velocity components (section 10.5).

and Δs is the integral over this depth of the horizontally and temporally averaged entropy gradient. We define the Reynolds number, Re , which measures how turbulent the system is, as

$$\text{Re} \equiv \frac{\max_z [u'_{\text{rms}}(z)] L_{\text{CZ}}}{\nu} \quad (10.16)$$

where the prime denotes that the horizontally averaged velocity has been removed. The Nusselt number, Nu , is the ratio of the total energy flux to the radiative flux. We evaluate it by taking the radiative flux at the midpoint of the region where the entropy gradient is negative. Rotational influence on the flow is characterized by the Coriolis number, which we define as

$$\text{Co} \equiv \frac{\Omega L_{\text{CZ}}}{\max_z [u'_{\text{rms}}(z)]} \quad (10.17)$$

Table 10.1 shows the parameter values for which simulations were run, along with the values of the diagnostics defined above.

10.3 The non-rotating simulation

Figure 10.1 shows various fluxes of the energy, along with some quantities describing the background state. We see that the stratification is unstable (negative entropy gradient) in roughly $0.4 < z/L < 0.95$. The domain covers around 5 pressure scale heights, out of which around 3.5 are within this unstable region. The entropy gradient attains a large negative value in a thin layer near the top of the domain, but most of the CZ has an entropy gradient close to zero. The extension of the CZ beyond the unstably stratified region (overshoot) can be inferred from the fact that F_{kin} and F_{conv} are nonzero in (roughly) $0.2 < z/L < 0.95$.

An SSD is excited in this case. While its growth rate is quite slow in the steady state, it is much higher in the initial transient phase (up to time $10^3 L/c_0$) due to the turbulent velocity being higher then. The magnetic energy reaches around 3×10^{-5} of the kinetic energy at time $3 \times 10^3 L/c_0$. This magnetic field is included in the initial condition for all the rotating cases.

10.4 Rotational effects on the saturation of the dynamo

We use horizontal averages to define mean variables, such that, e.g., the second moment of the fluctuating magnetic field is given by

$$\langle |\mathbf{B}'|^2 \rangle_{xy} = \langle |\mathbf{B}|^2 \rangle_{xy} - \left| \langle \mathbf{B} \rangle_{xy} \right|^2 \quad (10.18)$$

Figure 10.1: Horizontally and temporally averaged vertical fluxes and other quantities in the non-rotating simulation. The constant flux marked as F_{bot} is that used to set the boundary condition for the entropy at the bottom of the domain. F_{tot} is the sum of F_{conv} , F_{kin} , F_{rad} , and F_{cool} ; the contribution due to F_{visc} has not been included.

Figure 10.2: Ratio of the fluctuating magnetic energy to the fluctuating kinetic energy in the saturated state as a function of the colatitude for different rotation rates. The filled circles denote the parameters for which simulations were performed.

The volume average of the fluctuations is then calculated as the z -average of the xy -average above, i.e. $\langle |\mathbf{B}'|^2 \rangle \equiv \langle \langle |\mathbf{B}'|^2 \rangle_{xy} \rangle_z$.

Figure 10.2 shows how the saturated strength of the magnetic field depends on the rotation rate and on the colatitude.³ Note that for $\Omega = c_0/L$, the runs with $\theta \in \{0^\circ, 30^\circ\}$ exhibit no dynamo, and so we have set the corresponding values to zero. For $\Omega = 0.1 c_0/L$ (the case with the slowest rotation), the saturated strength of the magnetic field decreases with θ , contrary to what one would expect from the unstratified anisotropically forced simulations described in section 6.6. This is most likely due to the decrease in Re with increasing θ ; table 10.1. On the other hand, for $\Omega \in \{0.5, 1\} c_0/L$, the saturation level increases tremendously with latitude. Could the dynamo in these cases be due to a large-scale vortex, as in section 6.4?

Recall that in the isotropically forced rotating simulations described in section 6.4, we found that in the absence of a large-scale vortex, the saturation fraction of the magnetic energy decreases with increasing rotational rate. Here too, if one restricts one's attention to $\theta \in \{0^\circ, 30^\circ\}$, one finds the saturation level decreasing as Ω increases. Once a large-scale vortex is formed, the saturation fraction is expected to increase with the rotation rate. However, here, at the high- θ end, the saturation level for $\Omega = c_0/L$ is still lower than that for $\Omega = 0.5 c_0/L$.

To understand the role of stratification (which was absent in chapter 6), we examine how the profile of the magnetic energy varies with depth. Figure 10.3 shows the profile of the ratio of the fluctuating magnetic energy to the fluctuating kinetic energy (we shall refer to this as the fractional magnetic energy or the

³We estimate the kinetic energy as $\langle \rho \rangle \langle u^2 \rangle / 2$; this is acceptable at low Mach number.

Figure 10.3: Depth-dependence of the ratio of the fluctuating magnetic energy to the fluctuating kinetic energy. To make the depth-dependence clear, we have scaled all the profiles to have a peak value of 1.

saturation fraction) for different colatitudes and rotation rates. For the slowly rotating ($\Omega = 0.1 c_0/L$) case, the profile of the magnetic field is not very sensitive to the value of θ . In these cases, the saturation fraction invariably peaks near the bottom of the CZ. For the faster rotators, the magnetic field profile tends to peak closer to the base of the CZ near the equator ($\theta = 90^\circ$), but peaks closer to the surface at other latitudes.

We would now like to check if the differences between the slow and fast rotators are due to the formation of large-scale flow structures (such as vortices). Let us consider the correlation length, defined in equation 10.31 (appendix 10.A).⁴ Figure 10.4 shows how the correlation lengths of the velocity and magnetic fields vary with depth for different rotational rates and colatitudes. Note that these particular quantities have been computed from single snapshots, and so stochastic errors (which we have not attempted to estimate) are expected to be significant.

In the slowest rotators ($\Omega \in \{0.1, 0.5\} c_0/L$), there is no significant latitudinal effect on the correlation lengths of the velocity and magnetic fields. In the $\Omega = c_0/L$ case, the velocity correlation length increases near the surface with increasing θ .

For the $\Omega = c_0/L$ case, from figure 10.4, we see that in the region where the magnetic energy is significant, the correlation length of the magnetic field is of the order of (but somewhat less than) that of the velocity field. This suggests that the LSD, if any, is not the dominant mechanism for the growth of the magnetic field. Interestingly, comparison of figures 10.3 and 10.4 suggests that for this particular

⁴Käpylä (2024) discusses how various length scales of the velocity field are affected by the rotation rate in simulations of convection.

Figure 10.4: Depth-dependence of the correlation lengths of the velocity and magnetic fields. Note that these have been divided by the pressure scale height, which is also a function of depth.

Figure 10.5: Depth-dependence of the shear parameter for various latitudes and $\Omega = c_0/L$.

rotational rate, regardless of the value of θ , the fractional magnetic energy peaks in the region where the correlation length of the velocity field is the lowest.

One possible mechanism for the enhancement of the magnetic field strength for $\theta \in \{60^\circ, 90^\circ\}$ and $\Omega = c_0/L$ is the effect of shear on the SSD. By simulating forced turbulence in a shearing box, Singh, Rogachevskii, and Brandenburg (2017) have found that shear enhances the growth rate of the SSD. While the effect of shear on the saturation level of the SSD has not been studied so far, it seems reasonable to assume that it would lead to an increase in the saturation level as well. Singh, Rogachevskii, and Brandenburg (2017) quantified the strength of the shear by a shear parameter, Sh . We define the analogous parameter in our setup as

$$Sh \equiv \frac{H_P}{u'_{\text{rms},0}} \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial \langle u_x \rangle}{\partial z}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \langle u_y \rangle}{\partial z}\right)^2} \quad (10.19)$$

where H_P is the pressure scale height; $u'_{\text{rms},0} \equiv \sqrt{\langle u'^2 \rangle}$ is calculated from the non-rotating case; and $\langle \square \rangle$ denotes the temporal average (over the last 500 time units) of the horizontal average of \square . Note that this is a function of z .

Figure 10.5 shows the depth-dependence of Sh in the simulations with $\Omega = c_0/L$. We note that Singh, Rogachevskii, and Brandenburg (2017) found an effect only for $Sh \gtrsim 1.2$.⁵ Only in the $\theta = 90^\circ$ case does the shear parameter, calculated as

⁵We have accounted for the fact that our definition of Sh is larger than theirs by a factor of 2π . However, we note that the equivalent of the forcing scale (which they used to define the shear parameter) in our setup would be the correlation length of the velocity field, which is invariably larger than the scale height in the rotating cases (see figure 10.4). We have thus probably underestimated the influence of shear by a factor of a few.

Figure 10.6: Left: 2D power spectrum of the velocity field at different depths in the simulation with $\Omega = c_0/L$ and $\theta = 60^\circ$, calculated from a single snapshot at $t = 3000 L/c_0$. The power spectra have been normalized such that the integral over all wavenumbers is one. The dotted vertical lines mark $k = 2\pi/H_P$, where H_P is the pressure scale height at a particular depth. Right: the same data with a linear scale on the horizontal axis, in order to include $k = 0$.

above, exceed this threshold. Thus it seems vertical shear alone cannot explain the enhancement of the SSD.

Figure 10.6 shows the two-dimensional (horizontal) power spectrum of the velocity field for the simulation with $\Omega = c_0/L$ and $\theta = 60^\circ$. We find that significant flows are generated with a wavenumber equal to the lowest nonzero wavenumber supported by the domain. It seems likely that these flows (which are strong at all depths) are responsible for the growth of the magnetic field. On the other hand, for the case with $\Omega = c_0/L$ and $\theta = 90^\circ$, figure 10.7 shows that the $k = 0$ component dominates at all depths, suggesting one has to appeal to shear in this case.

Motivated by the power spectra discussed above, we suggest the following explanation for the trends observed in figures 10.2 and 10.3. For $\Omega = c_0/L$, the anisotropy generated is strong enough that the SSD is suppressed for $\theta \in \{0^\circ, 30^\circ\}$. However, the generation of large-scale flows for $\theta \in \{60^\circ, 90^\circ\}$ counteracts this effect by enhancing the SSD. We recall that in these convection simulations, the RMS turbulent velocity is the largest near the top of the domain, and decreases as one goes deeper (figure 10.1). For $\theta = 60^\circ$, the large-scale flows seem to be present at all depths. However, the larger turbulent velocity at the top leads to the magnetic energy growing the fastest (and saturating at the highest value) there. On the other hand, for $\theta = 90^\circ$, the shear parameter has a much larger value at the bottom of the CZ than at the top. This ensures that even though the kinetic energy at the bottom is lower than that at the top, the SSD grows faster at the bottom, leading to the magnetic energy growing the fastest there and saturating at

Figure 10.7: Left: 2D power spectrum of the velocity field at different depths in the simulation with $\Omega = c_0/L$ and $\theta = 90^\circ$, calculated from a single snapshot at $t = 2000 L/c_0$. The power spectra have been normalized such that the integral over all wavenumbers is one. The dotted vertical lines mark $k = 2\pi/H_P$, where H_P is the pressure scale height at a particular depth. Right: the same data with a linear scale on the horizontal axis, in order to include $k = 0$.

a higher level.

In the picture described above, the large-scale magnetic fields in the radiative region (see figure 10.4) can be explained as follows. The SSD-generated magnetic field diffuses into the RZ, after which the small-scale components decay quickly and the remaining part of the magnetic field gets stretched by shear.

10.5 Magnetic cycles in fast rotators

Figure 10.8 shows the time series of the RMS velocity and magnetic fields in a simulation at a higher rotation rate ($\Omega = 2 c_0/L$) than considered in section 10.4. We find cyclic behaviour of the horizontal velocity components and of the RMS magnetic field. The rotation first induces an increase in the horizontal velocity components. This increase induces growth of the magnetic field, which in turn suppresses the horizontal velocity. Once the horizontal velocity is suppressed, the magnetic field decays, allowing the cycle to start again.⁶

Figure 10.9 shows how the horizontally averaged magnetic and velocity fields vary with depth and time. We see prominent cycles in B_x and B_y , along with oscillations of u_y about its temporal average. However, note from figure 10.8 that the mean magnetic field is energetically insignificant.

Figure 10.10 shows the depth-dependence of the magnetic energy at various

⁶The first cycle looks different from the others, presumably since it is affected by transient effects.

Figure 10.8: Time series of the volume-averaged RMS velocity (componentwise) and magnetic fields (total and mean-subtracted) in a simulation with $\Omega = 2 c_0/L$ and $\theta = 60^\circ$.

Figure 10.9: Horizontally averaged horizontal magnetic field components, along with the fluctuations of the horizontally averaged horizontal velocity components about their temporal averages. To remove short-duration fluctuations, the quantities have further been smoothed along the temporal axis with a boxcar filter of half-width $50 L/c_0$. Note that in these plots, the time starts from $t = 500 L/c_0$.

Figure 10.10: Depth-dependence of the horizontally and temporally averaged fluctuating magnetic energy at different times. Temporal averages are taken over intervals of width $100 L/c_0$ centered at the indicated times.

times. In the growing phase of the cycle (cf. figure 10.8), the magnetic energy is larger near the top of the domain. However, when the magnetic energy peaks ($t \approx 6000 L/c_0$), the depth-dependence of the magnetic energy becomes flatter, with the magnetic energy being large even in the deeper parts of the CZ. After this, the magnetic energy decays, with the energy at the bottom of the CZ initially decaying slower.

Guervilly, Hughes, and Jones (2017) have reported cycles of the horizontally averaged magnetic field in rapidly rotating Boussinesq convection with $\theta = 0^\circ$. In their setup, the cycles were associated with formation of a large-scale vortex, and were observed only in the absence of an SSD. Nevertheless, Bushby et al. (2018), also setting $\theta = 0^\circ$, found a regime in which cycles of the components of the horizontally averaged magnetic field (corresponding to rotation of the horizontally averaged magnetic field vector) coexist with a steady SSD, despite suppression of the initially formed large-scale vortex. Our $\theta = 60^\circ$ case seems to be somewhat different from these cases: in fact, we find that the magnetic field decays in a simulation with $\theta = 0^\circ$ and all other input parameters kept the same. Further, we observe significant fluctuations in the RMS magnetic field itself, rather than in only the components of the horizontally averaged field.

Figure 10.11 shows two-dimensional magnetic power spectra⁷ in horizontal

⁷As discussed in section 2.2.1, care is needed while interpreting such spectra, especially when the field being studied does not have the appropriate symmetry. For example, horizontal spectra might be of some use if one already knows that the velocity field is dominated by plume-like structures. On the other hand, the magnetic field need not have such structures. For this reason, one must proceed cautiously.

Figure 10.11: Left: power spectra of the magnetic field in horizontal planes at different depths, calculated from single snapshots at the indicated times. The power spectra have been normalized such that the integral over all wavenumbers is one. The dotted vertical lines mark $k = 2\pi/H_P$, where H_P is the pressure scale height at a particular depth. Right: the same data with a linear scale on the horizontal axis, in order to include $k = 0$.

Figure 10.12: Similar to figure 10.11, but for the velocity field.

planes at different depths, calculated from single snapshots at the indicated times. The times have been chosen to cover the growing phase of one of the magnetic cycles. Figure 10.12 shows similarly calculated power spectra of the velocity field. The velocity spectra in the convection zone show secondary peaks at the lowest nonzero wavenumber during the phase of the cycle where the horizontal components of the velocity field increase and the magnetic field grows.

The fact that a (slowly growing) SSD is present in the non-rotating case but not in an otherwise identical rotating case with $\Omega = 2c_0/L$ and $\theta = 0^\circ$ suggests that rotational suppression of the SSD is still at play here. Despite this, we observe an SSD (as can be inferred from the magnetic spectrum near the top of the domain, where the magnetic energy peaks) at $\theta = 60^\circ$. Just as in the $\Omega = c_0/L$ case which we analysed in section 10.4, we attribute the excitation of this SSD to the large-scale flows which are produced at $\theta = 60^\circ$, but not at $\theta = 0^\circ$.

Given the large-scale peaks in the magnetic power spectra in deeper layers, it is tempting to attribute this to an LSD that operates independent of the SSD. However, this is not completely convincing, as (i) the magnetic spectra at the top of the CZ (where the magnetic field is the strongest) peak at much smaller scales; and (ii) the fluctuations in the small-scale magnetic field are much stronger than those in the horizontally averaged field (see figures 10.8 and 10.11). The dominance of large-scale magnetic fields in the deeper layers may simply be a consequence of magnetic fields diffusing from the top layers, in the course of which one expects the smaller scales to decay quicker, leaving only residual large-scale fields.

10.6 Conclusions

We have found that depending on the latitude, rotation can either suppress or enhance the SSD. Near the poles, rotation suppresses the SSD. On the other hand, as one moves closer to the equator, large-scale flow structures are generated which enhance the SSD.

At higher rotational rates, we find cycles of the horizontal velocity components, along with cycles of the magnetic field. In a limited parameter scan, we have found that such cycles are latitude-dependent: we observe them at $\theta = 60^\circ$, but there is no dynamo at all in an otherwise identical box at $\theta = 0$. Further, while cycles are observed in the horizontally averaged magnetic fields and in the fluctuating magnetic fields, the former are energetically insignificant throughout the cycle.

In previous studies which demonstrated cycles in rotating convection, the cycles were in the horizontally averaged components, while the fluctuating magnetic fields themselves did not show much variation. Cycles of the kind we have found seem to be representative of a hitherto unexplored region of the parameter space.

Even though the magnetic boundary conditions are not thought to significantly affect the SSD, future work should check if they have any influence on the cycles we report. A more extensive parameter study would be useful to pin down the conditions under which these cycles operate, and the factors determining their

period.

Appendices to chapter 10

10.A Relation between the correlation length and the 2D spectrum

Let us consider a vector field whose mean is zero, and which is isotropic and homogeneous in the horizontal plane. We define its autocorrelation function as

$$F(r, x_3) \equiv \langle u_i(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{r}) u_i(\mathbf{x}) \rangle \quad (10.20)$$

where $\langle \square \rangle$ denotes the ensemble average of \square , and \mathbf{r} is restricted to lie in the horizontal plane. Note that this autocorrelation function can have arbitrary dependence on the vertical coordinate. One can define the correlation length as

$$l(z) \equiv \frac{1}{F(0, z)} \int_0^\infty F(r, z) dr \quad (10.21)$$

We expect computing the above for a given vector field to be expensive, and would thus like to find out how $l(z)$ is related to the horizontal power spectrum of the vector field.

Since the vector field is homogeneous and isotropic in the horizontal plane, we can define its horizontal power spectrum $E(k, z)$ such that

$$\frac{1}{2} \langle \tilde{u}_i(\mathbf{p}_\perp, x_3) \tilde{u}_i(\mathbf{q}_\perp, x_3) \rangle \equiv E(|\mathbf{p}_\perp|, x_3) \delta(\mathbf{p}_\perp + \mathbf{q}_\perp) \quad (10.22)$$

where \mathbf{A}_\perp denotes the horizontal part of a vector \mathbf{A} . We write

$$\int_0^\infty F(r, z) dr = \int_0^\infty \langle u_i(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{r}) u_i(\mathbf{x}) \rangle dr \quad (10.23)$$

$$= \int_0^\infty dr \int d\mathbf{p}_\perp d\mathbf{q}_\perp \langle \tilde{u}_i(\mathbf{p}_\perp, x_3) \tilde{u}_i(\mathbf{q}_\perp, x_3) \rangle e^{i(\mathbf{p}_\perp + \mathbf{q}_\perp) \cdot \mathbf{x}_\perp + i\mathbf{p}_\perp \cdot \mathbf{r}} \quad (10.24)$$

$$= 2 \int_0^\infty dr \int d\mathbf{p}_\perp E(|\mathbf{p}_\perp|, x_3) e^{i\mathbf{p}_\perp \cdot \mathbf{r}} \quad (10.25)$$

$$= 2 \int_0^\infty dr \int_0^\infty dp \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta E(p, x_3) e^{ipr \cos \theta} \quad (10.26)$$

$$= 4\pi \int_0^\infty dr \int_0^\infty dp E(p, x_3) J_0(pr) \quad (10.27)$$

$$= 4\pi \int_0^\infty dp \frac{E(p, x_3)}{p} \quad (10.28)$$

where we have used p and θ to denote the amplitude and polar argument of \mathbf{p}_\perp , and used the results (Olver et al. 2024, eqs. 10.9.E1, 10.22.E41)

$$\int_0^{2\pi} \exp(ia \cos \theta) d\theta = 2\pi J_0(a) \quad (10.29)$$

$$\int_0^\infty J_0(r) dr = 1 \quad (10.30)$$

where J is the Bessel function of the first kind.

Noting that $F(0, z) = 2 \int_0^\infty E(k, z) dk$, we write the correlation length (equation 10.21) as

$$l(z) = \frac{2\pi}{\int_{+0}^\infty E(p, z) dp} \int_{+0}^\infty dp \frac{E(p, x_3)}{p} \quad (10.31)$$

In the lower limits, ‘+0’ indicates that we exclude $k = 0$. This is required when applying equation 10.31 to a field with nonzero mean.

Equation 10.31 is, except for the numerical prefactor, the same as the relation between the correlation length and the 3D spectrum for a three-dimensionally homogeneous, isotropic, and incompressible vector field (Monin and Yaglom 1975, eq. 12.82). This is despite the fact that for three-dimensionally homogeneous and isotropic turbulence, the interpretation of the 2D power spectrum is different from that of the 3D power spectrum (see equation 2.16).

Part VI
Helioseismology

Chapter 11

On the number of radial nodes of the lowest p mode

11.1 Introduction

Modes which are formed by the trapping of sound waves are called p modes. Along with f modes (which we will discuss in chapter 12), these are routinely observed on the surface of the Sun.

Conventionally, solar p modes are numbered according to the number of radial nodes of the corresponding radial displacement profile, with the lowest p mode thought to have one radial node (e.g. Christensen-Dalsgaard 2002, section. 3B). The number of radial nodes is inferred by the agreement of the frequencies of observed solar modes with the eigenfrequencies of linearized perturbations about inferred solar models. For example, Schunker et al. (2011) report that the lowest p mode has one radial node, based on analysing perturbations about the observationally inferred ‘Solar Model S’ (Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 1996).

In an infinite medium where the sound speed varies with depth, a particular sound wave is reflected from the depth where the sound speed becomes equal to the wave’s horizontal phase speed (Leibacher and Stein 1981, pp. 272–274). Using this fact, Duvall (1982) performed a regression analysis of observed Doppler shifts on the solar surface. They found that assuming the lowest observed p mode has one radial node leads to disagreement with a simple model in which the solar surface is treated as a free boundary (Leibacher and Stein 1981). They suggested that this discrepancy may be due to the presence of the solar atmosphere.

The eigenfunctions of stellar oscillations are sensitive to the boundary conditions. While the boundary conditions at the bottom are thought to be understood, it is unclear what boundary conditions should be imposed at the top. Comparison of the eigenmodes of an open organ pipe with those of a closed one suggests that the boundary conditions can indeed significantly affect the eigenmodes and the corresponding frequencies.

In simulations of step-isothermal forced turbulence with impenetrable bound-

aries, the lowest p mode is found to have zero vertical nodes (Singh et al. 2015, fig. 5). We will soon show that the same holds in simulations of stratified convection.

This chapter attempts to resolve the disagreements mentioned above. In section 11.2, we describe the evolution equations for linearized perturbations, along with the algorithms used to solve them. Section 11.3 describes the numerical methods we use. In section 11.4, we analyse the eigenmodes corresponding to a background state taken from a simulation of convection. In section 11.5, we repeat the same analysis with the background taken from a solar model. In section 11.6, we use eigenfunctions computed by ADIPLS to examine the impact of the approximations we make. Finally, we summarize our findings in section 11.7. The scripts used for this chapter are available at https://github.com/Kishore96in/model_S_modes.

11.2 Equations determining the eigenmodes in a plane parallel model

11.2.1 Derivation

Consider a plane parallel model, with vertical coordinate z pointing upwards. Let us suppose we are given a static background state (which need not be in hydrostatic equilibrium), with prescribed $\rho_0(z)$, $c(z)$, $p_0(z)$, and $s_0(z)$ (the density, the adiabatic sound speed, the pressure, and the entropy respectively). Ignoring viscosity, the continuity, momentum, and entropy equations can be written as

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v}) = 0 \quad (11.1)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + \rho (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} = -\nabla p + \rho \mathbf{g} \quad (11.2)$$

$$\frac{Ds}{dt} = \frac{1}{\rho T} \nabla \cdot (K \nabla T) \quad (11.3)$$

where ρ is the density; \mathbf{v} is the velocity; p is the pressure; s is the entropy; K is the thermal conductivity; T is the temperature; and \mathbf{g} is the acceleration due to gravity. We express the pressure, the entropy, and the density as perturbations about the background state, i.e. $p = p_0 + p'$, $s = s_0 + s'$ and $\rho = \rho_0 + \rho'$. Further, \mathbf{v} is treated as a perturbation. In general, \mathbf{g} itself can be affected by the perturbations, so one would need to consider an evolution equation for the gravitational potential, in addition to the equations listed above (e.g. Osaki and Hansen 1973, appendix A). However, we assume \mathbf{g} is unaffected by the perturbations (the Cowling approximation: Cowling 1941, p. 368).

Linearizing the continuity and momentum equations (equations 11.1 and 11.2) gives us

$$\frac{\partial \rho'}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (\rho_0 \mathbf{v}) \quad (11.4)$$

$$\rho_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} = -\nabla p_0 - \nabla p' + \rho_0 \mathbf{g} + \rho' \mathbf{g} \quad (11.5)$$

In principle, s' can only be related to ρ' and p' through an equation of state. However, we use the following approximation which is true for linear adiabatic perturbations of an ideal gas:¹

$$\frac{\rho_0}{C_P} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial p'}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \rho'}{\partial t} \quad (11.6)$$

This corresponds to assuming that non-ideal effects do not significantly affect the perturbations (except through the prescribed background state; see appendix 11.A). Linearizing equation 11.3, neglecting the thermal conductivity in terms involving the perturbations, and using the above, we write

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial p'}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \rho'}{\partial t} + \frac{\rho_0}{C_P} \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla s_0 = \frac{1}{\rho_0 T_0} \nabla \cdot (K \nabla T_0) \quad (11.7)$$

Further defining

$$N^2 \equiv -\frac{\mathbf{g} \cdot \nabla s_0}{C_P} \quad (11.8)$$

we can write

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial p'}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \rho'}{\partial t} - \frac{\rho_0 N^2}{|\mathbf{g}|^2} \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{g} = \frac{1}{\rho_0 T_0} \nabla \cdot (K \nabla T_0) \quad (11.9)$$

Let us now Fourier-transform the perturbations temporally ($t \rightarrow \omega$) and in the horizontal directions ($(x, y) \rightarrow \mathbf{k}$, where \mathbf{k} is the horizontal wavevector), e.g.

$$\rho'(x, y, z, t) = \int d\omega dx dy \tilde{\rho}(k_x, k_y, z, \omega) e^{ik_x x + ik_y y - i\omega t} \quad (11.10)$$

In what follows, we use \tilde{p} and $\tilde{\rho}$ to denote the Fourier transforms of p' and ρ' . The Fourier transform of the vertical velocity is denoted by \tilde{u} , while the Fourier transform of the horizontal velocity is denoted by $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}$. These are now functions of \mathbf{k} , ω , and z . The equations for these Fourier components (given a particular choice of k, ω) follow from the Fourier transforms of equations 11.4, 11.5, and 11.9.

$$-i\omega \tilde{\rho} = -\frac{d(\rho_0 \tilde{u})}{dz} - i\rho_0 \mathbf{k} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{v}} \quad (11.11)$$

$$-i\omega \rho_0 \tilde{u} = \left(-\frac{dp_0}{dz} + \rho_0 g \right) \delta(\omega) \delta(\mathbf{k}) - \frac{d\tilde{p}}{dz} + \tilde{\rho} g - \rho_0 \Gamma \tilde{u} \quad (11.12)$$

$$-i\omega \rho_0 \tilde{\mathbf{v}} = -i\mathbf{k} \tilde{p} - \rho_0 \Gamma \tilde{\mathbf{v}} \quad (11.13)$$

$$-\frac{i\omega \tilde{p}}{c^2} = -i\omega \tilde{\rho} + \frac{\rho_0 N^2 \tilde{u}}{g} + \frac{1}{\rho_0 T_0} \frac{d}{dz} \left(K \frac{dT_0}{dz} \right) \delta(\omega) \delta(\mathbf{k}) \quad (11.14)$$

¹Birch, Kosovichev, and Duvall (2004, eq. 37) seem to call this the ‘adiabatic approximation’. However, note that this requires an assumption about the equation of state in addition to adiabaticity.

where $g \equiv \mathbf{g} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{z}} < 0$. Note that to facilitate comparison of the derived equations with the work of other authors (Birch, Kosovichev, and Duvall 2004; Schunker et al. 2011, sec. 2.3), we have heuristically inserted a damping term (where Γ may be a function $\Gamma(k, z)$) in all three components of the momentum equation; we intend to set this term to zero in our analysis. Since the evolution equations for the rest of the quantities only depend on $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}$ through $\mathbf{k} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{v}}$, we define $\tilde{v} \equiv \hat{\mathbf{k}} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{v}}$, and write

$$-i\omega\tilde{\rho} = -\frac{d(\rho_0\tilde{u})}{dz} - i\rho_0k\tilde{v} \quad (11.15)$$

$$-i\omega\rho_0\tilde{u} = \left(-\frac{dp_0}{dz} + \rho_0g\right)\delta(\mathbf{k})\delta(\omega) - \frac{d\tilde{p}}{dz} + \tilde{\rho}g - \rho_0\Gamma\tilde{u} \quad (11.16)$$

$$-i\omega\rho_0\tilde{v} = -ik\tilde{p} - \rho_0\Gamma\tilde{v} \quad (11.17)$$

$$-\frac{i\omega\tilde{p}}{c^2} = -i\omega\tilde{\rho} + \frac{\rho_0N^2\tilde{u}}{g} + \frac{1}{\rho_0T_0}\frac{d}{dz}\left(K\frac{dT_0}{dz}\right)\delta(\omega)\delta(\mathbf{k}) \quad (11.18)$$

Assuming $\omega \neq 0$, we can use equation 11.18 to eliminate $\tilde{\rho}$ from the other equations. Further defining

$$-i\beta \equiv \Gamma - i\omega \quad (11.19)$$

we write

$$\frac{-i\omega\tilde{p}}{c^2} - \frac{\rho_0N^2\tilde{u}}{g} = -\frac{d(\rho_0\tilde{u})}{dz} - i\rho_0k\tilde{v} \quad (11.20)$$

$$-i\beta\rho_0\tilde{u} = -\frac{d\tilde{p}}{dz} + \frac{g\tilde{p}}{c^2} + \frac{\rho_0N^2\tilde{u}}{i\omega} \quad (11.21)$$

$$-i\beta\rho_0\tilde{v} = -ik\tilde{p} \quad (11.22)$$

Using equation 11.22 to eliminate \tilde{v} from equation 11.20, we are left with

$$\frac{-i\omega\tilde{p}}{c^2} - \frac{\rho_0N^2\tilde{u}}{g} = -\frac{d(\rho_0\tilde{u})}{dz} - \frac{ik^2\tilde{p}}{\beta} \quad (11.23)$$

$$-i\beta\rho_0\tilde{u} = -\frac{d\tilde{p}}{dz} + \frac{g\tilde{p}}{c^2} + \frac{\rho_0N^2\tilde{u}}{i\omega} \quad (11.24)$$

Following Birch, Kosovichev, and Duvall (2004, eqs. A8–A9) and Schunker et al. (2011, appendix B), we define

$$y_1 \equiv \frac{i\tilde{p}}{\sqrt{\rho_0c}} \quad (11.25)$$

$$y_2 \equiv \tilde{u}\sqrt{\rho_0c} \quad (11.26)$$

and write

$$\frac{dy_1}{dz} = \left(-\frac{1}{2}\frac{d\ln\rho_0}{dz} - \frac{1}{2}\frac{d\ln c}{dz} + \frac{g}{c^2}\right)y_1 + \left(\frac{N^2}{\omega c} - \frac{\beta}{c}\right)y_2 \quad (11.27a)$$

$$\frac{dy_2}{dz} = \left(\frac{\omega}{c} - \frac{ck^2}{\beta}\right)y_1 + \left(-\frac{1}{2}\frac{d\ln\rho_0}{dz} + \frac{1}{2}\frac{d\ln c}{dz} + \frac{N^2}{g}\right)y_2 \quad (11.27b)$$

11.2.2 Boundary conditions

11.2.2.1 Impenetrable boundary

For a boundary at $z = z_b$, this corresponds to requiring

$$y_2(z_b) = 0 \quad (11.28)$$

11.2.2.2 Zero Lagrangian pressure perturbation

The Lagrangian pressure perturbation is defined as

$$\delta p \equiv \partial p + \boldsymbol{\xi} \cdot \nabla p \quad (11.29)$$

where ∂p is the Eulerian pressure perturbation, and $\boldsymbol{\xi}$ is the fluid displacement vector. Linearizing the above and identifying $p' = \partial p$ gives us

$$\delta p = p' + \boldsymbol{\xi} \cdot \nabla p_0 \quad (11.30)$$

The fluid displacement can be related to the velocity as

$$\mathbf{v} = \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}}{\partial t} \quad (11.31)$$

In Fourier space, we thus find

$$\tilde{u} = -i\omega \tilde{\xi}_z \quad (11.32)$$

Setting $\delta p = 0$ in equation 11.30, taking its horizontal and temporal Fourier transforms, and using the above, we write

$$\tilde{p} - \frac{\tilde{u}}{i\omega} \frac{dp_0}{dz} = 0 \quad (11.33)$$

In terms of the variables y_1 and y_2 , this becomes^{2,3}

$$\omega y_1 - \frac{y_2}{\rho_0 c} \frac{dp_0}{dz} = 0 \quad (11.34)$$

11.2.3 Simplification assuming hydrostatic equilibrium and ideal-gas background

Although we will not be using these assumptions, we perform this simplification in order to check that the equations we have derived are consistent with those given by Birch, Kosovichev, and Duvall (2004).

²Schunker et al. (2011, sec 2.2 and p. 24) define the relationship between the velocity and the displacement to include the damping term, and so their boundary condition contains contributions from the damping term as well.

³Schunker et al. (2011, p. 24) seem to have accidentally taken ξ_z to be the derivative of u , rather than the other way around. Their boundary condition is thus different from ours.

11.2.3.1 Evolution equation

For an ideal gas with the ratio of specific heats given by γ , one can write

$$N^2 = -\frac{g}{C_P} \frac{ds_0}{dz} \quad (11.35)$$

$$= -g \left(\frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{d \ln p_0}{dz} - \frac{d \ln \rho_0}{dz} \right) \quad (11.36)$$

Moreover, hydrostatic equilibrium of the background state implies

$$\frac{d \ln p_0}{dz} = \frac{\gamma g}{c^2} \quad (11.37)$$

Using these, we write

$$-\frac{1}{2} \frac{d \ln \rho_0}{dz} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{d \ln c}{dz} + \frac{N^2}{g} = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{d \ln \rho_0}{dz} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{d \ln c}{dz} - \left(\frac{g}{c^2} - \frac{d \ln \rho_0}{dz} \right) \quad (11.38)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \frac{d \ln \rho_0}{dz} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{d \ln c}{dz} - \frac{g}{c^2} \quad (11.39)$$

Thus, defining

$$\frac{1}{H} \equiv -\frac{1}{2} \frac{d \ln \rho_0}{dz} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{d \ln c}{dz} + \frac{g}{c^2} \quad (11.40)$$

we can write equations 11.27a and 11.27b as

$$\frac{dy_1}{dz} = \frac{y_1}{H} + \left(\frac{N^2}{\omega c} - \frac{\beta}{c} \right) y_2 \quad (11.41a)$$

$$\frac{dy_2}{dz} = \left(\frac{\omega}{c} - \frac{ck^2}{\beta} \right) y_1 - \frac{y_2}{H} \quad (11.41b)$$

These are the same as the equations derived by Birch, Kosovichev, and Duvall (2004, eqs. A10–A11).⁴

11.2.3.2 Zero Lagrangian pressure perturbation boundary condition

Assuming hydrostatic equilibrium, equation 11.34 can be simplified as

$$\omega y_1 - \frac{g}{c} y_2 = 0 \quad (11.42)$$

which matches the expression given by Birch, Kosovichev, and Duvall (2004, eq. A21).

Figure 11.1: The algorithm used to construct the dispersion relation, which has the parameters ω_{\min} , ω_{\max} , n_{ω} , and Δ . This algorithm gives the modes for a particular value of k , and can be repeated for as many values as required.

11.3 Numerical methods

Equations 11.27, along with appropriate boundary conditions, describe a boundary value problem. For a given choice of background profiles and k , solutions consistent with the imposed boundary conditions typically exist only for discrete values of ω . We restrict ω to be real; this means that even if the background is unstably stratified, we do not obtain the corresponding unstable eigenmodes. To make the problem numerically well-determined, we impose the normalization condition

$$\int_{z_{\text{bot}}}^{z_{\text{top}}} \frac{|y_2|^2}{c} dz = \text{sgn}(\omega) \quad (11.43)$$

where the quantity on the LHS is proportional to the vertical kinetic energy. The use of $\text{sgn}(\omega)$ instead of 1 on the RHS allows us to select $\omega > 0$.

We use the `solve_bvp` function provided by SciPy (Virtanen et al. 2020) to solve the equations for a chosen value of k . Choosing different initial guesses for ω , y_1 , and y_2 allows us to find different values of ω , and the corresponding solutions $y_1(z)$ and $y_2(z)$. The initial guess for y_2 is chosen in terms of the functions

$$\psi_p(n) \equiv \sin \left((n+1) \pi \frac{z - z_{\text{bot}}}{z_{\text{top}} - z_{\text{bot}}} \right) \quad (11.44)$$

$$\psi_f \equiv \begin{cases} e^{-|kz|} & z < 0 \\ 1 - \frac{z}{z_{\text{top}}} & z \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (11.45)$$

Figure 11.1 describes the algorithm used to construct the dispersion relations of modes of interest in the k - ω plane, and obtain the corresponding eigenfunctions.

11.4 Eigenmodes in a simulation of convection

Let us consider a background state constructed from the statistically steady state of the simulation described in section 12.4. The required quantities are first horizontally averaged, and then temporally averaged over multiple turnover times. Figure 11.2 shows some of the quantities obtained in this way, in units such that $g = -1$.

Using the procedure described in section 11.3, we solve equations 11.27. The top and bottom boundaries are kept impenetrable, while the damping, Γ , is set to zero.

Figure 11.3 shows the obtained dispersion relation. Above the $\omega = c_{\text{bot}}k$ line, p modes are reflected from the impenetrable boundary at the bottom of the domain. On the other hand, p modes below this line are reflected from higher layers, and do not reach the bottom boundary. We see that when p modes are reflected from

⁴Note that Birch, Kosovichev, and Duvall (2004) seem to take $g > 0$, while we take $g < 0$.

Figure 11.2: Profiles of background quantities from a simulation of convection.

Figure 11.3: Eigenvalues of equations 11.27 with the background taken from a simulation of convection. Eigenvalues are coloured according to the number of vertical nodes in the corresponding $u(k, z, \omega)$. The black dashed line shows $\omega = c_{\text{bot}}k$. The highest mode which is completely below this line (with 0 vertical nodes throughout) is the f mode. Modes above this are the p modes. Note that the g modes have not been completely captured since the k, ω grid used did not contain such low frequencies. We have defined $\tilde{\omega} \equiv \omega c_{\text{top}}/|g|$ and $\tilde{k} \equiv k c_{\text{top}}^2/|g|$.

Figure 11.4: Similar to figure 11.3, but with the background now taken from Solar model S. The black dashed line is $\omega = c_{\text{bot}}k$, while the solid black line is $\omega = \sqrt{g_{\text{top}}}k$.

an impenetrable boundary at the bottom of the domain, the lowest p mode has 0 vertical nodes. On the other hand, when p modes are reflected due to total internal reflection (without touching the bottom boundary), the lowest p mode has one radial node. Note that for p modes, the $\omega = c_{\text{bot}}k$ line marks the transition from $\omega \propto k^2$ (expected for low k when all the mode cavities are the same) to $\omega \propto \sqrt{k}$ (expected when the mode cavities are determined by total internal reflection; see Leibacher and Stein 1981, p. 277)

11.5 The eigenmodes of Solar Model S

Using the procedure described in section 11.3, we solve equations 11.27, with the background now taken from Solar Model S (Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 1996). At the top boundary, the Lagrangian pressure perturbation is set to zero; the bottom boundary is kept impenetrable; and the damping, Γ , is set to zero. To compute the entropy gradient in Solar Model S, we follow the procedure outlined in section 11.A.

Figure 11.4 shows the k - ω diagram obtained by setting $z_{\text{bot}} = -690$ Mm and $z_{\text{top}} = 0.45$ Mm. As in section 11.4, we see that the number of radial nodes for the p modes changes by one as one crosses the $\omega = c_{\text{bot}}k$ line. We note that due to the extreme vertical truncation of their domain, Schunker et al. (2011) could've

Figure 11.5: Similar to figure 11.4, but with N^2 restricted to be ≤ 0 Hz. While the f mode is slightly closer to its theoretical dispersion relation at low k , the deviations are still significant.

Figure 11.6: Similar to figure 11.4, but with the domain truncated at $z = -200$ Mm to exclude the radiative zone. Note that the f mode is now closer to its theoretical dispersion relation at low k .

Figure 11.7: The components of the p mode eigenfunction, following the ridge that passes through $\omega \approx 2.7 \text{ mHz}$ at $kR_{\odot} = 0$. Recall that y_1 describes the pressure perturbations, while y_2 describes those of the radial velocity.

obtained a p mode with zero radial nodes by just halving their lowest reported value of k .

Since the peak Brunt-Väisälä frequency in the solar radiative zone corresponds to $\omega \approx 3 \times 10^{-3}$ Hz, one may naively attribute the deviation of the f mode from its expected dispersion relation ($\omega = \sqrt{g_{\text{top}}k}$) at low k in figure 11.4 to avoided crossings between the g and f modes.⁵ However, figure 11.5 shows that the f mode deviates even when the g modes are artificially removed by keeping $N^2 \leq 0$ in the domain (i.e., setting $N^2 = 0$ in regions where it is positive, while keeping the other parameters in equations 11.27 unchanged). On the other hand, when the domain is truncated by placing an impenetrable boundary at -200 Mm (i.e. excluding the radiative zone), the f mode closely follows its expected dispersion relation (figure 11.6). A deeper domain leads to a longer sound travel time, and thus decreases the frequency of the lowest p mode (compare figure 11.4 with 11.6 at low k). It thus seems that the f mode deviates from its expected dispersion relation when its frequency becomes close to that of the lowest p mode.

Figure 11.7 shows how the eigenfunction of the p mode changes across the $\omega = c_{\text{bot}}k$ line, following the same ridge.

11.6 Application to the Sun

Till now, we have been using a plane-parallel model with an impenetrable boundary placed at the bottom. One expects waves which penetrate close to the center of the Sun to be affected both by spherical effects and the boundary condition chosen at the center.

ADIPLS (Christensen-Dalsgaard 2008) is a widely used program that computes eigenmodes of the linearized perturbation equations, including the effects of spherical geometry and without using the Cowling approximation. To understand if the discussion in section 11.5 is applicable to the Sun, we now examine the eigenfunctions computed by ADIPLS. For these calculations, we use a solar model (famd1.19b1.d.202c) distributed along with the program.

First, let us relax the plane-parallel assumption, but still work with a truncated domain (with the inner 5% of the radial extent removed) in the Cowling approximation. As before, we set the radial displacement to zero at the bottom boundary. Figure 11.8 shows the number of nodes of the radial displacement for the eigenfunctions calculated by ADIPLS. Just relaxing the plane-parallel assumption seems to have made the line, along which the node number changes, much steeper than before, such that one would have to go to p modes of very high radial order to actually find a regime where, say, the number of nodes for a particular p mode at $l = 1$ is different from that for the same mode at $l = 2$.

To check the effect of the radial truncation, we now use the full radial extent, but retain the Cowling approximation. The boundary condition at the center,

⁵For example, Aizenman, Smeyers, and Weigert (1977, fig. 6) show, in a model of a $16M_{\odot}$ star, that there are avoided crossings between the f and g modes.

Figure 11.8: Eigenvalues computed by ADIPLS using Solar Model S with a radially truncated domain in the Cowling approximation. As before, the eigenvalues are coloured according to the number of nodes (excluding the boundaries) of the corresponding radial displacement. The left panel covers $\ell \leq 2$, while the right panel covers $\ell > 2$. The solid black line marks $\omega = \sqrt{|g|k}$, with $|g|$ taken at the solar surface and $k \equiv \ell(\ell + 1)/R_\odot$. The dashed black line marks $\omega = c_{\max}k$.

Figure 11.9: Eigenvalues computed by ADIPLS using the full radial extent of Solar Model S in the Cowling approximation. The colouring is as in figure 11.8.

Figure 11.10: Eigenvalues computed by ADIPLS using the full radial extent of Solar Model S without the Cowling approximation. The vertical grey line marks $l = 1$. The colouring is as in figure 11.8.

which is a singular point in spherical coordinates, is now determined by requiring that the solution be finite at the origin (Christensen-Dalsgaard, Dilke, and Gough 1974, eqs. 4.8). Figure 11.9 shows that for all the radial orders considered, the number of nodes now only differs between the radial ($l = 0$) and non-radial p modes. While this distinction was noticed by Osaki (1975, sec. 4b), who also used the Cowling approximation, they rationalized it by arguing that the center of the star should also be considered a node when $l = 0$.

One would expect the Cowling approximation to be accurate for objects such as the Sun. Nevertheless, relaxing the Cowling approximation qualitatively changes the picture. In figure 11.10, we see that the line along which the number of nodes changes now has a *negative* slope. While the the lowest two p modes change node number for $l > 1$ (such that a particular ridge has a different number of nodes for $l > 1$ as compared to $l \leq 1$), the higher p modes change node number for $l > 0$. While the behaviour of the lowest p mode could perhaps be understood as an avoided crossing with the f mode, it seems difficult to interpret the behaviour of the second lowest p mode in the same way. Christensen-Dalsgaard (2018, p. 14) also mentions this issue, and attributes it to effects which are not captured by the Cowling approximation.

11.7 Conclusions

By numerically computing the eigenfunctions and eigenvalues of the linearized perturbation equations for adiabatic oscillations in a plane-parallel domain under

the Cowling approximation, we have shown that if one follows a particular ridge in the k - ω diagnostic diagram, the number of vertical nodes of the vertical displacement changes across the $\omega = c_{\text{bot}}k$ line, where c_{bot} is the sound speed at the bottom of the domain. The number of vertical nodes for $\omega > c_{\text{bot}}k$ is one less than the number of vertical nodes of the same ridge for $\omega < c_{\text{bot}}k$. This distinction seems to be related to the fact that k determines the depth from which a wave of a particular frequency is reflected (Leibacher and Stein 1981, p. 273).

Simulations, such as those reported by Singh et al. (2015) or that used in section 11.4, typically have very limited vertical variation of the sound speed (if at all). For example, in the simulation considered in section 11.4, $c_{\text{top}}/c_{\text{bot}} = 0.3$. It is thus easiest to measure modes above the $\omega = c_{\text{bot}}k$ line, and one ends up finding that the lowest p mode has no vertical nodes. On the other hand, Schunker et al. (2011) exclusively considered high values of k , and concluded that the lowest p mode has one radial node.

When the effects of a spherical geometry are taken into account and the entire radial extent of the Sun is considered, the picture above fails. Still working in the Cowling approximation gives the result that if one restricts oneself to a single p mode ridge in l - ω space, the p mode has one node less for $l = 0$ than for $l \neq 0$ (this was shown for a star of mass $10M_{\odot}$ by Osaki 1975, sec. 4b). In the case of the Sun, relaxing the Cowling approximation qualitatively changes the first few p modes: in particular, for the first two p modes, moving from $l = 1$ to $l = 2$ changes the number of nodes of the radial displacement corresponding to the eigenfunctions (Christensen-Dalsgaard 2018, p. 14).

Appendices to chapter 11

11.A Computation of the entropy gradient from Solar Model S

For an ideal gas, one can calculate the entropy gradient from the gradients of the logarithmic temperature and density, along with the gas constant and the ratio of specific heats. However, using such an approximation for Solar Model S (Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 1996) wrongly predicts that the majority of the convection zone is stably stratified. To correctly calculate the entropy gradient, one has to use a more general approach, which we describe below.

The general expression for the entropy gradient (without assuming ideality) is

$$\nabla S = C_V \nabla \ln T - \frac{P}{\rho T} \nabla \ln \rho \quad (11.46)$$

The model S data⁶ do not directly provide C_V , and so this expression needs to be rewritten in terms of the available quantities.

Recall the following relations between the specific heat capacities (Gaskell 2003, eq. 5.38 and problem 5.9; Çengel and Boles 2015, eq. 12.49):

$$C_P - C_V = \frac{T\alpha^2}{\rho\beta_T} \quad (11.47)$$

$$\frac{C_P}{C_V} = \frac{\beta_T}{\beta_S} \quad (11.48)$$

where

$$\alpha \equiv \left(-\frac{\partial \ln \rho}{\partial T} \right)_P \quad (11.49)$$

$$\beta_T \equiv \left(\frac{\partial \ln \rho}{\partial P} \right)_T \quad (11.50)$$

$$\beta_S \equiv \left(\frac{\partial \ln \rho}{\partial P} \right)_S \quad (11.51)$$

⁶Available at https://users-physics.au.dk/~jcd/solar_models/.

Among the provided model variables, we have C_P , $\delta \equiv T\alpha$, and $\Gamma_1 \equiv (P\beta_S)^{-1}$. We use equations [11.47](#) and [11.48](#) to write

$$C_V = C_P^2 \left(\frac{P}{\rho T} \Gamma_1 \delta^2 + C_P \right)^{-1} \quad (11.52)$$

After computing C_V using the above, we can use equation [11.46](#) to compute the entropy gradient.

Chapter 12

Magnetic effects on helioseismic modes

12.1 Introduction

At a free surface, the incompressible deep-water equations support waves whose eigenfunctions decay exponentially with depth over a scale proportional to their horizontal wavelength (e.g. Acheson 1990, sec. 3.2). Such surface waves are also supported at interfaces with a finite density contrast (Singh et al. 2015, section 3.2 and references therein). In the stellar context, the corresponding modes are usually referred to as f (‘fundamental’) modes. Since their eigenfunctions decay rapidly with depth (at least for large horizontal wavenumbers), these modes are only expected to be affected by the near-surface layers of the Sun.

Singh, Raichur, and Brandenburg (2016) and Waidele et al. (2023) have found that localized strengthening of the solar f mode precedes the emergence of an active region by up to 48 hours. For the large horizontal wavenumbers considered in these observations, the eigenfunction of the f mode is expected to decay with depth over a scale of a few Mm. For example, Singh, Raichur, and Brandenburg (2016) considered f modes with $kR_{\odot} > 1200$, which decay over less than 0.6 Mm. This suggests that the precursors of active regions are present in the upper few Mm of the CZ 48 hours before the emergence of the region.

Sunspot formation is often explained by appealing to magnetic flux tubes buried at the bottom of the convection zone (CZ), approximately 200 Mm below the surface (for reviews, see Charbonneau 2020; Karak et al. 2014, section 2). Such flux tubes may rise either due to magnetic buoyancy (Parker 1975), or due to kink instabilities (Babcock 1961, p. 577). Rising flux tubes are expected to cross the top 10 Mm of the CZ (around 11 pressure scale heights) in a few hours (Cheung et al. 2010). This is difficult to reconcile with the aforementioned observations.

Going beyond the qualitative reasoning described above, one would like to use observations to quantitatively constrain the location, strength, and configuration of subsurface magnetic fields. However, analytical predictions of the effects of magnetic

fields on helioseismic modes exist only for some very simple field configurations: e.g. a uniform magnetic field (Miles, Allen, and Roberts 1992), a dipolar magnetic field (Rui and Fuller 2023), and a horizontal magnetic field with exponential vertical variation (Tripathi and Mitra 2022, 2024). Further, while such analytical studies predict dispersion relations, they do not say much about the amplitudes of the modes.

Singh, Brandenburg, and Rheinhardt (2014) and Singh et al. (2015, 2020) have performed 2D simulations where turbulence is driven by a prescribed forcing function in a piecewise isothermal background. Imposing magnetic fields of different configurations, they observed changes in both the frequencies and amplitudes of various modes. Singh et al. (2015, sec. 4.2) found that in the presence of a strong, uniform, horizontal magnetic field, the amplitude of the f mode is suppressed at large wavenumbers. Singh, Brandenburg, and Rheinhardt (2014, eq. 6) and Singh et al. (2020, eqs. 6, 7) studied more realistic magnetic field configurations: both harmonic profiles and localized sinusoids. For the harmonic profile, they reported strengthening of the f mode at all wavenumbers (Singh et al. 2020, figs. 3), along with widening (‘fanning’) of the f mode (Singh, Brandenburg, and Rheinhardt 2014, fig. 4) For a localized magnetic field, Singh et al. (2020) found that the f mode is strengthened at large wavenumbers, but only when magnetic fields is near the surface.

The amplitude of a particular mode depends on the spectral properties of the forcing function used (see Christensen-Dalsgaard 2002, section V.F). In the case of the Sun, the modes are excited by convective flows, which may themselves be affected by the magnetic field through the Lorentz force. Thus, while the analytical studies and idealized forced-turbulence simulations described above can be used to understand how the frequencies of various modes are affected by magnetic fields, it is unclear if their findings on the amplitudes of various modes can be applied to convective systems. The amplitudes are sensitive to the nature of the fluid flows, and so one has to perform nonlinear simulations of stratified convection to capture the relevant effects. While many authors have observed modes (f, p, and inertial) in simulations of convection (e.g. Zhao et al. 2007; Waidele, Zhao, and Kitiashvili 2023; Blume, Hindman, and Matilsky 2024), we are not aware of any studies of magnetic effects on modes in such simulations.

In this chapter, we use simulations in which convection is driven by a prescribed cooling function at the top of the domain. Peaks of the horizontally and temporally Fourier-transformed vertical velocity from such simulations can be associated with f, p, and g modes. Imposing magnetic fields of various configurations, we measure their effects on mode amplitudes near the top of the domain.

Section 12.2 discusses our numerical setup. Section 12.3 sets forth the definitions, conventions, and models we employ. Section 12.4 describes our non-magnetic convection simulation. In section 12.5, we study how imposed magnetic fields at various depths affect the f mode. Finally, section 12.6 summarizes our conclusions and points out future directions.

12.2 Numerical setup

12.2.1 Domain and evolution equations

We consider a Cartesian domain, periodic in the x and y directions. Gravity points along the $-\hat{\mathbf{z}}$ direction. The domain extends vertically between $-0.45l < z < 1.05l$, where l is the depth of the initially unstable region. A similar setup has been used earlier by Käpylä (2019c).

We solve the following evolution equations:

$$\frac{D \ln \rho}{dt} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \quad (12.1)$$

$$\rho \frac{D \mathbf{u}}{dt} = -\nabla p - \rho g \hat{\mathbf{z}} + \mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B} + \nabla \cdot (2\rho\nu \overleftrightarrow{S}) \quad (12.2)$$

$$\rho T \frac{Ds}{dt} = q - \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{F}_{\text{rad}} + \mathbf{F}_{\text{SGS}}) + 2\rho\nu S_{ij} S_{ij} \quad (12.3)$$

where

$$\mathbf{B} \equiv \nabla \times \mathbf{A} \quad (12.4)$$

$$\mathbf{J} \equiv \frac{\nabla \times \mathbf{B}}{\mu_0} \quad (12.5)$$

$$S_{ij} \equiv \frac{1}{2} \left(\partial_i u_j + \partial_j u_i - \frac{2}{3} \delta_{ij} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \right) \quad (12.6)$$

with ρ being the density; \mathbf{u} the velocity; p the pressure; g the acceleration due to gravity; \mathbf{A} a prescribed magnetic vector potential (we will later specify the forms used in this study); ν the kinematic viscosity; s the specific entropy; μ_0 the magnetic permeability; and $D/dt \equiv \partial/\partial t + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla$ the convective derivative.

We choose units such that $g = C_P = l = \rho_0 = 1$, where C_P is the specific heat at constant pressure and ρ_0 is the initial density at the top of the domain. With these choices, the unit for length is l ; mass is $\rho_0 l^3$; time is $\sqrt{l/g}$; temperature is gl/C_P ; and magnetic field is $\sqrt{\mu_0 \rho_0 gl}$. We assume the kinematic viscosity is a constant ($\nu = 10^{-4} l^{3/2} g^{1/2}$), and neglect the bulk viscosity (omitted from the expressions above).

In the evolution equation for the entropy, \mathbf{F}_{rad} is the radiative flux determined by the Kramers opacity formula (i.e. the thermal conductivity is itself a function of the temperature and the density), such that

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{rad}} = -K_0 \rho^{-2} T^{13/2} \nabla T \quad (12.7)$$

where T is the temperature. Käpylä et al. (2017) have studied how such a prescription differs from more common choices. We set $K_0 = 1.4131275 \rho_0^3 C_P^{15/2} l^{-5} g^{-6}$.

Following Käpylä (2021), we also have a subgrid-scale (SGS) diffusivity that acts on the fluctuations of the entropy about its horizontal average. The SGS diffusivity is set to $\chi_{\text{SGS}} = 10^{-4} l^{3/2} g^{1/2}$, and the entropy flux due to it is given by

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{SGS}} \equiv -\rho T \chi_{\text{SGS}} \nabla s', \quad s' \equiv s - \langle s \rangle_{xy} \quad (12.8)$$

This is required because in a stratified Kramers setup, the thermal conductivity is typically much smaller at the top of the domain than at the bottom. Trying to keep $\text{Pr} \lesssim 1$ at the top of the domain would then lead to an extremely large thermal diffusivity at the bottom of the domain (and thus infeasibly small timesteps). On the other hand, setting a numerically reasonable value of the thermal conductivity at the bottom of the domain would lead to $\text{Pr} \gg 1$ at the top of the domain. We make the latter choice. Adding a subgrid diffusivity then (i) allows us to have a grid much coarser than the thermal microscale corresponding to the Kramers conductivity at the top of the domain; and (ii) ensures that the turbulence ‘sees’ $\text{Pr} \lesssim 1$.

A cooling function, q , of the form

$$q = -\frac{\rho(c_s^2 - c_{\text{cool}}^2)}{\tau_{\text{cool}}} \Theta\left(\frac{z - z_{\text{cool}}}{w_{\text{cool}}}\right) \quad (12.9)$$

with $\Theta(z) \equiv (1 + \text{erf}(z))/2$, $z_{\text{cool}} = l$, $c_{\text{cool}}^2 = 0.09 gl$, $w_{\text{cool}} = 0.025 l$, and $\tau_{\text{cool}} = (1/27) \sqrt{l/g}$ has also been added to the entropy equation. This forces the sound speed in $z > z_{\text{cool}}$ to c_{cool} over a timescale τ_{cool} .

The fluid is chosen to be an ideal gas, whose equation of state is

$$p = \rho RT = \rho_0 RT_0 \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0}\right)^\gamma e^{\gamma s/C_P} \quad (12.10)$$

where $R \equiv C_P - C_V$ and $\gamma \equiv C_P/C_V$, with C_V being the specific heat at constant volume. We set $\gamma = 5/3$, corresponding to a monoatomic gas. Note that the zero point of the entropy is determined by the constant T_0 , which we choose such that $(\gamma - 1) C_P T_0 = c_{\text{cool}}^2$.

These evolution equations are solved using the PENCIL code (Pencil Code Collaboration et al. 2021).¹ Spatial derivatives are discretized using a sixth-order finite difference scheme, while the equations are evolved in time using a third-order Runge-Kutta method. Upwinding is used for advection of the density, the velocity, and the entropy. We use $N_x \times N_y \times N_z = 1152^2 \times 288$ grid points with $L_x = L_y = 16l$.

12.2.2 Modelling the magnetic field

The magnetic field affects helioseismic modes in two ways: first, it affects the velocity field through the Lorentz force, thus changing the driving of the modes; second, it introduces new families of waves. The interaction of the latter with hydrodynamic waves can modify the dispersion relations of various modes. An additional complicating factor is that the evolution of the magnetic field is itself affected by the velocity field.

We would like to be able to control the strength and the configuration of the magnetic field independent of the other system parameters. Motivated by this,

¹<http://pencil-code.org>

we take the simplest possible approach, which is to prescribe a time-independent magnetic field by choosing an appropriate functional form for \mathbf{A} . The result of the magnetic field (or rather, the vector potential) not being a dynamical quantity is that all the waves in our system are purely hydrodynamic, with modes only being affected indirectly due to changes in the statistical properties of the velocity field.

Alternatively, one can control the configuration of the magnetic field, without eliminating magnetic waves, by solving an evolution equation for \mathbf{A} which contains a prescribed EMF in addition to the usual inductive and resistive terms. This approach was used by Singh, Brandenburg, and Rheinhardt (2014) and Singh et al. (2020) in their forced-turbulence simulations, wherein the prescribed EMF was chosen to give a highly super-equipartition magnetic field. In our preliminary experiments, we found that this approach did not allow sufficiently precise control of near- or sub-equipartition magnetic fields. Nevertheless, since our approach has drastic limitations, future work should explore how one can control the configuration of the magnetic field without completely eliminating magnetic waves.

12.2.3 Boundary conditions

The vertical boundaries are made free-slip and impenetrable. The enthalpy flux at the bottom is constrained to be $5 \times 10^{-4} \rho_0 g^{3/2} l^{3/2}$, while the temperature at the top is constrained to be T_0 .

12.2.4 Initial conditions

To have decent resolution in k -space, we require the aspect ratio (horizontal/vertical dimension) of the domain to be large. However, running such simulations till they reach a statistically steady state is expensive. To circumvent this, we use the following procedure wherein a simulation with the required large aspect ratio (width/height) is initialized from one with a lower aspect ratio.

We first run a non-magnetic simulation with $L_x = L_y = l$ for $10^4 \sqrt{l/g}$ time units. For this simulation, the initial condition is piecewise polytropic, with the polytropic index being given by

$$\begin{cases} 3.25 & z < 0 \\ 1.5 & 0 < z < l \\ \infty & l < z \end{cases} \quad (12.11)$$

The temperature at the top is set to T_0 . The velocity at each grid point is randomly chosen such that each of its components are uniformly distributed between $\pm 10^{-4} \sqrt{gl}$.

A snapshot (an array containing all the state variables at each grid point) from this simulation is then periodically tiled to generate the initial condition for the non-magnetic simulation. To break the symmetry of the initial condition, low-amplitude grid-scale noise (with each of its components at each grid point

uniformly distributed between $\pm 10^{-3}\sqrt{gl}$) is added to the velocity field. This leads to the symmetry of the initial condition being broken within a few turnover times. Four realizations are produced, differing only in the initial random component of the velocity field. For all our analyses, we ignore data from the first $300\sqrt{l/g}$ time units of the larger non-magnetic simulations.

The magnetic simulations are initialized from snapshots of the non-magnetic simulations. To ensure statistical independence of the different realizations of a particular magnetic configuration, we make sure that even when two such realizations are initialized from the same non-magnetic realization, the snapshots have a minimum time-separation of $1000\sqrt{l/g}$.

12.2.5 Simulation output

The horizontal Fourier transform of the vertical component of the velocity is saved at all depths for $|k_x|, |k_y| \leq \gamma g/c_{\text{top}}^2$ at intervals of $0.1\sqrt{l/g}$ time units ($0.5\sqrt{l/g}$ for the non-magnetic case). The temporal Fourier transform is later performed during post-processing.

12.2.6 Sources of error

We expect the two main sources of error to be (i) the finiteness of the integration time; and (ii) the spatial discretization used. We estimate the error due to the former by considering multiple realizations of the same configuration. The realizations of a particular configuration differ only in the random component of the velocity field, added to the initial condition.

The error in the power spectrum of the vertical component of the velocity field (the quantity which we later define as P) is estimated by averaging over all realizations; we consider the error in this estimate to be σ/\sqrt{N} , where σ is the standard deviation between different realizations and N is the number of realizations. Note that an estimate of this kind does not account for the error due to the spatial discretization.

12.3 Definitions, conventions, and models

12.3.1 Fourier transform

We define the discrete Fourier transform (see appendix 7.C) as

$$f_n = \frac{1}{L} \int_{-L/2}^{L/2} f(x) e^{-ikx} dx \quad (12.12)$$

where $k \equiv 2\pi n/L$ (the inverse transformation is given by equation 7.24). If we are only given values of x on a discrete grid with spacing δx , we cannot resolve

wavenumbers for which $|n| > L/(2\delta x)$ (the Nyquist limit, e.g. Bracewell 2000, p. 223).

Equations 7.24 and 12.12 imply²

$$\delta(x - a) = \frac{1}{L} \sum_n \exp\left(-i \frac{2n\pi}{L} (x - a)\right) \quad (12.13)$$

This means we can write

$$\sum_n f_n f_n^* = \frac{1}{L^2} \int_{-L/2}^{L/2} dx_1 \int_{-L/2}^{L/2} dx_2 f(x_1) f^*(x_2) \exp\left(-i \frac{2n\pi}{L} (x_1 - x_2)\right) \quad (12.14)$$

$$= \frac{1}{L} \int_{-L/2}^{L/2} dx f(x) f^*(x) \quad (12.15)$$

The quantity on the RHS is the mean-square average of $f(x)$; the RMS value of $f(x)$ thus seems to be a natural scale to nondimensionalize f_n . Further, note that

1. f_n has the same dimensions as $f(x)$; and
2. $f_0 = \langle f(x) \rangle_x$

12.3.2 Dimensional scales

As the length and frequency scales, we take

$$L_0 \equiv \frac{c_{\text{top}}^2}{\gamma g} \quad (12.16)$$

$$\omega_0 \equiv \frac{g}{c_{\text{top}}} \quad (12.17)$$

Note that L_0 would be the pressure scale height at the top of the domain if it were in hydrostatic equilibrium; ω_0 is twice the acoustic cutoff frequency corresponding to an isothermal background. Using these, we define dimensionless wavenumbers and frequencies as

$$\tilde{\omega} \equiv \frac{\omega}{\omega_0} \quad (12.18)$$

$$\tilde{k}_i \equiv k_i L_0 \quad (12.19)$$

12.3.3 Power spectrum

12.3.3.1 Definition

Defining $\tilde{u}(\omega, k_x, k_y, z)$ as the discrete Fourier transform of $u_z(t, x, y, z)$ in time and the two horizontal directions, we define the power as

$$P(\tilde{\omega}, \tilde{k}_x, \tilde{k}_y, z) \equiv |\tilde{u}(\omega, k_x, k_y, z)|^2 \quad (12.20)$$

²Use equation 7.24 to write $f(a)$ in terms of f_n , use equation 12.12 for f_n , and bring the summation inside the integral.

12.3.3.2 Comments on other possible choices

Singh, Brandenburg, and Rheinhardt (2014, eq. 5) and Singh et al. (2015, eq. 12, 2020, eq. 8) used the absolute value of the Fourier-transformed velocity, rather than its square. Our choice has been used by observational studies (Singh, Raichur, and Brandenburg 2016, p. 2); we shall later see that it allows us to quantify the specific kinetic energy associated with a particular mode. Further, we note that it is the squared magnitude of the Fourier transform that is expected to show a Lorentzian mode profile (Christensen-Dalsgaard 2002, sec. V.F; Batchelor 1953, sec. 4.1).

It seems desirable to normalize P , e.g., by dividing it by $\langle u_z^2 \rangle_{x,y,t}$. However, since such a normalization is depth-dependent, it makes it difficult to study the mode amplitude as a function of depth. Alternatively, one may try a depth-independent normalization, e.g. using the sound speed at a particular depth, or the volume-averaged RMS velocity (Singh et al. 2020, eq. 8). The imposition of strong magnetic fields leads to minor changes in both volume-averaged diagnostics and in the profiles of background quantities. Since our main goal is to compare simulations with differing magnetic field configurations, we prefer to deal with the unnormalized P defined in equation 12.20.

Private communication suggests that Singh et al. (2015) took the ‘running difference’ of the vertical velocity before taking its Fourier transform, and that all their results concern such running differences of the velocity (and not the velocity itself, as reported). This was done to suppress the impact of low-frequency flow structures and allow proper visualization of the excited normal modes, and is apparently consistent with the practice in observational studies (e.g. Singh, Raichur, and Brandenburg 2016; Waidele et al. 2023; Sreenivas et al. 2024). For equidistant temporal sampling, the running difference is proportional to the time derivative of the velocity; it thus seems the quantity plotted in their \tilde{k} - $\tilde{\omega}$ diagrams is actually proportional to $\tilde{\omega}^2 P$, rather than P .

12.3.4 Fitting modes

Consider the power spectrum, defined in equation 12.20, at fixed \tilde{k}_x , \tilde{k}_y , and z . We model it as the sum of a power-law (the continuum) and a number of Lorentzians (each corresponding to a mode).

Additionally, we find it necessary to smooth the power spectrum along the frequency axis by a Lorentzian of half-width $5 \times 10^{-3} \omega_0$ before fitting. We note that such smoothing seems to be ubiquitous. Singh, Raichur, and Brandenburg (2016) use a boxcar profile, while private communication suggests this was also done in other studies (Singh, Brandenburg, and Rheinhardt 2014; Singh et al. 2015, 2020). Our choice of a Lorentzian smoothing profile is motivated by the fact that the convolution of a Lorentzian with a Lorentzian is another Lorentzian.

Prior to fitting, we smooth the error in the power spectrum (estimated as described in section 12.2.6) with a top hat of half-width $0.1 \omega_0$. This error can then be used to estimate errors in the fit parameters. During this process, we follow the

standard procedure of applying a scaling factor to the errors in the fit parameters such that the reduced χ^2 of the fit to the power spectrum becomes 1.

12.3.5 Mode mass

Given a particular mode, if the resolution in ω is not much smaller than the width of that mode, the peak value of $\tilde{u}(\omega)$ is sensitive both to the resolution and to any additional smoothing kernels that one may employ. As a measure of the strength of a particular mode, Singh et al. (2015, eq. 19) define a ‘mode mass’, which is proportional to $\int \Delta\tilde{u}d\omega$, where $\Delta\tilde{u}$ denotes \tilde{u} after removal of a ‘continuum’ (and possibly other modes of disinterest).

Since we define $\tilde{u}(\omega)$ as a discrete Fourier transform, we define the mode mass as

$$\mu \equiv \sum_{\tilde{\omega}} \Delta P(\tilde{\omega}) \quad (12.21)$$

where $\Delta P(\tilde{\omega})$ is the Lorentzian corresponding to the mode of interest in the fit to the power spectrum (section 12.3.4). By virtue of equation 12.15, μ defined in this way measures the temporally averaged kinetic energy associated with a particular mode; it is independent of the integration time if the system is in a statistically steady state. The analogous quantities defined by Singh et al. (2015, eq. 19, 2020, eq. 9) do not have this property.^{3,4}

The errors in the fit parameters (section 12.3.4) are used to estimate the error in the mode mass by computing the mode mass for 10^4 realizations of the fit parameters (assumed to be normally distributed, with the distribution truncated at zero for parameters which are expected to be non-negative). The upper and lower errors in the mode mass are then estimated from the 84.1 and 15.9 percentile values of the mode mass (these correspond to $1\text{-}\sigma$ deviates for a normal distribution).

12.3.6 Fluxes

The averaged total energy density (kinetic + internal + gravitational) is transported by the following fluxes:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{conv}} \equiv \langle \rho C_P \mathbf{u} T \rangle \quad (12.22)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{kin}} \equiv \langle \rho \mathbf{u}^2 \mathbf{u} / 2 \rangle \quad (12.23)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{visc}} \equiv - \left\langle 2\rho\nu\mathbf{u} \cdot \vec{S} \right\rangle \quad (12.24)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{cool}} \equiv - \hat{\mathbf{z}} \int_{z_{\text{bot}}}^z \langle q \rangle dz \quad (12.25)$$

³Singh et al. (2020, p. 207) allude to this.

⁴This can be understood by noting that if $\sum_{\omega} P$ is independent of the integration time (say T), one can write $P \sim 1/T \implies |\tilde{u}_z| \sim 1/\sqrt{T} \implies \sum_{\omega} |\tilde{u}_z| \sim \sqrt{T}$.

where q is defined in equation 12.9, along with the averages of the radiative and SGS fluxes defined in equations 12.7 and 12.8. Note that the expression for \mathbf{F}_{cool} above assumes $\langle q \rangle$ is independent of the horizontal coordinates (this is guaranteed if we are using horizontal averages).

12.3.7 Diagnostics

We define the Rayleigh number (Ra), which describes the degree of supercriticality of convection, as

$$\text{Ra} \equiv \frac{g |\Delta s| L^3}{C_P \nu \chi} \quad (12.26)$$

where L is the depth over which the entropy gradient remains negative (i.e. excluding the stably stratified layers at the top and the bottom of the domain); Δs is the integral over this depth of the horizontally and temporally averaged entropy gradient; and χ is the thermal conductivity (in our case, that arising from the Kramers opacity formula). We choose the value of χ corresponding to the midpoint of the region where the entropy gradient is negative. A similar quantity can be defined using the subgrid diffusivity:

$$\text{Ra}_{\text{SGS}} \equiv \frac{g |\Delta s| L^3}{C_P \nu \chi_{\text{SGS}}} \quad (12.27)$$

We define the Reynolds number, Re, which measures how turbulent the system is, as

$$\text{Re} \equiv \frac{\max_z [u_{\text{rms}}(z)] L}{\nu} \quad (12.28)$$

The Nusselt number, Nu, is the ratio of the total energy flux to the radiative flux. We evaluate it by taking the radiative flux at the midpoint of the region where the entropy gradient is negative.

12.4 The non-magnetic case

We first consider a non-magnetic simulation, initialized as described in section 12.2.4. Figure 12.1 shows the vertical components of various fluxes of energy, along with the density, the squared sound speed, the vertical entropy gradient, and the the RMS velocity (all horizontally and temporally averaged) as a function of depth. The temporal averages have been taken over six turnover times in the statistically steady phase of the simulation. The turnover time, calculated by taking the square root of the maximum value of $\langle u^2 \rangle_{xy,t}$ as the characteristic velocity and l as the characteristic length, is $25\sqrt{gl}$. Table 12.1 lists various diagnostics calculated from such averages (the non-magnetic case discussed here is marked as ‘NF’). The stratification becomes stable for $z < 0.36l$, but still remains close to adiabatic for $0 \lesssim z < 0.36l$. Similar to the Kramers runs discussed by Käpylä et al. (2017), our setup contains an extended Deardorff zone, where the convective flux is directed

Figure 12.1: Horizontally and temporally averaged vertical fluxes and other quantities in a realization of the nonmagnetic simulation. The constant flux marked as F_{bot} is that used to set the boundary condition for the entropy at the bottom of the domain. F_{tot} is the sum of F_{conv} , F_{kin} , F_{rad} , and F_{cool} ; contributions due to F_{SGS} and F_{visc} have not been included.

Name	Time range	#	N_z	Ra_{SGS}	Re	Ra_{rad}	Nu	Ma_{max}
NF	300–1300	4	288	1.6×10^6	265	7.5×10^7	15	0.12
ST	0–250	8	288	2.7×10^6	373	1.3×10^8	13	0.16
ST	250–500	8	288	1.9×10^6	336	9.5×10^7	14	0.15
SB	0–250	6	288	1.6×10^6	268	7.5×10^7	15	0.12
ET	0–250	6	288	1.6×10^6	273	7.6×10^7	14	0.13

Table 12.1: Summary of the discussed simulations, along with diagnostics computed from a single realization thereof. ‘NF’ (no field) denotes the non-magnetic case described in section 12.4, and the remaining configurations are discussed in section 12.5. For the magnetic cases, $t = 0$ corresponds to the time when the magnetic field is imposed. ‘#’ denotes the number of realizations. N_z is the number of grid points in the vertical direction; the numbers of grid points in the horizontal directions are scaled by the same factor relative to the non-magnetic case.

Figure 12.2: Diagnostic k - ω diagrams generated by averaging over four realizations of the non-magnetic case for (left) $z = l$; and (right) $z = -0.1l$. In both cases, we have set $\tilde{k}_y = 0$. The dashed black line shows the theoretical dispersion relation of the f mode.

Name	$C/\sqrt{\mu_0\rho_0gl}$	z_1/l	z_2/l
ST (strong top)	0.5	0.4	1.05
ET (equipartition top)	0.14	0.4	1.05
SB (strong bottom)	0.5	-0.45	0.2

Table 12.2: Parameters of the different large-scale magnetic field configurations discussed in section 12.5.

upward despite the stratification being stable. The prescribed cooling function leads to almost isothermal stratification for $z > l$, leading to a steep drop in the density. This density drop is expected to support an f mode.

Figure 12.2 shows k - ω diagrams generated at two heights by averaging over four independent time series of length $1000\sqrt{l/g}$ each. We observe both p and f modes in the slice taken near the top of the domain, while g modes are also visible in the slice taken from the stably stratified overshoot region. The expected dispersion relation of the f mode ($\omega = \sqrt{gk_x}$) has been indicated as a dashed grey line. We believe the deviation of the f mode frequencies from the theoretical curve is due to the upper boundary of the domain being close to the density jump at $z = l$.

12.5 Strengthening of the f mode due to large-scale fields

We consider magnetic fields corresponding to vector potentials of the form

$$A_y = \begin{cases} \frac{2C}{\pi}(z_2 - z_1) & z < z_1 \\ \frac{C}{\pi}(z_2 - z_1) \left(1 + \cos\left[\pi \frac{z - z_1}{z_2 - z_1}\right]\right) & z_1 \leq z < z_2 \\ 0 & z_2 \leq z \end{cases} \quad (12.29)$$

with $A_x = A_z = 0$. This has been constructed in such a way that the resultant magnetic field is in the \hat{x} direction, is a function of only z , is localized in the region $z_1 < z < z_2$, and has the maximal value C . Further, it is consistent with what one would expect if the top and bottom boundaries were perfect conductors (appendix 12.A). Table 12.2 gives the values of C , z_1 , and z_2 (each combination of which we refer to as a configuration) for the simulations using magnetic fields of this form, while the resulting profiles of B_x are plotted in figure 12.3.

For each configuration, multiple realizations were run. Table 12.1 gives the number of realizations along with some diagnostics for each magnetic field configuration.

Figures 12.4 and 12.5 show the k - ω diagrams (at $z = l$ and $\tilde{k}_y = 0$, averaged over all realizations) for the ST (where the maximum magnetic field is thrice the

Figure 12.3: The large-scale magnetic field configurations considered in section 12.5. For all these configurations, $B_y = B_z = 0$, and B_x is a function of only z . The left panel shows the value of the magnetic field, while the right shows it as a fraction of its equipartition value. The equipartition value has been calculated from horizontal-temporal averages of ρ and u^2 separately; this is valid for low Mach number.

Figure 12.4: k - ω diagram in the ST case (considering $0 < t < 500\sqrt{l/g}$) for $z = l$ and $\tilde{k}_y = 0$.

Figure 12.5: k - ω diagram in the SB case for $z = l$ and $\tilde{k}_y = 0$.

Figure 12.6: The mass of the f mode at $z = l$ and $\tilde{k}_y = 0$ as a function of \tilde{k}_x .

equipartition value) and SB cases respectively. The most prominent feature is a vertical band at $\tilde{k}_x = 0$. Recall that the magnetic field we have imposed has no spatial variation in the horizontal direction (corresponding to $\tilde{k}_x = \tilde{k}_y = 0$). Similar vertical features (referred to as *Bloch modes*) have been observed in earlier work, at multiples of twice the wavenumber of the horizontal variation of the magnetic field (Singh, Brandenburg, and Rheinhardt 2014, p. 4; Singh et al. 2020, sec. 3.2). In appendix 12.B, we consider a case where the magnetic field varies horizontally, and show that such vertical lines are obtained. Singh et al. (2020, section 3.3) have shown that for a horizontally localized magnetic field, the Bloch modes are absent. Since the magnetic fields in sunspots are localized, we do not believe the Bloch modes observed in our setup have any direct observational relevance.

The second most prominent feature is the presence of horizontal lines that intersect the p modes at $\tilde{k}_x = 0$. These appear to be caused by nonlinear interactions due to the large amplitudes of the p modes at $\tilde{k}_x = 0$. In line with our comments on Bloch modes, we ignore wavenumber ranges where the f mode is affected by this mode coupling.

Figure 12.6 shows the mass of the f mode as a function of \tilde{k}_x . Note that we have chosen a range of \tilde{k}_x where the coupling discussed above is not prominent. We find that the SB, ET, and NF cases have very similar mode masses. From other simulations not reported here, we expect the error due to the spatial discretization (recall that our error bars only include the error due to the finite integration time) to be of the same order as the spread between these three lines; we thus consider the difference between them insignificant. The ST-early case (where the mode masses have been measured immediately after imposing the magnetic field; see table 12.1) shows significantly elevated mode masses. However, the same case shows significantly lower mode masses later (ST-late). To summarize,

1. superequipartition magnetic fields near the top of the CZ strengthen the f mode;
2. neither equally strong magnetic fields near the bottom nor equipartition magnetic fields at the top have a similar effect; and
3. the strengthening of the f mode is a transient effect.

We note that our findings on the required strength of the magnetic field are consistent with earlier 2D forced-turbulence studies (Singh, Brandenburg, and Rheinhardt 2014; Singh et al. 2015, 2020), since they used a magnetic field which was highly superequipartition.

12.6 Conclusions

Moving beyond previous highly simplified forced-turbulence studies, we have demonstrated magnetic effects on the amplitudes of helioseismic modes in simulations of

convection. As a first step, we considered a vertically localized layer of horizontal magnetic flux. We found strengthening of the f mode when the magnetic field is near the top of the convection zone and its strength is thrice the equipartition value. However, neither an equally strong magnetic field near the bottom of the CZ nor an equipartition magnetic field near the top of the CZ has a significant effect on the f mode. Further, this effect is transient, in that the f mode strength decreases with time even when the magnetic field is static.

A major caveat of the work described in this chapter is the use of a static magnetic field. As discussed earlier, the resulting elimination of magnetic waves is expected to qualitatively affect the effect of the magnetic field on various modes present in the system. Future work will focus on less drastic simplifications that allow the effects of magnetic waves to be captured.

Appendices to chapter 12

12.A Constraints on the vector potential at a perfectly conducting boundary

For a perfectly conducting boundary, we have

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \times \mathbf{E} = \mathbf{0} \quad (12.30)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ is the normal to the boundary. This implies

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_S \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{S} \quad (12.31)$$

for a pillbox with surface S straddling the boundary. If the magnetic field outside the domain is zero, we have

$$\mathbf{B} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} = 0 \quad (12.32)$$

on the inner face of the boundary as well.

In Gaussian units,

$$\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial t} = -\mathbf{E} - \nabla \phi \quad (12.33)$$

$$\mathbf{J} = \frac{c}{4\pi} \nabla \times \mathbf{B} \quad (12.34)$$

$$\mathbf{J} = \frac{c^2}{4\pi\eta} \left(\mathbf{E} + \frac{\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}}{c} \right) \quad (12.35)$$

The default gauge used by PENCIL is

$$\phi = -\frac{\eta}{c} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{A} \quad (12.36)$$

in which case the evolution equation for \mathbf{A} is

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial t} = \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B} + \eta \nabla^2 \mathbf{A} + (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}) \nabla \eta \quad (12.37)$$

For concreteness, let us work in Cartesian coordinates and take $\hat{\mathbf{n}} = \hat{\mathbf{z}}$. If we impose

$$\partial_x A_x = \partial_y A_x = \partial_x A_y = \partial_y A_y = \partial_z A_z = 0 \quad (12.38)$$

Figure 12.7: (left) magnetic field configuration, and (right) k - ω diagram at $z = l$ and $\tilde{k}_x = 0$ for the case discussed in appendix 12.B.

on the boundary, we have $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A} = 0$, and thus $\phi = 0$ (equation 12.36). Equations 12.30 and 12.33 then imply

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial t} \times \hat{\mathbf{n}} = \mathbf{0} \quad (12.39)$$

Using equation 12.37, we then find

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \times (\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}) + \eta \hat{\mathbf{n}} \times (\nabla^2 \mathbf{A}) = \mathbf{0} \quad (12.40)$$

If $u_z = 0$, the required boundary conditions on \mathbf{B} can be imposed by setting

$$\partial_x A_x = \partial_y A_x = \partial_x A_y = \partial_y A_y = \partial_z^2 A_x = \partial_z^2 A_y = \partial_z A_z = 0 \quad (12.41)$$

on the boundary. Conventionally, this is specified by users of PENCIL by setting $A_x = A_y = \partial_z A_z = 0$ on the boundary. However, as in this chapter, it is permissible to set $\partial_z A_z = 0$ and require A_x and A_y to be antisymmetric about a prescribed value on the boundary.

12.B Bloch modes

In figures 12.4 and 12.5, we saw a vertical band of excess power at $\tilde{k}_x = \tilde{k}_y = 0$. Figure 12.7 shows a case (not discussed in the main text) where the magnetic vector potential is given by

$$A_z = -\frac{C\lambda_y}{2\pi} \exp\left(-\frac{(z-z_0)^2}{2w^2}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi y}{\lambda_y}\right) \quad (12.42)$$

with $C = 0.5\sqrt{\mu_0\rho_0gd}$, $\lambda_y = 2l$, $z_0 = 0.75l$, $w = 0.05l$, and $A_x = A_y = 0$. We indeed find vertical stripes at twice the associated wavenumber, as reported by Singh, Brandenburg, and Rheinhardt (2014, p. 4).

Part VII
Wrapping up

Chapter 13

Main results

Part I

Chapter 2

We find that in solenoidally forced rotating turbulence, rotational destabilization of vortices can lead to one-dimensionalization of the flow below the forcing scale, with the velocity component along the rotational axis being larger than the other two components. This mechanism of generation of anisotropy is not controlled by the position of the Zeman scale.

Part II

Chapter 3

We find that fluctuations of the turbulent diffusivity (which is related to the turbulent kinetic energy) can lead to the growth of a large-scale magnetic field. While crude estimates appear to rule out the operation of this mechanism on the surface of the Sun, these estimates depend on quantities which are not very well constrained by observations.

Chapter 4

In a velocity field with nonzero correlation time, the turbulent diffusivities of both the mean of a passive scalar and the mean of a magnetic field are suppressed. Nevertheless, the diffusivity for the mean magnetic field turns out to be less than that for the mean passive scalar. We also show that when the correlation time is nonzero, the quasilinear approximation misses terms at all orders in the correlation time beyond the lowest one.

Chapter 5

We derive evolution equations for the second moment of the magnetic field in both helical and nonhelical velocity fields with nonzero correlation time. Analysing the nonhelical case in the limit of high Pr_m , we find that the growth rate is suppressed much more strongly than reported in earlier studies, and point out the reasons for the discrepancies.

Part III

Chapter 6

In isotropically forced simulations of rotating turbulence, we find that the anisotropy generated by rotation (chapter 2) suppresses both the growth rate and the saturation level of the SSD. While the suppression of the growth rate becomes weak at high Re , the suppression of the saturation level remains strong.

The crucial role of anisotropy is demonstrated by using simulations of anisotropically forced non-rotating turbulence, where we find that the SSD is suppressed as the degree of anisotropy increases.

We then consider simulations with an angle between the rotational axis and the direction along which the forcing function is anisotropic (with this angle being analogous to the colatitude). We find that the saturation level is much more sensitive to the latitude than the growth rate. Drawing on our earlier analysis of the effect of rotation on the SSD, we suggest that this could be explained if the Λ effect were to affect the Reynolds stress predominantly at large scales.

Part IV

Chapter 7

Comparing synoptic vector magnetograms from two different instruments (SDO/HMI and SOLIS/VSM), we find persistent disagreements in the magnetic fields at high latitudes, and in both the sign and the magnitude of the magnetic helicity. This suggests that currently available synoptic magnetograms are not reliable enough to constrain the spatial and spectral distribution of the magnetic helicity.

Part V

Chapter 8

We find that modelling overshooting thermals as entraining vortex rings predicts overshoot depths of a few percent of the scale height, in agreement with helioseismic constraints. On the other hand, simpler models that do not account for entrainment

predict penetration depths of the order of the scale height. We also find a scaling relation between the size of a vortex ring and its penetration depth.

Chapter 9

We extend shell models, used in qualitative studies of unstratified or Boussinesq turbulence, to strongly stratified systems. The result is a model where variables are a function of both wavenumber and height.

Numerically solving the resulting model, we find that Pr strongly influences the coupling between convection at different depths, with the velocity amplitude being suppressed in deeper layers at low Pr . This suggests that the effect of a low Pr should not be ignored if one is to explain the convective conundrum.

Chapter 10

In simulations of rotating convection with an angle between the rotational axis and the gravitational acceleration, we find that rotation can either enhance or suppress the growth rate of the SSD: near the poles, the SSD is suppressed by rotation, while near the equator, the formation of large-scale flow structures enhances the SSD.

At higher rotational rates, we find cycles of the horizontal velocity components and the magnetic field. Such cycles appear at $\theta = 60^\circ$ (where θ is the colatitude) but not at $\theta = 0^\circ$. Unlike previously reported cases of magnetic cycles (which mostly dealt with the $\theta = 0^\circ$ case), we find that the energy of the fluctuating part of the magnetic field itself displays cycles, with the horizontally averaged magnetic field remaining energetically insignificant.

Part VI

Chapter 11

Applying the Cowling approximation in a plane-parallel domain, we find that the number of radial nodes of the p mode of a fixed order depends on the frequency, with modes trapped by the bottom boundary having one node less than modes trapped at an intermediate depth.

However, when the effects of a spherical geometry are taken into account, one just finds that the number of nodes for the p modes at $\ell = 0$ is one less than when $\ell \neq 0$. Relaxing the Cowling approximation muddies the picture even further.

Chapter 12

We use simulations of convection with imposed static magnetic fields to study magnetic effects on helioseismic modes. We find that while a magnetic field close

to the surface transiently strengthens the f mode, a magnetic field deep in the domain does not. This is consistent with the results of previous studies that used simulations of forced turbulence. A caveat is that the assumption of a static magnetic field eliminates magnetic waves, and thus limits the applicability of our results to real systems; future work will focus on relaxing this restriction.

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List of publications

Part of this thesis

10. Kishore Gopalakrishnan and Nishant K. Singh (2023). “Mean-field dynamo due to spatio-temporal fluctuations of the turbulent kinetic energy”. In: *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* 973, A29. DOI: [10.1017/jfm.2023.765](https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2023.765). Based on chapter 3.
9. Kishore Gopalakrishnan and Nishant K Singh (2024). “Small-scale Dynamo with Nonzero Correlation Time”. In: *The Astrophysical Journal* 970.1, p. 64. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ad4ee4](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ad4ee4). Based on chapter 5.

Submitted, based on this thesis

8. G. Kishore, Nishant K Singh, Petri Käpylä, and Markus Roth. Strengthening of the f mode due to subsurface magnetic fields in simulations of convection. arXiv: [2409.14840](https://arxiv.org/abs/2409.14840). Based on chapter 12.
7. G. Kishore and Nishant K Singh. Turbulent transport in a non-Markovian velocity field. arXiv: [2502.02946](https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.02946). Based on chapter 4.
6. G. Kishore and Nishant K Singh. Rotational effects on the small-scale dynamo. arXiv: [2502.17178](https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.17178). Based on chapters 2 and 6.
5. G. Kishore and Nishant K Singh. The spectra of solar magnetic energy and helicity. arXiv: [2503.03332](https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.03332). Based on chapter 7.

In preparation, based on this thesis

4. Kishore Gopalakrishnan, Nishant K Singh, Petri Käpylä, and Markus Roth. On the number of radial nodes of the lowest p mode (*in preparation*). Based on chapter 11.

3. Kishore Gopalakrishnan and Nishant K Singh. Magnetic cycles and angular momentum transport in simulations of convection (*in preparation*). Based on chapter 10.

Not part of this thesis

2. Kishore Gopalakrishnan and Kandaswamy Subramanian (2023). “Magnetic Helicity Fluxes from Triple Correlators”. In: *The Astrophysical Journal* 943.1, p. 66. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aca808](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aca808).
1. G Kishore and Anupam Kundu (2021). “Local time of an Ornstein–Uhlenbeck particle”. In: *Journal of Statistical Mechanics: Theory and Experiment* 2021.3, p. 033218. DOI: [10.1088/1742-5468/abe93d](https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-5468/abe93d).